

On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant? Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn (Proposal to the Polish National Science Centre)

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Introduction

I submitted the proposal *On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant* to the Polish National Science Centre (NCN) seven times over five years with three institutions. It made it to the second stage twice. I have decided to publish this proposal (its key elements) and reviews because I believe that there is an important social interest in doing so. I suspect that other researchers (especially young) may be in similar situation. I am aware that everything looks different from the perspective of someone who receives a monthly salary from a full-time position at a university. Perhaps this publication will help those evaluating proposals to better understand the applicant's situation. But not only them – I want to reveal the (invisible to outsiders) process of evaluating grant applications – this publication is a form of criticism of that process. Besides, I still think the project idea is a good one, and since I am unable to implement it, I am publishing it. Perhaps someone else will do what I believe should be done.

Proposals submitted to the NCN undergo a two-stage evaluation process. In the first stage, they are evaluated by internal experts (panel members). If a proposal advances to the second stage, it is sent to external reviewers, usually two. Based on their reviews, a decision is then made by the panel of internal experts.

When reviewing and analysing this publication, one should bear in mind that in the justification for the proposal evaluation the NCN provides 1) the score that the proposal received in each criterion, 2) general justification and 3) individual opinions of experts/reviewers (I am not sure if always in full, it seems to me that sometimes the coordinator 'censors' these individual opinions). Individual opinions are not decisive; what is decisive is (2) the general justification signed by the entire panel of internal experts. Nevertheless, individual opinions are important because they show what guided the internal panel members' discussion.

As for deadlines, the OPUS competition is announced twice a year. If a proposal is rejected at the first stage, it is punished – it cannot be submitted in the next edition of the call for proposals, but only after 12 months.

I consulted the content of all subsequent proposals with Hajo Greif from the Warsaw University of Technology – he helped me refine them each time. He appears as a team member (wykonawca_1) in each version of the proposal.

When citing the justification for the evaluation, I provide the name of the call for proposals, followed by the date of submission of the proposal in brackets and information about the stage at which the proposal was rejected. Then I give the overall assessment of the proposal, *calculated by me* on the basis of the weights of particular criteria (the criteria have changed slightly over the past five years, but my calculations always take the weights into account). I must admit that at one point I thought that my proposal was being deliberately and unfairly rejected. But I dismissed this thought as implausible. In the table below, the reader can easily see how much the level of proposals submitted to the NCN has increased over these five years. In 2020, rating 58,90% (see table below) was enough to move on to the second stage, but three years later, 76% is not enough.

Call	OPUS 19	OPUS 20	OPUS 22	OPUS 23	OPUS 25	OPUS 27	OPUS 29
Institution	PW	PW	UWr	UWr	UWr	ZNiO	ZNiO
Submitted	06.2020	12.2020	12.2021	06.2022	06.2023	06.2024	06.2025
general assessment	58,99%	49,00%	72,38%	64,50%	76,38%	76,50%	73,00%
rejected at	2 stage	1 stage	2 stage	1 stage	1 stage	1 stage	1 stage

Although subsequent versions of the proposal differ slightly, the fundamental objective of the project has remained unchanged, so reading the latest version (OPUS 29) should suffice if one is interested in the idea itself. However, I also encourage reading the reviews, especially the external reviews (look for the word ‘reviewer’) that the proposal received in the second stage, because as a rule they are written by specialists – in the first stage, the proposal may be evaluated by representatives of related disciplines. Apart from these few general comments and suggestions in this introduction, I do not comment on the reviews of the proposal.

What changed in subsequent versions of the proposal? Of course, my achievements – the first time (June 2020, OPUS 19), I had not yet published three articles in English – but despite this, the proposal moved on to the second stage. December 2021 (OPUS 22) is the moment when the two most important articles for the project (*Stimmung/Mood...* and *Aristotle Experience...*) are either published or accepted for publication, which is reflected in significantly higher ratings for subsequent proposals.

The second important change concerns text analysis tools. I planned to use the AntConc computer programme for analysis in all versions of the proposal – in the penultimate version (OPUS 27), I added the use of artificial intelligence tools. I planned to have one more team member – an AI tool specialist from the Warsaw University of Technology. I also slightly modified the tasks. But I abandoned this idea in the latest version of the proposal because reviewers gave it a negative assessment. I thought at the time that the experts had used this as an excuse to reject the proposal, but I dismissed the thought as implausible. According to the experts, I did not describe in detail in the short description (5 pages) what the use of AI tools would consist of. Since such a description is impossible due to lack of space, and it was only supposed to be an addition to the project, with the real cost oscillating around 3% of the total project costs, I decided to withdraw this task and, if successful, finance it from the pool of indirect costs.

In general, I was including reviewers' comments that I considered at least somewhat reasonable in the next versions of the proposal. This was the case, for example, with the suggestion that the project could be implemented in international cooperation. I did not think this was necessary, but I came up with an idea on how to incorporate this recommendation in a way that would add value to the project. So, from the OPUS 27 version onwards, I added a group of external experts who were to act as reviewers of the project during its implementation – I involved both supporters and opponents of the radical plagiarism hypothesis. The aim of this team was to ensure greater objectivity in the project results. The other changes were basically cosmetic. The final version of the proposal is certainly better than the first one, but I believe that the first version was good enough to get funding. After all, the proposal made it to the second stage the first time around, even though my track record was much weaker.

In the first edition (OPUS 19, June 2020), the project received six external reviews in addition to two internal reviews – two reviews (reviewers 2 and 5) expressed some doubts, but were not unequivocally negative. To the best of my knowledge, the number of external reviews is exceptional. Usually, in addition to the standard two internal reviews, a proposal receives two or, at most, three external

reviews. I must admit that it occurred to me that the proposal was sent to subsequent external reviewers until at least one negative review was obtained. However, I dismissed this thought as implausible. And since the doubts of reviewers 2 and 5 were, in my opinion, the result of misunderstandings, I tried to express more precisely in subsequent versions of the proposal to prevent such doubts. Nevertheless, even then, most of the external reviews were positive, if not enthusiastic.

In the third edition (OPUS 22, December 2021), the project advanced to the second stage for the second time and, in addition to two internal reviews, received four external reviews, which was again more than usual. Only one of them (reviewer 2) was clearly negative, not to say biased. In the general justification for refusing funding, the panel wrote that it was a good proposal and should be funded, but there was not enough money. Since then, the proposal has never been sent for external reviews. I admit that it occurred to me that this was because sending the proposal outside risked positive reviews and someone decided not to take the risk anymore (you can't write again that the proposal is great, but we didn't have enough money). But of course, I dismissed this thought as implausible.

Why am I deciding to publish my grant proposal? Firstly, perhaps someone will take it into account in the discussion on research funding in Poland? Secondly, if we take the experts' assessments seriously, my achievements (limited in international scope and overly focused on Fleck) are the main obstacle to obtaining funding. And since I have not been working at a university or in research for almost four years, and I have family commitments, I am unable to increase my achievements in any meaningful way, and certainly I cannot increase my achievements at the rate of increasing quality of proposals submitted to the NCN. And because I consider the idea to be a good one and – unlike some experts – I rate its potential international impact very highly, I am handing the idea over to others. Perhaps someone will 'take up the baton'. I only ask that the authorship be acknowledged.

The proposals are included below in chronological order (page numbers are the page numbers of the PDF file):

- OPUS 19 – proposal, p. 4-36
- OPUS 19 – reviews, p. 37-47
- OPUS 20 – proposal, p. 48-84
- OPUS 20 – reviews, p. 85-87
- OPUS 22 – proposal, p. 88-116
- OPUS 22 – reviews, p. 117-126
- OPUS 23 – proposal, p. 127-154
- OPUS 23 – reviews, p. 155-157
- OPUS 25 – proposal, p. 158-186
- OPUS 25 – reviews, p. 187-190
- OPUS 27 – proposal, p. 191-221
- OPUS 27 – reviews, p. 222-223
- OPUS 29 – proposal, p. 224-259
- OPUS 29 – reviews, p. 260-264

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

OPUS-19

Wniosek o finansowanie projektu badawczego, w tym finansowanie zakupu lub wytworzenia aparatury naukowo-badawczej niezbędnej do realizacji tego projektu

Na ramionach niewidocznego olbrzyma? Odkrywanie wpływu Ludwika Flecka na Thomasa Kuhna

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

Politechnika Warszawska

Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych

OPIS SKRÓCONY

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On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant? Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

1. Scientific goal of the project

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962). It is evident that these similarities are not purely coincidental, and that there was an **influence that Fleck's thought exerted on Kuhn's. However**, the nature, depth and scope of that influence are not very well documented or analysed to date.

There is a whole spectrum of possible explanations of how this influence came to pass, given that Kuhn **was at least informed of the existence of Fleck's earlier book** but only acknowledged him in passing. Possible explanatory hypotheses range from the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, **as Kuhn did not read or fully understand Fleck's book (Fleck anticipated Kuhn in a process of parallel discovery)**, via the intermediate hypotheses that Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either had an indirect and un- or even subconscious influence on him (Fleck inspired Kuhn) or a more direct but weakly acknowledged influence (Fleck informed Kuhn), to the claim that Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him (Kuhn plagiarised Fleck).

The aim of this inquiry in the history of philosophy of science is to provide an in-depth account of the genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work in light of the best available evidence. It will do so by exploring the above-mentioned spectrum of possible hypotheses, with emphasis on the intermediate variants, by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. The guiding hypothesis of this project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledge.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented. Mending this situation requires both comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by the two authors and tracing the possible routes of transfer of related vocabulary and metaphors. Although either task is relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to demonstrate how and to what extent **Fleck's concepts informed Kuhn.**

Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence (see the paragraph below), the novelty of this project lies in the combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn.

There are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979), Braunstein (2003), Brorson and Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Dahms (2016), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006), Marín (2010), Mößner (2011), but most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. With the exception of Baldamus' study, which compares the vocabularies of **Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books**, there is little attention being paid to how **Fleck's concepts may actually have informed Kuhn's.** Therefore, research on the **relations between Kuhn's and Fleck's work** need to be deepened, by asking what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved. It also needs to be broadened, by analysing the metaphors and *development* of vocabulary in **Kuhn's writings**, including his unpublished materials. Tracing the underlying genealogical relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, whatever its concrete nature might be, will help to shed light on the conceptual similarities and differences involved.

Other influences on Kuhn – from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (**Kuhn's teacher and boss while at Harvard**) – will also be taken into account, as will shared influences

on Fleck and Kuhn, such as *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler) and art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin). An analysis of the relationship between Kuhn and the French epistemologists shows that there are indeed similarities (Simons 2017), but these are far fewer than between Fleck and Kuhn, whereas the former but not the latter are documented in Kuhn's footnotes. A study that demonstrates Conant's while denying Fleck's influence on Kuhn (Wray 2016) is countered by the fact that Conant read Fleck's book in 1950 (see Trenn 1981), so there still might be a mediated influence. The influence of the Gestalt psychologists on both authors is obvious and straightforward by comparison. It seems that both Kuhn and Fleck have similarly transferred (this is kind of a metaphor) the knowledge of psychologists to epistemology. The question of whether they have done it independently of each other is one matter of investigation.

In the late 1970s, Wilhelm Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979) suggested that Thomas Kuhn may have committed plagiarism, but these allegations – presumably due to the popularity of Kuhn's book and his authority at the time – were never thoroughly investigated. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix–x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed that he **read Fleck's book** in 1949, and we know that his first attempts to write *The Structure* dates to 1950/1951, when Kuhn was preparing his Lowell Lectures (“The development of Kuhn's new image of the nature of science began with the 1951 Lowell lectures”, Marcum 2015), i.e. after reading Fleck. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn claimed that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited, because of the language barrier, and that in 1949 he found in Fleck what he had already conceived of earlier, **that is, before he read Fleck's work**, so that **Fleck's ideas only confirmed his own ideas**. This is the primary evidence for an insufficiently **acknowledged influence from Fleck on Kuhn, and for a shifting perception in Kuhn of what Fleck's import on his own thought actually was**.

However, if the claim that Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge the merits of Fleck in one way or another is true, an important complementary task will be to reflect on what Kuhn likely missed in his adoption **of Fleck's thought** – and, in consequence, what the tradition in the history and philosophy of science that he spawned may also have missed. There are some relevant insights for contemporary philosophy of science to be gathered here, for instance from **Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój***, which is not properly translatable into English – it is **usually translated as “mood”** and apparently not grasped by Kuhn – **but crucial to Fleck's approach**.

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars: 1. **textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings**, 2. analysis of secondary sources and 3. archival research. While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in Gestalt psychology and art history. Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. For the analysis of the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and **while reading had to “translate” Fleck into contemporary English**.

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:
 - 1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship **between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?**
 - 1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?
 - 1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?
 - 1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?
2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:
 - 2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?

2.2. What was the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts?

3. Archival research aims to provide:

3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.

3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

The project is divided into four nine-month periods, during which we will A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below), B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able, C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).

Work Plan

- I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- III. Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.
- IV. Archive research in
 - i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] in order to: collect unpublished texts to be analysed in regard of vocabulary development and metaphors used; **check accuracy of Kuhn's language barrier argument and resulting limited understanding of Fleck's book**; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949 (when he read **Fleck's book**); check when Kuhn first read about Gestalt psychology; search for early relations about **famous "Aristotle experience"**; **check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible and if yes – what Kuhn noted on margins and what underlined**;
 - ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] in order to check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn [according to **Trenn Conant read Fleck's book in 1950**],
 - iii. Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics] in order to check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability),
 - iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] in order to study materials regarding the **American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck**,
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] in order to check whether Polanyi **read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*)** and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi,
 - vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know anything that could **shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).**
- V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.

- VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
- VIII. Comparison of vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, taking into account development of his vocabulary in time).
- IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories - from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.

Preliminary research

Besides work on the peculiarities of translating Fleck (Jarnicki 2016), the PI has written two extensive articles over the last two years, which are under review for

1. "Studies in History and Philosophy of Science": *Stimmung/nastrój as content of modern science. On musical metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives*;
2. "Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie": *The Legend of Thomas Kuhn in the light and in relation to Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives*.

In the first article, I show that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój* is part of the musical metaphors (the term is not properly translatable into English and usually rendered as "mood") and that he adopted it from art historians (Woelfflin and Riegl). I then point out that one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of development of art and science as shown in Oliveira's (2017) analysis of the first unpublished chapter of the *Structure*. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other. In the second article, I first highlight the numerous similarities between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, and then show that considerations of Ludwik Fleck's work are largely absent from the corpus of publications on Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science. I analyse Kuhn's statements about Fleck to conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of revelation to his 1947 "Aristotle experience" exactly when he found out about the work on the American edition of Fleck. Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. Analysis of the printed sources does not allow to exclude the suspicion of the plagiarism by Kuhn. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

4. Research methodology

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or near-native knowledge of English (Principal Investigator, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (Principal Investigator). The project will apply archival research methods (IV, work plan); text analysis (I, II, III, V, VI, work plan) assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit; and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002).

5. Project literature

- Baldamus, W. (1976) *The structure of sociological inference*. Barnes & Noble Books.
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for/Aufsätze für Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156, *Amsterdams Sociologisch Tijdschrift*). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). *Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung*. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Braunstein, J.-F. (2003). Thomas Kuhn lecteur de Ludwik Fleck. *Archives de Philosophie*, 66, 403–422.
- Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.

- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). *Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência*. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argumentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). *Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência*. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.
- Dahms, H.-J. (2016). *Thomas Kuhn's Structure: An "Exemplary Document of the Cold War Era"?* In E. Aronova & S. Turchetti (Eds.), *Science Studies during the Cold War and Beyond: Paradigms Defected* (pp. 103–125). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.
- Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: "Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego" oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). *Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif*. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266–276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). *The genesis of 'scientific community'*. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157–168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006). *Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn*. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163–173.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). *Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) *On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations*, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd edition 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). *Foreword*. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2005). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?*. London, New York: Continuum.
- Marín, M. P. (2010). *Ludwik Fleck: precursor del pensamiento de Thomas Kuhn*. *Eidos: Revista de Filosofía de la Universidad del Norte*(13), 130–149.
- Mößner, N. (2011). *Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn*. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). *Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure*. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Sigurdsson, S. (2016). *The nature of scientific knowledge: an interview with Thomas S. Kuhn*. In *Shifting paradigms: Thomas S. Kuhn and the history of science* (pp. 17–30): Edition Open Access.
- Simons, M. (2017). *The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology*. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Trenn, T. J. (1981). *Paper prepared for the Hamburg Colloquium on Ludwik Fleck held September 13th-16th, 1981: Some Reflections on the Chicago Edition of Fleck's Monograph*. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5 .
- Werner, S., & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). *The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.

OPIS SZCZEGÓŁOWY

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Odkrywanie wpływu Ludwika Flecka na
Thomasa Kuhna

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On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant? Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

1. Scientific goal of the project

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962). It is evident that these similarities are not purely coincidental, and that **there was an influence that Fleck's thought exerted on Kuhn's. However**, the nature, depth and scope of that influence are not very well documented or analysed to date.

Both authors opposed speculation about how science should work and were interested in how it actually works; both claimed that scientific knowledge is not simply additive, but that it changes as a whole; both questioned the classic definition of truth and the possibility of pure observation; both observed the influence of social factors on the content of scientific knowledge claims; both observed the role the history of science plays in reflections on science; both introduced historical case studies to the philosophy of science; both claimed that scientists are connected as larger wholes (thought collectives/styles, scientific communities/paradigms); both emphasised the importance of non-verbalizable elements in the development of science; both used the concepts of incommensurability and untranslatability between scientific theories and both pointed out that there are several stages of development of theories; both used metaphor of Gestalt switch to show how differently the same things appear to scientists; both suggested that scientists representing different thought styles/paradigms live in different worlds; both claimed that the meaning of scientific terms is constantly changing and depends on a given thought style/paradigm. **The similarities between Fleck's and Kuhn's** views of science are numerous, but how precisely did they come to pass?

There is a whole spectrum of possible explanations of how **Fleck's writings came to influence Kuhn's thought, given that Kuhn was at least informed of the existence of Fleck's earlier book but only acknowledged him in passing.** Possible explanatory hypotheses include, at one end of the spectrum, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn did not read or fully understand Fleck's book, so any talk of an influence is exaggerated: "**Fleck (1935/1979), for example, is often cited as having anticipated Kuhn, although more careful studies suggest that the similarities between their views are superficial.**" (Wray 2016, p. 4) At most, Fleck anticipated some views of Kuhn in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum, there are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him: "**The reader who is familiar with Kuhn's work will easily recognize that the majority of [Fleck's] terms is virtually identical with the basic terminology of *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*.**" (Baldamus 1977, p. 151) Between those extremes, there are views according to which Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it only had an indirect and un- or even subconscious or a more direct but either way weakly acknowledged influence on him. One manifestation of this kind of influence would be that Fleck "**even illustrated the idea with some of the same examples Kuhn later adopted.**" (Oberheim 2012, p. 128).

The aim of this inquiry in the history of philosophy of science is to provide an in-depth account of the genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work in light of the best available evidence. It will do so by exploring the above-mentioned spectrum of possible hypotheses, with emphasis on the intermediate variants, by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. The guiding hypothesis of this

project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledge.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented. On the one hand, statistics from the Scopus database show that at there at least six times between 1979-2019 as many works on Kuhn than on Fleck.

Between 1979-2019 in Scopus there are 938 papers about/related to Kuhn, whereas only 157 about/related to Fleck.

On the other hand, a pilot survey among Polish academics in May 2020 by the PI documents a **perceived need of acknowledging Fleck's contribution** (P. Jarnicki, *A Survey on the Opinion of Polish Researchers on the Relationship between the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn*). The survey **was conducted on a sample of 23 philosophers from Poland, who consider their knowledge of Kuhn's and Fleck's theories to be at least good.** According to the judgement of the majority of respondents, there was an influence from Fleck on Kuhn that the latter only insufficiently acknowledged¹.

Mending this situation requires both comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and tracing the possible routes of transfer of related vocabulary and metaphors. Although either task is relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to **demonstrate how and to what extent Fleck's concepts informed Kuhn.** Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence (see below), the novelty of this project lies in the combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn.

There are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979), Braunstein (2003), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Dahms (2016), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006), Marín (2010), Mößner (2011), but most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus', which compares the vocabularies of Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books, there is little attention being paid to how Fleck's concepts may actually have informed Kuhn's. Therefore, **research on the relations between Kuhn's and Fleck's work need to be deepened, by asking what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved. It also needs to be broadened, by analysing the metaphors and development of vocabulary in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials.** Tracing the underlying

¹ To the question about the connection between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, 1 answered "don't know" and only 1 pointed that there is "no influence", 5 chose "anticipated" (which we interpret as no genealogical connection), 5 chose "forerunner" (which we interpret as weak genealogical connection), 7 chose "source of inspiration" (which we interpret as genealogical connection), 2 chose "strong influence" (which we interpret as significant genealogical connection), 2 chose "plagiarism". So, 16/23 Polish philosophers see the weaker or stronger genealogical connection. To the question if "Thomas Kuhn has acknowledged the merits of Ludwik Fleck sufficiently", 3 answered "don't know", only 5 answered "yes" and as many as 15 (i.e. 65%) answered "no".

genealogical relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, whatever its concrete nature might be, will help to shed light on the conceptual similarities and differences involved.

Even if from today's perspective, **Fleck's and Kuhn's theories** appear different to an observer – he or she might be, for instance, aware of **the differences between Fleck's and Kuhn's** concepts of **"incommensurability"** – one has to bear in mind that such differences were probably not nearly as apparent as they are today. In the wake of the publication of *The Structure*, a wide variety of approaches developed in the social and cultural studies of science, and today we are aware of many more nuances that probably were imperceptible to people who read *The Structure* right after its publication, when it not only caused a major stir but also first gave rise to much of the social and **cultural studies of science that now form the observer's vantage point**. On the other hand, many **influences that shaped both Fleck's and Kuhn's views are not at all obvious to the contemporary observer** but were nonetheless important in all the nuance and detail that escape us now.

On this background, numerous influences on Kuhn besides Fleck will be taken into account – **from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem, (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (Kuhn's teacher and boss while at Harvard)**... An analysis of the relationship between Kuhn and the French epistemologists shows that there are indeed similarities (Simons 2017), but these are far fewer than between Fleck and Kuhn, whereas the former but not the latter are documented in Kuhn's footnotes. A study that demonstrates Conant's while denying Fleck's influence on Kuhn (Wray 2016) is countered by the fact that Conant read Fleck's book in 1950 (see Trenn 1981), so there still might be a mediated influence.

Shared influences on Fleck and Kuhn will be accounted for, too, in particular art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether or not Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is one matter of investigation.

Oliveira's (2017) paper about the first – unpublished – chapter of *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* demonstrates that in the beginnings one of the key ideas of Kuhn was to make the image of science appear closer to the image of art (as the latter develops in a non-cumulative way). In doing this, he transferred some elements of knowledge about art history to the way we understand science. Since Fleck was informed of the concepts of style and mood (*nastrój/Stimmung*) in art history, it seems justified to ask whether these influences – on Kuhn and Fleck – were totally independent. This question might become even more pertinent in light of the observation that Fleck remained critical of art-historical notions of style that render it as an objective characteristic of a given collective that would allow for equally objective comparison rather than the nucleus of a proto-concept of incommensurability, as it would later be articulated by Kuhn (Zittel 2011).

The influence of the Gestalt psychologists on both authors is obvious and straightforward by comparison. It seems that both Kuhn and Fleck have similarly transferred (this is kind of a metaphor) the knowledge of psychologists to epistemology (**for Fleck's reference to Gestalt psychology, see Zittel 2014 and Hagner 2012; the latter comparatively evaluates Gestalt psychology's import on Fleck and Michael Polanyi, who in turn is often cited as another under-acknowledged influence on Kuhn**).

In the late 1970s, Wilhelm Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979) suggested that Thomas Kuhn may have plagiarised Fleck, but these allegations – presumably due to the popularity of Kuhn's book and his authority at the time – were never thoroughly investigated. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly **claimed that he read Fleck's book in 1949, and we know that his first attempts to write *The Structure* dates to 1950/1951, when Kuhn was preparing his Lowell Lectures ("The development of Kuhn's new image of the nature of science began with the 1951 Lowell lectures", Marcum 2015), i.e. after reading Fleck**. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn claimed that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited, because of the language barrier, and that in 1949 he found in Fleck what he had already conceived of **earlier, that is, before he read Fleck's work, so that Fleck's ideas only confirmed his own ideas**. This is the primary evidence for an insufficiently acknowledged influence from Fleck on Kuhn, and for a shifting perception in Kuhn of what **Fleck's import on his own thought actually was**.

In any case, the focus of Kuhn scholarship has long been distracted from possible influences exerted by Fleck, on the grounds of one peculiar Kuhnian narrative. From 1976 onwards, Kuhn started to trace the origins of his reasoning to what he called the “Aristotle Experience”. According to his own account, this foundational experience took place in 1947 when he was a 25 years old PhD student in physics, and was asked by James B. Conant, his superior at the time, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. When Kuhn found himself struggling to **understand Aristotle’s *Physics***, which initially seemed ridiculously mistaken and misconceived to him, he suddenly realised that **Aristotle’s physics is not false and meaningless but simply different from the contemporary physics that he himself was taught**. For a long time, this explanation of how the idea of scientific revolutions originated was considered sufficient. **One aim of this project is to test Kuhn’s narrative of autonomous discovery for its credibility in light of evidence concerning the question of whether Kuhn conceived of some of his “revolutionary/paradigmatic” ideas already before 1949, and if there are any traces that he read either the Gestalt psychologists or art historians before 1949.**

However, if the claim that Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge **Fleck’s influence** in one way or another is true, an important complementary task will be to reflect on what Kuhn likely missed in his **adoption of Fleck’s thought** in particular – and, in consequence, what the tradition in the history and philosophy of science that he spawned may also have missed. There are some relevant insights for **contemporary philosophy of science to be gathered here, for instance from Fleck’s concept of *Stimmung/nastrój***, which is not properly translatable into English – **it is usually translated as “mood”** and apparently not grasped by Kuhn – **but crucial to Fleck’s approach.**

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars:

1. **textual analysis of Kuhn’s and Fleck’s writings**
2. analysis of historical sources and
3. archival research.

While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in Gestalt psychology and art history. Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. For the analysis of the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn learned about Fleck’s theory **in German and while reading him had to “translate” Fleck into contemporary English.**

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:
 - 1.1. Does the development of Kuhn’s vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical **relationship between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories?**
 - 1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?
 - 1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?
 - 1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?

2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:
 - 2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?
 - 2.2. **What was the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts?**
3. Archival research aims to provide:
 - 3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.
 - 3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

Work plan

The project is divided into four nine-month periods, during which we will **A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below), B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able, C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).**

- I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- III. **Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings regarding** metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.
- IV. Archive research in
 - i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] in order to: collect unpublished texts to be analysed in **regard of vocabulary development and metaphors used; check accuracy of Kuhn's language barrier argument and resulting limited understanding of Fleck's book; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in Structure before 1949 (when he read Fleck's book); check when Kuhn first read about Gestalt psychology; search for early relations about famous "Aristotle experience"; check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible and if yes – what Kuhn noted on margins and what underlined;**
 - ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] in order to check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn **[according to Trenn Conant was to read Fleck's book in 1950],**
 - iii. **Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics] in order to check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability),**

- iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] in order to study materials regarding the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] in order to check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*) and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi,
 - vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know anything that could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).
- V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
- VIII. Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (accounting for the development of vocabulary over time with respect to Kuhn in particular).
- IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories - from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.

Preliminary research – previous work

In 2016, the PI published a paper in *The Translator*: "On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations". Using the example of the concept of communication/circulation of thoughts [*Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli*], it showed that, since both his Polish and his German texts are original texts (in which one theory was formulated), a translator of Fleck's work or should mind that the level of equivalence between these texts is the level of concepts (rather than the level of lexical meaning). Similarly, when studying the relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, we will assume similarity not so much on the level of linguistic expressions, but on the level of concepts and their relations.

Over the last two years, the PI has written two extensive articles, which are under review for

1. "Studies in History and Philosophy of Science": *Stimmung/nastrój as content of modern science. On musical metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives*;
2. "Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie": *The Legend of Thomas Kuhn in the light and in relation to Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives*.

In the first article, I show that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój* is part of the musical metaphors (the term is not properly translatable into English and usually rendered as "mood") and that he adopted it from art historians (Woelfflin and Riegl). I then point out that one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of development of art and science as shown in Oliveira's (2017) analysis of the first unpublished chapter of the *Structure*. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other. In the second article, I first highlight the numerous similarities between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, and then show that considerations of Ludwik Fleck's work are

largely absent from the corpus of publications on Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science. I analyse Kuhn's statements about Fleck to conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of revelation to his 1947 "Aristotle experience" exactly when he found out about the work on the American edition of Fleck. Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. Analysis of the printed sources does not allow to exclude the suspicion of the plagiarism by Kuhn. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

Preliminary research – vocabulary development

A prime example to demonstrate that tracking the development of Kuhn's vocabulary may prove fruitful lies in the evolution of his use of the word "thought". In Kuhn's first book (1957), we find the following passages:

Such texts are a relatively frequent and extremely significant phenomenon in the *development of scientific thought*. They may be described as texts that *shift* the direction in which *scientific thought develops* [...] As a whole the *De Revolutionibus* stands almost entirely within an ancient astronomical and cosmological tradition; yet within its generally classical framework are to be found a few novelties which *shifted* the direction of *scientific thought* in ways unforeseen by its author and which gave rise to a rapid and complete break with the ancient tradition. (Kuhn 1957, p. 135) [emphasis – PJ]

[...] the *De Revolutionibus* marks a *shift* in the direction in which astronomical *thought developed*." (Kuhn 1957, p. 182) [emphasis – PJ].

So in 1957 Kuhn writes about the "development of thought", whereas in his second book (1962) "thought" in this sense appears only once, as it seems, by accident: "conflict between competing schools of scientific thought" (Kuhn 1970, p. 96), because in 1962 he prefers to write about development of *science* instead of *thought*.

As we know, Ludwik Fleck wrote about the "development of thought", "thought styles" and "thought collectives". This is the first of the tracks to be followed: is it possible that Kuhn initially, under the influence of Fleck, wrote about the development of thought, only to liberate himself from the Fleckian vocabulary after 13 years?

Preliminary research – metaphors with shared aims

In the table below quotations from Fleck (1935 original and 1979 translation) and Kuhn (1962) that employ similar metaphors are juxtaposed. Both texts are about a group of people who look at one thing but see something different over the course of time. In Kuhn, the group has to experience a conversion (which is a religious metaphor), in Fleck the mood of the group has to change (which is a conceptual transfer from art history, and the concept of mood was one of the key concepts for temple architects). Both examples are given in the context of scientific discovery, and in both cases the passage is about a new emerging thought style (for Fleck, a shared mood [*Stimmung*] is a precondition of shared thought style) and about a new emerging paradigm. Both paradigm and thought style determine perception by the group. The source domain from which both paradigm and thought style are conceptualised is seeing *gestalts*. In both cases, the *gestalt* metaphor is also used to underline that it is impossible to understand previous thought style/paradigm in terms of the subsequent one (and vice versa). In both cases, the metaphor is used to show that the change is not induced by reasoning and logic, and that it happens independently of the intentions of the **group's** members. In the present project, this line of investigation will be further pursued, in much more detail and on a large corpus of Fleck's and Kuhn's writings.

Fleck 1935 (original)	Fleck 1979 (translation)	Kuhn 1962 (original)
<p>eine Massensuggestion, die die gesamte Mannschaft eines Schiffes, auf der Suche nach einem verunglückten Boote befindlich, dieses Boot mit den Insassen wahrnehmen ließ, sogar Signalzeichen und Rufe. Erst in der letzten Minute der Annäherung platzte auf einmal die kollektive Halluzination: das Boot entpuppte sich als ein Baum mit Asten und Blättern, von den Fluten getrieben. Dieser Fall könnte geradezu als Paradigma vieler Entdeckungen gelten: das stimmungsmäßige Gestaltsehen und der plötzliche Umschlag: andersartiges Gestaltsehen. Plötzlich versteht man überhaupt nicht, wie die frühere Gestalt möglich war und wie das ihr Widersprechende unbemerkt bleiben konnte. Genau so verhält es sich mit der wissenschaftlichen Entdeckung, nur aus der Aufregung und dem Fieber in Gleichmaß und Dauer übersetzt. Die disziplinierte, gleichmäßige und viele Generationen dauernde Stimmung eines Kollektives erzeugt das "wirkliche Bild" genau so, wie die fieberhafte eine Halluzination. In beiden Fällen verlaufen parallel Stimmungswechsel (Denkstilwechsel) und Bildwechsel. (Fleck 1935, p. 117)</p>	<p>a case of mass suggestion which induced the entire crew of a ship, while searching for a boat in distress, to see this craft and its crew and even to hear shouts and see signals. This collective hallucination was suddenly dispelled but only during the last minute of approach. The "boat" turned out to be a tree with branches and leaves drifting in the water. This case could be considered the very paradigm of many discoveries. The mood-conforming gestalt-seeing and its sudden reversal: the different gestalt-seeing. Suddenly one can no longer even understand how the previous form was possible and how features contradicting it could have gone unnoticed. The same situation obtains in scientific discovery, only translated from excitement and feverish activity into equanimity and permanence. The disciplined and even-tempered mood, persisting through many generations of a collective, produces the "real image" in exactly the same way as the feverish mood produces a hallucination. In both cases switch of mood (switch of thought style) and switch of image proceed in parallel. (Fleck 1979, p. 111)</p>	<p>Practicing in different worlds, the two groups of scientists see different things when they look from the same point in the same direction. Again, that is not to say that they can see anything they please. Both are looking at the world, and what they look at has not changed. But in some areas they see different things, and they see them in different relations one to the other. That is why a law that cannot even be demonstrated to one group of scientists may occasionally seem intuitively obvious to another. Equally, it is why, before they can hope to communicate fully, one group or the other must experience the conversion that we have been calling a paradigm shift. Just because it is a transition between incommensurables, the transition between competing paradigms cannot be made a step at a time, forced by logic and neutral experience. Like the gestalt switch, it must occur all at once (though not necessarily in an instant) or not at all. (Kuhn 1970, p. 150)</p>

4. Research methodology

The project will employ a set of methods common to the humanities:

1. philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve surveying and analysing primary and secondary sources, retracing key concepts, arguments and references used and considering their context;

2. archival research methods (item IV in the work plan);
3. linguistic text analysis (items I, II, III, V, VI in the work plan), assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002).

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or near-native knowledge of English (Principal Investigator, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (Principal Investigator).

5. Project literature

- Baldamus, W. (1976) *The structure of sociological inference*. Barnes & Noble Books.
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for/Aufsätze für Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156, *Amsterdams Sociologisch Tijdschrift*). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). *Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.**
- Braunstein, J.-F. (2003). Thomas Kuhn lecteur de Ludwik Fleck. *Archives de Philosophie*, 66, 403–422.
- Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). *Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência*. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.**
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). *Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência*. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.**
- Dahms, H.-J. (2016). *Thomas Kuhn's Structure: An "Exemplary Document of the Cold War Era"?* In E. Aronova & S. Turchetti (Eds.), *Science Studies during the Cold War and Beyond: Paradigms Defected* (pp. 103–125). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.
- Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: "Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego" oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej.**
- Hagner, M. (2012). Perception, knowledge and freedom in the age of extremes: on the historical epistemology of Ludwik Fleck and Michael Polanyi. *Studies in Eastern European Thought*, 64, 107–120
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266–276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). *The genesis of 'scientific community'*. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157–168.**
- Jacobs, S. (2006). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163–173.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). *Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.**

- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd edition 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2005). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?*. London, New York: Continuum.
- Marín, M. P. (2010). Ludwik Fleck: precursor del pensamiento de Thomas Kuhn. *Eidos: Revista de Filosofía de la Universidad del Norte*(13), 130–149.
- Mößner, N. (2011). *Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn*. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oberheim, E. (2012). *Feyerabend's Philosophy*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of *Structure*. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Reisch, G. A. (2016). *Aristotle in the Cold War: On the Origins of Thomas Kuhn's The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. In R. J. Richards & L. Daston (Eds.), *Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions at Fifty: Reflections on a science classic*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.
- Sigurdsson, S. (2016). The nature of scientific knowledge: an interview with Thomas S. Kuhn. In *Shifting paradigms: Thomas S. Kuhn and the history of science* (pp. 17–30): Edition Open Access.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Trenn, T. J. (1981). Paper prepared for the Hamburg Colloquium on Ludwik Fleck held September 13th-16th, 1981: **Some Reflections on the Chicago Edition of Fleck's Monograph**. Robert K. Merton Papers, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5 .
- Werner, S., & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). **The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions**. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.
- Zittel, C. (2011). Ludwik Fleck und der Stilbegriff in den Naturwissenschaften. Stil als **wissenschaftshistorische, epistemologische und ästhetische Kategorie**. In H. Bredekamp & J. Krois (Eds.), *Sehen und Handeln*. Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, pp. 171–206.
- Zittel, C. (2014). Ludwik Flecks Gestaltbegriff und sein Blick auf die Gestaltpsychologie seiner Zeit. *NTM Zeitschrift für Geschichte der Wissenschaften, Technik und Medizin*, 22(1), 9–29.

PLAN BADAŃ

Lp.	Nazwa zadania	Podmioty
1	Analiza tekstów opublikowanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do roku 1962 włącznie - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
2	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Ludwika Flecka do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć z jego teorii i pojęć z teorii zastanych.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories.	
3	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów opublikowanych).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of published texts).	
4	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Thomasa Kuhna [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	
5	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Jamesa Conanta [Harvard University Archives Repository]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in James Conant Archive [Harvard University Archives Repository]	

6	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Paula Feyerabenda [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
Archive research in Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]		
7	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Roberta Mertona [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
Archive research in Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]		
8	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Michaela Polanyi'ego [University of Chicago Library]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
Archive research in Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library]		
9	Badania w innych archiwach i wywiady z osobami, które mogą posiadać wiedzę mogącą rzucić światło na genealogiczny związek między teoriami Flecka i Kuhna, jak na przykład rodzina Wilhelma Baldamusa, która przechowuje jego korespondencję, poszukiwanie materiałów Thaddeusa Trewna i Harolda K. Schillinga z Pennsylvania State University.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
Research in other archives and interviews with individuals who might possess knowledge that could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, search for materials of Thaddeus Trenn and Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University		
10	Analiza niepublikowanych tekstów Thomasa Kuhna (do roku 1962 włącznie) - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development		

11	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów niepublikowanych).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of unpublished texts).	
12	Porównanie metafor stosowanych przez Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	
13	Porównanie słownictwa Flecka i Kuhna (w odniesieniu do tego ostatniego, w ujęciu diachronicznym).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, in diachronic terms).	
14	Rozważenie możliwych wyjaśnień podobieństwa teorii Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	

ANKIETY CZŁONKÓW ZESPOŁU

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki, Kierownik (PI)

PRZEBIEG KARIERY NAUKOWEJ

Informacje o przebiegu kariery naukowej [w języku angielskim]

- From October 2018 (to June 2021) - **assistant professor** (half time) at Warsaw University of Technology; Faculty of Administration and Social Sciences; Department of Philosophy and Ethics in Administration.
- From May 2015 - member of the Academy of Young Scholars and Artists (Wrocław), from May 2017 to July 2019 Vice-Chairman.
- From May, 2013 to April, 2016 - **associated researcher** of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich).
- From April, 2013 (to September, 2016) - **principal investigator** of the project 'Philological analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical works and its translations into Polish, English and German'. The project is funded by National Science Centre in Cracow (Narowe Centrum Nauki w Krakowie) in HARMONIA scheme (international cooperation) and is realized in Project Science Foundation (Fundacja Projekt Nauka).
- From 2012 - member of the Board of Project Science Foundation, from December 2016 do December 2019 **Chairman of the Board**.
- 15 May, 2012 - **PhD in humanities**. Thesis: 'Metaphorical conceptualizations of the notion of 'text' and changes of thought styles in literary studies'. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty.
- 2009-2011 - **investigator** within the doctoral project (University of Wrocław) funded by Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (State Committee for Scientific Research in Poland [Komitet Badań Naukowych] titled: 'A method of analysis of metaphors in scientific texts as factors of change in science'.
- 15 July, 2005 - **Master of Arts**, thesis: 'Metaphors of intertextuality. Onomasiological-cognitive Analysis'. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty, Institute of Polish Philology.

In the last two years, PI has written two extensive articles, which are under review in

- "Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie": *The Legend of Thomas Kuhn in the light and in relation to Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives* (almost 20 000 words);
- "Studies in History and Philosophy of Science": *Stimmung/nastroj as content of modern science. On musical metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives* (over 10 000 words).

PUBLIKACJE NAUKOWE

Publikacje naukowe

1. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Translator
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	22 (2016), 3, p. 271–286
Rok publikacji	2016
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	5
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	10.1080/13556509.2015.1126881
PDF publikacji	On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish German and English translations.pdf

2. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989)</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989)
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science

Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	1 (2016 - special issue on Ludwik Fleck), p. 21-30
Rok publikacji	2016
Otwarty dostęp	Tak
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	0
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	10.24117/2526-2270.2016.i1.05
PDF publikacji	Jarnicki.pdf

3. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Metaforyczne konceptualizacje pojęcia 'tekstu' a przemiany stylów myślowych w literaturoznawstwie [Metaphorical conceptualizations of the concept of 'text' and changes of thought styles in history and theory of literature]</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Metaforyczne konceptualizacje pojęcia 'tekstu' a przemiany stylów myślowych w literaturoznawstwie [Metaphorical conceptualizations of the concept of 'text' and changes of thought styles in history and theory of literature]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	książka
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	Wrocław: Wydawnictwo 'Projekt Nauka', pp. 246
Rok publikacji	2014
Otwarty dostęp	Tak
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	2
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	Metaforyczne konceptualizacje - Paweł Jarnicki.pdf

4. Paweł Jarnicki, Bożena Płonka-Syroka, Bogdan Balicki , <i>Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje [Ludwik Fleck - traditions - inspirations - interpretations]; [in the volume: Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie, p. 235–37; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim, p. 239–55; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim, p. 257–94; Postowie, p. 295–96]</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki, Bożena Płonka-Syroka, Bogdan Balicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje [Ludwik Fleck - traditions - inspirations - interpretations]; [in the volume: Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie, p. 235–37; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim, p. 239–55; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim, p. 257–94; Postowie, p. 295–96]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	książka
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich
Rok publikacji	2015
Otwarty dostęp	Tak
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	3
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

5. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Kłopoty z przedwojenną recepcją koncepcji Ludwika Flecka: [On some problems with the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in the prewar period]</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Kłopoty z przedwojenną recepcją koncepcji Ludwika Flecka: [On some problems with the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in the prewar period]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	STUDIA PHILOSOPHICA WRATISLAVIENSIA
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	6. (2), p. 133–39

Rok publikacji	2011
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	1
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

6. Paweł Jarnicki , *Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of "legitimation"* [Polish extended version appeared as: *O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka*. In: *Stan Rzeczy 10*, p. 355-373]

Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of "legitimation" [Polish extended version appeared as: <i>O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka</i> . In: <i>Stan Rzeczy 10</i> , p. 355-373]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Divinatio: Studia Culturologica Series
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	vol. 41, autumn-winter, p. 167-184
Rok publikacji	2015
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	0
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

7. Paweł Jarnicki , *Ludwika Flecka nauka bez prawdy?* [Science by Ludwik Fleck - without truth?]

Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Ludwika Flecka nauka bez prawdy? [Science by Ludwik Fleck - without truth?]

Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Przegląd Filozoficzny - Nowa Seria
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	19 (2 (74)): p. 63–79
Rok publikacji	2010
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	1
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

8. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Metafory dyskursu intertekstualności, metaforyka tekstylna [Metaphors of intertextuality. Textile metaphors]</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Metafory dyskursu intertekstualności, metaforyka tekstylna [Metaphors of intertextuality. Textile metaphors]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Kształcenie Językowe
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	13 (23): p. 49–72
Rok publikacji	2015
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	0
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

9. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>W sprawie wystąpienia Wojciecha Sadego pt. 'O tym, co decyduje o naukowości badań przyrodniczych'</i> [On Wojciech Sady's lecture: 'What determines the scientific nature of scientific research']	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	W sprawie wystąpienia Wojciecha Sadego pt. 'O tym, co decyduje o naukowości badań przyrodniczych' [On Wojciech Sady's lecture: 'What determines the scientific nature of scientific research']
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	STUDIA PHILOSOPHICA WRATISLAVIENSIA
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	6, nr 2, s. 55–61.
Rok publikacji	2011
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	0
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

10. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Antytotalitarne motywy twórczości Ludwika Flecka</i> [Antitotalitarian motives in Ludwik Fleck's writings]	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Antytotalitarne motywy twórczości Ludwika Flecka [Antitotalitarian motives in Ludwik Fleck's writings]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	rozdział
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	W: Nauka w kontekście wzorców kultury, red. Bożena Płonka-Syroka, s. 91–102. Seria: Antropologia wiedzy 5. Warszawa: DiG.
Rok publikacji	2011
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań bez autocytowań	0

Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

BADANIA NAUKOWE FINANSOWANE PRZEZ NCN

Informacje o kierowaniu projektami badawczymi lub innym uzyskanym finansowaniu w ramach konkursów NCN [w języku angielskim]

DANE POBRANE AUTOMATYCZNIE

Tytuł w języku polskim	Filologiczna analiza filozoficznych dzieł Ludwika Flecka oraz ich tłumaczeń w językach: polskim, niemieckim i angielskim
Nr rejestracyjny	2012/06/M/HS2/00313
Źródło(a) finansowania	NCN
Kwota	405512 PLN
Podmiot realizujący w języku polskim	Projekt Nauka. Fundacja na rzecz promocji nauki polskiej
Data rozpoczęcia realizacji	2013-03-25
Data zakończenia realizacji	2016-08-24

<p>Lista najważniejszych publikacji będących rezultatem projektu (skopiowana automatycznie z ostatniego raportu zaakceptowanego przez NCN)</p>	<p>Publikacje w czasopismach:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Paweł Jarnicki, Sandra Lang ("Introduction"); Paweł Jarnicki ("The beginnings..."), Introduction; The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989), <i>Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science</i>, 1, 3-5; 21-30, Graduate Program in History (Science and Culture in History) of Federal University of Minas Gerais (Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais), Brasil, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane - Paweł Jarnicki, On the Shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the Bilingual Philosophical Legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English Translations, <i>The Translator</i>, 22 (3), 271–286, Routledge, 2016, IF: 0.483, - Opublikowane - Paweł Jarnicki, O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka, <i>Stan Rzeczy</i>, 10, 355-373, Instytut Socjologii UW, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane - Paweł Jarnicki, Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of “legitimation”, <i>Divinatio</i>, 41 (Aut.-Win.), 167-184, University of Sofia, Department of Cultural Studies, 2015, IF: 0, - Opublikowane <p>Publikacje książkowe/ rozdziały w publikacjach książkowych:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Paweł Jarnicki, Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim; Postowie, Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje, (nie dotyczy), 235-296, Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich we Wrocławiu, 2015, Wrocław, http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2705.3208, - Opublikowane
<p>Publikacje dodane przez redaktora</p>	
<p>W przypadku braku publikacji naukowych, zwięzły opis innych efektów badań</p>	

NAJWAŻNIEJSZE OSIĄGNIĘCIA NAUKOWE

Informacje o najważniejszym osiągnięciu naukowym [w języku angielskim]

The most important achievement is clarification of the status of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives. Its specific situation generates specific problems for translators, who unfortunately had not recognised this specific status of Fleck's theory, so all the existing translations have to be deeply revised. Fleck's philosophical/sociological theory was expressed in two languages (Polish and German) more or less simultaneously by a bilingual author, who did not self-translate his texts into the second language, but published original texts in both of these languages. It means that both Polish and German texts are of equal value, and if we want to speak of the level of equivalence, I argue we can find it at the level of concepts - it means that expressions which differ in lexical meaning may denote the very same concept. The problem is described - with an example of "circulation of thoughts" [Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli] expression - in a paper "On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations" published in *The Translator*.

DOŚWIADCZENIE NAUKOWE

Doświadczenie naukowe zdobyte w kraju i za granicą [w języku angielskim]

- From May, 2013 to April 2016 - associated researcher of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich), [regular short stays within the realization of grant number 2012/06/M/HS2/00313].
- 07-09.2009 query in British Library (London), [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].
- 11-12.2009 query in Ludwik Fleck Archive in Zurich and Library of the University of Zurich [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].

Organisational activity:

- 2016, 10-11 March – organisation of an international conference in Wrocław (Project Science Foundation): "Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives – translations and receptions".
- 2014, 19-20 March - organisation of an international conference in Wrocław (Project Science Foundation): "Ludwik Fleck – traditions, inspirations, interpretations".
- 2014, 24-25 January - co-organisation of an international workshop in Zurich (Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum): "Translation of Science – Science of Translation".
- 2009, 14-15 October - organisation of the First Polish Constructivist Symposium in Wrocław.
- 2008 - foundation of "Science of science" circle in Wrocław - a series of meetings of PhD students and academics (34 meetings took place).

OPUS 19 (submitted 06.2020) – rejected at the second stage – 58,99%

A1. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (40%) – **3,50** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

A.2. EVALUATION OF THE INNOVATIVE NATURE OF THE PROJECT AND THE IMPACT OF ITS IMPLEMENTATION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINE (15%)

- Character of the project: **2.00** (on a scale of 0 to 3).
- Impact of the project: **2.33** (on a scale of 0–3).

B. ASSESSMENT OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR ACHIEVEMENTS (40%)

- Scientific achievements: **2.00** (on a scale of 0 to 5).
- Projects previously financed: **2.00** (on a scale of 0-5).

C. ASSESSMENT OF FEASIBILITY (5%) – **2.50** (on a scale of 0-3).

GENERAL JUSTIFICATION

Although the project is clearly interesting and could contribute significantly to the advancement of knowledge of important figures in the recent history of the philosophy of science, the team of experts has decided not to recommend the project on the basis of the reviews of the external reviewers. The main reasons have been the following:

Firstly, according to the comments of some reviewers, the connection between Fleck's and Kuhn's work has already been explored by other authors which reduces the project's innovation substantially.

Secondly, the fact that Thomas Kuhn's work is more commented on from the perspective of its influence on contemporary works together with the lack of international prestige of the principal researcher's CV raises serious doubts about the possible impact of the project at an international level and the possibility to have the results published in prestigious journals.

INDIVIDUAL REVIEWS

A.1. ASSESSMENT OF THE SCIENTIFIC LEVEL OF RESEARCH OR TASKS PLANNED FOR IMPLEMENTATION 40%

Expert 1:

The project presents a historiographic study of Ludwik Fleck's influence on Thomas Kuhn. Although the similarities between the two authors have already been documented and Thomas Kuhn himself admitted to having read Fleck's work, Fleck's influence does not seem to have been admitted, and the project proposes to attempt to unravel the extent to which Fleck's speech may have unconsciously influenced Thomas Kuhn's work.

Although the project is interesting and Thomas Kuhn's philosophy is still much discussed, I have doubts about whether the results of the project could be published in the most prestigious journals in the area. Although one finds many papers on Kuhn's philosophy, most of these papers deal with the possible influence of Kuhn on the philosophy of contemporary science, on his concepts and how

they should be understood or on how some contemporary concepts (e.g. deep disagreement) could have been advanced by the author. However, little of this literature is devoted to the influences of Thomas Kuhn. Proof of this is also that, with the exception of Jacob's paper in *Social Epistemology*, most of the publications cited in the project (Condé, Marín, Collins) are not in the top of SJR or another relevant index.

Expert 2:

This is a very good project in the fields of the history of science and the philosophy of science. The PI intends to elucidate the relationship between the basic ideas of T. Kuhn's theory of scientific revolutions and L. Fleck's ideas concerning the scientific fact, the style of thought of a research collective etc. While the similarities between the two thinkers are evident and have been often noted in the literature, a thorough and comprehensive study which would explain the actual relationship between the two conceptions (in particular, the degree of Kuhn's acquaintance with Fleck's work before publication of *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*) has not been undertaken so far. The project is based on previous research and excellent knowledge of the literature concerning these two philosophers. It clearly identifies its objectives and outlines the basic problems to be addressed. The project will go beyond typical textual studies. It will also explore the archives related to the work of the two philosophers. The data obtained from archival work can have a decisive significance for some aspects of the project's main topic. An additional merit of this project is the PI's background in literary studies and the methods of textual analysis which will be used in this research. In this way the project has the potential to trace links which typical philosophical analysis may not reveal. To strengthen the project, the PI intends to cooperate with a Co-Investigator with expertise in philosophy. These methodological aspects promise very good, novel, and high quality results.

Reviewer 1:

This project does, in a very promising way, target a crucial issue concerning the background and nature of one of the most influential philosophical enterprises of the 20th century (Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science, which e.g. introduced the term "paradigm" as basic resource in everyday talk in many languages). It does so by relating it to an earlier philosophical enterprise (Ludwik Fleck's "comparative epistemology"), which tends to attract interest in proportion to degrees of familiarity (the more people actually read Fleck's work, the higher they tend to value the challenges of its contents, whether they approve or not). There has been a lot of speculation concerning the relationship between the two enterprises, hardly ever founded on meticulous study of published and unpublished sources. In particular, much of the speculation has been hampered by an imbalance, due to the fact that one of the enterprises (Kuhn's) is far better known and easier to assess for an international audience of scholars in terms of language and accessibility of sources, whereas most assumptions have been made with more or less scanty knowledge of the other project (Fleck's). This has created quite a striking lacuna in the literature on one of the major names in 20th century philosophy. This project will offer a remedy to that, and there will be eager readers all over the world. That the project will increase an international readership's understanding of the lesser known enterprise will be a bonus (which may prove to be quite as valuable in the long run). In short: here is a research problem of highest interest, and the project's approach and methods to deal with the problem promises research on a very advanced scientific level.

Reviewer 2:

Without more of a proven track record (for example, the two pending papers mentioned by the applicant), it is not abundantly clear that the results would be published in a top journal like *Studies*

in the History and Philosophy of Science, or HOPOS, although clearly, it does have that potential, so that it could have easily received the top score. But it is not a 'mainstream' publication either.

Preliminary work and project description shows the applicant to be very well-informed and very well-positioned to attempt a challenging task. That there is no mention of Kuhn's direct role in having Fleck's book translated into English and published by the prestigious Chicago University Press seems odd, as do suggestions of plagiarism, given the prominent and widely encompassing acknowledgment to Fleck by Kuhn in the opening pages of *The Structure*, as is also lack of explicit mention of Reichenbach's role in bringing Kuhn to Fleck.

The proposed concept and work plan are sufficiently detailed, plausible, up to date, and convincingly designed. One deficiency in the design is the conspicuous lack of consideration of the sizable differences in their accounts of science generally, as well as specifically with respect to the similarities (often superficial) the applicant lists. More attention should be paid to precisely what Kuhn and Fleck were trying to say, and how much more radical and rich Fleck's views are than Kuhn's. For example, Fleck offers an externalist account (meaning is not the property of an individual's ideas, but an external relation between an individual and his community) of continuous meaning change that is fluid and fruitful between specialist communities and increasingly wider circles through to the general public and back (roughly speaking), while Kuhn has isolated technical vocabularies that are more or less insulated from outside forces and get their meaning from the application of exemplary problem solutions. There could and thus should be a list of striking differences between Kuhn and Fleck accounts, which then also should be further investigated. It is not obvious that it makes sense to start the investigation predicated on the claim that Kuhn was somehow more in debt to Fleck than Kuhn acknowledged.

Reviewer 3:

The influence of Fleck on Kuhn is an interesting topic. Unfortunately, as the applicant correctly points out, it has not been adequately examined yet. The significance of Fleck's work is also still underrated to a great extent. The project will make an important contribution to the scholarship of both Fleck and Kuhn. The research output of the project may be publishable in the specialist journals in the history of philosophy of science, such as HOPOS (The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science) and *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science*.

Reviewer 4:

The project aims at providing an in-depth account of the genealogical relationship Fleck's and Kuhn's work "in light of the best available evidence". The project contains a very strong plan for searching new historical evidence in a number of highly relevant archives, and I am confident that new and interesting material can be found here which can also lead to publications of relevance to the community of scholars interested in Fleck.

It is both a strength and a weakness of the project that it takes a linguistic/philological approach and examines metaphors and vocabulary. Clearly, only little has been done from this perspective so far, and hence it is very likely to bring new knowledge. But at the same time, that includes a risk of underestimating the importance of the overall philosophical context, and that may limit the interest of philosophers in the produced results.

Any investigation of the development of Kuhn's early work needs to consult the very detailed and careful analyses made by Hoyningen-Huene. Work of other Kuhn scholars may be highly relevant as well. I find that missing from the project description and the bibliography.

Kuhn was a very eclectic scholar and it *is* possible that he was, in fact, only in a superficial way inspired by Fleck. If that turns out to be the case, the applicant may need to revise part of the plan - but the research produced may still be very valuable.

Reviewer 5:

The research proposed by the PI has a *raison d'être*, but he slightly overestimates its novelty and significance. Its scientific level is similar to his works so far. The result will certainly be a paper which can be published in a specialist international journal. However, it is not certain that everything will develop according to the PI's expectations, for example, it is not very likely that he will find anything relevant in the Feyerabend, Lakatos, and Polányi Archives.

Reviewer 6:

The aim of the study, working hypothesis and research method are clearly defined. The principle investigator knows well the state of research on the subject of the project. The central question of to what extent Kuhn's theory of scientific revolutions is a plagiarism of Fleck's theory of thought collectives and thought styles - given Kuhn's place on the philosophical stage - causes shivers of emotions. If the working hypothesis is confirmed, articles on this topic are likely to appear in leading journals.

A.2. ASSESSMENT OF THE INNOVATIVE NATURE OF THE PROJECT AND THE IMPACT OF ITS IMPLEMENTATION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINE 15%

Expert 1:

Demonstrating the influence of one author on another always has a potential element of innovation and scientific impact in the area of the history of philosophy. However, since the relationship between Fleck and Kuhn has already been documented, such impact is limited. Furthermore, the main thesis that Fleck's influence on Kuhn as a sort of sub-conscious relationship is not pretty well formulated and some how hard to proof or not to proof.

Expert 2:

This project can have a substantial impact on the philosophy of science due to its methodological approach: 1) it will rely on methods which involve, among others, analyses of the metaphors and imageries that shaped the thought of Fleck and Kuhn, 2) it will use extensive archival research which can reveal new data.

Reviewer 1:

To ask for "innovative potential" regarding this project proposal may be misleading concerning its value within its broader research field. The project promises to do something that in a way is very obvious, something that many people must have realised "should have been done", but that has never been done, basically due to lack of the kind of qualifications that the principal investigator in this project possesses. An adequate understanding of "Kuhn in context" demands a serious ability to understand "Fleck in context". (See my assessment of the research track of the principal investigator.) To approach an "obvious" research task, with a large potential readership all over the world, with the adequate very particular qualifications (and clever choices of research material and methods) is probably the most innovative aspect of this project. From my point of view it makes it highly recommendable.

Reviewer 2:

A careful comparative analysis of Fleck and Kuhn's ideas, if done successfully, would lead to a welcome and much-needed improvement to our understanding of a key episode in the genesis and development of contemporary science studies. The project has the potential to advance the field substantially.

While there have already been numerous similar such comparisons in the past, this endeavor is innovative with respect to making use of archival resources, which promise to be a fruitful source of new insights into the relations between Kuhn and Fleck's ideas.

Reviewer 3:

The influence of Fleck on Kuhn has been examined, though, as the applicant suggests, there is no systematic and in-depth analysis. The proposed project has innovative elements in the sense that it focuses on the textual analysis of the original texts of Fleck, Kuhn, and others. In particular, the examination of the role of Polanyi in the works of Kuhn and his relation to Fleck is much needed in the literature. I believe that the proposed project will shed new light on the scholarship of Fleck, Kuhn, Polanyi, and history of philosophy of science more generally.

Reviewer 4:

No one has examined these archival resources in order to clarify the relation between the work of Kuhn and Fleck before. I am quite sure that it will reveal new details about the relation between a number of scholars

Reviewer 5:

New findings may emerge through textual and conceptual analysis, but the main topic (the relationship between Fleck and Kuhn) actually has been examined more broadly than the PI presents. Let's just refer to a few papers/books: Babich, B. E.: From Flecks Denkstil to Kuhns Paradigm: Conceptual Schemes and Incommensurability. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92. (2003); Alexander Bird: Thomas Kuhn. *Acumen* 2000 (Bird deals with Fleck and the issues discussed by the PI in a whole subsection of this book, and he also has papers on this subject.); Eva Hedfors: The Reading of Ludwik Fleck ... *Social Epistemology* Vol. 20, No. 2, pp. 131-161. (2006) and other papers by her; J. A. Marcum's book has a newer edition (2015) than the author mentions (2005) in the project literature, and there's a lot more about Fleck than before; Alexander Peine: Challenging Incommensurability: What We Can Learn from Ludwik Fleck for the Analysis of Configurational Innovation. *Minerva* 49:489-508 (2011).

The PI perhaps also exaggerates a bit the significance of the project for the advancement of philosophy of science. In short, even if we look at the most extreme case, so that Kuhn plagiarized Fleck, it is still a fact that Kuhn had a huge impact on the history of philosophy of science, and not Fleck, who was almost unknown in the West. Or, as Collins puts it in a paper known to the PI, too: "Is Kuhn's book great because it is a brilliant performance, in spite of the fact that it was not as original as we all once thought? I would say that if you think as a scientist, then it is Fleck who deserves the larger part of the credit: Fleck did it first and, in a lot of ways did it best. After all, Fleck (1979 [1935]) did not just explain thought collectives, he showed how they operated through a reflexive case study of his own work. Kuhn was a mere historian and philosopher, not a participant. If you think as a social scientist, however, Kuhn created the social change by coming along at the right time and writing in English; Fleck wrote in German and there was no English translation until 1979. Thinking as an artist, you might give Kuhn credit for dreaming up the dramatic illustrations and the vocabulary. Kuhn's scientific contribution is restricted to his more or less original ideas: scientific revolution - though I

am going to show that this too was anticipated - and incommensurability. And, of course, he was responsible for telling the history of science in a thought-collective kind of way." Harry Collins: Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science* 42(3) 420-423 (2012).

Reviewer 6:

Thomas Kuhn is the most cited philosopher of science of the twentieth century, his influence goes far beyond the philosophy of science itself. He is seen as having changed our ideas about the nature of scientific knowledge and the mechanisms of its development.

During the heated discussions around his "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" in the 1960s and 1970s, no one examined the dependence of his ideas on the epistemology of Ludwik Fleck, published in the 1930s. To this day, Fleck remains in Kuhn's shadow.

If it turned out that Kuhn did in fact plagiarized Fleck, much of the philosophy of science in the 20th century would have to be rewritten.

B. EVALUATION OF THE ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PI 40%

Expert 1:

Although the principal investigator has a good number of publications and is a recognized expert in the area of study, his curriculum is not particularly interesting from the point of view of international recognition. Most of his publications are in low impact journals and many of his writings are in Polish.

Expert 2:

The PI has completed a research project with good results published in good venues. Most of the results have been published in international journals.

Reviewer 1:

There is reason to emphatically stress the importance of the principal investigator's qualifications - particularly in terms of language skills and a documented frame of reference concerning the historical, cultural, and linguistic context of Fleck's philosophical enterprise - in order to achieve what the project promises to achieve (see my assessment concerning "scientific level"). Preliminary results for the project, such as the shrewd observation concerning the timing of Kuhn's launching of his story of the Aristotle epiphany (before he read Fleck in the late 1940s) by the time of Fleck becoming available in an English translation, are also persuasive and promising.

Reviewer 2:

The applicant has two potentially significant papers currently under review in top journals. My reservations about the feasibility of the project would have been substantially alleviated had these papers already been accepted for publication (having survived the peer-review process).

Reviewer 3:

The applicant has published extensively the works on Fleck, but most in Polish.

The project will make a contribution to the history of philosophy of science, broadly speaking. However, it should be noted that history of philosophy of science (HOPOS) is not a big branch of the philosophy of science. It is difficult to get HOPOS work published in the leading philosophy of science journals such as *Philosophy of Science* and *British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*. That said, I think that the research output of the proposed project will be publishable in the specialist journals

like *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science* and *HOPOS* (The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science).

Reviewer 4:

The project examines the relation between two major works in philosophy/philosophy of science. Major international journals for history of philosophy of science would be *HOPOS*, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science* and similar. Alas, publications in non-English/German/French in only accessible to a small audience.

Reviewer 5:

The PI has one internationally recognized paper, which was published in a Q2 (now Q1) journal in 2016, to which 9 (6 independent) citations were made.

Reviewer 6:

In 2016, the principal investigator published an article in "The Translator", a magazine that is currently awarded 100 points by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education. Google Scholar lists 5 citations of this article by foreign authors. This is a very good result, unfortunately the only one so far. Let us hope that the two texts mentioned in the project will be accepted for publication.

C. ASSESSMENT OF THE FEASIBILITY OF IMPLEMENTATION 5%

Expert 1:

Given the prior knowledge of the principal investigator, the infrastructure of the host institution and the type of sources needed to carry out the project, I see no reason why the project should not be feasible

Expert 2:

The PI's previous work and his methodology show that the project is feasible. The philosophical expertise will be provided by the Co-Investigator in this project. The host institution has sufficient resources and facilities for this work.

Reviewer 1:

The plan is very straightforward, well-structured, and based on good knowledge of possible source materials to be used (e.g. the archives that keep potentially useful documentation), and it is well adapted to the project's overarching approach and aim.

Reviewer 2:

It is not clear to me that the applicant completely appreciates all of the potential hurdles and challenges the project would have to confront. The project seems more ambitious than the applicant realizes. On the level of shared metaphors and language, the applicant seems very competent to the task, and the feasibility of the project is convincing. However, on the more difficult and more interesting level of comparing their ideas about scientific development, it is less clear to me that the applicant is completely up to the task. Many of the similarities in their ideas listed by the applicant turn out, upon closer inspection, to be much less similar than they superficially appear. The project is predicated on a clear understanding of both Fleck and Kuhn's views on science. While many attempts have been made to make sense of Kuhn's ideas, in some respects they remain controversial, and they are easily misunderstood and developed over time significantly. The situation is even more difficult with respect to Fleck as there is no standard reconstruction of his views that

could then be compared to Kuhn. Furthermore, the results of the project would only be convincing if the ideas under scrutiny are set into a wider context of views about science at that time. The applicant seems to make assumptions about the novel aspects of Kuhn's ideas that do not sufficiently appreciate their context. For example, Kuhn's theory of science was not novel because he suggested there are scientific revolutions. It was novel because it defended a role for dogma and distinguished two kinds of progress that develop through distinct phases. More generally speaking, the applicant seems to assume that certain ideas of Kuhn were new but may have originated in Fleck when both Kuhn and Fleck were just two among many who were discussing the relevant issues (theory-ladenness of observation, incommensurability, world change, etc.), and their views about science, and the roles these issues have in it, are actually very different in many relevant respects.

Reviewer 3:

The proposed project is well planned. The PI has a solid background in the scholarship of Fleck and will be substantially complementary with the Co-I, who is supposed to have multilingual skills to scrutinise the material in English, German, and Polish.

Reviewer 4:

There is a detailed plan for which archives to visit and what to look for. That seems carefully planned. Of course, plans need to be adjusted as it turns out what material is actually there, but that is natural for this kind of project

Reviewer 5:

The proposed project is feasible. The PI has proven his skills in philological analysis and knows Fleck very well. Hopefully, the co-investigator will bring the required background in philosophy of science. Unfortunately, there is no explicit international cooperation, although it may be.

Reviewer 6:

The principal investigator has extensive experience in research on the role of metaphors in scientific and philosophical texts. This should allow him to make an innovative comparison of the published texts by Fleck and Kuhn.

Letters, private notes, etc. of Fleck from the 1930s have been lost, and the witnesses are also dead. On the other hand, there are rich Kuhnian archives (and also Feyerabendian, Lakatosian, etc.). Whether they contain materials that help resolve the central question of the project is unpredictable - but it should be checked.

STRENGTHS OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

The main strength of the project is that it presents an interesting thesis from a historiographic point of view, involving one of the most important philosophers of science in history. Furthermore, the project proposes the appropriate methodology for this type of work and the author has the necessary experience to carry it out.

Expert 2

A very important issue in the history of the philosophy of science will be studied. The literary studies methodology to be applied is novel in this kind of research and the support of an expert in

philosophy is a good decision. The PI has experience in this type of research and a good publication record resulting from a similar task. The adopted approach is very promising.

Reviewer 1

See my assessment of "scientific level", "innovative potential", and "research track record of the principal investigator". In short: this is a very promising project, that has good chances of providing an international research debate with qualified knowledge concerning a matter that has been the subject of much loose speculation - an essential matter at a key juncture in the history of 20th century philosophy, including its ramifications in research fields such as Science and Technology Studies (STS) and the history and sociology of science.

Reviewer 2

The aim of the project is clear and it is undoubtedly a worthy endeavor. Research on the topic is potentially very fruitful. The plan is detailed and well-designed. The applicant seems to be very well-informed and up to date (for example, Oliveira 2017). The preliminary work (especially the vocabulary development section) is intriguing, sparks interest, and appears promising. There is good use and presentation of specific examples. The applicant's proposal to investigate common influences on the basis of archival materials is very convincing and is definitely something someone really ought to do.

Reviewer 3

The significance of Fleck in the history of philosophy of science has been to a great extent overlooked, partly due to the fact that most of his works were written in German and Polish. It is an important task for Fleck scholars to make a systematic examination of Fleck's works and ideally make them more accessible to the reader globally, especially Anglo-American philosophers of science.

The project is promising and will make an important contribution to the scholarship of Fleck and Kuhn. I think that the topic is well focused. In addition, I particularly like the approach taken by the applicant, namely, careful textual analysis. I think that it would be fruitful to examine the shared vocabulary and metaphors by Fleck and Kuhn.

Reviewer 4

The strength of the proposal is that it carefully examines whether there are additional historical sources to be found that can cast light on the relation between the work of Kuhn and Fleck, and that in examining how words and metaphors develop in Kuhn manuscripts I may be able to trace influences from Fleck that have been overlooked before.

Reviewer 5

The topic of the project is interesting, it would be worthwhile to implement it to some extent, and it is feasible. The PI has adequate skills in the required text analysis and is very familiar with Fleck. He is able to write an English language publication of appropriate quality for a specialist international journal.

Reviewer 6

The working hypothesis that Kuhn invented the "Aristotle experience" to hide his borrowings from Fleck is entirely original and very interesting. If it were confirmed, it would require rewriting the history of the philosophy of science in the 20th century. One way or another, the implementation of

the project should contribute to the equalization of the status of Fleck and Kuhn's theories of science, which the former fully deserves.

WEAKNESSES OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

The main weakness of the project is its limited innovation and the fact that the main thesis is not very articulated. The principal investigator does not propose how an alleged unconscious influence could be shown from one author to another with textual evidence. Furthermore, the international impact of the principal investigator is also very limited.

Expert 2

The research plan and its main idea do not raise issues with regard to their quality or feasibility. There are some shortcomings regarding the ethics issues involved in this project and the data management plan: the potential access to personal data and the need to address the IPRs have not been identified in the proposal. These, however, can be improved at the early stage of the implementation of the project before commencement of the archival work.

Reviewer 1

My single reservation concerning the research proposal is actually an extremely positive one: there are hidden strengths in the project that the application could have made more explicit. A major asset in this project is that it is done with language skills and a frame of reference required to understand _Ludwik Fleck's_ philosophical enterprise in its proper historical context. Thus, there is a valuable potential in the project to make _comparative_ observations, which will shed light on both contexts through the intellectual interventions done by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn, respectively. If the hypotheses of the project will prove to hold water (which is plausible), one of the most valuable aspects of the result is the way it may mirror differences in the intellectual and social context: if Kuhn actually learned fairly substantial things from Fleck, what was it then, that made the outcome (e.g. the meaning of shared terms, metaphors, and examples) turn out to be so different? How did the "moral" of the arguments turn out to be so different, for example regarding the value of "Denkverkehr" versus communication outside a scientific community, or the ideas on "democracy" in thought and "dogmatism" in science, respectively?

Reviewer 2

The two main weaknesses of the proposal are (1) lack of accepted publications by the applicant and (2) lack of consideration of the striking differences between Kuhn and Fleck with over-emphasis of superficial similarities between their views. Kuhn was struggling with the idea of the world change as a component of scientific revolutions. That is what drew Kuhn to Fleck (according to Kuhn), and that would seem to be among the most significant similarities between their views (they agree that the facts of the matter change). But even this idea is not something newly introduced by Kuhn or Fleck. It is also something about which their views diverge considerably upon closer inspection.

With some relatively minor revisions (in the direction just indicated) and a couple of papers by the applicant actually accepted for publication, this could be an outstanding proposal about which I would have no reservations in full-heartedly supporting.

Reviewer 3

The project purports to undertake archival works of Feyerabend, Merton, and Polanyi, which I find really fruitful. That said, I think that a more in-depth analysis of Polanyi is worthy of exploration. Polanyi is known to influence Kuhn's book Structures of Scientific Revolution. It would be interesting to see whether Polanyi plays a medium role between Fleck and Kuhn.

Reviewer 4

The main weakness of the project is the way in which it treats the philosophical context. This is to some degree understandable, since the literature in the area is vast. However, the work of some key scholars ought to be included, especially the work of Hoyningen-Huene who has worked in details on the development of Kuhn's work.

Reviewer 5

The PI slightly overestimates the novelty and significance of the research. He wants to travel to too many places, some of which are almost certainly not worth it. Maybe an international collaboration would help a lot. In the budget, PI's salary seems too high and that of the co-researcher too low, but this is obviously better estimated by Polish evaluators. He probably calculated the cost of accommodation at hotel prices, but since he would spend weeks/months in one place, there may be much cheaper solutions.

Reviewer 6

The project is risky: it is not known whether the archives contain material that will significantly confirm the working hypothesis. But such risks are part of any original research.

The project does not analyze Kuhn's theorems which have no counterpart in Fleck's works, e.g. about the nature and role of crisis or about extraordinary research. It would also be necessary to point out in what respects Kuhn was independent of Fleck - and possibly look for the sources of these ideas.

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

OPUS-20

Wniosek o finansowanie projektu badawczego

Na ramionach niewidocznego olbrzyma? Odkrywanie wpływu Ludwika Flecka na Thomasa Kuhna

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

Politechnika Warszawska

Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych

OPIS SKRÓCONY

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On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant? Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

1. Scientific goal of the project

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). Given that Kuhn read the *Entstehung* more than a decade before he wrote the *Structure*, it is evident that these similarities are not purely coincidental. Given the number and degrees of similarity between key concepts, it is evident that Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thought has been notable. However, Kuhn acknowledged Fleck's importance only in a few places, only in passing and only with qualifications. Still, the nature, depth and scope of Fleck's influence on Kuhn are not very well documented or analysed to date.

The aim of this inquiry in the history of philosophy of science is to provide an in-depth account of the *genealogical relationship* between Fleck's and Kuhn's work in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to commonplace philosophy of science comparison of two "ready-made" theories, the present study will pick up on the few more historically minded inquiries into the Fleck-Kuhn relation and build a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence that Fleck's writings had on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. It will do so by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. It will use the information from those sources for exploring a spectrum of possible hypotheses concerning Fleck's influence on Kuhn and assess their merits. The guiding hypothesis of this project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledged.

The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at its sceptical end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of the existence but only superficially appreciated the *Entstehung* or did not fully understand it, so any talk of an influence is exaggerated (Wray 2016, 4). At most, Fleck anticipated some views of Kuhn in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum, there are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him (Baldamus 1977, 135, 151). Between those extremes, there are views according to which Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either only had an indirect and un- or even subconscious influence on him, or that Kuhn's reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his previous ideas.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented. Mending this situation requires both comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and tracing the possible routes of concept transfer. Although both tasks are relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to demonstrate how and to what extent Fleck's concepts informed Kuhn. Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence, **the novelty of this project lies in the combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn.**

Notably, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (i.a. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011) – write little or even nothing about Fleck. On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Mößner (2011), Peine (2011). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus', which compares the vocabularies of Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books, there is little attention being paid to how Fleck's concepts may actually have informed Kuhn's. Therefore, **research on the relations between Kuhn's and Fleck's work needs to be deepened, by asking what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved. It also needs to be broadened, by analysing the metaphors and *development* of vocabulary in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials, in light of his reading of Fleck and other, partly common sources. Kuhn's theory will therefore be investigated *in statu nascendi*.**

Numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account – from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (Kuhn's teacher and boss while at Harvard), but also from Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015). Shared influences on Fleck and Kuhn will be accounted for, too, in particular those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether or not Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is one matter of investigation.

All the parallels and shared influences raise the question of what precise position of influence Fleck had on Kuhn. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed that he read Fleck's book in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date to 1950/1951, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn started to claim that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited, due to a limited grasp of Fleck's German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 only confirmed ideas that he had already conceived of before. At around the same time (in his 1976 Foreword to the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn started to trace the origins of his reasoning to what he called the "Aristotle Experience", which he dates back to 1947, when he was a 25 years old PhD student in physics who was asked by James B. Conant, his superior, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. When Kuhn found himself struggling to understand Aristotle's *Physics*, he suddenly realised that Aristotle's science is not false and meaningless but simply different from the contemporary physics that he himself was taught. From 1976 onwards, Kuhn would describe this experience as a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were born, too.

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars: 1. textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings, 2. analysis of secondary sources and 3. archival research. While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in Gestalt psychology and art history. Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. For the analysis of the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and while reading had to "translate" Fleck into contemporary English.

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:
 - 1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?
 - 1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?
 - 1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?
 - 1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?
2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:
 - 2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?
 - 2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts has been ascribed to Fleck's writings?
3. Archival research aims to provide:
 - 3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.
 - 3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

The project is divided into four nine-month periods, during which we will A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below), B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able, C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).

Work Plan

- I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
 - II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
 - III. Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.
 - IV. Archive research in
 - i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] - collect unpublished texts to be analysed in regard of vocabulary development and metaphors used; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949; check when Kuhn first read about Gestalt psychology; search for early relations about the "Aristotle experience"; check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible;
 - ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] - check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn,
 - iii. Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics] - check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability),
 - iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] - study materials regarding the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] - check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*) and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi,
 - vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know more on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).
 - V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
 - VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
 - VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
 - VIII. Comparison of vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, taking into account development of his vocabulary in time).
 - IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories - from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.
- In order to ensure prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive under (IV) will be prefaced by a detailed inquiry with the keepers of the archives into the kind and scope of material to be expected.

Preliminary research

Besides work on the peculiarities of translating Fleck (Jarnicki 2016), the PI has written two extensive articles over the last two years, which are under review for

- 1) *Foundations of Science*: “Stimmung/nastrój as content of modern science. On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck’s Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives”;
- 2) with Hans-Joachim Greif: *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*: “The Aristotle Experience Revisited. Thomas Kuhn, Ludwik Fleck and the Genesis and Development of a Scientific Revolution”.

In the first article, it is shown that Fleck’s concept of *Stimmung/nastrój* belongs to the domain of musical metaphors (the term is not properly translatable into English and usually rendered as “mood”) and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). According to Oliveira (2017) one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn’s philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other. In the second article, the authors analyse Kuhn’s few statements about Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his 1947 “Aristotle experience” and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience exactly when he found out about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn had a direct role in having Fleck’s book translated into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton Archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who got Merton into convincing University of Chicago Press to publish Fleck’s book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, who reluctantly agreed – and started to recount the Aristotle Experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

4. Research methodology

The project will employ a set of methods common to the humanities: 1) philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve surveying and analysing primary and secondary sources, retracing key concepts, arguments and references used and considering their context; 2) archival research methods (item IV in the work plan); 3) linguistic text analysis (items I, II, III, V, VI in the work plan), assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002); 4) philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve semantic analysis of key terms and as well as the development of hypotheses on the grounds of the results of the philological, conceptual and archival work.

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or near-native knowledge of English (PI, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (PI).

5. Project literature

- Babich, B. E. (2003a). “From Fleck’s Denkstil to Kuhn’s paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability”. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75–92.
- Babich, B. E. (2003b). “Kuhn’s paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller’s Tale of Harvard to Fleck’s *Unsung Lvov*”. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2–3).
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The Sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Acumen (2014 Routledge), p. 15–18.
- Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.

- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: "Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego" oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Lublin: Wydawnictwo UMCS.
- Cedarbaum, D. G. (1983). Paradigms, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, Volume 14, Issue 3, p. 173-213.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1989, *Die Wissenschaftsphilosophie Thomas S. Kuhns: Rekonstruktion und Grundlagenprobleme*. Eng. Trans. (1993). *Reconstructing Scientific Revolutions: Thomas S. Kuhn's Philosophy of Science*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1990, "Kuhn's conception of incommensurability" *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 21: 481–92.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266–276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157–168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163–173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, *English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd ed. 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G. & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?* London/New York: Bloomsbury.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Peine, A. (2011). Challenging incommensurability: What we can learn from Ludwik Fleck for the analysis of configurational innovation. *Minerva*, 49(4), 489-508.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Werner, S. & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.

OPIS SZCZEGÓŁOWY

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There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). Given that Kuhn read the *Entstehung* more than a decade before he wrote the *Structure*, it is evident that these similarities are not purely coincidental. Given the number and degrees of similarity between key concepts, it is evident that **Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thought** has been notable. However, Kuhn acknowledged Fleck's importance only in a few places, only in passing and only with qualifications. Still, the nature, depth and scope of **Fleck's influence on Kuhn** are not very well documented or analysed to date.

In his theory of thought styles and thought collectives, Fleck, like Kuhn would do after him, opposed speculation about how science should work while highlighting the importance of how it actually works. Both Fleck and Kuhn explicitly claimed that scientific knowledge is not simply additive, that it changes as a whole and questioned the classic definition of truth and the possibility of pure observation. Fleck, like Kuhn after him, observed the influence of social factors and non-verbalisable elements on the content of scientific cognition and looked at the role the history of science plays in the reflection on science. The scientists connected by one "thought style" constitute a "thought collective" in Fleck, which does not differ significantly from Kuhn's "scientific community." Kuhn's use of the term "paradigm" often does not follow his own specific technical meaning but the broad meaning of a "conceptual framework." This broad meaning is fairly close to Fleck's "thought style". Fleck, like Kuhn after him, also saw the stages of the development of a thought style. In the moments of breakthrough (Fleck writes about "intellectual unrest"), scientists seem to alternately see the old "Gestalt" and the new one, and after the breakthrough, the world in which scientists live will have changed. Fleck also referred to the incommensurability and untranslatability of thought styles and the dependence of words' meanings on thought styles – all concepts that would resurface in Kuhn.

The aim of this inquiry in the history of philosophy of science is to provide an in-depth account of the genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to the comparison of two "ready-made" theories (as presented in *Entstehung* and *Structure* respectively) that has so far been common practice in philosophy of science, the present study will pick up on the relatively few more historically minded inquiries into the Fleck-Kuhn relation and build a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence that Fleck's writings had on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. It will do so by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. It will use the information from those sources to explore a spectrum of possible hypotheses concerning Fleck's influence on Kuhn and asses their merits. The guiding hypothesis of this project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledge.

The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at its sceptical end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of the existence but only superficially appreciated the *Entstehung* or did not fully understand it, so any talk of an influence is exaggerated: "Fleck (1935/1979), for example, is often cited as having anticipated Kuhn, although more careful studies suggest that the similarities between their views are superficial." (Wray 2016, p. 4) At most, Fleck anticipated some views of Kuhn

in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum, there are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him: “The reader who is familiar with Kuhn's work will easily recognize that the majority of [Fleck’s] terms is virtually identical with the basic terminology of *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*.” (Baldamus 1977, p. 151) “Invented by Ludwik Fleck [the concept of ‘scientific community’ ...] remained ignored until Thomas Kuhn appropriated it in 1962.” (Baldamus 1977, p. 135) Between those extremes, there are views according to which Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either only had an indirect and un- or even subconscious influence on him, which might be supported by the observation that Fleck “even illustrated the idea with some of the same examples Kuhn later adopted” (Oberheim 2012, p. 128); or that Kuhn’s reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his previous ideas, which might be supported by Baldamus’ (1979) observation that key concepts that are present in Fleck can be found in Kuhn’s writings in increasing frequency over the course of the years.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented.

On the one hand, statistics from the Scopus database show that at there at least six times between 1979-2019 as many works on Kuhn than on Fleck.

Between 1979-2019 in Scopus there are 938 papers about/related to Kuhn, whereas only 157 about/related to Fleck (data from June 2020).

On the other hand, a pilot survey among Polish academics in May 2020 by the PI documents a **perceived need of acknowledging Fleck’s contribution** (P. Jarnicki, *A Survey on the Opinion of Polish Researchers on the Relationship between the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn*). The survey was conducted on a sample of 23 philosophers from Poland, who consider their knowledge of Kuhn’s and Fleck's theories to be at least good. According to the judgement of the majority of respondents, there was an influence from Fleck on Kuhn that the latter only insufficiently acknowledged¹.

Mending this situation requires both comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and tracing the possible routes of transfer of related vocabulary and metaphors. Although either task is relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to **demonstrate how and to what extent Fleck’s concepts informed Kuhn**. Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence (see below), **the novelty of this project lies in the**

¹ To the question about the connection between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories, 1 answered “don’t know” and only 1 pointed that there is “no influence”, 5 chose “anticipated” (which we interpret as no genealogical connection), 5 chose “forerunner” (which we interpret as weak genealogical connection), 7 chose “source of inspiration” (which we interpret as genealogical connection), 2 chose “strong influence” (which we interpret as significant genealogical connection), 2 chose “plagiarism”. So, 16/23 Polish philosophers see the weaker or stronger genealogical connection. To the question if “Thomas Kuhn has acknowledged the merits of Ludwik Fleck sufficiently”, 3 answered “don’t know”, only 5 answered “yes” and as many as 15 (i.e. 65%) answered “no”.

combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn.

Notably, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (i.a. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000, 2005, 2007), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011) – write little or even nothing about Fleck. For example, Alexander Bird (2000) discusses Fleck completely separately from Kuhn as just one of many elements of the background who “encouraged the rejection of the picture of science as the accumulation of knowledge driven by a rational scientific method.” In a subsection on Fleck the name Kuhn is not mentioned even once. Similarly, Marcum (2015) briefly discusses Fleck as one intellectual influence among others, such as Wittgenstein. Part of the mission of the present proposal is **to vindicate the assumption that Fleck’s influence on Kuhn has been more prominent and more pronounced than Kuhn scholarship generally acknowledges.**

On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Braunstein (2003), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Dahms (2016), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Marín (2010), Mößner (2011) and Peine (2011). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus’, which compares the vocabularies of Fleck’s 1935 and Kuhn’s 1962 books, there is little attention being paid to how Fleck’s concepts may actually have informed Kuhn’s. Therefore, **research on the relations between Kuhn’s and Fleck’s work needs to be deepened, by asking what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved. It also needs to be broadened, by analysing the metaphors and development of vocabulary in Kuhn’s writings, including his unpublished materials.** Tracing the underlying genealogical relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, whatever its concrete nature might be, will help to shed light on the conceptual similarities and differences involved.

Even when authors sympathizing with Fleck, such as Peine (2011) or Collins (2012), write about the relation between Fleck and Kuhn, they usually do not recognize this relation as genealogical one. Peine’s intention, for instance, is to show that some of Fleck’s concepts are complementary to Kuhn’s theory, as if they were synchronous affairs. Because Peine *sets out from a discussion of the differences between two “ready-made” theories*, he readily convinces himself that Kuhn rejected more than took from Fleck: “while Kuhn has indeed resembled some of Fleck’s central ideas, he was reluctant to accept Fleck’s more radical claim that science is an essentially social process”. In contrast, **the present inquiry will start from identifying the most incontrovertible similarities, and Kuhn’s theory will be compared with Fleck’s not as a “ready-made” theory, but first and foremost as a theory *in statu nascendi*.**

In the late 1970s, Wilhelm Baldamus (1977, 1979), when comparing the development of Kuhn’s vocabulary over time to Fleck’s, implicitly suggested that Thomas Kuhn may have plagiarised Fleck, in terms of “appropriating” Fleck’s key ideas and concepts to a larger extent than he would acknowledge. These allegations – presumably due to the popularity of Kuhn’s book and his authority at the time – were never thoroughly investigated. Baldamus was more outspoken in private correspondence with Robert Merton (Baldamus 1980). Notably, suspicions of plagiarism or other forms of illicit appropriation of Fleck’s ideas by Kuhn, are frequently raised in informal fashion but rarely discussed in writing. The only explicit reference to a possible charge of plagiarism against Kuhn in the literature can be found in what actually is an awkward denial of that charge. Babette Babich (2003b) claims that even if Kuhn had intended to refer to Fleck to a larger extent than he did, or even if he had been inclined to commit plagiarism, he would have been prevented from doing so because of the partly inquisitory nature of Cold War anti-communism at that time in the USA. Any reference to such “ideologically problematic terms like ‘thought collective’ and ‘thought style’” would have put Kuhn’s reputation and academic career at risk.

Conversely, Collins (2012) writes that Kuhn was not “as original as we all once thought”, because “Fleck did it first and, in a lot of ways did it best”, while adding that finally Kuhn was the one “responsible for telling the history of science in a thought-collective kind of way”, because he was the one who “created the social change by coming along at the right time and writing in English”. Some

may conclude that even if the most extreme explanation of the similarities between Kuhn and Fleck is true, namely Kuhn plagiarised Fleck, it is still a fact that Kuhn had a huge impact on the history of philosophy of science, and not Fleck, **so Fleck's philosophy is just a historical footnote**. Of course, one might think this way – the one who was successful, the one who had a successful career standing on the shoulders of other people's intellectual accomplishments is the one who carries the day. However, this is thinking in categories that one would consider outside the sphere of science – cynical thinking. If there is any reasonable evidential support for a suspicion that Thomas Kuhn illicitly appropriated his most important philosophical ideas from Ludwik Fleck, then this possibility must be explicitly considered (Jarnicki/Greif, under review).

Even if from today's perspective, **Fleck's and Kuhn's theories** appear different to an observer – he or she might be, for instance, aware of the differences between Fleck's and Kuhn's concepts of **"incommensurability"** – one has to bear in mind that such differences were probably not nearly as apparent as they are today. In the wake of the publication of the *Structure*, a wide variety of approaches to the social and cultural studies of science developed, and today we are aware of many more nuances that probably were imperceptible to people who read the *Structure* right after its publication, when it not only caused a major stir but also still had to give rise to the very social and cultural studies of science that now form the **observer's vantage point**. This is an argument against the claim that the similarity between Kuhn and Fleck is superficial upon closer inspection. Only today are we able to point out all the differences. It should also be emphasized that, in the case of an obvious relation between two authors, it would be untoward in terms of strategy and method of inquiry to discuss the differences without accounting for the similarities first. In order to adequately discuss the differences between Kuhn's and Fleck's theories, we must first thoroughly study and explicate the similarities between them and identify, to the greatest possible extent, which of these similarities are of genealogical nature.

On the other hand, **many influences that shaped both Fleck's and Kuhn's views are not at all** obvious to the contemporary observer but were nonetheless important to them in all the nuance and detail that escape us now. Accordingly, numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account – from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (**Kuhn's teacher and boss** while at Harvard), but also from Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015). An analysis of the relationship between Kuhn and the French epistemologists shows that there are indeed similarities (Simons 2017), but these appear to be far fewer than between Fleck and Kuhn, whereas the former but not the latter are documented in Kuhn's footnotes. Wray's (2016) **downplaying of Fleck's influence** in his demonstration of Conant's influence on Kuhn is weakened by the fact that Conant read Fleck's book in 1950 (see Trenn 1981), so there still might be a mediated influence.

According to Moleski (2006), **Kuhn and Polanyi met in 1958 and after publication of Kuhn's *Structure*** Polanyi had a (not publicly stated) belief that Kuhn was dishonest to him. Jacobs (2002), who argues for Kuhn's undisclosed debt to Polanyi, claims that **Kuhn's notion of scientific community is taken from Polanyi rather than from Fleck, because Fleck's thought** collective **"denotes a considerably wider class of social groups"**. Debt to Fleck certainly does not exclude debt to Polanyi, but Kuhn read Fleck earlier than he read Polanyi. We must also take into account the possibility that that Kuhn, with **Polanyi's help**, narrowed down **Fleck's general theory** of thought collectives, which is applicable to science, fashion, religion and other domains, to scientific communities. However, **Fleck's book was in fact a study of a scientific thought collective**, while many of **Kuhn's concepts**, such as 'paradigm shift', were later readily applied to domains other than science.

Shared influences on Fleck and Kuhn will be accounted for, too, in particular those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether or not Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is one matter of investigation. Oliveira's (2017) paper about the first – unpublished – chapter of the *Structure* demonstrates that in the beginnings one of the key ideas of Kuhn was to make the image of science appear closer to the image of art (as the latter develops in a non-cumulative way). In doing

this, he transferred some elements of knowledge about art history to the way we understand science. Since Fleck was informed of the concepts of style and mood (*nastrój/Stimmung*) in art history, it seems justified to ask whether these influences – on Kuhn and Fleck – were wholly independent. This question might become even more pertinent in light of the observation that Fleck remained critical of art-historical notions of style that render it as an objective characteristic of a given collective that would allow for equally objective comparison rather than the nucleus of a proto-concept of incommensurability, as it would later be articulated by Kuhn (Zittel 2011).

The influence of the Gestalt psychologists on both authors is obvious and straightforward by comparison. It seems that both Kuhn and Fleck have similarly transferred (this is kind of a metaphor) **the knowledge of psychologists to epistemology (for Fleck's reference to Gestalt psychology, see Zittel 2014 and Hagner 2012; the latter comparatively evaluates Gestalt psychology's import on Fleck and Michael Polanyi, who has also been cited as an under-acknowledged influence on Kuhn, see above).** In 1979, Cedarbaum (1983) interviewed Kuhn and wrote: **"Also, Kuhn allows that Fleck's discussion of, and emphasis on, Gestalt psychology may have awakened his own interest in the field; that contribution alone would make G.D.S.F. [*Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*] enormously significant in the formation of *Structure*."**

All these parallels and shared influences raise the question of what precise position of influence Fleck held in that relation. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed that he read Fleck's book in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date to 1950/1951, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures (**"The development of Kuhn's new image of the nature of science began with the 1951 Lowell lectures"**, Marcum 2015), i.e., after reading Fleck. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn claimed that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited, because of a **limited grasp of Fleck's** German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 were ideas that he had already conceived of before he read Fleck, **so that Fleck's *Entstehung* only confirmed his own ideas.** This change of narrative over the years is the **primary evidence for a shifting perception in Kuhn of what Fleck's import on his own thought actually was, and ultimately for an insufficiently acknowledged influence from Fleck.**

In any case, the focus of Kuhn scholarship has long been distracted from possible influences exerted by Fleck (and Polanyi?), on the grounds of one peculiar Kuhnian narrative. From 1976 (in his Foreword to *Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*, the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn started to trace the origins of his reasoning to what he called the "Aristotle Experience". According to his own account, this foundational experience took place in 1947 when he was a 25 years old PhD student in physics, and was asked by James B. Conant, his superior at the time, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. When Kuhn found himself struggling to understand Aristotle's *Physics*, which initially seemed ridiculously mistaken and misconceived to him, he suddenly realised that Aristotle's physics is not false and meaningless but simply different from the contemporary physics that he himself was taught. According to the autobiographic narrative that Kuhn would develop from 1976 onwards, this was a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were born, too. Many Kuhn scholars went along with this narrative for many years. **One aim of this project is to test Kuhn's narrative for its credibility in light of evidence of traces of his ideas concerning revolutions and paradigms that he might have formulated between his 1947 Aristotle Experience and his 1949 encounter with the *Entstehung*, and of any reading of the Gestalt psychologists or art historians before that time.**

However, if the claim that Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge Fleck's influence in one way or another is true, an important complementary task will be to reflect on what Kuhn has likely missed in **his adoption of Fleck's thought** in particular – and, in consequence, what the tradition in the history and philosophy of science that he spawned may also have missed. There are some relevant insights for **contemporary philosophy of science to be gathered here, for instance from Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój*, which is not properly translatable into English – it is usually translated as "mood" and apparently not grasped by Kuhn – but crucial to Fleck's approach.** The applicant can build on previous work on this topic (Jarnicki 2016, Jarnicki, under review).

Only when we answer the question what the similarities between the two theories are, and once we can determine with certainty what Kuhn did *not* take from Fleck, it will be possible to appreciate Kuhn's innovations – which primarily seem to be his concept of paradigms in the narrow sense and the notion of a revolutionary instead of an evolutionary development of science. Only when we know what ideas Kuhn took from Fleck, and how, we can properly gauge the nature and influence of the most famous philosophy of science book of the twentieth century. Therefore, the results of this inquiry might be relevant beyond the disciplinary debates in the history of philosophy of science.

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars:

1. **textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings**
2. analysis of historical sources and
3. archival research.

While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. For the analysis of the genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn **learned about Fleck's theory in German and had to "translate" Fleck into English** while reading.

Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in Gestalt psychology and art history. Despite living in different places at different times working and under different conditions, both authors appear to have been embedded in a similar intellectual *milieu* that deserves to be reconstructed.

Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. Therefore, archive research in various locations in Europe and the USA will form one of the pillars of the project. In order to ensure prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive will be prefaced by a detailed inquiry with its keepers into the kind and scope of material to be expected.

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:
 - 1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?
 - 1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?
 - 1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?
 - 1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?
2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:
 - 2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?
 - 2.2. **What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts has been ascribed to Fleck's writings?**
3. Archival research aims to provide:
 - 3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.
 - 3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

Work plan

The project is divided into four nine-month periods (A-D), during which we will:

- A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below),**
- B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able,**
- C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and**
- D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).**

- I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- III. **Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.**
- IV. Archive research in the following locations:
 - i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] in order to: collect unpublished texts to be analysed in **regard of vocabulary development and metaphors used; check accuracy of Kuhn's language barrier argument and resulting limited understanding of Fleck's book; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949 (when he read Fleck's book); check when Kuhn first read about Gestalt psychology; search for early relations about famous "Aristotle experience"; check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible and if yes – what Kuhn noted on margins and what underlined, check if there is any correspondence between Merton and Kuhn about Fleck, especially from the time when Merton was proofreading the translation of Fleck's book into English 1975-1979.**
 - ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] in order to check if there are any mentions of Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn [**according to Trenn Conant was to read Fleck's book in 1950**].
 - iii. Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics] in order to check if there are any mentions of Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability) - because the similarity between Fleck and Kuhn at that time must have appeared striking, it is possible that these philosophers commented on it in private correspondence.
 - iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] in order to study materials regarding the American edition **of Fleck's book**, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] in order to check whether **Polanyi read Fleck's book**; we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading

Polanyi's Personal Knowledge); check whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi.

- vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know anything that **could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence**, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011), Edward Shills, who according to **Trenn read Fleck's book** in 1937, Mark Kac, who knew both Kuhn and Fleck personally.
- V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
- VIII. Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (accounting for the development of vocabulary over time with respect to Kuhn in particular).
- IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories – from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.

Preliminary research – previous work

In 2016, the PI published a paper in *The Translator*: “On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations”. Using the example of the concept of communication/circulation of thoughts [*Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli*], it demonstrated that, since both his Polish and his German texts are original texts (in which one theory was formulated), a translator of Fleck's **work** or should mind that the level of equivalence between these texts is the level of concepts (rather than the level of lexical meaning). Similarly, when studying the relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, we will assume similarity not so much on the level of linguistic expressions, but on the level of concepts and their relations.

Over the last two years, the PI has written two extensive articles related to the topic of this proposal:

1. *Stimmung/nastrój as content of modern science. On musical metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives* (over 10 000 words), which according to information presented in the first version of this proposal was submitted to *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science. Part A*. It received one positive review (minor revisions) and one negative review and was rejected by the editor. After minor revisions it was submitted to "Foundations of Science". [Current status: under review since November 3, 2020].
2. *The Legend of Thomas Kuhn in the light and in relation to Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives* (almost 20 000 words), which according to information presented in the first version of this proposal was submitted to *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*. Following the editor-in-chief's **recommendation**, the paper was substantially revised – now in cooperation with Hans-Joachim Greif – and shortened to 16000 words before review and resubmitted to the same journal under the new title “The Aristotle Experience Revisited. Thomas Kuhn, Ludwik Fleck and the Genesis and Development of a Scientific Revolution”. [Current status: under review since November 7, 2020].

In the first article, it is shown that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój* belongs to the domain of musical metaphors (the term is not properly translatable into English **and usually rendered as “mood”**) and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). The PI then points out that one of the

most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of development of art and science as shown in Oliveira's (2017) analysis of the first, unpublished chapter of the *Structure*. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other.

In the second article, the authors first highlight the numerous similarities between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, and then show that considerations of Fleck's work are largely absent from the corpus of publications on Kuhn's philosophy of science (especially when it comes to from outside the domain of history of philosophy of science). Kuhn's few statements about Fleck are analysed in comparison with the development of his recollections of his 1947 "Aristotle experience" and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe a revelatory character to this experience exactly when he found out about the work on an English translation of Fleck. Despite his endorsement of Fleck's *Entstehung* in the *Structure*, it is doubtful that Kuhn had a direct role in having Fleck's book translated into English. According to our limited knowledge of the Robert Merton Archive, the initiative came from Trenn, who got Merton into convincing University of Chicago Press to publish Fleck's book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, who reluctantly agreed – and started to recount the Aristotle Experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

Preliminary research – vocabulary development

A prime example to demonstrate that tracking the development of Kuhn's vocabulary may prove fruitful lies in the evolution of his use of the word "thought". In Kuhn's first book (1957), we find the following passages:

Such texts are a relatively frequent and extremely significant phenomenon in the *development of scientific thought*. They may be described as texts that *shift* the direction in which *scientific thought develops* [...] As a whole the *De Revolutionibus* stands almost entirely within an ancient astronomical and cosmological tradition; yet within its generally classical framework are to be found a few novelties which *shifted* the direction of *scientific thought* in ways unforeseen by its author and which gave rise to a rapid and complete break with the ancient tradition. (Kuhn 1957, p. 135) [emphasis – PJ]

[...] the *De Revolutionibus* marks a *shift* in the direction in which astronomical *thought developed*." (Kuhn 1957, p. 182) [emphasis – PJ].

So in 1957 Kuhn writes about the "development of thought", whereas in his second book (1962) "thought" in this sense appears only once, as it seems, by accident: "conflict between competing schools of scientific thought" (Kuhn 1970, p. 96), because in 1962 he prefers to write about development of *science* instead of *thought*.

As we know, Ludwik Fleck wrote about the "development of thought", "thought styles" and "thought collectives". This is the first of the tracks to be followed: is it possible that Kuhn initially, under the influence of Fleck, wrote about the development of thought, only to liberate himself from the Fleckian vocabulary after 13 years? This makes the assumption more likely that Kuhn over time was narrowing Fleck's general theory to science.

Preliminary research – metaphors with shared aims

In the table below quotations from Fleck (1935 original and 1979 translation) and Kuhn (1962) that employ similar metaphors are juxtaposed. Both texts are about a group of people who look at one thing but see something different over the course of time. In Kuhn, the group has to experience a conversion (which is a religious metaphor), in Fleck the mood of the group has to change (which is a conceptual transfer from art history, and the concept of mood was one of the key concepts for *temple* architects). Both examples are given in the context of scientific discovery, and in both cases the passage is about a new emerging thought style (for Fleck, a shared mood [*Stimmung*] is a precondition of shared

thought style) and about a new emerging paradigm. Both paradigm and thought style determine perception by the group. The source domain from which both paradigm and thought style are conceptualised is seeing gestalts. In both cases, the gestalt metaphor is also used to underline that it is impossible to understand previous thought style/paradigm in terms of the subsequent one (and vice versa). In both cases, the metaphor is used to show that the change is not induced by reasoning and logic, and that it happens independently of the intentions of the **group's** members. In the present project, this line of investigation will be further pursued, in much more detail and on a large corpus of **Fleck's and Kuhn's writings**.

Fleck 1935 (original)	Fleck 1979 (translation)	Kuhn 1962 (original)
<p>eine Massensuggestion, die die gesamte Mannschaft eines Schiffes, auf der Suche nach einem verunglückten Boote befindlich, dieses Boot mit den Insassen wahrnehmen ließ, sogar Signalzeichen und Rufe. Erst in der letzten Minute der Annäherung platzte auf einmal die kollektive Halluzination: das Boot entpuppte sich als ein Baum mit Ästen und Blättern, von den Fluten getrieben. Dieser Fall könnte geradezu als Paradigma vieler Entdeckungen gelten: das stimmungsmäßige Gestaltsehen und der plötzliche Umschlag: andersartiges Gestaltsehen. Plötzlich versteht man überhaupt nicht, wie die frühere Gestalt möglich war und wie das ihr Widersprechende unbemerkt bleiben konnte. Genau so verhält es sich mit der wissenschaftlichen Entdeckung, nur aus der Aufregung und dem Fieber in Gleichmaß und Dauer übersetzt. Die disziplinierte, gleichmäßige und viele Generationen dauernde Stimmung eines Kollektives erzeugt das "wirkliche Bild" genau so, wie die fieberhafte eine Halluzination. In beiden Fällen verlaufen parallel Stimmungswechsel (Denkstilwechsel) und Bildwechsel. (Fleck 1935, p. 117)</p>	<p>a case of mass suggestion which induced the entire crew of a ship, while searching for a boat in distress, to see this craft and its crew and even to hear shouts and see signals. This collective hallucination was suddenly dispelled but only during the last minute of approach. The "boat" turned out to be a tree with branches and leaves drifting in the water. This case could be considered the very paradigm of many discoveries. The mood-conforming gestalt-seeing and its sudden reversal: the different gestalt-seeing. Suddenly one can no longer even understand how the previous form was possible and how features contradicting it could have gone unnoticed. The same situation obtains in scientific discovery, only translated from excitement and feverish activity into equanimity and permanence. The disciplined and even-tempered mood, persisting through many generations of a collective, produces the "real image" in exactly the same way as the feverish mood produces a hallucination. In both cases switch of mood (switch of thought style) and switch of image proceed in parallel. (Fleck 1979, p. 111)</p>	<p>Practicing in different worlds, the two groups of scientists see different things when they look from the same point in the same direction. Again, that is not to say that they can see anything they please. Both are looking at the world, and what they look at has not changed. But in some areas they see different things, and they see them in different relations one to the other. That is why a law that cannot even be demonstrated to one group of scientists may occasionally seem intuitively obvious to another. Equally, it is why, before they can hope to communicate fully, one group or the other must experience the conversion that we have been calling a paradigm shift. Just because it is a transition between incommensurables, the transition between competing paradigms cannot be made a step at a time, forced by logic and neutral experience. Like the gestalt switch, it must occur all at once (though not necessarily in an instant) or not at all. (Kuhn 1970, p. 150)</p>

4. Research methodology

The project will employ a set of methods common to the humanities:

1. Philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve surveying and analysing primary and secondary sources, retracing key concepts, arguments and references used and considering their context.
2. Archival research methods (item IV in the work plan).
3. Linguistic text analysis (items I, II, III, V, VI in the work plan), assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002).
4. Philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which will be conceptual in nature: They involve, first, probing for the meanings – as sense and reference – of key terms in Fleck, Kuhn and other relevant authors, the presumed logical relations between these terms and their place in a larger argumentative framework. Second, this work will be argumentative itself, in terms of developing hypotheses on the grounds of the results of the philological, conceptual and archival work.

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or near-native knowledge of English (Principal Investigator, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (Principal Investigator).

5. Project literature

- Babich, B. E. (2003a). From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.
- Babich, B. E. (2003b). Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).
- Baldamus, W. (1976) The structure of sociological inference. Barnes & Noble.
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for/Aufsätze für Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156, *Amsterdams Sociologisch Tijdschrift*). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. in Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The Sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Baldamus, W. (1980). Letter to R. Merton, February 6, 1980. *Robert K. Merton Papers, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5*.
- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Chesham: Acumen. Reprint (2014) London: Routledge.
- Braunstein, J.-F. (2003). Thomas Kuhn lecteur de Ludwik Fleck. *Archives de Philosophie*, 66, 403–422.
- Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.
- Cedarbaum, D. G. (1983). Paradigms. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 14(3), 173-213.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.

- Dahms, H.-J. (2016). **Thomas Kuhn's Structure: An "Exemplary Document of the Cold War Era"?** In E. Aronova & S. Turchetti (Eds.), *Science Studies during the Cold War and Beyond: Paradigms Defected* (pp. 103–125). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.
- Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: "Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego" oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Lublin: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej.
- Hagner, M. (2012). Perception, knowledge and freedom in the age of extremes: on the historical epistemology of Ludwik Fleck and Michael Polanyi. *Studies in Eastern European Thought*, 64, 107–120.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (1989). *Die Wissenschaftsphilosophie Thomas S. Kuhns: Rekonstruktion und Grundlagenprobleme*, Eng. trans. (1993) *Reconstructing Scientific Revolutions: Thomas S. Kuhn's Philosophy of Science*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (1990). **Kuhn's conception of incommensurability** *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 21: 481–92.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266–276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'**. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157–168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163–173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory**. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse. *English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (under review). Stimmung/nastrój as content of modern science. On musical metaphors in **Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives**
- Jarnicki, P., Greif, H.-J. (under review). The Aristotle Experience Revisited. Thomas Kuhn, Ludwik Fleck and the Genesis and Development of a Scientific Revolution.
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd edition 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The Essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). **Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?** London/New York: Bloomsbury.

- Marín, M. P. (2010). Ludwik Fleck: precursor del pensamiento de Thomas Kuhn. *Eidos: Revista de Filosofía de la Universidad del Norte*(13), 130–149.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oberheim, E. (2012). *Feyerabend's Philosophy*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Peine, A. (2011). Challenging incommensurability: What we can learn from Ludwik Fleck for the analysis of configurational innovation. *Minerva*, 49(4), 489-508.
- Reisch, G. A. (2016). **Aristotle in the Cold War: On the Origins of Thomas Kuhn's The Structure of Scientific Revolutions**. In R. J. Richards & L. Daston (Eds.), *Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions at Fifty: Reflections on a science classic*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.
- Sigurdsson, S. (2016). The nature of scientific knowledge: an interview with Thomas S. Kuhn. In A. Blum, K. Gavroglu, C. Joas, J. Renn (Eds.), *Shifting paradigms: Thomas S. Kuhn and the history of science* (pp. 17–30): Edition Open Access.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Trenn, T. J. (1981). Paper prepared for the Hamburg Colloquium on Ludwik Fleck held September 13th-16th, 1981: **Some Reflections on the Chicago Edition of Fleck's Monograph**. *Robert K. Merton Papers, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5*.
- Werner, S., & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions**. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.
- Zittel, C. (2011). Ludwik Fleck und der Stilbegriff in den Naturwissenschaften. Stil als wissenschaftshistorische, epistemologische und ästhetische Kategorie. In H. Bredekamp & J. Krois (Eds.), *Sehen und Handeln*. Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, pp. 171–206.
- Zittel, C. (2014). Ludwik Flecks Gestaltbegriff und sein Blick auf die Gestaltpsychologie seiner Zeit. *NTM Zeitschrift für Geschichte der Wissenschaften, Technik und Medizin*, 22(1), 9–29.

PLAN BADAŃ

Lp.	Nazwa zadania	Podmioty
1	Analiza tekstów opublikowanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do roku 1962 włącznie - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
2	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Ludwika Flecka do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć z jego teorii i pojęć z teorii zastanych.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories.	
3	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów opublikowanych).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of published texts).	
4	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Thomasa Kuhna [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	
5	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Jamesa Conanta [Harvard University Archives Repository]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in James Conant Archive [Harvard University Archives Repository]	

6	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Paula Feyerabenda [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	
7	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Roberta Mertona [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	
8	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Michaela Polanyi'ego [University of Chicago Library]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library]	
9	Badania w innych archiwach i wywiady z osobami, które mogą posiadać wiedzę mogącą rzucić światło na genealogiczny związek między teoriami Flecka i Kuhna, jak na przykład rodzina Wilhelma Baldamusa, która przechowuje jego korespondencję, poszukiwanie materiałów Thaddeusa Trenna i Harolda K. Schillinga z Pennsylvania State University, Marka Kaca i Edwarda Shillsa.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Research in other archives and interviews with individuals who might possess knowledge that could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, search for materials of Thaddeus Trenn and Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University, Mark Kac and Edward Shills.	
10	Analiza niepublikowanych tekstów Thomasa Kuhna (do roku 1962 włącznie) - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	

11	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów niepublikowanych).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of unpublished texts).	
12	Porównanie metafor stosowanych przez Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	
13	Porównanie słownictwa Flecka i Kuhna (w odniesieniu do tego ostatniego, w ujęciu diachronicznym).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, in diachronic terms).	
14	Rozważenie możliwych wyjaśnień podobieństwa teorii Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politechnika Warszawska, Wydział Administracji i Nauk Społecznych
	Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	

ANKIETY CZŁONKÓW ZESPOŁU

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki, Kierownik (PI)

PRZEBIEG KARIERY NAUKOWEJ

Informacje o przebiegu kariery naukowej [w języku angielskim]

- From October 2018 (to June 2024) - **assistant professor** (half time) at Warsaw University of Technology; Faculty of Administration and Social Sciences; Department of Philosophy and Ethics in Administration.
- From May 2015 - member of the Academy of Young Scholars and Artists (Wrocław), from May 2017 to July 2019 Vice-Chairman.
- From May, 2013 to April, 2016 - **associated researcher** of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich).
- From April, 2013 to September, 2016 - **principal investigator** of the project 'Philological analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical works and its translations into Polish, English and German' (2012/06/M/HS2/00313). The project is funded by National Science Centre in Cracow (Narowe Centrum Nauki w Krakowie) in HARMONIA scheme (international cooperation) and is realized in Project Science Foundation (Fundacja Projekt Nauka).
- From 2012 - member of the Board of Project Science Foundation, from December 2016 to December 2019 **Chairman of the Board**.
- 15 May, 2012 - PhD in humanities. Thesis: 'Metaphorical conceptualizations of the notion of 'text' and changes of thought styles in literary studies'. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty.
- 2009-2011 - **investigator** within the doctoral project (University of Wrocław) funded by Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (State Committee for Scientific Research in Poland [Komitet Badań Naukowych] titled: 'A method of analysis of metaphors in scientific texts as factors of change in science' (N N101 060336).
- 15 July, 2005 - **Master of Arts**, thesis: 'Metaphors of intertextuality. Onomasiological-cognitive Analysis'. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty, Institute of Polish Philology.

It should be noted that although PI's academic career has lasted for over a dozen of years (he begun his doctoral studies in 2005), the period of his full-time employment lasted for four years and a half (from April, 2013 to September, 2016 - full time, from October 2018 to November 2020 - half time). During his doctoral studies, PI did not receive any scholarship that would allow him to not take up other works. He is a father of three children (born in 2011, 2015 and 2019).

In the last two years, PI has written two extensive articles:

1. *The Legend of Thomas Kuhn in the light and in relation to Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives* (almost 20 000 words), which according to informations presented in the first version of this proposal was submitted to "Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie". The paper was - in cooperation with Hans-Joachim Greif - shortened to 16000 words, substantially revised (as suggested by the the Editor-in-chief) and resubmitted to the same journal under the new title ***The Aristotle Experience Revisited. Thomas Kuhn, Ludwik Fleck and the Genesis and Development of a Scientific Revolution***. [Current status: under review since November 7, 2020].
2. ***Stimmung/nastroj as content of modern science. On musical metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives*** (over 10 000 words), wchich according to informations presented in the first version of this proposal was submitted to "Studies in History and Philosophy of Science". It received one positive review (minor revisions) and one negative review and was rejected by the editor. After minor revisions it was submitted to "Foundations of Science". [Current status: under review since November 3, 2020].

Besides that, PI is now finalizing with Maria Ciesielska a book in Polish entitled ***Ludwik Fleck - a microbiologist and philosopher*** (to be published in 2021), which systematizes to date and present new knowledge about both Fleck's biography and microbiological and philosophical achievements. PI is also finalizing work on a **new Polish translation of Fleck's book *Entstehung und Entwicklung...*** (to be published in 2021). Both books are included in the publishing plan of the Warsaw University of Technology Publishing House.

PUBLIKACJE NAUKOWE

1. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Translator
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	22 (2016), 3, p. 271–286
Rok publikacji	2016
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	8
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	10.1080/13556509.2015.1126881
PDF publikacji	On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish German and English translations.pdf

2. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989)</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989)
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	1 (2016 - special issue on Ludwik Fleck), p. 21-30
Rok publikacji	2016

Otwarty dostęp	Tak
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	0
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	10.24117/2526-2270.2016.i1.05
PDF publikacji	Jarnicki.pdf

3. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Metaforyczne konceptualizacje pojęcia 'tekstu' a przemiany stylów myślowych w literaturoznawstwie [Metaphorical conceptualizations of the concept of 'text' and changes of thought styles in history and theory of literature]</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Metaforyczne konceptualizacje pojęcia 'tekstu' a przemiany stylów myślowych w literaturoznawstwie [Metaphorical conceptualizations of the concept of 'text' and changes of thought styles in history and theory of literature]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	książka
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	Wrocław: Wydawnictwo 'Projekt Nauka', pp. 246
Rok publikacji	2014
Otwarty dostęp	Tak
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	2
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	Metaforyczne konceptualizacje - Paweł Jarnicki.pdf

4. Paweł Jarnicki, Bożena Płonka-Syroka, Bogdan Balicki , <i>Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje [Ludwik Fleck - traditions - inspirations - interpretations]; [in the volume: Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie, p. 235–37; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim, p. 239–55; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim, p. 257–94; Postowie, p. 295–96]</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki, Bożena Płonka-Syroka, Bogdan Balicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje [Ludwik Fleck - traditions - inspirations - interpretations]; [in the volume: Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie, p. 235–37; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim, p. 239–55; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim, p. 257–94; Postowie, p. 295–96]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	książka

Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich
Rok publikacji	2015
Otwarty dostęp	Tak
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	4
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

5. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Kłopoty z przedwojenną recepcją koncepcji Ludwika Flecka: [On some problems with the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in the prewar period]</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Kłopoty z przedwojenną recepcją koncepcji Ludwika Flecka: [On some problems with the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in the prewar period]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	STUDIA PHILOSOPHICA WRATISLAVIENSIA
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	6. (2), p. 133–39
Rok publikacji	2011
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	2
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

6. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of "legitimation" [Polish extended version appeared as: O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka. In: Stan Rzeczy 10, p. 355-373]</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki

Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of "legitimation" [Polish extended version appeared as: O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka. In: Stan Rzeczy 10, p. 355-373]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Divinatio: Studia Culturologica Series
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	vol. 41, autumn-winter, p. 167-184
Rok publikacji	2015
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	0
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

7. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Ludwika Flecka nauka bez prawdy?</i> [Science by Ludwik Fleck - without truth?]	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Ludwika Flecka nauka bez prawdy? [Science by Ludwik Fleck - without truth?]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Przegląd Filozoficzny - Nowa Seria
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	19 (2 (74)): p. 63–79
Rok publikacji	2010
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	1
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada

PDF publikacji	
8. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Metafory dyskursu intertekstualności, metaforyka tekstylna</i> [Metaphors of intertextuality. Textile metaphors]	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Metafory dyskursu intertekstualności, metaforyka tekstylna [Metaphors of intertextuality. Textile metaphors]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	Kształcenie Językowe
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	13 (23): p. 49–72
Rok publikacji	2015
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	0
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

9. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>W sprawie wystąpienia Wojciecha Sadego pt. 'O tym, co decyduje o naukowości badań przyrodniczych'</i> [On Wojciech Sady's lecture: 'What determines the scientific nature of scientific research']	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	W sprawie wystąpienia Wojciecha Sadego pt. 'O tym, co decyduje o naukowości badań przyrodniczych' [On Wojciech Sady's lecture: 'What determines the scientific nature of scientific research']
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	artykuł
Czasopismo	STUDIA PHILOSOPHICA WRATISLAVIENSIA
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	6, nr 2, s. 55–61.
Rok publikacji	2011
Otwarty dostęp	Nie

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	0
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

10. Paweł Jarnicki , <i>Antytalitarne motywy twórczości Ludwika Flecka [Antitotalitarian motives in Ludwik Fleck's writings]</i>	
Autorzy	Paweł Jarnicki
Tytuł w języku oryginalnym [oraz tłumaczenie tytułu na język angielski]	Antytalitarne motywy twórczości Ludwika Flecka [Antitotalitarian motives in Ludwik Fleck's writings]
Artykuł/książka/rozdział	rozdział
Informacje dodatkowe, np.: tytuł monografii w języku oryginalnym, wydawca, miejsce wydania, numer tomu/zeszytu, strony, ISBN/ISSN, redaktorzy i inne.	W: Nauka w kontekście wzorców kultury, red. Bożena Płonka-Syroka, s. 91–102. Seria: Antropologia wiedzy 5. Warszawa: DiG.
Rok publikacji	2011
Otwarty dostęp	Nie
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań)	0
Status publikacji	Opublikowane
DOI	nie posiada
PDF publikacji	

BADANIA NAUKOWE FINANSOWANE PRZEZ NCN

DANE POBRANE AUTOMATYCZNIE

Tytuł w języku polskim	Filologiczna analiza filozoficznych dzieł Ludwika Flecka oraz ich tłumaczeń w językach: polskim, niemieckim i angielskim
Nr rejestracyjny	2012/06/M/HS2/00313
Źródło(a) finansowania	NCN
Nazwa konkursu	HARMONIA-3
Kwota	405 512 PLN
Podmiot realizujący w języku polskim	Projekt Nauka. Fundacja na rzecz promocji nauki polskiej
Data rozpoczęcia realizacji	2013-03-25
Data zakończenia realizacji	2016-08-24
Wynik oceny raportu końcowego	Uznanie umowy za wykonaną
Lista najważniejszych publikacji będących rezultatem projektu (skopiowana automatycznie z ostatniego raportu zaakceptowanego przez NCN)	<p>Publikacje w czasopismach:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Paweł Jarnicki, Sandra Lang ("Introduction"); Paweł Jarnicki ("The beginnings..."), Introduction; The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989), <i>Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science</i>, 1, 3-5; 21-30, Graduate Program in History (Science and Culture in History) of Federal University of Minas Gerais (Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais), Brasil, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane - Paweł Jarnicki, On the Shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the Bilingual Philosophical Legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English Translations, <i>The Translator</i>, 22 (3), 271–286, Routledge, 2016, IF: 0.483, - Opublikowane - Paweł Jarnicki, O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka, <i>Stan Rzeczy</i>, 10, 355-373, Instytut Socjologii UW, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane - Paweł Jarnicki, Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of “legitimation”, <i>Divinatio</i>, 41 (Aut.-Win.), 167-184, University of Sofia, Department of Cultural Studies, 2015, IF: 0, - Opublikowane <p>Publikacje książkowe/ rozdziały w publikacjach książkowych:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Paweł Jarnicki, Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim; Postówie, Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje, (nie dotyczy), 235-296, Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich we Wrocławiu, 2015, Wrocław, http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2705.3208, - Opublikowane
Publikacje dodane przez redaktora	

INNE PROJEKTY BADAWCZE SPOZA NCN

Tytuł	Metoda analizy metafor w tekstach naukowych jako czynników zmiany w nauce [A method of analysis of metaphors in scientific texts as factors of change in science]
Nr rejestracyjny	N N101 060336
Źródło(a) finansowania	Komitet Badań Naukowych [Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (State Committee for Scientific Research)]
Kwota	31 850 PLN
Podmiot realizujący	Uniwersytet Wrocławski [University of Wrocław]
Data rozpoczęcia realizacji	2009-03-11
Data zakończenia realizacji	2011-09-10
Lista najważniejszych publikacji będących rezultatem projektu	<p>1. P. Jarnicki, Jak przeprowadzić analizę onomazjologiczno-kognitywną tekstu teoretycznego, w zbiorze: Kultura w nauce o literaturze, red. B. Balicki, B. Ryż, E. Szczerbuk, Wrocław 2009, s. 197-207.</p> <p>2. Redakcja numeru specjalnego "Studia Philosophica Wratislaviensia" 2011, nr 2 (numer poświęcony Ludwikowi Fleckowi), w tym tomie teksty:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - P. Jarnicki, Wstęp [redaktora numeru], s. 5-12. - P. Jarnicki, W sprawie wystąpienia Wojciecha Sadego pt. 'O tym, co decyduje o naukowości badań przyrodniczych', s. 55-61. - P. Jarnicki, Początki anglojęzycznej recepcji koncepcji L. Flecka, s. 77-79. - P. Jarnicki, Kłopoty z przedwojenną recepcją koncepcji Ludwika Flecka, s. 133-137. - P. Jarnicki, Trzeci tom Fleckowski [rec. Ludwik Fleck, Style myślowe i fakty. Artykuły i świadectwa, red. S. Werner, C. Zittel, F. Schmaltz, Warszawa, IFiS PAN 2007], s. 191-204. - (Tłumaczenie P. Jarnicki z Dariuszem Zienkiewiczem) H. Petersen, Ludwig Flecks Lehre vom Denkstil und dem Denkkollektiv, ("Klinische Wochenschrift" 1936 (7), 15.02.1936, p. 239-242). - (Tłumaczenie P. Jarnicki z Marceliną Zuber: T. S. Kuhn, Foreword, in: L. Fleck, Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact, ed. T. J. Trenn, R. K. Merton, tłum. F. Bradley, University of Chicago Press 1979), s. 81-85. - (Tłumaczenie P. Jarnicki z Marceliną Zuber: W. Baldamus, Ludwig Fleck and the development of the sociology of science, in: Human Figurations. Essays for Aufsätze für Norbert Elias, ed. P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, H. Korte, Amsterdams Socialogisch Tijdschrift 1977), s.87-105. - (Tłumaczenie P. Jarnicki z Marceliną Zuber: R. S. Cohen, Th. Schnelle, Introduction, in: Cognition and Fact: Materials on Ludwik Fleck, ed. R. S. Cohen, Th. Schnelle, Reidel 1986), s. 107-129.
W przypadku braku publikacji naukowych, zwięzły opis innych efektów badań	

NAJWAŻNIEJSZE OSIĄGNIĘCIA NAUKOWE

Informacje o najważniejszym osiągnięciu naukowym [w języku angielskim]

The most important achievement is clarification of the status of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives. Its specific situation generates specific problems for translators, who unfortunately had not recognised this specific status of Fleck's theory, so all the existing translations have to be deeply revised. Fleck's philosophical/sociological theory was expressed in two languages (Polish and German) more or less simultaneously by a bilingual author, who did not self-translate his texts into the second language, but published original texts in both of these languages. It means that both Polish and German texts are of equal value, and if we want to speak of the level of equivalence, I argue we can find it at the level of concepts - it means that expressions which differ in lexical meaning may denote the very same concept. The problem is described - with an example of "circulation of thoughts" [Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli] expression - in a paper "On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations" published in The Translator.

DOŚWIADCZENIE NAUKOWE

Doświadczenie naukowe zdobyte w kraju i za granicą [w języku angielskim]

- From May, 2013 to April 2016 - associated researcher of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich), [regular short stays within the realization of grant number 2012/06/M/HS2/00313].
- 07-09.2009 query in British Library (London), [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].
- 11-12.2009 query in Ludwik Fleck Archive in Zurich and Library of the University of Zurich [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].

Organisational activity:

- 2016, 10-11 March – organisation of an international conference in Wrocław (Project Science Foundation): "Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives – translations and receptions".
- 2014, 19-20 March - organisation of an international conference in Wrocław (Project Science Foundation): "Ludwik Fleck – traditions, inspirations, interpretations".
- 2014, 24-25 January - co-organisation of an international workshop in Zurich (Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum): "Translation of Science – Science of Translation".
- 2009, 14-15 October - organisation of the First Polish Constructivist Symposium in Wrocław.
- 2008 - foundation of "Science of science" circle in Wrocław - a series of meetings of PhD students and academics (34 meetings took place).

CONFERENCE PAPERS (from 2014)

- 24-25 January, 2014, Zurich, international workshop: "Translation of Science – Science of Translation" (Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum) two papers: 1) "Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings: some editions and translations compared", 2) "The first and the last philosophical texts of Ludwik Fleck, and the translations compared";
- 19-20 March, 2014, Wrocław, international conference: "Ludwik Fleck – traditions, inspirations, interpretations", (Fundacja Projekt Nauka); paper: "On some problems with English, Polish and German translations of Ludwik Fleck";
- 10-11 April, 2014, Toruń, conference: IV Polish Constructivist Symposium in Toruń (Institute of Philosophy of Nicolaus Copernicus University), paper: "Metaphors of eugenics";
- 17-19 September, 2014, Toruń, international conference: "Situating Solidarities" (European Association for the Study of Science and Technology and Nicolaus Copernicus University), paper: "'Gestalts' of Ludwik Fleck";
- 27-29 November, 2014, Berlin, international conference: "Self-Translation as Transfer of Knowledge" (Zentrum für Literatur- und Kulturforschung), paper: "Ludwik Fleck's Legacy – an Example of Self-Translation?"
- 3-8 August, 2015, Helsinki, international conference: 15th Congress on Logic, Methodology, and Philosophy of Science 2015 (University of Helsinki), paper: "The reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives in English"
- 28-30 October 2015, Marburg, international conference: "Entangled science? Relocating German-Polish scientific relations" (the Leibniz Association and the Polish Academy of Sciences), poster: "Ludwik Fleck's "Polish-German" theory of thought styles and thought collectives, and problems arising from its translation";
- 10-11 March 2016, Wrocław, international conference: "Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives – translations and receptions" (Fundacja Projekt Nauka in cooperation with Ludwik Fleck Zentrum, Max-Planck-Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte, Ludwik Fleck Kreis), two talks: 1) [with Rainer Egloff] On translating Ludwik Fleck between Polish, German and English, 2) Reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Poland.
- June 23-26, 2020, Singapore, international conference HOPOS 2020 (The Thirteenth Biennial Congress of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science), paper: "The role of (conceptual) metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings" selected for presentation but the event was cancelled.

OPUS 20 (submitted 12.2020) – rejected at the first stage – 49,00%

A1. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (25%) – **4,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

A2. POTENTIAL IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%) – **1,00** (on a scale of 0 to 2).

A3. FEASIBILITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%) – **1,00** (on a scale of 0 to 2).

B.1 QUALIFICATIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (35%) – **2,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

B2. PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR'S INVOLVEMENT IN RESEARCH PROJECTS NOT CO-FINANCED FROM THE POLISH BUDGET, SELECTED IN THE EUROPEAN UNION RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMMES (ERC, 7TH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME, HORIZON 2020 AND HORIZON EUROPE) (10%) – **0,00** (on a scale of 0 to 4)

GENERAL JUSTIFICATION

The research project is of high quality: it addresses a problem of high importance and interest to historians of the philosophy of science. It has a clear research questions, some hypotheses to answer it, and a well-described methodology for how the hypotheses will be pursued. It has some minor weaknesses however, e.g. it could improve in motivating more why the hypothesis of two parallel 'ready-made' theories is not well supported, and thus motivate better the need of developing the alternative ones the project aims to investigate.

The potential impact of the project is moderate. It is possible that the project will lead to some novel results but also possible that it will conclude with the hypothesis that is currently favoured/established of two parallel "ready-made" theories. The application does not make a cogent case that the project will have surely significant impact on the advancement of the research field.

The feasibility of the project is moderate. The assessors have found the general methodological approach appropriate for the project. However, since there is no cogent case made in the project that the current views (in particular the hypothesis of two parallel "ready-made" theories) are not well grounded, it remains unclear whether the research that the applicant proposed to carry out will deliver a breakthrough. This is an important risk that the proposal does not discuss.

The scientific achievements of the applicant are moderate. The publications are either books published in Polish, or appear in low-impact venues.

INDIVIDUAL REVIEWS

A1. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (25%)

Expert 1:

The proposal poses a question of interest to historians of the philosophy of science. It has a clear research questions, some hypotheses to answer it, and a well-described methodology for how the hypotheses will be pursued. It could improve in motivating more why the hypothesis of two parallel 'ready made' theories is not well supported and thus motivates the developing of alternative ones.

Expert 2:

The author proposes to study the impact on a not very well known philosopher of science on Kuhn, another philosopher of science, whose extreme positions are usually not considered plausible by people working in the philosophy of science nowadays. This is a purely historical study, to be performed from a literary perspective by focusing on how the relevant figures used certain metaphors and the vocabularies used by the authors. While of limited interest to researchers working on a rather narrow class of problems in the history of philosophy of science, the results don't seem to cast new light on deeper philosophical problems of wider interest.

Panel I:

Experts agreed on the final score for this criterion.

A2. POTENTIAL IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%)

Expert 1:

It is possible that the project will lead to some novel results but also possible that it will conclude with the hypothesis that is currently favoured/established of two parallel "ready made" theories. Also for the project to have impact, the results needs to be published in international if possible competitive publication venues; and it is not clear from the evidence presented that the applicant will be able to do this.

Expert 2:

While of limited interest to researchers working on a rather narrow class of problems in the history of philosophy of science, the results don't seem to cast new light on deeper philosophical problems of wider interest.

Panel I:

Experts agreed on the final score for this criterion.

A3. FEASIBILITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%)

Expert 1:

My assessment to be accurate is between high and moderate. certainly the project can be carried out as an exploration of various hypotheses but what it will include and how cogent it will be, remains to be seen. Since there is no cogent case made that the current views are not well grounded it remains unclaeer that they will be really overturned.

Expert 2:

Comparing the vocabularies used by two different authors is doable.

Panel I:

Experts agreed on the final score for this criterion.

B1. SCIENTIFIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (35%)

Expert 1:

While the PI gives some reasons to explain his productivity and achievements, the issue is not 'quantity' but rather than none of his publications for instance can be seen to have had international recognition and impact and his profile overall is not of international 'weight'

Expert 2:

Publications are either books published in Polish, or appear in low-impact venues. Note also lack of background in philosophy, which might make doing sensible research in the philosophy of science tricky (and the content of the proposal does not reveal any philosophical depth).

B2. PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR'S INVOLVEMENT IN RESEARCH PROJECTS NOT CO-FINANCED FROM THE POLISH BUDGET, SELECTED IN THE EUROPEAN UNION RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMMES (ERC, 7TH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME, HORIZON 2020 AND HORIZON EUROPE) (10%)

Expert 1:

The PI has not been involved in projects that meet the criteria in B2 section.

Expert 2:

Self-explanatory.

Panel I

Experts agreed on the final score for this criterion.

STRENGTHS OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

Generally speaking it may be worthwhile reassessing the 'genealogy' of Kuhn's ideas and what might have influenced them. Further the applicant makes a great effort to explain his hypotheses and his methods in detail. There are some aspects of the proposed collaborations that are well motivated (e.g. archive visits).

Expert 2

- PI has the literary competence to run the comparative study

WEAKNESSES OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

The two main weaknesses of the proposal are: the fact that the current view is not adequately shown to need re-discussion and in fact remains in play as one of the possible hypotheses of the project; the applicant does not show evidence of a robust publications and research leadership track record, especially within an international context.

Expert 2

it is not clear why such a comparative study should be performed

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

OPUS-22

Wniosek o finansowanie projektu badawczego

Na ramionach niewidocznego olbrzyma? Odkrywanie wpływu Ludwika Flecka na Thomasa Kuhna

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

Uniwersytet Wrocławski

Wydział Nauk Społecznych

OPIS SKRÓCONY

On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant?

Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

1. Scientific goal of the project

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). Given that Kuhn read the *Entstehung* more than a decade before he wrote the *Structure*, it is evident that these similarities are not purely coincidental. Given the number and degrees of similarity between key concepts, it is evident that Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thought has been notable. However, Kuhn acknowledged Fleck's importance only in a few places, only in passing and only with qualifications. Still, the nature, depth and scope of Fleck's influence on Kuhn are not very well documented or analysed to date.

The aim of this inquiry in the history of philosophy of science is to provide an in-depth account of the **genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work** in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to commonplace philosophy of science comparison of two "ready-made" theories, the present study will pick up on the few more historically minded inquiries into the Fleck-Kuhn relation and build a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence that Fleck's writings had on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. It will do so by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. It will use the information from those sources for exploring a spectrum of possible hypotheses concerning Fleck's influence on Kuhn and assess their merits. The guiding hypothesis of this project is that **Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledged.**

The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at its sceptical end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of the existence but only superficially appreciated the *Entstehung* or did not fully understand it, so any talk of an influence is exaggerated (Wray 2016, 4). At most, Fleck anticipated some views of Kuhn in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum, there are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him (Baldamus 1977, 135, 151). Between those extremes, there are views according to which Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either only had an indirect and un- or even subconscious influence on him, or that Kuhn's reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his previous ideas.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented. Mending this situation requires both comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and tracing the possible routes of concept transfer. Although both tasks are relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to demonstrate how and to what extent Fleck's concepts informed Kuhn. Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence, **the novelty of this project lies in the combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn.**

Notably, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (i.a. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011) – write little or even nothing about Fleck. On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Mößner (2011), Peine (2011). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus', which compares the vocabularies of Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books, there is little attention being paid to how Fleck's concepts may actually have informed Kuhn's. Therefore, research on the relations between Kuhn's and Fleck's work needs to be deepened, by asking **what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved.** It also needs to be broadened, by **analysing the metaphors and development of vocabulary in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials,** in light of his reading of Fleck and other, partly common sources. **Kuhn's theory will therefore be investigated *in statu nascendi.***

Numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account – from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (Kuhn's teacher and boss while at Harvard), but also from Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015). Shared influences on Fleck and Kuhn will be accounted for, too, in particular those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether or not Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is one matter of investigation.

All the parallels and shared influences raise the question of what precise position of influence Fleck had on Kuhn. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed that he read Fleck's book in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date to 1950/1951, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn started to claim that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited, due to a limited grasp of Fleck's German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 only confirmed ideas that he had already conceived of before. At around the same time (in his 1976 *Foreword* to the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn started to trace the origins of his reasoning to what he called the "Aristotle Experience", which he dates back to 1947, when he was a 25 years old PhD student in physics who was asked by James B. Conant, his superior, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. When Kuhn found himself struggling to understand Aristotle's Physics, he suddenly realised that Aristotle's science is not false and meaningless but simply different from the contemporary physics that he himself was taught. From 1976 onwards, Kuhn would describe this experience as a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were born, too. (For more on these circumstantial evidences, see: Jarnicki, Greif 2021)

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars: 1. textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings, 2. analysis of secondary sources and 3. archival research. While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in *Gestalt* psychology and art history. Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. For the analysis of the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and while reading had to "translate" Fleck into contemporary English.

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:

1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?

1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?

1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?

1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?

2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:

2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?

2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts has been ascribed to Fleck's writings?

3. Archival research aims to provide:

3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.

3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

Work Plan

The project is divided into four nine-month periods, during which we will A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below), B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able, C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).

- I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- III. **Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.**
- IV. Archive research in
 - i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] - collect unpublished texts to be analysed in regard of vocabulary development and metaphors used; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949; check when Kuhn first read about *Gestalt psychology*; **search for early relations about the "Aristotle experience"; check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible;**
 - ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] - check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn,
 - iii. **Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics]** - check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability),
 - iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] - study **materials regarding the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,**
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] - **check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*) and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi,**
 - vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know more on the **genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).**
- V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
- VIII. Comparison of vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, taking into account development of his vocabulary in time).
- IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories - from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.

In order to ensure prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive under (IV) will be prefaced by a detailed inquiry with the keepers of the archives into the kind and scope of material to be expected.

Preliminary research

Besides work on the peculiarities of translating Fleck (Jarnicki 2016), the PI has written two extensive articles over the last two years (Jarnicki 2021; Jarnicki, Greif 2021). In the first article, it is shown that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój* belongs to the domain of musical metaphors (the term is not properly translatable into English and usually rendered as “mood”) and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). According to Oliveira (2017) one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other. In the second article, the authors analyse Kuhn's few statements about Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his 1947 “Aristotle experience” and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience exactly when he found out about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn had a direct role in having Fleck's book translated into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton Archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who got Merton into convincing University of Chicago Press to publish Fleck's book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, who reluctantly agreed – and started to recount the Aristotle Experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

4. Research methodology

The project will employ a set of methods common to the humanities:

- 1) philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve surveying and analysing primary and secondary sources, retracing key concepts, arguments and references used and considering their context;
- 2) archival research methods (item IV in the work plan);
- 3) linguistic text analysis (items I, II, III, V, VI in the work plan), assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002);
- 4) philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve semantic analysis of key terms and as well as the development of hypotheses on the grounds of the results of the philological, conceptual and archival work.

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or near-native knowledge of English (PI, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (PI).

5. Project literature

- Babich, B. E. (2003a). “From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability”. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.
- Babich, B. E. (2003b). “Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*”. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The Sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Acumen (2014 Routledge), p. 15-18.
- Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: "Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego" oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Lublin: Wydawnictwo UMCS.
- Cedarbaum, D. G. (1983). Paradigms, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, Volume 14, Issue 3, p. 173-213.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1989, *Die Wissenschaftsphilosophie Thomas S. Kuhns: Rekonstruktion und Grundlagenprobleme*. Eng. Trans. (1993). *Reconstructing Scientific Revolutions: Thomas S. Kuhn's Philosophy of Science*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1990, "Kuhn's conception of incommensurability" *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 21: 481–92.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266–276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157–168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163–173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, *English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) *Stimmung/Nastrój* as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives. *Foundations of Science* (early on-line).
- Jarnicki, P.; Greif, H. (2021) The Aristotle Experience Revisited. Thomas Kuhn, Ludwik Fleck and the Genesis and Development of a Scientific Revolution, *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie* (accepted with minor corrections, enclosed to the proposal).
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd ed. 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G. & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?* London/New York: Bloomsbury.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Peine, A. (2011). Challenging incommensurability: What we can learn from Ludwik Fleck for the analysis of configurational innovation. *Minerva*, 49(4), 489-508.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Werner, S. & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.

OPIS SZCZEGÓŁOWY

On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant? Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

1. Scientific goal of the project

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). Given that Kuhn read the *Entstehung* more than a decade before he wrote the *Structure*, it is evident that these similarities are not purely coincidental. Given the number and degrees of similarity between key concepts, it is evident **that Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thought has been notable. However, Kuhn acknowledged Fleck's importance only in a few places, only in passing and only with qualifications. Still, the nature, depth and scope of Fleck's influence on Kuhn are not very well documented or analysed to date.**

In his theory of thought styles and thought collectives, Fleck, like Kuhn would do after him, opposed speculation about how science should work while highlighting the importance of how it actually works. Both Fleck and Kuhn explicitly claimed that scientific knowledge is not simply additive, that it changes as a whole and questioned the classic definition of truth and the possibility of pure observation. Fleck, like Kuhn after him, observed the influence of social factors and non-verbalisable elements on the content of scientific cognition and looked at the role the history of science plays in **the reflection on science. The scientists connected by one "thought style" constitute a "thought collective" in Fleck, which does not differ significantly from Kuhn's "scientific community."** Kuhn's use of the term "paradigm" often does not follow his own specific technical meaning but the broad meaning of a "conceptual framework." This broad meaning is fairly close to Fleck's "thought style". Fleck, like Kuhn after him, also saw the stages of the development of a thought style. In the moments of breakthrough (Fleck writes about "intellectual unrest"), scientists seem to alternately see the old "Gestalt" and the new one, and after the breakthrough, the world in which scientists live will have changed. Fleck also referred to the incommensurability and untranslatability of thought styles and the **dependence of words' meanings on thought styles** – all concepts that would resurface in Kuhn.

The aim of this **inquiry in the history of philosophy of science** is to provide an in-depth account of the **genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work** in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to the comparison of two "ready-made" theories (as presented in *Entstehung* and *Structure* respectively) that has so far been common practice in philosophy of science, the present study will pick up on the relatively few more historically minded inquiries into the Fleck-Kuhn relation and **build a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence that Fleck's writings had on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. It will do so by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. It will use the information from those sources to explore a spectrum of possible hypotheses concerning Fleck's influence on Kuhn and asses their merits. The guiding hypothesis of this project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledge.**

The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at its sceptical end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of the existence but only superficially appreciated the *Entstehung* or did not fully understand it, so any talk of an influence is exaggerated: "Fleck (1935/1979), for example, is

often cited as having anticipated Kuhn, although more careful studies suggest that the similarities between their views are superficial.” (Wray 2016, p. 4) At most, Fleck anticipated some views of Kuhn in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum, there are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him: “The reader who is familiar with Kuhn's work will easily recognize that the majority of [Fleck's] terms is virtually identical with the basic terminology of *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*.” (Baldamus 1977, p. 151) “Invented by Ludwik Fleck [the concept of ‘scientific community’ ...] remained ignored until Thomas Kuhn appropriated it in 1962.” (Baldamus 1977, p. 135) Between those extremes, there are views according to which Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either only had an indirect and un- or even subconscious influence on him, which might be supported by the observation that Fleck “even illustrated the idea with some of the same examples Kuhn later adopted” (Oberheim 2012, p. 128); or that Kuhn's reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his previous ideas, which might be supported by Baldamus' (1979) observation that key concepts that are present in Fleck can be found in Kuhn's writings in increasing frequency over the course of the years.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented.

On the one hand, statistics from the Scopus database show that at there at least six times between 1979-2019 as many works on Kuhn than on Fleck.

Between 1979-2019 in Scopus there are 938 papers about/related to Kuhn, whereas only 157 about/related to Fleck.

On the other hand, a pilot survey among Polish academics in May 2020 by the PI documents a perceived need of acknowledging Fleck's contribution (P. Jarnicki, *A Survey on the Opinion of Polish Researchers on the Relationship between the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn*). The survey was conducted on a sample of 23 philosophers from Poland, who consider their knowledge of Kuhn's and Fleck's theories to be at least good. According to the judgement of the majority of respondents, there was an influence from Fleck on Kuhn that the latter only insufficiently acknowledged¹.

Mending this situation requires both **comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and tracing the possible routes of transfer of related vocabulary and metaphors**. Although either task is relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to demonstrate how and to what extent Fleck's concepts informed Kuhn. Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence (see below), **the novelty of this project lies in the**

¹ To the question about the connection between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, 1 answered “don't know” and only 1 pointed that there is “no influence”, 5 chose “anticipated” (which we interpret as no genealogical connection), 5 chose “forerunner” (which we interpret as weak genealogical connection), 7 chose “source of inspiration” (which we interpret as genealogical connection), 2 chose “strong influence” (which we interpret as significant genealogical connection), 2 chose “plagiarism”. So, 16/23 Polish philosophers see the weaker or stronger genealogical connection. To the question if “Thomas Kuhn has acknowledged the merits of Ludwik Fleck sufficiently”, 3 answered “don't know”, only 5 answered “yes” and as many as 15 (i.e. 65%) answered “no”.

combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn.

Notably, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (i.a. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000, 2005, 2007), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011) – write little or even nothing about Fleck. For example, Alexander Bird (2000) discusses Fleck completely separately from Kuhn as just one of **many elements of the background who “encouraged the rejection of the picture of science as the accumulation of knowledge driven by a rational scientific method.”** In a subsection on Fleck the name Kuhn is not mentioned even once. Similarly, Marcum (2015) briefly discusses Fleck as one intellectual influence among others, such as Wittgenstein. Part of the mission of the present proposal is to **vindicate the assumption that Fleck’s influence on Kuhn has been more prominent and more pronounced than Kuhn scholarship generally acknowledges.**

On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Braunstein (2003), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Dahms (2016), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Marín (2010), Mößner (2011) and Peine (2011). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus’, which compares the vocabularies of Fleck’s 1935 and Kuhn’s 1962 books, there is little attention being paid to how Fleck’s concepts may actually have informed Kuhn’s. Therefore, research on the relations between Kuhn’s and Fleck’s work needs to be deepened, by asking **what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved.** It also needs to be broadened, by **analysing the metaphors and development of vocabulary in Kuhn’s writings, including his unpublished materials.** Tracing the underlying genealogical relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, whatever its concrete nature might be, will help to shed light on the conceptual similarities and differences involved.

Even when authors sympathizing with Fleck, such as Peine (2011) or Collins (2012), write about the relation between Fleck and Kuhn, they usually do not recognize this relation as genealogical one. Peine’s intention, for instance, is to show that some of Fleck’s concepts are complementary to Kuhn’s theory, as if they were synchronous affairs. Because Peine sets out from a discussion of the differences between two “ready-made” theories, he readily convinces himself that Kuhn rejected more than took from Fleck: “while Kuhn has indeed resembled some of Fleck’s central ideas, he was reluctant to accept Fleck’s more radical claim that science is an essentially social process”. In contrast, the **present inquiry will start from identifying the most incontrovertible similarities, and Kuhn’s theory will be compared with Fleck’s not as a “ready-made” theory, but first and foremost as a theory *in statu nascendi*.**

In the late 1970s, Wilhelm Baldamus (1977, 1979), when comparing the development of Kuhn’s vocabulary over time to Fleck’s, implicitly suggested that Thomas Kuhn may have plagiarised Fleck, in terms of “appropriating” Fleck’s key ideas and concepts to a larger extent than he would acknowledge. These allegations – presumably due to the popularity of Kuhn’s book and his authority at the time – were never thoroughly investigated. Baldamus was more outspoken in private correspondence with Robert Merton (Baldamus 1980). Notably, suspicions of plagiarism or other forms of illicit appropriation of Fleck’s ideas by Kuhn, are frequently raised in informal fashion but rarely discussed in writing. The only explicit reference to a possible charge of plagiarism against Kuhn in the literature can be found in what actually is an awkward denial of that charge. Babette Babich (2003b) claims that even if Kuhn had intended to refer to Fleck to a larger extent than he did, or even if he had been inclined to commit plagiarism, he would have been prevented from doing so because of the partly inquisitory nature of Cold War anti-communism at that time in the USA. Any reference to such “ideologically problematic terms like ‘thought collective’ and ‘thought style’” would have put Kuhn’s reputation and academic career at risk.

Conversely, Collins (2012) writes that Kuhn was not “as original as we all once thought”, because “Fleck did it first and, in a lot of ways did it best”, while adding that finally Kuhn was the one “responsible for telling the history of science in a thought-collective kind of way”, because he was the one who “created the social change by coming along at the right time and writing in English.” Some may conclude that even if the most extreme explanation of the similarities between Kuhn and Fleck is true, namely Kuhn plagiarised Fleck, it is still a fact that Kuhn had a huge impact on the history of philosophy of science, and not Fleck, so Fleck’s philosophy is just a historical footnote. Of course, one might think this way – the one who was successful, the one who had a successful career standing on the shoulders of other people’s intellectual accomplishments is the one who carries the day. However, this is thinking in categories that one would consider outside the sphere of science – cynical thinking. If there is any reasonable evidential support for a suspicion that Thomas Kuhn illicitly appropriated his most important philosophical ideas from Ludwik Fleck, then this possibility must be explicitly considered (Jarnicki, Greif 2021).

Even if from today’s perspective, Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories appear different to an observer – he or she might be, for instance, aware of the differences between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s concepts of “incommensurability” – one has to bear in mind that such differences were probably not nearly as apparent as they are today. In the wake of the publication of the *Structure*, a wide variety of approaches to the social and cultural studies of science developed, and today we are aware of many more nuances that probably were imperceptible to people who read the *Structure* right after its publication, when it not only caused a major stir but also still had to give rise to the very social and cultural studies of science that now form the observer’s vantage point. This is an argument against the claim that the similarity between Kuhn and Fleck is superficial upon closer inspection. Only today are we able to point out all the differences. It should also be emphasized that, in the case of an obvious relation between two authors, it would be untoward in terms of strategy and method of inquiry to discuss the differences without accounting for the similarities first. In order to adequately discuss the differences between Kuhn’s and Fleck’s theories, we must first thoroughly study and explicate the similarities between them and identify, to the greatest possible extent, which of these similarities are of genealogical nature.

On the other hand, many influences that shaped both Fleck’s and Kuhn’s views are not at all obvious to the contemporary observer but were nonetheless important to them in all the nuance and detail that escape us now. Accordingly, numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account – from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Héléne Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (Kuhn’s teacher and boss while at Harvard), but also from Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015). An analysis of the relationship between Kuhn and the French epistemologists shows that there are indeed similarities (Simons 2017), but these appear to be far fewer than between Fleck and Kuhn, whereas the former but not the latter are documented in Kuhn’s footnotes. Wray’s (2016) downplaying of Fleck’s influence in his demonstration of Conant’s influence on Kuhn is weakened by the fact that Conant read Fleck’s book in 1950 (see Trenn 1981), so there still might be a mediated influence.

According to Moleski (2006), Kuhn and Polanyi met in 1958 and after publication of Kuhn’s *Structure* Polanyi had a (not publicly stated) belief that Kuhn was dishonest to him. Jacobs (2002), who argues for Kuhn’s undisclosed debt to Polanyi, claims that Kuhn’s notion of scientific community is taken from Polanyi rather than from Fleck, because Fleck’s thought collective “denotes a considerably wider class of social groups”. Debt to Fleck certainly does not exclude debt to Polanyi, but Kuhn read Fleck earlier than he read Polanyi. We must also take into account the possibility that that Kuhn, with Polanyi’s help, narrowed down Fleck’s general theory of thought collectives, which is applicable to science, fashion, religion and other domains, to scientific communities. However, Fleck’s book was in

fact a study of a scientific thought collective, while many of Kuhn's concepts, such as 'paradigm shift', were later readily applied to domains other than science.

Shared influences on Fleck and Kuhn will be accounted for, too, in particular those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether or not Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is one matter of investigation. Oliveira's (2017) paper about the first – unpublished – chapter of the *Structure* demonstrates that in the beginnings one of the key ideas of Kuhn was to make the image of science appear closer to the image of art (as the latter develops in a non-cumulative way). In doing this, he transferred some elements of knowledge about art history to the way we understand science. Since Fleck was informed of the concepts of style and mood (*nastrój/Stimmung*) in art history, it seems justified to ask whether these influences – on Kuhn and Fleck – were wholly independent (Jarnicki 2021). This question might become even more pertinent in light of the observation that Fleck remained critical of arthistorical notions of style that render it as an objective characteristic of a given collective that would allow for equally objective comparison rather than the nucleus of a proto-concept of incommensurability, as it would later be articulated by Kuhn (Zittel 2011).

The influence of the Gestalt psychologists on both authors is obvious and straightforward by comparison. It seems that both Kuhn and Fleck have similarly transferred (this is kind of a metaphor) the knowledge of psychologists to epistemology (for Fleck's reference to Gestalt psychology, see Zittel 2014 and Hagner 2012; the latter comparatively evaluates Gestalt psychology's import on Fleck and Michael Polanyi, who has also been cited as an under-acknowledged influence on Kuhn, see above). In 1979, Cedarbaum (1983) interviewed Kuhn and wrote: "Also, Kuhn allows that Fleck's discussion of, and emphasis on, Gestalt psychology may have awakened his own interest in the field; that contribution alone would make G.D.S.F. [*Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*] enormously significant in the formation of *Structure*."

All these parallels and shared influences raise the question of what precise position of influence Fleck held in that relation. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed that he read Fleck's book in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date to 1950/1951, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures ("The development of Kuhn's new image of the nature of science began with the 1951 Lowell lectures", Marcum 2015), i.e., after reading Fleck. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn claimed that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited, because of a limited grasp of Fleck's German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 were ideas that he had already conceived of before he read Fleck, so that Fleck's *Entstehung* only confirmed his own ideas. This change of narrative over the years is the primary evidence for a shifting perception in Kuhn of what Fleck's import on his own thought actually was, and ultimately for an insufficiently acknowledged influence from Fleck (Jarnicki, Greif 2021).

In any case, the focus of Kuhn scholarship has long been distracted from possible influences exerted by Fleck (and Polanyi?), on the grounds of one peculiar Kuhnian narrative. From 1976 (in his Foreword to *Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*, the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn started to trace the origins of his reasoning to what he called the "Aristotle Experience". According to his own account, this foundational experience took place in 1947 when he was a 25 years old PhD student in physics, and was asked by James B. Conant, his superior at the time, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. When Kuhn found himself struggling to understand Aristotle's Physics, which initially seemed ridiculously mistaken and misconceived to him, he suddenly realised that Aristotle's physics is not false and meaningless but simply different from the contemporary physics that he himself was taught. According to the autobiographic narrative that Kuhn would develop from 1976 onwards, this was a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were born, too. Many Kuhn scholars went along with this narrative for many

years (Jarnicki, Greif 2021). One aim of this project is to test Kuhn's narrative for its credibility in light of evidence of traces of his ideas concerning revolutions and paradigms that he might have formulated between his 1947 Aristotle Experience and his 1949 encounter with the *Entstehung*, and of any reading of the Gestalt psychologists or art historians before that time.

However, if the claim that Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge Fleck's influence in one way or another is true, an important complementary task will be to reflect on what Kuhn has likely missed in his adoption of Fleck's thought in particular – and, in consequence, what the tradition in the history and philosophy of science that he spawned may also have missed. There are some relevant insights for contemporary philosophy of science to be gathered here, for instance from Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastroj*, which is not properly translatable into English – it is usually translated as “mood” and apparently not grasped by Kuhn – but crucial to Fleck's approach. The applicant can build on previous work on this topic (Jarnicki 2016, Jarnicki 2021).

Only when we answer the question what the similarities between the two theories are, and once we can determine with certainty what Kuhn did not take from Fleck, it will be possible to appreciate Kuhn's innovations – which primarily seem to be his concept of paradigms in the narrow sense and the notion of a revolutionary instead of an evolutionary development of science. Only when we know what ideas Kuhn took from Fleck, and how, we can properly gauge the nature and influence of the most famous philosophy of science book of the twentieth century. Therefore, the results of this inquiry might be relevant beyond the disciplinary debates in the history of philosophy of science.

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars:

1. textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings
2. analysis of historical sources and
3. archival research.

While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. For the analysis of the genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and had to “translate” Fleck into English while reading.

Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in Gestalt psychology and art history. Despite living in different places at different times working and under different conditions, both authors appear to have been embedded in a similar intellectual milieu that deserves to be reconstructed.

Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. Therefore, archive research in various locations in Europe and the USA will form one of the pillars of the project. In order to ensure prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive will be prefaced by a detailed inquiry with its keepers into the kind and scope of material to be expected.

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:
 - 1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?

- 1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?
- 1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?
- 1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?
2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:
 - 2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?
 - 2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts has been ascribed to Fleck's writings?**
3. Archival research aims to provide:
 - 3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.
 - 3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

Work plan

The project is divided into four nine-month periods (A-D), during which we will:

- A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below),
- B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able,
- C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and
- D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).

I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.

II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.

III. Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's **philosophical writings regarding metaphors used to create concepts** of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.

IV. Archive research in the following locations:

- i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] in order to: collect unpublished texts to be analysed in regard of **vocabulary development and metaphors used; check accuracy of Kuhn's language barrier argument and resulting limited understanding of Fleck's book; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in Structure before 1949 (when he read Fleck's book);** check when Kuhn first read about Gestalt psychology; search for early relations about famous "Aristotle experience"; **check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible and if yes – what Kuhn noted on margins and what underlined, check if there is any correspondence between Merton and Kuhn about Fleck, especially from the time when Merton was proofreading the translation of Fleck's book into English 1975-1979.**

- ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] in order to check if there are any mentions of Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn [according to **Trenn Conant was to read Fleck's book in 1950**].
 - iii. **Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos Archive** [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics] in order to check if there are any mentions of Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability) - because the similarity between Fleck and Kuhn at that time must have appeared striking, it is possible that these philosophers commented on it in private correspondence.
 - iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] in order to **study materials regarding the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,**
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] in order to check whether Polanyi **read Fleck's book; we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's Personal Knowledge)**; check whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi.
 - vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know anything that could **shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling** from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, **see Werner 2011**), **Edward Shills, who according to Trenn read Fleck's book in 1937**, Mark Kac, who knew both Kuhn and Fleck personally.
- V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
- VIII. Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (accounting for the development of vocabulary over time with respect to Kuhn in particular).
- IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories – from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.

Preliminary research – previous work

In 2016, the PI published a paper in *The Translator*: “**On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations**”. Using the example of the concept of communication/circulation of thoughts [*Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli*], it demonstrated that, since both his Polish and his German texts are original texts (in which one theory **was formulated**), **a translator of Fleck's work or should mind that the level of equivalence between these texts is the level of concepts (rather than the level of lexical meaning)**. Similarly, when studying the relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, we will assume similarity not so much on the level of linguistic expressions, but on the level of concepts and their relations.

Over the last two years, the PI has written two extensive articles related to the topic of this proposal (Jarnicki 2021; Jarnicki, Greif 2021). In the first article, it is shown that Fleck's concept of **Stimmung/nastroj** belongs to the domain of musical metaphors (the term is not properly translatable

into English and usually rendered as “mood”) and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). According to Oliveira (2017) one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other.

In the second article, the authors analyse Kuhn's few statements about Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his 1947 “Aristotle experience” and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience exactly when he found out about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn had a direct role in having Fleck's book translated into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton Archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who got Merton into convincing University of Chicago Press to publish Fleck's book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, who reluctantly agreed – and started to recount the Aristotle Experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

Preliminary research – vocabulary development

A prime example to demonstrate that tracking the development of Kuhn's vocabulary may prove fruitful lies in the evolution of his use of the word “thought”. In Kuhn's first book (1957), we find the following passages:

Such texts are a relatively frequent and extremely significant phenomenon in the *development of scientific thought*. They may be described as texts that *shift* the direction in which *scientific thought develops* [...] As a whole the *De Revolutionibus* stands almost entirely within an ancient astronomical and cosmological tradition; yet within its generally classical framework are to be found a few novelties which *shifted* the direction of *scientific thought* in ways unforeseen by its author and which gave rise to a rapid and complete break with the ancient tradition. (Kuhn 1957, p. 135) [emphasis – PJ]

[...] the *De Revolutionibus* marks a *shift* in the direction in which astronomical *thought developed*. (Kuhn 1957, p. 182) [emphasis – PJ].

So in 1957 Kuhn writes about the “development of thought”, whereas in his second book (1962) “thought” in this sense appears only once, as it seems, by accident: “conflict between competing schools of scientific thought” (Kuhn 1970, p. 96), because in 1962 he prefers to write about development of *science* instead of *thought*.

As we know, Ludwik Fleck wrote about the “development of thought”, “thought styles” and “thought collectives”. This is the first of the tracks to be followed: is it possible that Kuhn initially, under the influence of Fleck, wrote about the development of thought, only to liberate himself from the Fleckian vocabulary after 13 years? This makes the assumption more likely that Kuhn over time was narrowing Fleck's general theory to science.

Preliminary research – metaphors with shared aims

In the table below quotations from Fleck (1935 original and 1979 translation) and Kuhn (1962) that employ similar metaphors are juxtaposed. Both texts are about a group of people who look at one thing but see something different over the course of time. In Kuhn, the group has to experience a conversion (which is a religious metaphor), in Fleck the mood of the group has to change (which is a conceptual transfer from art history, and the concept of mood was one of the key concepts for temple architects). Both examples are given in the context of scientific discovery, and in both cases the passage is about a new emerging thought style (for Fleck, a shared mood [*Stimmung*] is a precondition of shared

thought style) and about a new emerging paradigm. Both paradigm and thought style determine perception by the group. The source domain from which both paradigm and thought style are conceptualised is seeing gestalts. In both cases, the gestalt metaphor is also used to underline that it is impossible to understand previous thought style/paradigm in terms of the subsequent one (and vice versa). In both cases, the metaphor is used to show that the change is not induced by reasoning and logic, and that it happens independently of the intentions of the group's members. In the present project, this line of investigation will be further pursued, in much more detail and on a large corpus of Fleck's and Kuhn's writings.

Fleck 1935 (original)	Fleck 1979 (translation)	Kuhn 1962 (original)
<p>eine Massensuggestion, die die gesamte Mannschaft eines Schiffes, auf der Suche nach einem verunglückten Boote befindlich, dieses Boot mit den Insassen wahrnehmen ließ, sogar Signalzeichen und Rufe. Erst in der letzten Minute der Annäherung platzte auf einmal die kollektive Halluzination: das Boot entpuppte sich als ein Baum mit Asten und Blättern, von den Fluten getrieben. Dieser Fall könnte geradezu als Paradigma vieler Entdeckungen gelten: das stimmungsmäßige Gestaltsehen und der plötzliche Umschlag: andersartiges Gestaltsehen. Plötzlich versteht man überhaupt nicht, wie die frühere Gestalt möglich war und wie das ihr Widersprechende unbemerkt bleiben konnte. Genau so verhält es sich mit der wissenschaftlichen Entdeckung, nur aus der Aufregung und dem Fieber in Gleichmaß und Dauer übersetzt. Die disziplinierte, gleichmäßige und viele Generationen dauernde Stimmung eines Kollektives erzeugt das "wirkliche Bild" genau so, wie die fieberhafte eine Halluzination. In beiden Fällen verlaufen parallel Stimmungswechsel (Denkstilwechsel) und Bildwechsel. (Fleck 1935, p. 117)</p>	<p>a case of mass suggestion which induced the entire crew of a ship, while searching for a boat in distress, to see this craft and its crew and even to hear shouts and see signals. This collective hallucination was suddenly dispelled but only during the last minute of approach. The "boat" turned out to be a tree with branches and leaves drifting in the water. This case could be considered the very paradigm of many discoveries. The mood-conforming gestalt-seeing and its sudden reversal: the different gestalt-seeing. Suddenly one can no longer even understand how the previous form was possible and how features contradicting it could have gone unnoticed. The same situation obtains in scientific discovery, only translated from excitement and feverish activity into equanimity and permanence. The disciplined and even-tempered mood, persisting through many generations of a collective, produces the "real image" in exactly the same way as the feverish mood produces a hallucination. In both cases switch of mood (switch of thought style) and switch of image proceed in parallel. (Fleck 1979, p. 111)</p>	<p>Practicing in different worlds, the two groups of scientists see different things when they look from the same point in the same direction. Again, that is not to say that they can see anything they please. Both are looking at the world, and what they look at has not changed. But in some areas they see different things, and they see them in different relations one to the other. That is why a law that cannot even be demonstrated to one group of scientists may occasionally seem intuitively obvious to another. Equally, it is why, before they can hope to communicate fully, one group or the other must experience the conversion that we have been calling a paradigm shift. Just because it is a transition between incommensurables, the transition between competing paradigms cannot be made a step at a time, forced by logic and neutral experience. Like the gestalt switch, it must occur all at once (though not necessarily in an instant) or not at all. (Kuhn 1970, p. 150)</p>

4. Research methodology

The project will employ a set of methods common to the humanities:

1. Philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve surveying and analysing primary and secondary sources, retracing key concepts, arguments and references used and considering their context.

2. Archival research methods (item IV in the work plan).

3. Linguistic text analysis (items I, II, III, V, VI in the work plan), assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002).

4. Philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which will be conceptual in nature: They involve, first, probing for the meanings – as sense and reference – of key terms in Fleck, Kuhn and other relevant authors, the presumed logical relations between these terms and their place in a larger argumentative framework. Second, this work will be argumentative itself, in terms of developing hypotheses on the grounds of the results of the philological, conceptual and archival work.

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or near-native knowledge of English (Principal Investigator, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (Principal Investigator).

5. Project literature

Babich, B. E. (2003a). From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.

Babich, B. E. (2003b). Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).

Baldamus, W. (1976) *The structure of sociological inference*. Barnes & Noble Books.

Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for/Aufsätze für Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156, *Amsterdams Sociologisch Tijdschrift*). Amsterdam.

Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.

Baldamus, W. (1980). Letter to R. Merton, February 6, 1980. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5.

Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Chesham: Acumen. Reprint (2014) London: Routledge.

Braunstein, J.-F. (2003). Thomas Kuhn lecteur de Ludwik Fleck. *Archives de Philosophie*, 66, 403–422.

Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.

Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.

Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.

Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.

Dahms, H.-J. (2016). Thomas Kuhn's Structure: An "Exemplary Document of the Cold War Era"? In E. Aronova & S. Turchetti (Eds.), *Science Studies during the Cold War and Beyond: Paradigms Defected* (pp. 103–125). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.

- Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Fleck, L. (1935). Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: „Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego” oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej.
- Hagner, M. (2012). Perception, knowledge and freedom in the age of extremes: on the historical epistemology of Ludwik Fleck and Michael Polanyi. *Studies in Eastern European Thought*, 64, 107–120
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266–276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of ‘scientific community’.** *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157–168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163–173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn’s memory.** *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) **Stimmung/Nastrój** as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck’s Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives. *Foundations of Science* (early on-line).
- Jarnicki, P; Greif, H. (2021) The Aristotle Experience Revisited. Thomas Kuhn, Ludwik Fleck and the Genesis and Development of a Scientific Revolution, *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie* (accepted with minor corrections, enclosed to the proposal).
- Jäkel, O. (2002). Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse.** *English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd edition 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). Metaphors we live by.** Chicago, IL: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). **Thomas Kuhn’s revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?** London/New York: Bloomsbury.
- Marín, M. P. (2010). Ludwik Fleck: precursor del pensamiento de Thomas Kuhn.** *Eidos: Revista de Filosofía de la Universidad del Norte*(13), 130–149.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn.** *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oberheim, E. (2012). *Feyerabend’s Philosophy*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.

- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Reisch, G. A. (2016). Aristotle in the Cold War: On the Origins of Thomas Kuhn's The Structure of Scientific Revolutions. In R. J. Richards & L. Daston (Eds.), *Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions at Fifty: Reflections on a science classic*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.
- Sigurdsson, S. (2016). The nature of scientific knowledge: an interview with Thomas S. Kuhn. In *Shifting paradigms: Thomas S. Kuhn and the history of science* (pp. 17–30): Edition Open Access.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Trenn, T. J. (1981). Paper prepared for the Hamburg Colloquium on Ludwik Fleck held September 13th-16th, 1981: Some Reflections on the Chicago Edition of Fleck's Monograph. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5 .
- Werner, S., & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.
- Zittel, C. (2011). Ludwik Fleck und der Stilbegriff in den Naturwissenschaften. Stil als **wissenschaftshistorische, epistemologische und ästhetische Kategorie**. In H. Bredekamp & J. Krois (Eds.), *Sehen und Handeln*. Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, pp. 171–206.
- Zittel, C. (2014). Ludwik Flecks Gestaltbegriff und sein Blick auf die Gestaltpsychologie seiner Zeit. *NTM Zeitschrift für Geschichte der Wissenschaften, Technik und Medizin*, 22(1), 9–29.

PLAN BADAŃ

Lp.	Nazwa zadania	Podmioty
1	Analiza tekstów opublikowanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do roku 1962 włącznie - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
2	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Ludwika Flecka do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć z jego teorii i pojęć z teorii zastanych	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories	
3	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów opublikowanych)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of published texts)	
4	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Thomasa Kuhna [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	
5	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Jamesa Conanta [Harvard University Archives Repository]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in James Conant Archive [Harvard University Archives Repository]	
6	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Paula Feyerabenda [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	

7	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Roberta Mertona [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	
8	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Michaela Polanyi'ego [University of Chicago Library]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library]	
9	Badania w innych archiwach i wywiady z osobami, które mogą posiadać wiedzę mogącą rzucić światło na genealogiczny związek między teoriami Flecka i Kuhna, jak na przykład rodzina Wilhelma Baldamusa, która przechowuje jego korespondencję, poszukiwanie materiałów Thaddeusa Trenna i Harolda K. Schillinga z Pennsylvania State University, Marka Kaca i Edwarda Shillsa.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Research in other archives and interviews with individuals who might possess knowledge that could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, search for materials of Thaddeus Trenn and Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University, Mark Kac and Edward Shills.	
10	Analiza niepublikowanych tekstów Thomasa Kuhna (do roku 1962 włącznie) - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
11	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów niepublikowanych)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of unpublished texts)	
12	Porównanie metafor stosowanych przez Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	

13	Porównanie słownictwa Flecka i Kuhna (w odniesieniu do tego ostatniego, w ujęciu diachronicznym)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, in diachronic terms)	
14	Rozważenie możliwych wyjaśnień podobieństwa teorii Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	

ANKIETY DOROBKU CZŁONKÓW ZESPOŁU

KIEROWNIK (PI)

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

PRZEBIEG KARIERY NAUKOWEJ

- From October 2018 (to February 2022) - **assistant professor** (half time) at Warsaw University of Technology; Faculty of Administration and Social Sciences; Department of Philosophy and Ethics in Administration.
- From May 2015 - member of the Academy of Young Scholars and Artists (Wrocław), from May 2017 to July 2019 Vice-Chairman.
- From May, 2013 to April, 2016 - **associated researcher** of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich). From April, 2013 to September, 2016 - principal investigator of the project 'Philological analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical works and its translations into Polish, English and German' (2012/06/M/HS2/00313). The project was funded by National Science Centre in Cracow (Narowe Centrum Nauki w Krakowie) in HARMONIA scheme (international cooperation) and was realized in Project Science Foundation (Fundacja Projekt Nauka).
- From 2012 - **member of the Board** of Project Science Foundation, from December 2016 to December 2019 **Chairman of the Board**.
- 15 May, 2012 - **Ph.D. in humanities**. Thesis: 'Metaphorical conceptualizations of the notion of 'text' and changes of thought styles in literary studies'. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty.
- 2009-2011 - **investigator** within the doctoral project (University of Wrocław) funded by Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (State Committee for Scientific Research in Poland [Komitet Badań Naukowych] titled: 'A method of analysis of metaphors in scientific texts as factors of change in science' (N N101 060336).
- 15 July, 2005 - **Master of Arts**, thesis: 'Metaphors of intertextuality. Onomasiological-cognitive Analysis'. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty, Institute of Polish Philology.

It should be noted that although PI's academic career has lasted for over a dozen of years (he begun his doctoral studies in 2005), the period of his full-time employment lasted for five years (from April, 2013 to September, 2016 - full time, from October 2018 to November 2021 - half time). During his doctoral studies, PI did not receive any scholarship that would allow him to not take up other works. He is a father of three children (born in 2011, 2015 and 2019).

PUBLIKACJE NAUKOWE

1. Paweł Jarnicki, Hajo Greif, *The Aristotle Experience Revisited. Thomas Kuhn, Ludwik Fleck and the Genesis and Development of a Scientific Revolution* (2021), artykuł, Archiv fur Geschichte der Philosophie, accepted with minor corrections
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: przyjęta do publikacji, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu, Potwierdzenie przyjęcia do druku do pobrania z systemu*
2. Paweł Jarnicki, *Stimmung/Nastrój as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives* (2021), artykuł, Foundations of Science, online since 05 April 2021
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10699-021-09792-3>
Status publikacji: opublikowane
3. Paweł Jarnicki, *On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations* (2016), artykuł, Translator, 22:3, 271-286
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 10
Otwarty dostęp: nie, DOI <https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2015.1126881>
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
4. Maria Ciesielska, Paweł Jarnicki, *Ludwik Fleck - mikrobiolog i filozof [Ludwik Fleck - microbiologist and philosopher]* (2021), książka, Oficyna Wydawnicza Politechniki Warszawskiej; ISBN 978-83-8156-251-5 (druk) ISBN

978-83-8156-252-2 (online)

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*

5. Paweł Jarnicki, *The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989)* (2016), artykuł, *Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science*, 1 (2016 - special issue on Ludwik Fleck), p. 21-30

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1

Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI 10.24117/2526-2270.2016.i1.05

Status publikacji: opublikowane

6. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metaforyczne konceptualizacje pojęcia 'tekstu' a przemiany stylów myślowych w literaturoznawstwie [Metaphorical conceptualizations of the concept of 'text' and changes of thought styles in history and theory of literature]* (2014), książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo 'Projekt Nauka', pp. 246

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 4

Otwarty dostęp: tak

Status publikacji: opublikowane

7. Paweł Jarnicki, Bożena Płonka-Syroka, Bogdan Balicki, *Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje [Ludwik Fleck - traditions - inspirations - interpretations]; [in the volume: Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie, p. 235–37; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim, p. 239–55; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim, p. 257–94; Postówie, p. 295–96]* (2015), książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 4

Otwarty dostęp: tak

Status publikacji: opublikowane

8. Paweł Jarnicki, *Kłopoty z przedwojenną recepcją koncepcji Ludwika Flecka: [On some problems with the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in the prewar period]* (2011), artykuł, *STUDIA PHILOSOPHICA WRATISLAVIENSIA*, 6. (2), p. 133–39

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 2

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane

9. Paweł Jarnicki, *Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of "legitimation" [Polish extended version appeared as: O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka. In: Stan Rzeczy 10, p. 355-373]* (2015), artykuł, *Divinatio: Studia Culturologica Series*, vol. 41, autumn-winter, p. 167-184

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane

10. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metafory dyskursu intertekstualności, metaforyka tekstylina [Metaphors of intertextuality. Textile metaphors]* (2015), artykuł, *Kształcenie Językowe*, 13 (23): p. 49–72

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane

DOKONANIA ARTYSTYCZNE

b.d.

BADANIA NAUKOWE FINANSOWANE PRZEZ NCN

DANE POBRANE AUTOMATYCZNIE

Tytuł w języku polskim: **Filologiczna analiza filozoficznych dzieł Ludwika Flecka oraz ich tłumaczeń w językach: polskim, niemieckim i angielskim**

Nr rejestracyjny: 2012/06/M/HS2/00313

Źródło(a) finansowania: NCN, Nazwa konkursu: HARMONIA-3

Kwota: **405 512 PLN**

Podmiot realizujący: **Projekt Nauka. Fundacja na rzecz promocji nauki polskiej**

Data rozpoczęcia realizacji: **2013-03-25**, Data zakończenia realizacji: **2016-08-24**

Wynik oceny: Uznanie umowy za wykonaną

Lista najważniejszych publikacji będących rezultatem projektu:

Publikacje w czasopismach:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Sandra Lang ("Introduction"); Paweł Jarnicki ("The beginnings..."), Introduction; The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989), *Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science*, 1, 3-5; 21-30, Graduate Program in History (Science and Culture in History) of Federal University of Minas Gerais (Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais), Brasil, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, On the Shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the Bilingual Philosophical Legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English Translations, *The Translator*, 22 (3), 271-286, Routledge, 2016, IF: 0.483, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka, *Stan Rzeczy*, 10, 355-373, Instytut Socjologii UW, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of “legitimation”, *Divinatio*, 41 (Aut.-Win.), 167-184, University of Sofia, Department of Cultural Studies, 2015, IF: 0, - Opublikowane

Publikacje książkowe/ rozdziały w publikacjach książkowych:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim; Postłowie, Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje, (nie dotyczy), 235-296, Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich we Wrocławiu, 2015, Wrocław, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2705.3208>, - Opublikowane

b.d.

INNE PROJEKTY BADAWCZE

Tytuł: **Metoda analizy metafor w tekstach naukowych jako czynników zmiany w nauce [A method of analysis of metaphors in scientific texts as factors of change in science]**

Nr rejestracyjny: N N101 060336

Źródło(a) finansowania: Komitet Badań Naukowych [Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (State Committee for Scientific Research)]

Kwota: **31 850 PLN**

Podmiot realizujący: **Uniwersytet Wrocławski [University of Wrocław]**

Data rozpoczęcia realizacji: **2009-03-11**, Data zakończenia realizacji: **2011-09-10**

Lista najważniejszych publikacji będących rezultatem projektu:

1. P. Jarnicki, Jak przeprowadzić analizę onomazjologiczno-kognitywną tekstu teoretycznego, w zbiorze: *Kultura w nauce o literaturze*, red. B. Balicki, B. Ryż, E. Szczerbuk, Wrocław 2009, s. 197-207. 2. Redakcja numeru specjalnego "Studia Philosophica Wratislaviensia" 2011, nr 2 (numer poświęcony Ludwikowi Fleckowi), w tym tomie teksty: - P. Jarnicki, Wstęp [redaktora numeru], s. 5-12. - P. Jarnicki, W sprawie wystąpienia Wojciecha Sadego pt. 'O tym, co decyduje o naukowości badań przyrodniczych', s. 55-61. - P. Jarnicki, Początki anglojęzycznej recepcji koncepcji L. Flecka, s. 77-79. - P. Jarnicki, Kłopoty z przedwojenną recepcją koncepcji Ludwika Flecka, s. 133-137. - P. Jarnicki, Trzeci tom Fleckowski [rec. Ludwik Fleck, *Style myślowe i fakty. Artykuły i świadectwa*, red. S. Werner, C. Zittel, F. Schmalz, Warszawa, IFiS PAN 2007], s. 191-204. - (Tłumaczenie P. Jarnicki z Dariuszem Zienkiewiczem) H. Petersen, Ludwig Flecks Lehre vom Denkstil und dem Denkkollektiv, ("Klinische Wochenschrift" 1936 (7), 15.02.1936, p. 239-242). - (Tłumaczenie P. Jarnicki z Marceliną Zuber: T. S. Kuhn, Foreword, in: L. Fleck, *Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*, ed. T. J. Trenn, R. K. Merton, tłum. F. Bradley, University of Chicago Press 1979), s. 81-85. - (Tłumaczenie P. Jarnicki z Marceliną Zuber: W. Baldamus, Ludwig Fleck and the development of the sociology of science, in: *Human Figurations. Essays for Aufsätze für Norbert Elias*, ed. P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, H. Korte, *Amsterdams Sociologisch Tijdschrift* 1977), s.87-105. - (Tłumaczenie P. Jarnicki z Marceliną Zuber: R. S. Cohen, Th. Schnelle, Introduction, in: *Cognition and Fact: Materials on Ludwig Fleck*, ed. R. S. Cohen, Th. Schnelle, Reidel 1986), s. 107-129.

NAJWAŻNIEJSZE OSIĄGNIĘCIE NAUKOWE

The most important achievement is the clarification of the status of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives. Its specific situation generates specific problems for translators, who unfortunately had not recognised this specific status of Fleck's theory, so all the existing translations have to be deeply revised. Fleck's philosophical/sociological theory was expressed in two languages (Polish and German) more or less simultaneously by a bilingual author, who did not self-translate his texts into the second language but published original texts in both of these languages. It means that both Polish and German texts are of equal value, and if we want to speak of the level of equivalence, I argue we can find it at the level of concepts - it means that expressions that differ in lexical meaning may denote the very same concept. The problem is described - with an example of "circulation of thoughts" [Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli] expression - in a paper "On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations" published in *The Translator*.

DOŚWIADCZENIE NAUKOWE

- From May, 2013 to April 2016 - associated researcher of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich), [regular short stays within the realization of grant number 2012/06/M/HS2/00313].
- 07-09.2009 query in British Library (London), [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].
- 11-12.2009 query in Ludwik Fleck Archive in Zurich and Library of the University of Zurich [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336]

WYRÓŻNIENIA I NAGRODY

b.d.

WYKŁADY I REFERATY

CONFERENCE PAPERS (from 2014)

- 24-25 January, 2014, **Zurich, Switzerland**, international workshop: "Translation of Science – Science of Translation" (Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum) two papers: 1) "Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings: some editions and translations compared", 2) "The first and the last philosophical texts of Ludwik Fleck, and the translations compared";
- 19-20 March, 2014, **Wrocław, Poland**, international conference: "Ludwik Fleck – traditions, inspirations, interpretations", (Fundacja Projekt Nauka); paper: "On some problems with English, Polish and German translations of Ludwik Fleck";
- 10-11 April, 2014, **Toruń, Poland**, conference: IV Polish Constructivist Symposium in Toruń (Institute of Philosophy of Nicolaus Copernicus University), paper: "Metaphors of eugenics";

- 17-19 September, 2014, **Toruń, Poland**, international conference: "Situating Solidarities" (European Association for the Study of Science and Technology and Nicolaus Copernicus University), paper: "'Gestalts' of Ludwik Fleck";
- 27-29 November, 2014, **Berlin, Germany**, international conference: "Self-Translation as Transfer of Knowledge" (Zentrum für Literatur- und Kulturforschung), paper: "Ludwik Fleck's Legacy – an Example of Self-Translation?"
- 3-8 August, 2015, **Helsinki, Finland**, international conference: 15th Congress on Logic, Methodology, and Philosophy of Science 2015 (University of Helsinki), paper: "The reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives in English"
- 28-30 October 2015, **Marburg, Germany**, international conference: "Entangled science? Relocating German-Polish scientific relations" (the Leibniz Association and the Polish Academy of Sciences), poster: "Ludwik Fleck's "Polish-German" theory of thought styles and thought collectives, and problems arising from its translation";
- 10-11 March 2016, **Wrocław, Poland**, international conference: "Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives – translations and receptions" (Fundacja Projekt Nauka in cooperation with Ludwik Fleck Zentrum, Max-Planck-Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte, Ludwik Fleck Kreis), two talks: 1) [with Rainer Egloff] On translating Ludwik Fleck between Polish, German and English, 2) Reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Poland.
- April 11-14, 2019, **Lviv, Ukraine**, international conference: "Ludwik Fleck and His Thought Collectives" (Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Center for Urban History of East Central Europe, Ukrainian Catholic University), paper: "What is 'mood'? About translating of 'Stimmung/nastroj' into English".
- June 23-26, 2020, **Singapore, Singapore** international conference HOPOS 2020 (The Thirteenth Biennial Congress of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science), paper: "The role of (conceptual) metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings" selected for presentation but the event was canceled.
- July 7-9, 2021, **Kent, Great Britain** (on-line), international conference: The British Society for the Philosophy of Science 2021 Annual Conference, paper [with Hans-Joachim Greif]: "The Aristotle Experience and the Genesis of the Kuhnian Revolution".

INNE ISTOTNE OSIĄGNIĘCIA W NAUCE

Organisational activity:

- 2016, 10-11 March – organisation of an international conference in Wrocław (Project Science Foundation): "Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives – translations and receptions".
- 2014, 19-20 March - organisation of an international conference in Wrocław (Project Science Foundation): "Ludwik Fleck – traditions, inspirations, interpretations".
- 2014, 24-25 January - co-organisation of an international workshop in Zurich (Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum): "Translation of Science – Science of Translation".
- 2009, 14-15 October - organisation of the First Polish Constructivist Symposium in Wrocław.
- 2008 - foundation of "Science of science" circle in Wrocław - a series of meetings of Ph.D. students and academics (34 meetings took place).

OPUS 22 (submitted 12.2021) – rejected at the second stage – 72,38%

A1. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (30%) – **4,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

A2. POTENTIAL IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%) – **1,25** (on a scale of 0 to 2).

A3. FEASIBILITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%) – **2,00** (on a scale of 0 to 2).

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (40%) – **3,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

GENERAL JUSTIFICATION

There was an agreement that the investigation on the relationship between the ideas of Fleck and Kuhn is an important task and requires support. However, we received a number of projects of high quality and unfortunately currently this proposal is not high enough in the ranking to allow its funding, given the budget limit of the call.

INDIVIDUAL REVIEWS

A1. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (30%)

Expert 1:

Kuhn is an important figure in the history of many disciplines. The origins of his ideas are of great interest. The project is very well organised, the methodology very clear and appropriate and careful. The results of this research will potentially be of great intellectual value.

Expert 2:

The proposal is very important for the history of philosophy of science. The proposed investigation should provide a definitive answer for the question concerning a proper relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's proposal.

Reviewer 1:

The main question of this proposal concerns the genealogical relation between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives and Thomas S. Kuhn's theory of paradigms and scientific revolutions. The PI's hypothesis is that "Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledge". With respect to this thesis, he takes into account different comparative studies which have already been pursued in the philosophy of science and concludes that there is a broad range of opinions as to what degree similarities can be noted between both approaches. Furthermore, the PI points out that explanations vary widely why these similarities appear. His proposal is meant to address this problem. By collecting and evaluating new information about the genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's accounts, the PI intends to find a better explanation regarding the actual connecting points between both approaches.

The proposal is well written. It shows an extensive background knowledge of the PI regarding the two theories and philosophers that are part of the investigation. The main objective of the project is

presented very clearly and will be of interest to scholars working on Fleck's and Kuhn's theories alike. Furthermore, the proposed analysis will be of relevance due to the fact that – besides the main line of investigation – it could shed some light on questions such as the following: what new ideas and subsequent developments, if any, does Kuhn's account put forward with respect to the philosophy of science (e.g. a new focus on social dynamics in science)? What can scholars working on Kuhn's theses still learn from Fleck's theory alone? That is, what can be regarded as the epistemic surplus of each theory alone and what enhancements with respect to the philosophy of science might a comparative account bring about?

With respect to methodology, the PI suggests to collect new evidence on the matter by analysing both the development of the vocabulary and metaphors used by both authors. As he has some background competence in literary studies, e.g. regarding the analysis of metaphors, and due to the fact that conceptual analysis is a common practice in philosophy, this seems to be a plausible account.

Finally, the PI suggests to approach the topic via different routes, namely via (a) text analysis (esp. focus on metaphors used), (b) analysis of secondary sources and (c) archival research, therefore some new results can indeed be expected.

Reviewer 2:

The project is not well conceived. First, the author seems to have their answer to their question before they have done the necessary research. They claim that they are investigating the influence of Fleck's work on Kuhn, but then they also claim that the effect is greater than is generally recognized. Nothing in their proposal supports the latter claim. Second, some of the suggested methods are flawed. They are going to use textual analysis and compare Kuhn's terms with Fleck's (in translation). They demonstrate what they will do with the term "thought". This is such a general term in the English language it cannot reveal anything insightful. Further, if they are going to use such a method, they would need to look at similar works by others, for example Popper. One might find Kuhn, Popper, and Fleck use the term "thought" equally as much. What are we to make of that? In addition, the translators of Fleck translated the book with the benefit of having read Kuhn's book. This may have effected their choices in translating. So, Fleck may have been made to look more like Kuhn than he actually is. Finally, it is unclear what the author expects to find in the archives that they want to visit. It is implied that they already have access to something from the Robert K. Merton papers, but nothing is reported that would give any indication that Kuhn was deeply influenced by Fleck.

Reviewer 3:

This is an excellent proposal.

The relationship between the ideas of the relatively unknown Polish doctor and philosopher Ludwik Fleck and the much more famous American philosopher and historian, Thomas Kuhn, has been remarked upon by a number of commentators. In some cases a philosophical comparison has been made. But there has been very little detailed historical or linguistic work on this relationship. This is because the comparisons have been made by philosophers (such as myself) who do not have the skills (or interest) to carry out that kind of study. This is the first large-scale investigation of the relationship that will draw on the archival material as well as linguistic analysis in addition to philosophical analysis of the two thinkers' ideas. I am convinced that it is important that we know the genealogy of Kuhn's ideas, given that they have been so influential. And that if Fleck's ideas are the true origin of Kuhn's ideas, as the PI suspects, then that ought to be known. Even if this turns out not

to be the case, I believe that a major study of the relationship between the two men would be very valuable.

Not only is the project aim valuable, the project is also very well conceived. The archival work needs not be done. The linguistic approach to comparing the texts is very interesting. The proposed Co-Investigator will have complementary skills. This will be productive of reliable and valuable results.

Reviewer 4:

The research project “On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant? Uncovering Ludwik Fleck’s Influence on Thomas Kuhn” aims to assess the influence of Fleck’s book “Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache” on Kuhn’s monograph “The Structure of Scientific Revolutions”.

Fleck is a Polish philosopher of science, largely underappreciated at his time, who had many original ideas. Particularly interesting was his sociological approach to science, through the thought styles and thought collectives. Unfortunately, for personal, philosophical, and even linguistic matters, his work did not receive the attention it deserved. His rediscovering was in part due to Kuhn, who mentioned his book in the Preface to “The Structure of Scientific Revolutions”. Kuhn acknowledged Fleck as having anticipated many of his own ideas. Despite that explicit recognition, Kuhn does not cite Fleck on his book, and his comments on the matter, as pointed by the PI, are rather ambiguous.

This fact justifies a deeper investigation on the connection between these two philosophers. In part this may help us to better understand some aspects of Kuhn’s philosophy, by demonstrating its origin in Fleck’s thought. Furthermore, analyzing the relation between them may put some light on Fleck’s originality; something that could be the source of new philosophical ideas.

The project, therefore, aims to study an important subject on the history of philosophy of science. The author is familiar with the main works about the Kuhn-Fleck relation, as these papers are cited in the proposal (I would just recommend a recently published book by Brad Wray, “Kuhn’s Intellectual Path”, which could be helpful in assessing Kuhn’s intellectual trajectory). The bibliography is up-to-date to current discussions on the works of Kuhn and Fleck.

Another point that is worth mentioning is the intention of examining the influence of Fleck in conceptual terms. It is common that Kuhn scholars are very much attached to explicit links with other authors. The idea of comparing metaphors and concepts may uncover non-superficial similarities between those authors. Linked to that, the archival research could find new points of contact; in particular, I believe, in non-published letters and annotated books (as the PI suggests).

Panel II

1. Justification for SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT

Panel endorsed the comments of Reviewer 1 and Reviewer 4

A2. POTENTIAL IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%)

Expert 1:

A well evidenced claim that Kuhn plagiarised, for example, would clearly garner great interest from across various areas of the academy (and indeed beyond).

Expert 2:

Theory of scientific revolutions is one of the fundamental ingredients of the philosophy of science. Taking into account its importance a research which helps to explain its origins is of interest for several scholars interested in science and its history.

Reviewer 1:

To start with, the research proposal puts forward an interesting question for both communities, that is, researchers interested in Fleck's work as well as researchers interested in Kuhn's work. Furthermore, the project is directed towards the history and the philosophy of science which means that, again, two communities will be affected by possible results of the project which broadens the scope of its potential impact significantly.

In case, the PI is successful in his research objective, namely to show that the genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's account is far closer than usually expected by philosophers, historians and sociologists of science, this would indeed have a huge impact on the community. The point is that, if this can be shown, a major proponent in the philosophy of science (namely, Thomas Kuhn) will be, metaphorically speaking, deprived of his power. Of course, it would also be interesting to know if this is not the case.

However, the worry is that the subtlety of the topic (a suspected case of plagiarism committed by Kuhn) and the difficulty to find clear evidence to support the PI's thesis will lead into a dead end only. Therefore, the potential impact of the research project has to be rated rather moderately.

Reviewer 2:

Given my remarks above, I do not think the author will find much of interest. I have accessed some of the archives they refer to and have found nothing that would support the author's claims. So, I do not think much of importance will come of this research. Even if the author were to uncover a larger influence of Fleck on Kuhn it is challenging to see how this would be of much consequence.

The author might do well to look with care at the entry of Fleck in the Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. (in fact, it is also written by a Polish scholar).

Reviewer 3:

Many commentators have noted the relationship between Fleck and Kuhn but almost none have conducted the kind of study need to establish a causal link between these thinkers or to determine what exactly the nature of the link is (from similarity to unconscious influence to outright plagiarism). Given the significance and influence of Kuhn, finding out about the sources of his ideas is highly significant. So I would expect the impact of this research to be considerable.

Reviewer 4:

If successful, this research could provide several contributions. First, it could help us to better understand the genesis of Kuhn's ideas. By now, scholars have not fully explored Fleck's influence on Kuhn.

A second contribution could be in reassessing Fleck's work. For many reasons, Fleck has not received the same attention in contemporary philosophy as other thinkers, such as Popper or Lakatos. This work could serve as a way to present unfamiliar aspects of Fleck's work to a larger audience.

Connected to that, this project may also bring new ideas to philosophy of science. Fleck' impact on the philosophy of science was largely mediated by Kuhn's reading. A fresher appreciation of his ideas

--- not only as a precursor to Kuhn, but as an original philosopher --- could offer new insights to contemporary debates; in particular, to the field of social epistemology.

Overall, there is a large space in the field for publications on this subject. Results would be particularly interesting if they presented new archival material or shed light on new relations between these authors.

A3. FEASIBILITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%)

Expert 1:

The project is very well-organised and the rigorous methodology very well thought through. I have every expectation that the research will achieve its aims. The team will be very well qualified and there are no obvious risks.

Expert 2:

The project, its methodology and work plan are very well prepared. There is rather no risk that it will not be realisable. The question is only what answer concerning the proper relationship between Fleck and Kuhn will be obtained as a result.

Reviewer 1:

The overall project design seems to be well elaborated. The PI and his team show the relevant competences to pursue the project as intended.

One minor worry concerns the research stays at different archives. Firstly, it is not quite clear why the time scale at different institutions differs between months and weeks. Secondly, why does the PI not intend to investigate into the origin of Fleck's theory and, thus, pursue some archive work with this regard, too? The latter point seems relevant to consider as the PI argues that Fleck and Kuhn might have used similar sources as a starting point to develop their ideas. Consequently, it would be relevant to know what exactly Fleck's sources of inspiration were.

Reviewer 2:

I have criticized the methods above.

To repeat, the author does not have an effective plan for textual analyses of Fleck's and Kuhn's works. They have not anticipated various methodological limitations and problems.

Second, there is no or little reason to believe that something is in the archives they hope to visit that will shed light on this research question.

Third, the author fails to take account of the fact that Fleck's book was largely unread UNTIL Kuhn drew attention to it. Hence, it is quite implausible that Kuhn lifted a lot from Fleck's book, but then proceeded to draw reader's attention to it. In fact, there is an early study that shows that book really languished after its publication.

Finally, the author says they hope to locate Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book, to examine any markings, etc. It is known that Kuhn used the copy in the Widener Library at Harvard, and that the book was not signed out much after Kuhn used it.

Reviewer 3:

Very feasible. The PI has a strong track record of research on Kuhn and Fleck behind him. He has an excellent understanding of the issues and it is natural to move this research onto the larger scale of

the proposed project. The project Co-investigator will be someone with a background in philosophy and history of science, and this will complement the PI's skills. It is right and important that the archival work is done — this could be very revealing. The linguistic approach is somewhat original in this context, but the PI has considerable experience of these matters.

Reviewer 4:

The project is feasible. It involves three main parts: 1. textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings 2. analysis of historical sources and 3. archival research.

Phases 1 and 2 can be accomplished in the predicted time, without much concern. As regards part 3, which involves archival research on other countries, the PI has already listed the archives he wants to visit. This gives a good amount of time to plan the trips and to get in contact with the responsible for the archives in advance, as to save some time in dealing with the files. This part of the research seems feasible too.

Panel II

1. Justification for FEASIBILITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT

The Experts endorsed the Reviews 1, 3 and 4

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND SCIENTIFIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (40%)

Expert 1:

Some international publications, international conferences, and some past grant activity. The highest levels here would require publications in very good international journals, which I can't see on the proposal.

Expert 2:

The PI is well prepared to realise this project. He has a rich experience with the kind of work required for such enterprise. In particular he is an expert in the area of Fleck's heritage.

Panel I

1. Justification for QUALIFICATIONS AND SCIENTIFIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR

agreement of the panel

Reviewer 1:

The scientific qualifications and achievements of the principle investigator are more than sufficient to fulfill the tasks mentioned in the proposal. He can make use of a variety of preliminary studies pursued by him and his co-authors. His works, mentioned in the proposal, comprise an extensive set of investigations concerning Ludwik Fleck's philosophy as well as the reception history of the latter. In this sense, the PI seems to be sufficiently well acquainted with Fleck's philosophical theses, although the main qualification of the PI is in literary studies.

Furthermore, the PI has also published a first comparative study ("The Aristotle Experience Revisited. Thomas Kuhn, Ludwik Fleck and the Genesis and Development of a Scientific Revolution") which will serve as a good starting point for his further investigations.

Moreover it is important to mention that the PI has a sufficient level of language expertise to take into account Fleck's papers written in German and in Polish as well as Kuhn's papers written in English. This mastery of those three languages seems to be a very important aspect to pursue the proposed analysis regarding the development of particular kinds of formulations and the tracing of the origin of certain concepts, metaphors and arguments used by Kuhn.

Finally, the PI is also well experienced regarding project work as can be read off his list of previously pursued research projects.

Reviewer 2:

I work extensively in the relevant field, and I have never heard of the PI before. Many of his publications are in Polish, and have not reach an international audience. I recognize that they are junior scholar, but their research is not being picked up by international scholars.

Reviewer 3:

The PI comes from am literary/linguistic background, which is unusual for work in philosophy. Nonetheless, he has a very solid set of publications in which he uses those skills to analyse the relationship between Fleck and Kuhn. It so happens that I was an anonymous reviewer for his most recent publication "The Aristotle experience revisited Thomas Kuhn, Ludwik Fleck, and the Genesis and Development of a Scientific Revolution" in *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*, the leading journal in its field. This is an excellent paper and I had no trouble in recommending it for publication. I am excited to see the author wanting to widen the scope of his research.

Possibly the only weakness in the PI is that he is not trained as a philosopher. But I do not think that this is a disadvantage, since his work shows philosophical sophistication and he plans to appoint someone with a background in philosophy as Co-Investigator.

I will score this as 4 rather than 5 since it is easy to see that some researchers might have a greater track record of highly cited articles and such like, But I should add that I do not think that the PI is in any way unsuited to lead this excellent project.

Reviewer 4:

The Principal Investigator (PI) has been studying the subject Fleck's work since his PhD. He has published several articles on Fleck and also an article on the relation between Kuhn and Fleck. He has published three papers in the last year.

The PI has been studying the Fleck's work and its reception for a while. His trajectory is consistent with a deep analysis of Fleck and its relation with Kuhn's philosophy. Moreover, the PI has already started to explore those issues, having obtained some preliminary results.

STRENGTHS OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

The broad interest of topic is a key strength. The intellectual importance of potential findings is high and broad. The organisation of the work plan is really very good with many potential snags forseen

and dealt with. The proposed research is methodologically rigorous. I have every confidence this will produce interesting and important outputs.

Expert 2

The strength points of the project are connected mainly with the theme of the project. Kuhn's theory is still one of the most influential proposals in the philosophy of science. On the other hand, the ideas of Fleck certainly deserve more attention and it is very important to establish precisely the kind of dependence between the two.

Reviewer 1

The proposal shows a very clear and plausible design of the work program.

Furthermore, it is based on sufficient background knowledge and scientific competence to gather and evaluate evidence regarding the questions put forward by the PI.

Finally, the multilingual competences (proficiency in the Polish, German, English language) of the PI and his team are of great significance to pursue the proposed conceptual analysis and to compare the developmental stages of both accounts.

Reviewer 2

I do not see any strengths worth flagging here. I do not support the funding of such a project. It seems very speculative, and it also seems that the author has already set out what he aims to argue, even before the research is done. This is not a proper way to conduct research. One needs to approach the question with an open mind. Further, when one outlines methods one needs to make clear that the methods will yield tangible results.

Reviewer 3

The proposal aims to settle an important question that has been mentioned by numerous authors but not properly addressed by them, certainly not in the systematic way proposed here.

The methodology is robust, using archival, historical, linguistic, and philosophical perspectives.

The PI has a strong track record in this field — he is well placed to produce excellent research.

Reviewer 4

The proposal can bring some light into the actual influence of Fleck on Kuhn's philosophy. The researcher has made clear that he does not intend to stay at a superficial level but wants to explore metaphorical connections among the authors. If appropriately done, this could represent an important work to reassess Fleck's philosophy and better understand the genealogy of Kuhn's ideas.

WEAKNESSES OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

There aren't many weaknesses. One is that the PI could have greater international standing and particularly track record in producing journal articles in top ranked international journals. Another is that the balance of the workload between the team could be better justified. It isn't obvious from the specifications of the work packages why the PI requires 1FTE and the other team member requires only a fraction of that.

Expert 2

The budget of the project is rather high. On the other hand it seems that it is well justified. The PI should obtain the full salary, since before the time of the project realization his present contract is over. Also the nature of the work in several archives scattered all over the world justifies high costs of journeys.

Reviewer 1

In the beginning of the proposal it is mentioned that there may be possible common sources used by Fleck and Kuhn to develop their respective theories. To put this hypothesis to a test, it seems relevant to pursue some research on Fleck's part too. Obviously, the PI has analysed Fleck's works previously as can be seen in his list of publications. However, Fleck only sparsely mentions the sources of his ideas. Therefore, it seems worthwhile to investigate the origins of his theory in the same way as it is planned regarding Kuhn's theory. It's a bit puzzling why the PI apparently does not intend to pursue this kind of research.

Furthermore, it is unclear why the PI does not intend to organize events – such as workshops – to distribute his research results and to contact further experts on the topic.

Reviewer 2

The weaknesses are many, and I have outlined them in detail in all the sections above.

To repeat:

The author seems to have an answer to his question before he has conducted the necessary research. The author plans to visit archives that may or may not have any relevant material, and he gives no reason for us to believe that they will have any truly insightful. And he fails to note that some resources, like the Lowell Lectures, are freely available on-line. They have been published by MIT libraries, and nothing in those lectures supports the author's claims. The author plans to conduct textual analyses, but he seems wholly unaware of quite basic objections to his proposed methods. And his one demonstration, using the word "though", is quite ill conceived, as thought is such a general term in the English language.

Reviewer 3

There are no real weaknesses. The only possible weakness is that the PI is not himself an experienced researcher in philosophy. But I don't think this matters for several reasons. (i) I have read his recent work and those aspects that do engage with philosophy are just fine; (ii) there is already a fair amount of philosophical commentary on this question — what is original and important about this proposal is that it will use methodologies from outside philosophy (archival and historical work, linguistic analysis); (iii) the Co-Investigator will be someone with philosophical skills.

Reviewer 4

As a general concern, the PI could have elaborated some of the hypothesis he intends to explore in the investigation. For example, he states in the project that “an important complementary task will be to reflect on what Kuhn has likely missed in his adoption of Fleck's thought in particular”. Although part of the answer will only be revealed throughout the research, the PI could have discussed some of the aspects of Fleck's thought that were not properly understood by Kuhn, or which Kuhn wrongly misinterpreted. The same could be pointed for some of the aspects (even if

tentatively pointed) of Kuhn's and Fleck's thought that are usually ignored or misunderstood and which the PI believes could be reassessed by this research.

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

OPUS-23

Wniosek o finansowanie projektu badawczego

Na ramionach niewidocznego olbrzyma? Odkrywanie wpływu Ludwika Flecka na Thomasa Kuhna

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OPIS SKRÓCONY

On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant?

Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

1. Scientific goal of the project

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). Given that Kuhn read the *Entstehung* more than a decade before he wrote the *Structure*, it is evident that these similarities are not purely coincidental. Given the number and degrees of similarity between key concepts, it is evident that Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thought has been notable. However, Kuhn acknowledged Fleck's importance only in a few places, only in passing and only with qualifications. Still, the nature, depth and scope of Fleck's influence on Kuhn are not very well documented or analysed to date.

The aim of this inquiry in the history of philosophy of science is to provide an in-depth account of the **genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work** in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to commonplace philosophy of science comparison of two "ready-made" theories, the present study will pick up on the few more historically minded inquiries into the Fleck-Kuhn relation and build a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence that Fleck's writings had on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. It will do so by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. It will use the information from those sources for exploring a spectrum of possible hypotheses concerning Fleck's influence on Kuhn and assess their merits. The guiding hypothesis of this project is that **Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledged**.

The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at its sceptical end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of the existence but only superficially appreciated the *Entstehung* or did not fully understand it, so any talk of an influence is exaggerated (Wray 2016, 4). At most, Fleck anticipated some views of Kuhn in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum, there are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him (Baldamus 1977, 135, 151). Between those extremes, there are views according to which Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either only had an indirect and un- or even subconscious influence on him, or that Kuhn's reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his previous ideas.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented. Mending this situation requires both comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and tracing the possible routes of concept transfer. Although both tasks are relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to demonstrate how and to what extent Fleck's concepts informed Kuhn. Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence, **the novelty of this project lies in the combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn**.

Notably, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (i.a. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011) – write little or even nothing about Fleck. On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Mößner (2011), Peine (2011). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus', which compares the vocabularies of Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books, there is little attention being paid to how Fleck's concepts may actually have informed Kuhn's. Therefore, research on the relations between Kuhn's and Fleck's work needs to be deepened, by asking **what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved**. It also needs to be broadened, by **analysing the metaphors and development of vocabulary in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials**, in light of his reading of Fleck and other, partly common sources. **Kuhn's theory will therefore be investigated *in statu nascendi***.

Numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account – from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (Kuhn's teacher and boss while at Harvard), but also from Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015). Shared influences on Fleck and Kuhn will be accounted for, too, in particular those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether or not Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is one matter of investigation.

All the parallels and shared influences raise the question of what precise position of influence Fleck had on Kuhn. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed that he read Fleck's book in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date to 1950/1951, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn started to claim that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited, due to a limited grasp of Fleck's German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 only confirmed ideas that he had already conceived of before. At around the same time (in his 1976 *Foreword* to the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn started to trace the origins of his reasoning to what he called the "Aristotle Experience", which he dates back to 1947, when he was a 25 years old PhD student in physics who was asked by James B. Conant, his superior, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. When Kuhn found himself struggling to understand Aristotle's Physics, he suddenly realised that Aristotle's science is not false and meaningless but simply different from the contemporary physics that he himself was taught. From 1976 onwards, Kuhn would describe this experience as a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were born, too. (For more on these circumstantial evidences, see: Jarnicki, Greif 2022)

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars: 1. textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings, 2. analysis of secondary sources and 3. archival research. While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in *Gestalt* psychology and art history. Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. For the analysis of the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and while reading had to "translate" Fleck into contemporary English.

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:

1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?

1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?

1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?

1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?

2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:

2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?

2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts has been ascribed to Fleck's writings?

3. Archival research aims to provide:

3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.

3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

Work Plan

The project is divided into four nine-month periods, during which we will A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below), B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able, C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).

- I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- III. **Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings** regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.
- IV. Archive research in
 - i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] - collect unpublished texts to be analysed in regard of vocabulary development and metaphors used; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949; check when Kuhn first read about *Gestalt psychology*; **search for early relations about the "Aristotle experience"**; **check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible**;
 - ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] - check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn,
 - iii. **Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics]** - check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability),
 - iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] - study **materials regarding the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,**
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] - **check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*) and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi,**
 - vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know more on the **genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).**
- V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
- VIII. Comparison of vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, taking into account development of his vocabulary in time).
- IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories - from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.

In order to ensure prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive under (IV) will be prefaced by a detailed inquiry with the keepers of the archives into the kind and scope of material to be expected.

Preliminary research

Besides work on the peculiarities of translating Fleck (Jarnicki 2016), the PI has written two extensive articles over the last two years (Jarnicki 2021; Jarnicki, Greif 2022). In the first article, it is shown that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój* belongs to the domain of musical metaphors (the term is not properly **translatable into English and usually rendered as “mood”**) and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). According to Oliveira (2017) one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other. In the **second article, the authors analyse Kuhn's few statements about Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his 1947 “Aristotle experience” and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience exactly when he found out about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn had a direct role in having Fleck's book translated into English.** According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton Archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who got Merton into **convincing University of Chicago Press to publish Fleck's book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, who reluctantly agreed – and started to recount the Aristotle Experience in a different light.** Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

4. Research methodology

The project will employ a set of methods common to the humanities:

- 1) philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve surveying and analysing primary and secondary sources, retracing key concepts, arguments and references used and considering their context;
- 2) archival research methods (item IV in the work plan);
- 3) linguistic text analysis (items I, II, III, V, VI in the work plan), assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002);
- 4) philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve semantic analysis of key terms and as well as the development of hypotheses on the grounds of the results of the philological, conceptual and archival work.

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or near-native knowledge of English (PI, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (PI).

5. Project literature

- Babich, B. E. (2003a). “From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability”. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75–92.
- Babich, B. E. (2003b). “Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*”. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2–3).
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The Sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Acumen (2014 Routledge), p. 15–18.
- Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: "Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego" oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Lublin: Wydawnictwo UMCS.
- Cedarbaum, D. G. (1983). Paradigms, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, Volume 14, Issue 3, p. 173-213.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1989, *Die Wissenschaftsphilosophie Thomas S. Kuhns: Rekonstruktion und Grundlagenprobleme*. Eng. Trans. (1993). *Reconstructing Scientific Revolutions: Thomas S. Kuhn's Philosophy of Science*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1990, "Kuhn's conception of incommensurability" *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 21: 481-92.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266-276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157-168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163-173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, *English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) *Stimmung/Nastrój as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives*. *Foundations of Science* (early on-line).
- Jarnicki, P.; Greif, H. (2022) The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure', *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*, early online (8.06.2022).
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd ed. 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii-xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G. & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?* London/New York: Bloomsbury.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362-371.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746-765.
- Peine, A. (2011). Challenging incommensurability: What we can learn from Ludwik Fleck for the analysis of configurational innovation. *Minerva*, 49(4), 489-508.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41-50.
- Werner, S. & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1-23.

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1. Scientific goal of the project

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In his theory of thought styles and thought collectives, Fleck, like Kuhn would do after him, opposed speculation about how science should work while highlighting the importance of how it actually works. Both Fleck and Kuhn explicitly claimed that scientific knowledge is not simply additive, that it changes as a whole and questioned the classic definition of truth and the possibility of pure observation. Fleck, like Kuhn after him, observed the influence of social factors and non-verbalisable elements on the content of scientific cognition and looked at the role the history of science plays in the reflection on science. **The scientists connected by one "thought style" constitute a "thought collective" in Fleck, which does not differ significantly from Kuhn's "scientific community."** Kuhn's use of the term "paradigm" often does not follow his own specific technical meaning but the broad meaning of a "conceptual framework." This broad meaning is fairly close to Fleck's "thought style". Fleck, like Kuhn after him, also saw the stages of the development of a thought style. In the moments of breakthrough (Fleck writes about "intellectual unrest"), **scientists seem to alternately see the old "Gestalt" and the new one, and after the breakthrough, the world in which scientists live will have changed.** Fleck also referred to the incommensurability and untranslatability of thought styles and the **dependence of words' meanings on thought styles** – all concepts that would resurface in Kuhn.

The aim of this **inquiry in the history of philosophy of science** is to provide an in-depth account of the **genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work** in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to the comparison of two "ready-made" theories (as presented in *Entstehung* and *Structure* respectively) that has so far been common practice in philosophy of science, the present study will pick up on the relatively few more historically minded inquiries into the Fleck-Kuhn relation and build a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the **influence that Fleck's writings had on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory.** It will do so by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. It will use the information from those sources to explore a spectrum of possible hypotheses concerning Fleck's influence on Kuhn and assess their merits. **The guiding hypothesis of this project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledge.**

The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at its sceptical end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of the existence but only superficially appreciated the *Entstehung* or did not fully understand it, so any talk of an influence is exaggerated: "Fleck (1935/1979), for example, is

often cited as having anticipated Kuhn, although more careful studies suggest that the similarities **between their views are superficial.**" (Wray 2016, p. 4) At most, Fleck anticipated some views of Kuhn in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum, there are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took **central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him:** "The reader who is familiar with Kuhn's work will easily recognize that the majority of [Fleck's] terms is virtually identical with the basic terminology of *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions.*" (Baldamus 1977, p. 151) "Invented by Ludwik Fleck [the concept of 'scientific community' ...] remained ignored until Thomas Kuhn appropriated it in 1962." (Baldamus 1977, p. 135) Between those extremes, there are views according to which Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either only had an indirect and un- or even subconscious influence on him, which might be supported by the observation that Fleck "even illustrated the idea with some of the same examples Kuhn later adopted" (Oberheim 2012, p. 128); or that Kuhn's reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his previous ideas, which might be supported by Baldamus' (1979) observation that key concepts that are present in Fleck can be found in Kuhn's writings in increasing frequency over the course of the years.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented.

On the one hand, statistics from the Scopus database show that at there at least six times between 1979-2019 as many works on Kuhn than on Fleck.

Between 1979-2019 in Scopus there are 938 papers about/related to Kuhn, whereas only 157 about/related to Fleck.

On the other hand, a pilot survey among Polish academics in May 2020 by the PI documents a **perceived need of acknowledging Fleck's contribution** (P. Jarnicki, *A Survey on the Opinion of Polish Researchers on the Relationship between the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn*). The survey was conducted on a sample of 23 philosophers from Poland, who consider their knowledge of Kuhn's and Fleck's theories to be at least good. According to the judgement of the majority of respondents, there was an influence from Fleck on Kuhn that the latter only insufficiently acknowledged¹.

Mending this situation requires both **comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and tracing the possible routes of transfer of related vocabulary and metaphors.** Although either task is relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to **demonstrate how and to what extent Fleck's concepts informed Kuhn.** Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence (see below), **the novelty of this project lies in the**

¹ To the question about the connection between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, 1 answered "don't know" and only 1 pointed that there is "no influence", 5 chose "anticipated" (which we interpret as no genealogical connection), 5 chose "forerunner" (which we interpret as weak genealogical connection), 7 chose "source of inspiration" (which we interpret as genealogical connection), 2 chose "strong influence" (which we interpret as significant genealogical connection), 2 chose "plagiarism". So, 16/23 Polish philosophers see the weaker or stronger genealogical connection. To the question if "Thomas Kuhn has acknowledged the merits of Ludwik Fleck sufficiently", 3 answered "don't know", only 5 answered "yes" and as many as 15 (i.e. 65%) answered "no".

combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn.

Notably, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (i.a. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000, 2005, 2007), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011) – write little or even nothing about Fleck. For example, Alexander Bird (2000) discusses Fleck completely separately from Kuhn as just one of **many elements of the background who “encouraged the rejection of the picture of science as the accumulation of knowledge driven by a rational scientific method.”** In a subsection on Fleck the name Kuhn is not mentioned even once. Similarly, Marcum (2015) briefly discusses Fleck as one intellectual influence among others, such as Wittgenstein. Part of the mission of the present proposal is to **vindicate the assumption that Fleck’s influence on Kuhn has been more prominent and more pronounced than Kuhn scholarship generally acknowledges.**

On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Braunstein (2003), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Dahms (2016), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Marín (2010), Mößner (2011) and Peine (2011). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus’, which compares the vocabularies of Fleck’s 1935 and Kuhn’s 1962 books, there is little attention being paid to how Fleck’s concepts may actually have informed Kuhn’s. Therefore, research on the relations between Kuhn’s and Fleck’s work needs to be deepened, by asking **what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved.** It also needs to be broadened, by **analysing the metaphors and development of vocabulary in Kuhn’s writings, including his unpublished materials.** Tracing the underlying genealogical relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, whatever its concrete nature might be, will help to shed light on the conceptual similarities and differences involved.

Even when authors sympathizing with Fleck, such as Peine (2011) or Collins (2012), write about the relation between Fleck and Kuhn, they usually do not recognize this relation as genealogical one. Peine’s intention, for instance, is to show that some of Fleck’s concepts are complementary to Kuhn’s theory, as if they were synchronous affairs. Because Peine sets out from a discussion of the differences between two “ready-made” theories, he readily convinces himself that Kuhn rejected more than took from Fleck: “while Kuhn has indeed resembled some of Fleck’s central ideas, he was reluctant to accept Fleck’s more radical claim that science is an essentially social process”. In contrast, the **present inquiry will start from identifying the most incontrovertible similarities, and Kuhn’s theory will be compared with Fleck’s not as a “ready-made” theory, but first and foremost as a theory *in statu nascendi*.**

In the late 1970s, Wilhelm Baldamus (1977, 1979), when comparing the development of Kuhn’s vocabulary over time to Fleck’s, implicitly suggested that Thomas Kuhn may have plagiarised Fleck, in terms of “appropriating” Fleck’s key ideas and concepts to a larger extent than he would acknowledge. These allegations – presumably due to the popularity of Kuhn’s book and his authority at the time – were never thoroughly investigated. Baldamus was more outspoken in private correspondence with Robert Merton (Baldamus 1980). Notably, suspicions of plagiarism or other forms of illicit appropriation of Fleck’s ideas by Kuhn, are frequently raised in informal fashion but rarely discussed in writing. The only explicit reference to a possible charge of plagiarism against Kuhn in the literature can be found in what actually is an awkward denial of that charge. Babette Babich (2003b) claims that even if Kuhn had intended to refer to Fleck to a larger extent than he did, or even if he had been inclined to commit plagiarism, he would have been prevented from doing so because of the partly inquisitory nature of Cold War anti-communism at that time in the USA. Any reference to such “ideologically problematic terms like ‘thought collective’ and ‘thought style’” would have put Kuhn’s reputation and academic career at risk.

Conversely, Collins (2012) writes that Kuhn was not “as original as we all once thought”, because “Fleck did it first and, in a lot of ways did it best”, while adding that finally Kuhn was the one “responsible for telling the history of science in a thought-collective kind of way”, because he was the one who “created the social change by coming along at the right time and writing in English.” Some may conclude that even if the most extreme explanation of the similarities between Kuhn and Fleck is true, namely Kuhn plagiarised Fleck, it is still a fact that Kuhn had a huge impact on the history of philosophy of science, and not Fleck, so **Fleck’s philosophy is just a historical footnote. Of course, one might think this way – the one who was successful, the one who had a successful career standing on the shoulders of other people’s intellectual accomplishments is the one who carries the day.** However, this is thinking in categories that one would consider outside the sphere of science – cynical thinking. If there is any reasonable evidential support for a suspicion that Thomas Kuhn illicitly appropriated his most important philosophical ideas from Ludwik Fleck, then this possibility must be explicitly considered (Jarnicki, Greif 2022).

Even if from today’s perspective, Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories appear different to an observer – he or she might be, for instance, aware of the differences between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s concepts of “incommensurability” – one has to bear in mind that such differences were probably not nearly as apparent as they are today. In the wake of the publication of the *Structure*, a wide variety of approaches to the social and cultural studies of science developed, and today we are aware of many more nuances that probably were imperceptible to people who read the *Structure* right after its publication, when it not only caused a major stir but also still had to give rise to the very social and cultural studies of science that now form the observer’s vantage point. **This is an argument against the claim that the similarity between Kuhn and Fleck is superficial upon closer inspection.** Only today are we able to point out all the differences. It should also be emphasized that, in the case of an obvious relation between two authors, it would be untoward in terms of strategy and method of inquiry to discuss the differences without accounting for the similarities first. In order to adequately discuss the **differences between Kuhn’s and Fleck’s theories, we must first thoroughly study and explicate the similarities between them and identify, to the greatest possible extent, which of these similarities are of genealogical nature.**

On the other hand, many influences that shaped both Fleck’s and Kuhn’s views are not at all obvious to the contemporary observer but were nonetheless important to them in all the nuance and detail that escape us now. Accordingly, numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account – from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Héléne Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (Kuhn’s teacher and boss while at Harvard), but also from Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015). An analysis of the relationship between Kuhn and the French epistemologists shows that there are indeed similarities (Simons 2017), but these appear to be far fewer than between Fleck and Kuhn, whereas the former **but not the latter are documented in Kuhn’s footnotes.** Wray’s (2016) downplaying of Fleck’s influence in his demonstration of Conant’s influence on Kuhn is weakened by the fact that Conant read Fleck’s book in 1950 (see Trenn 1981), so there still might be a mediated influence.

According to Moleski (2006), Kuhn and Polanyi met in 1958 and after publication of Kuhn’s *Structure* Polanyi had a (not publicly stated) belief that Kuhn was dishonest to him. Jacobs (2002), who argues for Kuhn’s undisclosed debt to Polanyi, claims that Kuhn’s notion of scientific community is taken from Polanyi rather than from Fleck, because Fleck’s thought collective “denotes a considerably wider class of social groups”. Debt to Fleck certainly does not exclude debt to Polanyi, but Kuhn read Fleck earlier than he read Polanyi. We must also take into account the possibility that that Kuhn, with Polanyi’s help, narrowed down Fleck’s general theory of thought collectives, which is applicable to science, fashion, religion and other domains, to scientific communities. However, Fleck’s book was in

fact a study of a scientific thought collective, while many of Kuhn's concepts, such as 'paradigm shift', were later readily applied to domains other than science.

Shared influences on Fleck and Kuhn will be accounted for, too, in particular those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether or not Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is one **matter of investigation**. Oliveira's (2017) paper about the first – unpublished – chapter of the *Structure* demonstrates that in the beginnings one of the key ideas of Kuhn was to make the image of science appear closer to the image of art (as the latter develops in a non-cumulative way). In doing this, he transferred some elements of knowledge about art history to the way we understand science. Since Fleck was informed of the concepts of style and mood (*nastrój/Stimmung*) in art history, it seems justified to ask whether these influences – on Kuhn and Fleck – were wholly independent (Jarnicki 2021). This question might become even more pertinent in light of the observation that Fleck remained critical of arthistorical notions of style that render it as an objective characteristic of a given collective that would allow for equally objective comparison rather than the nucleus of a proto-concept of incommensurability, as it would later be articulated by Kuhn (Zittel 2011).

The influence of the Gestalt psychologists on both authors is obvious and straightforward by comparison. It seems that both Kuhn and Fleck have similarly transferred (this is kind of a metaphor) **the knowledge of psychologists to epistemology** (for Fleck's reference to Gestalt psychology, see Zittel 2014 and Hagner 2012; the latter comparatively evaluates Gestalt psychology's import on Fleck and Michael Polanyi, who has also been cited as an under-acknowledged influence on Kuhn, see above). In 1979, Cedarbaum (1983) interviewed Kuhn and wrote: "Also, Kuhn allows that Fleck's discussion of, and emphasis on, Gestalt psychology may have awakened his own interest in the field; that contribution alone would make G.D.S.F. [*Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*] enormously significant in the formation of *Structure*."

All these parallels and shared influences raise the question of what precise position of influence Fleck held in that relation. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix–x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed that he read Fleck's book in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date to 1950/1951, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures ("The development of Kuhn's new image of the nature of science began with the 1951 Lowell lectures", Marcum 2015), i.e., after reading Fleck. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn claimed that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited, because of a limited grasp of Fleck's German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 were ideas that he had already conceived of before he read Fleck, so that Fleck's *Entstehung* only confirmed his own ideas. This change of narrative over the years is the primary evidence for a shifting perception in Kuhn of what Fleck's import on his own thought actually was, and ultimately for an insufficiently acknowledged influence from Fleck (Jarnicki, Greif 2022).

In any case, the focus of Kuhn scholarship has long been distracted from possible influences exerted by Fleck (and Polanyi?), on the grounds of one peculiar Kuhnian narrative. From 1976 (in his Foreword to *Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*, the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn started to trace the origins of his reasoning to what he called the "Aristotle Experience". According to his own account, this foundational experience took place in 1947 when he was a 25 years old PhD student in physics, and was asked by James B. Conant, his superior at the time, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. When Kuhn found himself struggling to understand Aristotle's *Physics*, which initially seemed ridiculously mistaken and misconceived to him, he suddenly realised that Aristotle's physics is not false and meaningless but simply different from the contemporary physics that he himself was taught. According to the autobiographic narrative that Kuhn would develop from 1976 onwards, this was a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were born, too. Many Kuhn scholars went along with this narrative for many

years (Jarnicki, Greif 2022). One aim of this project is to test Kuhn's narrative for its credibility in light of evidence of traces of his ideas concerning revolutions and paradigms that he might have formulated between his 1947 Aristotle Experience and his 1949 encounter with the *Entstehung*, and of any reading of the Gestalt psychologists or art historians before that time.

However, if the claim that Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge Fleck's influence in one way or another is true, an important complementary task will be to reflect on what Kuhn has likely missed in his adoption of Fleck's thought in particular – and, in consequence, what the tradition in the history and philosophy of science that he spawned may also have missed. There are some relevant insights for contemporary philosophy of science to be gathered here, for instance from Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój*, which is not properly translatable into English – it is usually translated as “mood” and apparently not grasped by Kuhn – but crucial to Fleck's approach. The applicant can build on previous work on this topic (Jarnicki 2016, Jarnicki 2021).

Only when we answer the question what the similarities between the two theories are, and once we can determine with certainty what Kuhn did not take from Fleck, it will be possible to appreciate Kuhn's innovations – which primarily seem to be his concept of paradigms in the narrow sense and the notion of a revolutionary instead of an evolutionary development of science. Only when we know what ideas Kuhn took from Fleck, and how, we can properly gauge the nature and influence of the most famous philosophy of science book of the twentieth century. Therefore, the results of this inquiry might be relevant beyond the disciplinary debates in the history of philosophy of science.

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars:

1. textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings
2. analysis of historical sources and
3. archival research.

While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. For the analysis of the genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and had to “translate” Fleck into English while reading.

Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in Gestalt psychology and art history. Despite living in different places at different times working and under different conditions, both authors appear to have been embedded in a similar intellectual milieu that deserves to be reconstructed.

Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. Therefore, archive research in various locations in Europe and the USA will form one of the pillars of the project. In order to ensure prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive will be prefaced by a detailed inquiry with its keepers into the kind and scope of material to be expected.

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:
 - 1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?

- 1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?
- 1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?
- 1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?
2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:
 - 2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?
 - 2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts has been ascribed to Fleck's writings?**
3. Archival research aims to provide:
 - 3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.
 - 3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

Work plan

The project is divided into four nine-month periods (A-D), during which we will:

- A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below),
- B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able,
- C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and
- D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).

I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.

II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.

III. Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.

IV. Archive research in the following locations:

- i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] in order to: collect unpublished texts to be analysed in regard of **vocabulary development and metaphors used; check accuracy of Kuhn's language barrier argument and resulting limited understanding of Fleck's book; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949 (when he read Fleck's book); check when Kuhn first read about Gestalt psychology; search for early relations about famous "Aristotle experience"; check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible and if yes – what Kuhn noted on margins and what underlined, check if there is any correspondence between Merton and Kuhn about Fleck, especially from the time when Merton was proofreading the translation of Fleck's book into English 1975-1979.**

- ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] in order to check if there are any mentions of Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn [according to **Trenn Conant was to read Fleck's book in 1950**].
 - iii. Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics] in order to check if there are any mentions of Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability) - because the similarity between Fleck and Kuhn at that time must have appeared striking, it is possible that these philosophers commented on it in private correspondence.
 - iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] in order to **study materials regarding the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,**
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] in order to check whether Polanyi **read Fleck's book; we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's Personal Knowledge);** check whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi.
 - vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know anything that could **shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011), Edward Shills, who according to Trenn read Fleck's book in 1937, Mark Kac, who knew both Kuhn and Fleck personally.**
- V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
- VIII. Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (accounting for the development of vocabulary over time with respect to Kuhn in particular).
- IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories – from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.

Preliminary research – previous work

In 2016, the PI published a paper in *The Translator*: “On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations”. Using the example of the concept of communication/circulation of thoughts [*Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli*], it demonstrated that, since both his Polish and his German texts are original texts (in which one theory was formulated), a translator of **Fleck's work or should mind that the level of equivalence between these texts is the level of concepts (rather than the level of lexical meaning)**. Similarly, when studying the relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, we will assume similarity not so much on the level of linguistic expressions, but on the level of concepts and their relations.

Over the last two years, the PI has written two extensive articles related to the topic of this proposal (Jarnicki 2021; Jarnicki, Greif 2022). In the first article, it is shown that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastroj* belongs to the domain of musical metaphors (the term is not properly translatable

into English and usually rendered as “mood”) and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). According to Oliveira (2017) one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other.

In the second article, the authors analyse Kuhn's few statements about Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his 1947 “Aristotle experience” and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience exactly when he found out about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn had a direct role in having Fleck's book translated into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton Archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who got Merton into convincing University of Chicago Press to publish Fleck's book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, who reluctantly agreed – and started to recount the Aristotle Experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

Preliminary research – vocabulary development

A prime example to demonstrate that tracking the development of Kuhn's vocabulary may prove fruitful lies in the evolution of his use of the word “thought”. In Kuhn's first book (1957), we find the following passages:

Such texts are a relatively frequent and extremely significant phenomenon in the *development of scientific thought*. They may be described as texts that *shift* the direction in which *scientific thought develops* [...] As a whole the *De Revolutionibus* stands almost entirely within an ancient astronomical and cosmological tradition; yet within its generally classical framework are to be found a few novelties which *shifted* the direction of *scientific thought* in ways unforeseen by its author and which gave rise to a rapid and complete break with the ancient tradition. (Kuhn 1957, p. 135) [emphasis – PJ]

[...] the *De Revolutionibus* marks a *shift* in the direction in which astronomical *thought developed*. (Kuhn 1957, p. 182) [emphasis – PJ].

So in 1957 Kuhn writes about the “development of thought”, whereas in his second book (1962) “thought” in this sense appears only once, as it seems, by accident: “conflict between competing schools of scientific thought” (Kuhn 1970, p. 96), because in 1962 he prefers to write about development of *science* instead of *thought*.

As we know, Ludwik Fleck wrote about the “development of thought”, “thought styles” and “thought collectives”. This is the first of the tracks to be followed: is it possible that Kuhn initially, under the influence of Fleck, wrote about the development of thought, only to liberate himself from the Fleckian vocabulary after 13 years? This makes the assumption more likely that Kuhn over time was narrowing Fleck's general theory to science.

Preliminary research – metaphors with shared aims

In the table below quotations from Fleck (1935 original and 1979 translation) and Kuhn (1962) that employ similar metaphors are juxtaposed. Both texts are about a group of people who look at one thing but see something different over the course of time. In Kuhn, the group has to experience a conversion (which is a religious metaphor), in Fleck the mood of the group has to change (which is a conceptual transfer from art history, and the concept of mood was one of the key concepts for temple architects). Both examples are given in the context of scientific discovery, and in both cases the passage is about a new emerging thought style (for Fleck, a shared mood [*Stimmung*] is a precondition of shared

thought style) and about a new emerging paradigm. Both paradigm and thought style determine perception by the group. The source domain from which both paradigm and thought style are conceptualised is seeing gestalts. In both cases, the gestalt metaphor is also used to underline that it is impossible to understand previous thought style/paradigm in terms of the subsequent one (and vice versa). In both cases, the metaphor is used to show that the change is not induced by reasoning and **logic, and that it happens independently of the intentions of the group's members. In the present project, this line of investigation will be further pursued, in much more detail and on a large corpus of Fleck's and Kuhn's writings.**

Fleck 1935 (original)	Fleck 1979 (translation)	Kuhn 1962 (original)
<p>eine Massensuggestion, die die gesamte Mannschaft eines Schiffes, auf der Suche nach einem verunglückten Boote befindlich, dieses Boot mit den Insassen wahrnehmen ließ, sogar Signalzeichen und Rufe. Erst in der letzten Minute der Annäherung platzte auf einmal die kollektive Halluzination: das Boot entpuppte sich als ein Baum mit Ästen und Blättern, von den Fluten getrieben. Dieser Fall könnte geradezu als Paradigma vieler Entdeckungen gelten: das stimmungsmäßige Gestaltsehen und der plötzliche Umschlag: andersartiges Gestaltsehen. Plötzlich versteht man überhaupt nicht, wie die frühere Gestalt möglich war und wie das ihr Widersprechende unbemerkt bleiben konnte. Genau so verhält es sich mit der wissenschaftlichen Entdeckung, nur aus der Aufregung und dem Fieber in Gleichmaß und Dauer übersetzt. Die disziplinierte, gleichmäßige und viele Generationen dauernde Stimmung eines Kollektives erzeugt das "wirkliche Bild" genau so, wie die fieberhafte eine Halluzination. In beiden Fällen verlaufen parallel Stimmungswechsel (Denkstilwechsel) und Bildwechsel. (Fleck 1935, p. 117)</p>	<p>a case of mass suggestion which induced the entire crew of a ship, while searching for a boat in distress, to see this craft and its crew and even to hear shouts and see signals. This collective hallucination was suddenly dispelled but only during the last minute of approach. The "boat" turned out to be a tree with branches and leaves drifting in the water. This case could be considered the very paradigm of many discoveries. The mood-conforming gestalt-seeing and its sudden reversal: the different gestalt-seeing. Suddenly one can no longer even understand how the previous form was possible and how features contradicting it could have gone unnoticed. The same situation obtains in scientific discovery, only translated from excitement and feverish activity into equanimity and permanence. The disciplined and even-tempered mood, persisting through many generations of a collective, produces the "real image" in exactly the same way as the feverish mood produces a hallucination. In both cases switch of mood (switch of thought style) and switch of image proceed in parallel. (Fleck 1979, p. 111)</p>	<p>Practicing in different worlds, the two groups of scientists see different things when they look from the same point in the same direction. Again, that is not to say that they can see anything they please. Both are looking at the world, and what they look at has not changed. But in some areas they see different things, and they see them in different relations one to the other. That is why a law that cannot even be demonstrated to one group of scientists may occasionally seem intuitively obvious to another. Equally, it is why, before they can hope to communicate fully, one group or the other must experience the conversion that we have been calling a paradigm shift. Just because it is a transition between incommensurables, the transition between competing paradigms cannot be made a step at a time, forced by logic and neutral experience. Like the gestalt switch, it must occur all at once (though not necessarily in an instant) or not at all. (Kuhn 1970, p. 150)</p>

4. Research methodology

The project will employ a set of methods common to the humanities:

1. Philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve surveying and analysing primary and secondary sources, retracing key concepts, arguments and references used and considering their context.

2. Archival research methods (item IV in the work plan).

3. Linguistic text analysis (items I, II, III, V, VI in the work plan), assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002).

4. Philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which will be conceptual in nature: They involve, first, probing for the meanings – as sense and reference – of key terms in Fleck, Kuhn and other relevant authors, the presumed logical relations between these terms and their place in a larger argumentative framework. Second, this work will be argumentative itself, in terms of developing hypotheses on the grounds of the results of the philological, conceptual and archival work.

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or near-native knowledge of English (Principal Investigator, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (Principal Investigator).

5. Project literature

Babich, B. E. (2003a). From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.

Babich, B. E. (2003b). Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).

Baldamus, W. (1976) *The structure of sociological inference*. Barnes & Noble Books.

Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for/Aufsätze für Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156, *Amsterdams Sociologisch Tijdschrift*). Amsterdam.

Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.

Baldamus, W. (1980). Letter to R. Merton, February 6, 1980. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5.

Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Chesham: Acumen. Reprint (2014) London: Routledge.

Braunstein, J.-F. (2003). Thomas Kuhn lecteur de Ludwik Fleck. *Archives de Philosophie*, 66, 403–422.

Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.

Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.

Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.

Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.

Dahms, H.-J. (2016). Thomas Kuhn's Structure: An "Exemplary Document of the Cold War Era"? In E. Aronova & S. Turchetti (Eds.), *Science Studies during the Cold War and Beyond: Paradigms Defected* (pp. 103–125). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.

- Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Fleck, L. (1935). Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: „Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego” oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej.
- Hagner, M. (2012). Perception, knowledge and freedom in the age of extremes: on the historical epistemology of Ludwik Fleck and Michael Polanyi. *Studies in Eastern European Thought*, 64, 107–120
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266–276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of ‘scientific community’.** *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157–168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163–173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn’s memory.** *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) *Stimmung/Nastrój as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck’s Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives.* *Foundations of Science* (early on-line).
- Jarnicki, P; Greif, H. (2022) **The ‘Aristotle Experience’ Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to ‘Structure’**, *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie* (early online since 8.06.2022, enclosed to the proposal).
- Jäkel, O. (2002). Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse. *English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd edition 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). Metaphors we live by.** Chicago, IL: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). **Thomas Kuhn’s revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?** London/New York: Bloomsbury.
- Marín, M. P. (2010). Ludwik Fleck: precursor del pensamiento de Thomas Kuhn. *Eidos: Revista de Filosofía de la Universidad del Norte*(13), 130–149.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oberheim, E. (2012). *Feyerabend’s Philosophy*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.

- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of *Structure*. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Reisch, G. A. (2016). Aristotle in the Cold War: On the Origins of Thomas Kuhn's *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. In R. J. Richards & L. Daston (Eds.), *Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions at Fifty: Reflections on a science classic*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.
- Sigurdsson, S. (2016). The nature of scientific knowledge: an interview with Thomas S. Kuhn. In *Shifting paradigms: Thomas S. Kuhn and the history of science* (pp. 17–30): Edition Open Access.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Trenn, T. J. (1981). Paper prepared for the Hamburg Colloquium on Ludwik Fleck held September 13th–16th, 1981: Some Reflections on the Chicago Edition of Fleck's Monograph. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5 .
- Werner, S., & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's *Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.
- Zittel, C. (2011). Ludwik Fleck und der Stilbegriff in den Naturwissenschaften. Stil als wissenschaftshistorische, epistemologische und ästhetische Kategorie. In H. Bredekamp & J. Krois (Eds.), *Sehen und Handeln*. Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, pp. 171–206.
- Zittel, C. (2014). Ludwik Flecks Gestaltbegriff und sein Blick auf die Gestaltpsychologie seiner Zeit. *NTM Zeitschrift für Geschichte der Wissenschaften, Technik und Medizin*, 22(1), 9–29.

PLAN BADAŃ

Lp.	Nazwa zadania	Podmioty
1	Analiza tekstów opublikowanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do roku 1962 włącznie - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
2	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Ludwika Flecka do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć z jego teorii i pojęć z teorii zastanych	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories	
3	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów opublikowanych)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of published texts)	
4	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Thomasa Kuhna [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	
5	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Jamesa Conanta [Harvard University Archives Repository]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in James Conant Archive [Harvard University Archives Repository]	

6	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Paula Feyerabenda [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	
7	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Roberta Mertona [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	
8	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Michaela Polanyi'ego [University of Chicago Library]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library]	
9	Badania w innych archiwach i wywiady z osobami, które mogą posiadać wiedzę mogącą rzucić światło na genealogiczny związek między teoriami Flecka i Kuhna, jak na przykład rodzina Wilhelma Baldamusa, która przechowuje jego korespondencję, poszukiwanie materiałów Thaddeusa Trenna i Harolda K. Schillinga z Pennsylvania State University, Marka Kaca i Edwarda Shillsa.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Research in other archives and interviews with individuals who might possess Społecznych knowledge that could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, search for materials of Thaddeus Trenn and Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University, Mark Kac and Edward Shills.	
10	Analiza niepublikowanych tekstów Thomasa Kuhna (do roku 1962 włącznie) - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	

11	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów niepublikowanych)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of unpublished texts)	
12	Porównanie metafor stosowanych przez Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	
13	Porównanie słownictwa Flecka i Kuhna (w odniesieniu do tego ostatniego, w ujęciu diachronicznym)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, in diachronic terms)	
14	Rozważenie możliwych wyjaśnień podobieństwa teorii Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	

ANKIETY CZŁONKÓW ZESPOŁU

KIEROWNIK (PI)

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

PRZEBIEG KARIERY NAUKOWEJ

- From 08.2018 to 02.2022 - **assistant professor** (half time) at Warsaw University of Technology; Faculty of Administration and Social Sciences.
- From 05.2015 - member of the Academy of Young Scholars and Artists (Wrocław).
- From 05.2013 to 04.2016 - **associated researcher** of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (ETHZ) and University of Zurich. From 04.2013 to 09.2016 - principal investigator of the project (see projects).
- From 2012 - a **member of the Board** of Project Science Foundation, from 12.2016 to 12.2019 Chairman of the Board.
- 15 May 2012 - **Ph.D. in humanities**. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty.
- 2009-2011 - **investigator** within the doctoral project (University of Wrocław) funded by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (State Committee for Scientific Research in Poland [Komitet Badań Naukowych] N N101 060336).
- 15 July 2005 - **Master of Arts**. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty, Institute of Polish Philology.

It should be noted that although PI's academic career has lasted for over a dozen years (he began his doctoral studies in 2005), the period of his full-time employment lasted for 5 years and two and a half months (from April 2013 to September 2016 - full time, from October 2018 to February 2022 - half time). During his doctoral studies, PI did not receive any scholarship that would allow him to not take up other works. He is a father of three children (born in 2011, 2015, and 2019).

PUBLIKACJE NAUKOWE

1. Paweł Jarnicki, Hajo Greif, *The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure'* (2022), artykuł, Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie, early online (8.06.2022)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0
Otwarty dostęp: nie, DOI 10.1515/agph-2020-0160
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
2. Paweł Jarnicki, *Stimmung/Nastrój as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives* (2021), artykuł, Foundations of Science, early online (5.04.2021)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI 10.1007/s10699-021-09792-3
Status publikacji: opublikowane
3. Paweł Jarnicki, *On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translation* (2016), artykuł, Translator, 22:3, 271-286
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 11
Otwarty dostęp: nie, DOI 10.1080/13556509.2015.1126881
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
4. Maria Ciesielska, Paweł Jarnicki, *Ludwik Fleck - mikrobiolog i filozof [Ludwik Fleck - microbiologist and philosopher]* (2021), książka, Oficyna Wydawnicza Politechniki Warszawskiej; ISBN 978-83-8156-251-5 (druk) ISBN 978-83-8156-252-2 (online)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
5. Paweł Jarnicki, *The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989)* (2016), artykuł, Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science, 1 (2016 - special issue on Ludwik Fleck), p.

21-30

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1

Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI 10.24117/2526-2270.2016.i1.05

Status publikacji: opublikowane

6. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metaforyczne konceptualizacje pojęcia 'tekstu' a przemiany stylów myślowych w literaturoznawstwie [Metaphorical conceptualizations of the concept of 'text' and changes of thought styles in history and theory of literature]* (2014), książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo 'Projekt Nauka', pp. 246

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 4

Otwarty dostęp: tak

Status publikacji: opublikowane

7. Paweł Jarnicki, Bożena Płonka-Syroka, Bogdan Balicki, *Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje [Ludwik Fleck - traditions - inspirations - interpretations]; [in the volume: Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie, p. 235–37; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim, p. 239–55; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim, p. 257–94; Postówie, p. 295–96]* (2015), książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 6

Otwarty dostęp: tak

Status publikacji: opublikowane

8. Paweł Jarnicki, *Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of "legitimation" [Polish extended version appeared as: O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka. In: Stan Rzeczy 10, p. 355-373]* (2015), artykuł, Divinatio: Studia Culturologica Series, vol. 41, autumn-winter, p. 167-184

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane

9. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metafory dyskursu intertekstualności, metaforyka tekstylna [Metaphors of intertextuality. Textile metaphors]* (2015), artykuł, Kształcenie Językowe, 13 (23): p. 49–72

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane

DOKONANIA ARTYSTYCZNE

b.d.

BADANIA NAUKOWE FINANSOWANE PRZEZ NCN

DANE POBRANE AUTOMATYCZNIE

Tytuł w języku polskim: **Filologiczna analiza filozoficznych dzieł Ludwika Flecka oraz ich tłumaczeń w językach: polskim, niemieckim i angielskim**

Nr rejestracyjny:

2012/06/M/HS2/00313

Źródło(a) finansowania:

NCN, Nazwa konkursu: HARMONIA-3

Kwota: **405 512 PLN**

Podmiot realizujący:

Projekt Nauka. Fundacja na rzecz promocji nauki polskiej

Data rozpoczęcia realizacji: **2013-03-25**, Data zakończenia realizacji: **2016-08-24**

Wynik oceny:

Uznanie umowy za wykonaną

Lista najważniejszych publikacji będących rezultatem projektu:

Publikacje w czasopiśmie:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Sandra Lang ("Introduction"); Paweł Jarnicki ("The beginnings..."), Introduction; The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989), *Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science*, 1, 3-5; 21-30, Graduate Program in History (Science and Culture in History) of Federal University of Minas Gerais (Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais), Brasil, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, On the Shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the Bilingual Philosophical Legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English Translations, *The Translator*, 22 (3), 271–286, Routledge, 2016, IF: 0.483, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka, *Stan Rzeczy*, 10, 355-373, Instytut Socjologii UW, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of “legitimation”, *Divinatio*, 41 (Aut.-Win.), 167-184, University of Sofia, Department of Cultural Studies, 2015, IF: 0, - Opublikowane

Publikacje książkowe/ rozdziały w publikacjach książkowych:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim; Posłowie, Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje, (nie dotyczy), 235-296, Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich we Wrocławiu, 2015, Wrocław, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2705.3208>, - Opublikowane

b.d.

INNE PROJEKTY BADAWCZE

b.d.

NAJWAŻNIEJSZE OSIĄGNIĘCIE NAUKOWE

The most important achievement is the clarification of the status of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives. Its specific situation generates specific problems for translators, who unfortunately had not recognized this specific status of Fleck's theory, so all the existing translations have to be deeply revised. Fleck's philosophical/sociological theory was expressed in two languages (Polish and German) more or less simultaneously by a bilingual author, who did not self-translate his texts into the second language but published original texts in both of these languages. It means that both Polish and German texts are of equal value, and if we want to speak of the level of equivalence, I argue we can find it at the level of concepts - it means that expressions that differ in lexical meaning may denote the very same concept. The problem is described - with an example of "circulation of thoughts" [Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli] expression - in the paper "On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations" published in *The Translator*.

DOŚWIADCZENIE NAUKOWE

- From May, 2013 to April 2016 - associated researcher of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich), [regular short stays within the realization of grant number 2012/06/M/HS2/00313].
- 07-09.2009 query in British Library (London), [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].
- 11-12.2009 query in Ludwik Fleck Archive in Zurich and Library of the University of Zurich [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336]

WYRÓŻNIENIA I NAGRODY

b.d.

WYKŁADY I REFERATY

CONFERENCE PAPERS (from 2014)

- 17-19.09.2014, Toruń, international conference: "Situating Solidarities" (European Association for the Study of Science and Technology and Nicolaus Copernicus University), paper: "'Gestalts' of Ludwik Fleck";
- 27-29.11.2014, Berlin, international conference: "Self-Translation as Transfer of Knowledge" (Zentrum für Literatur- und Kulturforschung), paper: "Ludwik Fleck's Legacy – an Example of Self-Translation?";
- 3-8.08.2015, Helsinki, international conference: 15th Congress on Logic, Methodology, and Philosophy of Science 2015 (University of Helsinki), paper: "The reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives in English";
- 28-30.10.2015, Marburg, international conference: "Entangled science? Relocating GermanPolish scientific relations" (the Leibniz Association and the Polish Academy of Sciences), poster: "Ludwik Fleck's "Polish-German" theory of thought styles and thought collectives, and problems arising from its translation";
- 11-14.04.2019, Lviv, international conference: "Ludwik Fleck and His Thought Collectives" (Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Center for Urban History of East Central Europe, Ukrainian Catholic University), paper: "What is 'mood'? About translating of 'Stimmung/nastrój' into English".
- 23-26.06.2020, Singapore, international conference HOPOS 2020 (The Thirteenth Biennial Congress of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science), paper: "The role of (conceptual) metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings" selected for presentation but the event was canceled.
- 7-9.07.2021, Kent (on-line), international conference: The British Society for the Philosophy of Science 2021 Annual Conference, paper [with Hajo Greif]: "The Aristotle Experience and the Genesis of the Kuhnian Revolution".

INNE ISTOTNE OSIĄGNIĘCIA W NAUCE

Organization:

- 03.2016-international conference in Wrocław: "Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives – translations and receptions".
- 03.2014-international conference in Wrocław: "Ludwik Fleck – traditions, inspirations, interpretations".
- 01.2014-international workshop in Zurich: "Translation of Science – Science of Translation".
- 10.2009-First Polish Constructivist Symposium in Wrocław.
- 2008-2012 foundation of "Science of science" circle in Wrocław - 34 meetings took place.

OPUS 23 (submitted 06.2022) – rejected at the first stage – 64,50%

A1. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (30%) – **3,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

A2. POTENTIAL IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%) – **1,00** (on a scale of 0 to 2).

A3. FEASIBILITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%) – **2,00** (on a scale of 0 to 2).

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (40%) – **3,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

GENERAL JUSTIFICATION

The experts found the project interesting and well written. The concept and work plan are clearly articulated and the project is feasible. The panel decided, however, not to send the project for further evaluation. The biggest worry concerns the significance of the project. Bringing the sociology of science to centre stage in the philosophy of science is an important development but the question of whether one specific individual working in the field influenced another and if so, how exactly, was thought to be of secondary importance. All in all the impact of the project on systematic issues in philosophy of science remains underdeveloped. The panel found that the PI has the right profile to lead the project as most of the items in the list of publications bear on Fleck's work. But for this stage of his career, the list of publications of the PI could contain more items in first ranked peer reviewed journals.

INDIVIDUAL REVIEWS

A1. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (30%)

Expert 1:

The project has mainly a historical interest as it compares the theories of Fleck and Kuhn with an emphasis on the textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings, and the analysis of the historical sources behind them in order to reveal eventually the direct influences and the common reference points. The originality of the project lies precisely in deepening the level of comparison between the two writers to a degree not attained by previous scholars. Unlike other similar works which compare Kuhn and Fleck, the current project looks at the way Fleck's concepts might have informed Kuhn's vocabulary. The project is very well written, the concept and work plan are clearly articulated. On a more critical side, one of the weaknesses lies in its philosophical part which remains undeveloped. What is, after all, the expected impact of the project on philosophy of science and methodological issues in contemporary debates? This weakness is also reflected in the research methodology (section 4) where the description of the philosophical methods to be employed is rather sketchy.

Expert 2:

Generally, I liked this research proposal. As is explained in the overview, opinions vary on the extent to which Thomas Kuhn's seminal "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" was influenced by the ideas of the Polish biologist Ludwik Fleck. (Thus, the PI is not the first to consider this matter.) The proposal aims to carry out detailed archival research in the hope of shedding some light on the issue. The

project itself is well-conceived and perfectly feasible. The PI appears to be well-equipped to undertake it. My biggest worry is how significant it is. Yes, bringing the sociology of science to centre stage in the philosophy of science is an important development, and it is worth trying to understand how it came about. But the question of whether one specific individual working in the field influenced another and if so, exactly how looks secondary.

A2. POTENTIAL IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%)

Expert 1:

If the research hypotheses of the project are substantiated, Fleck's influence on Kuhn's work might be seen in a new light and in a broader historical perspective. But it is more difficult to see, on the basis of the project, which focuses mainly on the similarities between the two, what other impact the project may have, especially its impact on systematic issues in philosophy of science. These issues should have been addressed in more detail.

Expert 2:

This would be a 2 if the notion of "research field" were more narrowly drawn.

The project aims to determine the extent to which Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions was influenced by Ludwik Fleck. The proposal outlines the range of opinions encountered in the literature. For those interested in Kuhn scholarship, the impact may be high. But---the fact that Kuhn's ideas are considered ground-breaking notwithstanding---how many people is that?

A3. FEASIBILITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%)

Expert 1:

The project goals are very well focused, rather narrow in scope, and within that scope the project is very well planned, with a clear timetable and methodology sustaining its objectives. The composition of the team is appropriate and the division of labor between the researchers is clearly correlated with the tasks and objectives.

Expert 2:

The investigation requires access to various archives. This seems to have been sensibly researched and thought through. The PI has experience of working in this area and knowledge of the relevant literature. There is essentially no reason why it shouldn't succeed. I worry a little about the possible difficulties of hiring a research assistant with knowledge of the area, very good English and native-level German. But maybe the PI has an individual in mind.

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND SCIENTIFIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (40%)

Expert 1:

The PI's academic career has lasted for about 12 years but we are told that he has effectively worked only for 5 years. The PI has the right profile to lead the project as most of the items in the list of publications bear on Fleck's work, which is essential for the current project. Also the list of publications witnesses well the PI's expertise in the field, and so does his research achievements which match very well the clarification of the status of Fleck's thought styles. Perhaps on a more critical side, many of the items in the publications list are in Polish, and the international experience (visits abroad, presentations to international conferences) is rather modest.

Expert 2:

The PI is ten years out of his PhD. He has a clutch of publications---some in minor venues, others in international journals, though these strike me as not being first-rank.

STRENGTHS OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

The project addresses an important theme: the comparison of the works of Fleck and Kuhn with the aim of clarifying the extent to which the former has influenced the latter. Given the enormous influence of Kuhn's work on contemporary philosophy and history of science, questions of priority are crucial. The strengths of the project lies in the historiographical and the comparative linguistic analysis covering also new unpublished material.

Expert 2

The proposal is very well-written, in perfect English.

The case for investigating the detailed influence of Fleck on Kuhn is well argued.

Kuhn is considered a pivotal figure in the development of the philosophy of science. Setting his work within the context of similar ideas in circulation at the time is of general interest.

The use of archive material seems to be well thought through.

WEAKNESSES OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

If weaknesses had to be found, they would concern the systematic part of the project and its consequences for contemporary issues in philosophy of science. I would have expected more working hypotheses to arise from the preliminary research on the conceptual similarities between Fleck and Kuhn. After all Kuhn's seminal monograph has been in place for 60 years. For my limited knowledge of these matters, the hypothesis mentioned in the project according to which Kuhn changed his account of Aristotle in order to distract scholars' attention from other influences does sound as a sheer speculation.

Expert 2

Notwithstanding Kuhn's importance, the project is very specialized: did this particular individual influence that one? Well who cares? (This sort of thing happens all the time.) None of this actually tells us anything about the structure of scientific revolutions.

There is a potential feasibility issue in terms of being able to hire an RA meeting the stated requirements.

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

OPUS-25

Wniosek o finansowanie projektu badawczego

Na ramionach niewidocznego olbrzyma? Odkrywanie wpływu Ludwika Flecka na Thomasa Kuhna

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Uniwersytet Wrocławski

Wydział Nauk Społecznych

OPIS SKRÓCONY

On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant?

Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

1. Scientific goal of the project

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). Given that Kuhn read the *Entstehung* more than a decade before he wrote the *Structure*, it is evident that these similarities are not purely coincidental. Given the number and degrees of similarity between key concepts, it is evident that Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thought has been notable. However, Kuhn acknowledged Fleck's importance only in a few places, only in passing and only with qualifications. Still, the nature, depth and scope of Fleck's influence on Kuhn are not very well documented or analysed to date.

The aim of this inquiry in the history of philosophy of science is to provide an in-depth account of the **genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work** in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to commonplace philosophy of science comparison of two "ready-made" theories, the present study will pick up on the few more historically minded inquiries into the Fleck-Kuhn relation and build a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence that Fleck's writings had on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. It will do so by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. It will use the information from those sources for exploring a spectrum of possible hypotheses concerning Fleck's influence on Kuhn and assess their merits. The guiding hypothesis of this project is that **Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledged**.

The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at its sceptical end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of the existence but only superficially appreciated the *Entstehung* or did not fully understand it, so any talk of an influence is exaggerated (Wray 2016, 4). At most, Fleck anticipated some views of Kuhn in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum, there are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him (Baldamus 1977, 135, 151). Between those extremes, there are views according to which Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either only had an indirect and un- or even subconscious influence on him, or that Kuhn's reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his previous ideas.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented. Mending this situation requires both comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and tracing the possible routes of concept transfer. Although both tasks are relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to demonstrate how and to what extent Fleck's concepts informed Kuhn. Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence, **the novelty of this project lies in the combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn**.

Notably, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (i.a. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011) – write little or even nothing about Fleck. On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Mößner (2011), Peine (2011). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus', which compares the vocabularies of Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books, there is little attention being paid to how Fleck's concepts may actually have informed Kuhn's. Therefore, research on the relations between Kuhn's and Fleck's work needs to be deepened, by asking **what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved**. It also needs to be broadened, by **analysing the metaphors and development of vocabulary in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials**, in light of his reading of Fleck and other, partly common sources. **Kuhn's theory will therefore be investigated *in statu nascendi***.

There is another article that, while not examining the Fleck-Kuhn relationship in detail, does provide arguments that show the importance of the project. Caneva (2005) notes the similarities between the theories, and even describes both conceptions as "essentially indistinguishable". He notes that the quality of the introduction to Fleck's book, written by Kuhn, is strange because it contrasts with Caneva's observation (Kuhn was his supervisor) that Kuhn was "an unsurpassed master when it came to understanding texts and teasing out their meanings and implications." Caneva then analyzes Kuhn's statements and considers the reasons of dislike to Fleck given by him as "hardly cogent." Caneva concludes his article with a message that once we realize the similarity between the two theories, "It is hard to resist the

speculation that [...] Kuhn distanced himself from his Polish predecessor the better to secure what he wished to be regarded as *his* intellectual property." Although Caneva's article does not conclusively settle the matter, it indeed confirms the need for to study the relationship between the two theories.

Numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account – from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (Kuhn's teacher and boss while at Harvard), but also from Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015). Shared influences on Fleck and Kuhn will be accounted for, too, in particular those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether or not Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is one matter of investigation.

All the parallels and shared influences raise the question of what precise position of influence Fleck had on Kuhn. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed that he read Fleck's book in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date to 1950/1951, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn started to claim that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited, due to a limited grasp of Fleck's German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 only confirmed ideas that he had already conceived of before. At around the same time (in his 1976 *Foreword* to the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn started to trace the origins of his reasoning to what he called the "Aristotle Experience", which he dates back to 1947, when he was a 25 years old PhD student in physics who was asked by James B. Conant, his superior, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. When Kuhn found himself struggling to understand Aristotle's Physics, he suddenly realised that Aristotle's science is not false and meaningless but simply different from the contemporary physics that he himself was taught. From 1976 onwards, Kuhn would describe this experience as a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were born, too. (For more on these circumstantial evidences, see: Jarnicki, Greif 2022)

Caneva (2005) notes the similarities between the theories, and even describes both conceptions as "essentially indistinguishable". He notes that the introduction to Fleck's book, written by Kuhn, is strange because it contrasts with Caneva's observation (Kuhn was his supervisor) that Kuhn was "an unsurpassed master when it came to understanding texts and teasing out their meanings and implications." Caneva then analyzes Kuhn's statements and considers the reasons of dislike to Fleck given by him as "hardly cogent." Caneva concludes his article, once we realize the similarity between the two theories, "It is hard to resist the speculation that [...] Kuhn distanced himself from his Polish predecessor the better to secure what he wished to be regarded as *his* intellectual property." Although Caneva's article does not conclusively settle the matter, it certainly confirms the need for to study the relationship between the two theories.

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars: 1. textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings, 2. analysis of secondary sources and 3. archival research. While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in *Gestalt* psychology and art history. Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. For the analysis of the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and while reading had to "translate" Fleck into contemporary English.

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:

1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?

1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?

1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?

1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?

2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:

2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?

2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts has been ascribed to Fleck's writings?

3. Archival research aims to provide:

- 3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.
- 3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

Work Plan

The project is divided into four nine-month periods, during which we will A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below), B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able, C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).

- I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- III. Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.
- IV. Archive research in
 - i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] - collect unpublished texts to be analysed in regard of vocabulary development and metaphors used; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949; check when Kuhn first read about *Gestalt* psychology; search for early relations about the "Aristotle experience"; check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible;
 - ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] - check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn,
 - iii. Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics] - check if there are any mentions about Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability),
 - iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] - study materials regarding the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] - check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*) and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi,
 - vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know more on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).
- V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.
- VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
- VIII. Comparison of vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, taking into account development of his vocabulary in time).
- IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories - from parallel discoveries to plagiarism - based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.

In order to ensure prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive under (IV) will be prefaced by a detailed inquiry with the keepers of the archives into the kind and scope of material to be expected.

Preliminary research

Besides work on the peculiarities of translating Fleck (Jarnicki 2016), the PI has written two extensive articles over the last two years (Jarnicki 2021; Jarnicki, Greif 2022). In the first article, it is shown that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastroj* belongs to the domain of musical metaphors (the term is not properly translatable into English and

usually rendered as “mood”) and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). According to Oliveira (2017) one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other. In the second article, the authors analyse Kuhn's few statements about Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his 1947 “Aristotle experience” and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience exactly when he found out about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn had a direct role in having Fleck's book translated into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton Archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who got Merton into convincing University of Chicago Press to publish Fleck's book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, who reluctantly agreed – and started to recount the Aristotle Experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

Risk assessment

The by far largest project risk is new pandemic, making travel to archives not only difficult but impossible. For this case, funds earmarked for travel are re-allocated to pay the archives for drawing copies of documents to be mailed to us.

4. Research methodology

The project will employ a set of methods common to the humanities:

- 1) philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve surveying and analysing primary and secondary sources, retracing key concepts, arguments and references used and considering their context;
- 2) archival research methods (item IV in the work plan);
- 3) linguistic text analysis (items I, II, III, V, VI in the work plan), assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002);
- 4) philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve semantic analysis of key terms and as well as the development of hypotheses on the grounds of the results of the philological, conceptual and archival work.

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or nearnative knowledge of English (PI, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (PI).

5. Project literature

- Babich, B. E. (2003a). “From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability”. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.
- Babich, B. E. (2003b). “Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*”. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The Sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Acumen (2014 Routledge), p. 15-18.
- Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.
- Caneva, K.L. (2005). ‘Discovery’ as a site for the collective construction of scientific knowledge. *Historical Studies in the Physical and Biological Sciences*, Vol. 35, No. 2 (March), 175-291.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: "Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego" oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Lublin: Wydawnictwo UMCS.
- Cedarbaum, D. G. (1983). Paradigms, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, Volume 14, Issue 3, p. 173-213.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1989, *Die Wissenschaftsphilosophie Thomas S. Kuhns: Rekonstruktion und Grundlagenprobleme*. Eng. Trans. (1993). *Reconstructing Scientific Revolutions: Thomas S. Kuhn's Philosophy of Science*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1990, "Kuhn's conception of incommensurability" *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 21: 481–92.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266–276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157–168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163–173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, *English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) *Stimmung/Nastrój* as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives. *Foundations of Science* (early on-line).
- Jarnicki, P.; Greif, H. (2022) The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure', *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*, early online (8.06.2022).
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd ed. 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G. & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?* London/New York: Bloomsbury.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Peine, A. (2011). Challenging incommensurability: What we can learn from Ludwik Fleck for the analysis of configurational innovation. *Minerva*, 49(4), 489-508.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Werner, S. & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.

OPIS SZCZEGÓŁOWY

On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant? Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

1. Scientific goal of the project

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). Given that Kuhn read the *Entstehung* more than a decade before he wrote the *Structure*, it is evident that these similarities are not purely coincidental. Given the number and degrees of similarity between key concepts, it is evident that Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thought has been notable. However, Kuhn acknowledged Fleck's importance only in a few places, only in passing and only with qualifications. Still, the nature, depth and scope of Fleck's influence on Kuhn are not very well documented or analysed to date.

In his theory of thought styles and thought collectives, Fleck, like Kuhn would do after him, opposed speculation about how science should work while highlighting the importance of how it actually works. Both Fleck and Kuhn explicitly claimed that scientific knowledge is not simply additive, that it changes as a whole and questioned the classic definition of truth and the possibility of pure observation. Fleck, like Kuhn after him, observed the influence of social factors and non-verbalisable elements on the content of scientific cognition and looked at the role the history of science plays in the reflection on science. The scientists connected by one "thought style" constitute a "thought collective" in Fleck, which does not differ significantly from Kuhn's "scientific community." Kuhn's use of the term "paradigm" often does not follow his own specific technical meaning but the broad meaning of a "conceptual framework." This broad meaning is fairly close to Fleck's "thought style". Fleck, like Kuhn after him, also saw the stages of the development of a thought style. In the moments of breakthrough (Fleck writes about "intellectual unrest"), scientists seem to alternately see the old "Gestalt" and the new one, and after the breakthrough, the world in which scientists live will have changed. Fleck also referred to the incommensurability and untranslatability of thought styles and the dependence of words' meanings on thought styles – all concepts that would resurface in Kuhn.

The aim of this **inquiry in the history of philosophy of science** is to provide an in-depth account of the **genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work** in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to the comparison of two "ready-made" theories (as presented in *Entstehung* and *Structure* respectively) that has so far been common practice in philosophy of science, the present study will pick up on the relatively few more historically minded inquiries into the Fleck-Kuhn relation and build a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence that Fleck's writings had on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. It will do so by critically considering primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. It will use the information from those sources to explore a spectrum of possible hypotheses concerning Fleck's influence on Kuhn and assess their merits. The **guiding hypothesis of this project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he himself and many philosophers of science after him generally acknowledge.**

The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at its sceptical end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of the existence but only superficially appreciated the

Entstehung or did not fully understand it, so any talk of an influence is exaggerated: “Fleck (1935/1979), for example, is often cited as having anticipated Kuhn, although more careful studies suggest that the similarities between their views are superficial.” (Wray 2016, p. 4) At most, Fleck anticipated some views of Kuhn in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum, there are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him: “The reader who is familiar with Kuhn's work will easily recognize that the majority of [Fleck's] terms is virtually identical with the basic terminology of *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*.” (Baldamus 1977, p. 151) “Invented by Ludwik Fleck [the concept of ‘scientific community’ ...] remained ignored until Thomas Kuhn appropriated it in 1962.” (Baldamus 1977, p. 135) Between those extremes, there are views according to which Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either only had an indirect and un- or even subconscious influence on him, which might be supported by the observation that Fleck “even illustrated the idea with some of the same examples Kuhn later adopted” (Oberheim 2012, p. 128); or that Kuhn's reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his previous ideas, which might be supported by Baldamus' (1979) observation that key concepts that are present in Fleck can be found in Kuhn's writings in increasing frequency over the course of the years.

2. Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which it is widely believed that Kuhn was an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence exerted by Fleck is at least insufficiently documented.

On the one hand, statistics from the Scopus database show that at there at least six times between 1979-2019 as many works on Kuhn than on Fleck.

Between 1979-2019 in Scopus there are 938 papers about/related to Kuhn, whereas only 157 about/related to Fleck.

On the other hand, a pilot survey among Polish academics in May 2020 by the PI documents a perceived need of acknowledging Fleck's contribution (P. Jarnicki, *A Survey on the Opinion of Polish Researchers on the Relationship between the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn*). The survey was conducted on a sample of 23 philosophers from Poland, who consider their knowledge of Kuhn's and Fleck's theories to be at least good. According to the judgement of the majority of respondents, there was an influence from Fleck on Kuhn that the latter only insufficiently acknowledged¹.

Mending this situation requires both **comparison of the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and tracing the possible routes of transfer of related vocabulary and metaphors.**

¹ To the question about the connection between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, 1 answered “don't know” and only 1 pointed that there is “no influence”, 5 chose “anticipated” (which we interpret as no genealogical connection), 5 chose “forerunner” (which we interpret as weak genealogical connection), 7 chose “source of inspiration” (which we interpret as genealogical connection), 2 chose “strong influence” (which we interpret as significant genealogical connection), 2 chose “plagiarism”. So, 16/23 Polish philosophers see the weaker or stronger genealogical connection. To the question if “Thomas Kuhn has acknowledged the merits of Ludwik Fleck sufficiently”, 3 answered “don't know”, only 5 answered “yes” and as many as 15 (i.e. 65%) answered “no”.

Although either task is relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to demonstrate how and to what extent Fleck's concepts informed Kuhn. Given that there are earlier attempts at demonstrating such an influence (see below), **the novelty of this project lies in the combination of a historiographical analysis of shared influences and a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn.**

Notably, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (i.a. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000, 2005, 2007), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011) – write little or even nothing about Fleck. For example, Alexander Bird (2000) discusses Fleck completely separately from Kuhn as just one of many elements of the background who “encouraged the rejection of the picture of science as the accumulation of knowledge driven by a rational scientific method.” In a subsection on Fleck the name Kuhn is not mentioned even once. Similarly, Marcum (2015) briefly discusses Fleck as one intellectual influence among others, such as Wittgenstein. Part of the mission of the present proposal is to **vindicate the assumption that Fleck's influence on Kuhn has been more prominent and more pronounced than Kuhn scholarship generally acknowledges.**

On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, especially Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Braunstein (2003), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Dahms (2016), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Marín (2010), Mößner (2011) and Peine (2011). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently thought style versus paradigm and thought collective versus scientific community. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus', which compares the vocabularies of Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books, there is little attention being paid to how Fleck's concepts may actually have informed Kuhn's. Therefore, research on the relations between Kuhn's and Fleck's work needs to be deepened, by asking **what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved.** It also needs to be broadened, by **analysing the metaphors and development of vocabulary in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials.** Tracing the underlying genealogical relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, whatever its concrete nature might be, will help to shed light on the conceptual similarities and differences involved.

Even when authors sympathizing with Fleck, such as Peine (2011) or Collins (2012), write about the relation between Fleck and Kuhn, they usually do not recognize this relation as genealogical one. Peine's intention, for instance, is to show that some of Fleck's concepts are complementary to Kuhn's theory, as if they were synchronous affairs. Because Peine sets out from a discussion of the differences between two “ready-made” theories, he readily convinces himself that Kuhn rejected more than took from Fleck: “while Kuhn has indeed resembled some of Fleck's central ideas, he was reluctant to accept Fleck's more radical claim that science is an essentially social process”. In contrast, the **present inquiry will start from identifying the most incontrovertible similarities, and Kuhn's theory will be compared with Fleck's not as a “ready-made” theory, but first and foremost as a theory *in statu nascendi.***

In the late 1970s, Wilhelm Baldamus (1977, 1979), when comparing the development of Kuhn's vocabulary over time to Fleck's, implicitly suggested that Thomas Kuhn may have plagiarised Fleck, in terms of “appropriating” Fleck's key ideas and concepts to a larger extent than he would acknowledge. These allegations – presumably due to the popularity of Kuhn's book and his authority at the time – were never thoroughly investigated. Baldamus was more outspoken in private correspondence with Robert Merton (Baldamus 1980). Notably, suspicions of plagiarism or other forms of illicit appropriation of Fleck's ideas by Kuhn, are frequently raised in informal fashion but rarely discussed in writing. The only explicit reference to a possible charge of plagiarism against Kuhn in the literature can be found in what actually is an awkward denial of that charge. Babette Babich (2003b) claims that even if Kuhn had intended to refer to Fleck to a larger extent than he did, or even

if he had been inclined to commit plagiarism, he would have been prevented from doing so because of the partly inquisitory nature of Cold War anti-communism at that time in the USA. Any reference to such “ideologically problematic terms like ‘thought collective’ and ‘thought style’” would have put Kuhn’s reputation and academic career at risk.

Conversely, Collins (2012) writes that Kuhn was not “as original as we all once thought”, because “Fleck did it first and, in a lot of ways did it best”, while adding that finally Kuhn was the one “responsible for telling the history of science in a thought-collective kind of way”, because he was the one who “created the social change by coming along at the right time and writing in English.” Some may conclude that even if the most extreme explanation of the similarities between Kuhn and Fleck is true, namely Kuhn plagiarised Fleck, it is still a fact that Kuhn had a huge impact on the history of philosophy of science, and not Fleck, so Fleck’s philosophy is just a historical footnote. Of course, one might think this way – the one who was successful, the one who had a successful career standing on the shoulders of other people’s intellectual accomplishments is the one who carries the day. However, this is thinking in categories that one would consider outside the sphere of science – cynical thinking. If there is any reasonable evidential support for a suspicion that Thomas Kuhn illicitly appropriated his most important philosophical ideas from Ludwik Fleck, then this possibility must be explicitly considered (Jarnicki, Greif 2022).

There is another article that, while not examining the Fleck-Kuhn relationship in detail, does provide arguments that show the importance of the project. Caneva (2005) notes the similarities between the theories, and even describes both conceptions as “essentially indistinguishable”. He notes that the quality of the introduction to Fleck’s book, written by Kuhn, is strange because it contrasts with Caneva’s observation (Kuhn was his supervisor) that Kuhn was “an unsurpassed master when it came to understanding texts and teasing out their meanings and implications.” Caneva then analyzes Kuhn’s statements and considers the reasons of dislike to Fleck given by him as “hardly cogent.” Caneva concludes his article with a message that once we realize the similarity between the two theories, “It is hard to resist the speculation that [...] Kuhn distanced himself from his Polish predecessor the better to secure what he wished to be regarded as *his* intellectual property.” Although Caneva’s article does not conclusively settle the matter, it indeed confirms the need for to study the relationship between the two theories.

Even if from today’s perspective, Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories appear different to an observer – he or she might be, for instance, aware of the differences between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s concepts of “incommensurability” – one has to bear in mind that such differences were probably not nearly as apparent as they are today. In the wake of the publication of the *Structure*, a wide variety of approaches to the social and cultural studies of science developed, and today we are aware of many more nuances that probably were imperceptible to people who read the *Structure* right after its publication, when it not only caused a major stir but also still had to give rise to the very social and cultural studies of science that now form the observer’s vantage point. This is an argument against the claim that the similarity between Kuhn and Fleck is superficial upon closer inspection. Only today are we able to point out all the differences. It should also be emphasized that, in the case of an obvious relation between two authors, it would be untoward in terms of strategy and method of inquiry to discuss the differences without accounting for the similarities first. In order to adequately discuss the differences between Kuhn’s and Fleck’s theories, we must first thoroughly study and explicate the similarities between them and identify, to the greatest possible extent, which of these similarities are of genealogical nature.

On the other hand, many influences that shaped both Fleck’s and Kuhn’s views are not at all obvious to the contemporary observer but were nonetheless important to them in all the nuance and detail that escape us now. Accordingly, numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account – from the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré,

Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017) and from James Bryant Conant (Kuhn's teacher and boss while at Harvard), but also from Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015). An analysis of the relationship between Kuhn and the French epistemologists shows that there are indeed similarities (Simons 2017), but these appear to be far fewer than between Fleck and Kuhn, whereas the former but not the latter are documented in Kuhn's footnotes. Wray's (2016) downplaying of Fleck's influence in his demonstration of Conant's influence on Kuhn is weakened by the fact that Conant read Fleck's book in 1950 (see Trenn 1981), so there still might be a mediated influence.

According to Moleski (2006), Kuhn and Polanyi met in 1958 and after publication of Kuhn's *Structure* Polanyi had a (not publicly stated) belief that Kuhn was dishonest to him. Jacobs (2002), who argues for Kuhn's undisclosed debt to Polanyi, claims that Kuhn's notion of scientific community is taken from Polanyi rather than from Fleck, because Fleck's thought collective "denotes a considerably wider class of social groups". Debt to Fleck certainly does not exclude debt to Polanyi, but Kuhn read Fleck earlier than he read Polanyi. We must also take into account the possibility that that Kuhn, with Polanyi's help, narrowed down Fleck's general theory of thought collectives, which is applicable to science, fashion, religion and other domains, to scientific communities. However, Fleck's book was in fact a study of a scientific thought collective, while many of Kuhn's concepts, such as 'paradigm shift', were later readily applied to domains other than science.

Shared influences on Fleck and Kuhn will be accounted for, too, in particular those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestaltpsychologie* (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether or not Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is one matter of investigation. Oliveira's (2017) paper about the first – unpublished – chapter of the *Structure* demonstrates that in the beginnings one of the key ideas of Kuhn was to make the image of science appear closer to the image of art (as the latter develops in a non-cumulative way). In doing this, he transferred some elements of knowledge about art history to the way we understand science. Since Fleck was informed of the concepts of style and mood (*nastrój/Stimmung*) in art history, it seems justified to ask whether these influences – on Kuhn and Fleck – were wholly independent (Jarnicki 2021). This question might become even more pertinent in light of the observation that Fleck remained critical of arthistorical notions of style that render it as an objective characteristic of a given collective that would allow for equally objective comparison rather than the nucleus of a proto-concept of incommensurability, as it would later be articulated by Kuhn (Zittel 2011).

The influence of the Gestalt psychologists on both authors is obvious and straightforward by comparison. It seems that both Kuhn and Fleck have similarly transferred (this is kind of a metaphor) the knowledge of psychologists to epistemology (for Fleck's reference to Gestalt psychology, see Zittel 2014 and Hagner 2012; the latter comparatively evaluates Gestalt psychology's import on Fleck and Michael Polanyi, who has also been cited as an under-acknowledged influence on Kuhn, see above). In 1979, Cedarbaum (1983) interviewed Kuhn and wrote: "Also, Kuhn allows that Fleck's discussion of, and emphasis on, Gestalt psychology may have awakened his own interest in the field; that contribution alone would make G.D.S.F. [*Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*] enormously significant in the formation of *Structure*."

All these parallels and shared influences raise the question of what precise position of influence Fleck held in that relation. In his three published statements dating from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix–x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed that he read Fleck's book in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date to 1950/1951, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures ("The development of Kuhn's new image of the nature of science began with the 1951 Lowell lectures", Marcum 2015), i.e., after reading Fleck. However, from 1976 onwards Kuhn claimed that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was limited,

because of a limited grasp of Fleck's German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 were ideas that he had already conceived of before he read Fleck, so that Fleck's *Entstehung* only confirmed his own ideas. This change of narrative over the years is the primary evidence for a shifting perception in Kuhn of what Fleck's import on his own thought actually was, and ultimately for an insufficiently acknowledged influence from Fleck (Jarnicki, Greif 2022).

In any case, the focus of Kuhn scholarship has long been distracted from possible influences exerted by Fleck (and Polanyi?), on the grounds of one peculiar Kuhnian narrative. From 1976 (in his Foreword to *Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*, the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn started to trace the origins of his reasoning to what he called the "Aristotle Experience". According to his own account, this foundational experience took place in 1947 when he was a 25 years old PhD student in physics, and was asked by James B. Conant, his superior at the time, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. When Kuhn found himself struggling to understand Aristotle's Physics, which initially seemed ridiculously mistaken and misconceived to him, he suddenly realised that Aristotle's physics is not false and meaningless but simply different from the contemporary physics that he himself was taught. According to the autobiographic narrative that Kuhn would develop from 1976 onwards, this was a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were born, too. Many Kuhn scholars went along with this narrative for many years (Jarnicki, Greif 2022). One aim of this project is to test Kuhn's narrative for its credibility in light of evidence of traces of his ideas concerning revolutions and paradigms that he might have formulated between his 1947 Aristotle Experience and his 1949 encounter with the *Entstehung*, and of any reading of the Gestalt psychologists or art historians before that time.

However, if the claim that Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge Fleck's influence in one way or another is true, an important complementary task will be to reflect on what Kuhn has likely missed in his adoption of Fleck's thought in particular – and, in consequence, what the tradition in the history and philosophy of science that he spawned may also have missed. There are some relevant insights for contemporary philosophy of science to be gathered here, for instance from Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój*, which is not properly translatable into English – it is usually translated as "mood" and apparently not grasped by Kuhn – but crucial to Fleck's approach. The applicant can build on previous work on this topic (Jarnicki 2016, Jarnicki 2021).

Only when we answer the question what the similarities between the two theories are, and once we can determine with certainty what Kuhn did not take from Fleck, it will be possible to appreciate Kuhn's innovations – which primarily seem to be his concept of paradigms in the narrow sense and the notion of a revolutionary instead of an evolutionary development of science. Only when we know what ideas Kuhn took from Fleck, and how, we can properly gauge the nature and influence of the most famous philosophy of science book of the twentieth century. Therefore, the results of this inquiry might be relevant beyond the disciplinary debates in the history of philosophy of science.

3. Concept and work plan

This inquiry is based on three pillars:

1. textual analysis of Kuhn's and Fleck's writings
2. analysis of historical sources and
3. archival research.

While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on literary and linguistic levels, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources that document any influence that Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilised in order to interpret the nature of those similarities and differences. For the

analysis of the genealogical relationship between the two theories, it will have to be taken into account that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and had to "translate" Fleck into English while reading.

Besides direct influences, common reference points for Fleck and Kuhn in pre-existing literature will have to be identified, for example in Gestalt psychology and art history. Despite living in different places at different times working and under different conditions, both authors appear to have been embedded in a similar intellectual milieu that deserves to be reconstructed.

Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and be scattered across various archives. It is here where most novel insights are to be expected. Therefore, archive research in various locations in Europe and the USA will form one of the pillars of the project. In order to ensure prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive will be prefaced by a detailed inquiry with its keepers into the kind and scope of material to be expected.

In more detail, the threefold structure of the project is this:

1. Text analysis aims to answer following questions:

1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the (published and unpublished) texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?

1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?

1.1.2. Did Kuhn use phrases in texts from before 1962 that were closer to those of Fleck when considering similar phenomena?

1.2. Does the selection of metaphors used both by Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of the received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?

2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:

2.1. What were influences and reference points shared by Fleck and Kuhn?

2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts has been ascribed to Fleck's writings?

3. Archival research aims to provide:

3.1. Unpublished sources that document the kind and degree of influence that Fleck's writings had upon Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.

3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for text analysis indicated in 1.1. and 1.2. above.

Work plan

The project is divided into four nine-month periods (A-D), during which we will:

- A) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III below),
- B) then we will conduct archive research and perform an analysis of unpublished texts (IV, V, VI below) in order to be able,
- C) to compare relevant data on Kuhn and Fleck's theories and answer the question what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VII, VIII below) and
- D) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that seek to explain the similarity (IX below).

I. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.

II. Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding published texts of Thomas Kuhn.

III. Text analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2 regarding texts of Ludwik Fleck.

IV. Archive research in the following locations:

i. Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] in order to: collect unpublished texts to be analysed in regard of vocabulary development and metaphors used; check accuracy of Kuhn's language barrier argument and resulting limited understanding of Fleck's book; check if Kuhn made any notes about ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949 (when he read Fleck's book); check when Kuhn first read about Gestalt psychology; search for early relations about famous "Aristotle experience"; check if Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible and if yes – what Kuhn noted on margins and what underlined, check if there is any correspondence between Merton and Kuhn about Fleck, especially from the time when Merton was proofreading the translation of Fleck's book into English 1975-1979.

ii. James Conant Archive [Part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] in order to check if there are any mentions of Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn [according to Trenn Conant was to read Fleck's book in 1950].

iii. Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, the library of the London School of Economics] in order to check if there are any mentions of Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently of each other, and they both stayed together and discussed a lot at Berkeley before they published their texts about incommensurability) - because the similarity between Fleck and Kuhn at that time must have appeared striking, it is possible that these philosophers commented on it in private correspondence.

iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] in order to study materials regarding the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,

v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] in order to check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book; we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*); check whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi.

vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know anything that could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011), Edward Shills, who according to Trenn read Fleck's book in 1937, Mark Kac, who knew both Kuhn and Fleck personally.

V. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - point 1.1. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.

VI. Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 regarding metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific

revolution etc.) and concepts of the received theories (truth, observation, fact etc.) - point 1.2. regarding unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn.

VII. Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.

VIII. Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (accounting for the development of vocabulary over time with respect to Kuhn in particular).

IX. Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the two theories – from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of existing literature.

Preliminary research – previous work

In 2016, the PI published a paper in *The Translator*: “On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations”. Using the example of the concept of communication/circulation of thoughts [*Denkverkehr/krążenie myśli*], it demonstrated that, since both his Polish and his German texts are original texts (in which one theory was formulated), a translator of Fleck’s work or should mind that the level of equivalence between these texts is the level of concepts (rather than the level of lexical meaning). Similarly, when studying the relationship between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories, we will assume similarity not so much on the level of linguistic expressions, but on the level of concepts and their relations.

Over the last two years, the PI has written two extensive articles related to the topic of this proposal (Jarnicki 2021; Jarnicki, Greif 2022). In the first article, it is shown that Fleck’s concept of *Stimmung/nastroj* belongs to the domain of musical metaphors (the term is not properly translatable into English and usually rendered as “mood”) and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). According to Oliveira (2017) one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn’s philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent of each other.

In the second article, the authors analyse Kuhn’s few statements about Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his 1947 “Aristotle experience” and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience exactly when he found out about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn had a direct role in having Fleck’s book translated into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton Archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who got Merton into convincing University of Chicago Press to publish Fleck’s book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, who reluctantly agreed – and started to recount the Aristotle Experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* might have effectively distracted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the grounds of further linguistic and archival research.

Preliminary research – vocabulary development

A prime example to demonstrate that tracking the development of Kuhn’s vocabulary may prove fruitful lies in the evolution of his use of the word “thought”. In Kuhn’s first book (1957), we find the following passages:

Such texts are a relatively frequent and extremely significant phenomenon in the *development of scientific thought*. They may be described as texts that *shift* the direction in which *scientific thought develops* [...] As a whole the *De Revolutionibus* stands almost entirely within an ancient astronomical and cosmological tradition; yet within its generally classical framework are to be found a few novelties which *shifted* the direction of *scientific thought* in ways unforeseen by its author and which gave

rise to a rapid and complete break with the ancient tradition. (Kuhn 1957, p. 135)
[emphasis – PJ]

[...] the *De Revolutionibus* marks a *shift* in the direction in which astronomical *thought* developed. (Kuhn 1957, p. 182) [emphasis – PJ].

So in 1957 Kuhn writes about the “development of thought”, whereas in his second book (1962) “thought” in this sense appears only once, as it seems, by accident: “conflict between competing *schools of scientific thought*” (Kuhn 1970, p. 96), because in 1962 he prefers to write about development of *science* instead of *thought*.

As we know, Ludwik Fleck wrote about the “development of thought”, “thought styles” and “thought collectives”. This is the first of the tracks to be followed: is it possible that Kuhn initially, under the influence of Fleck, wrote about the development of thought, only to liberate himself from the Fleckian vocabulary after 13 years? This makes the assumption more likely that Kuhn over time was narrowing Fleck’s general theory to science.

Preliminary research – metaphors with shared aims

In the table below quotations from Fleck (1935 original and 1979 translation) and Kuhn (1962) that employ similar metaphors are juxtaposed. Both texts are about a group of people who look at one thing but see something different over the course of time. In Kuhn, the group has to experience a conversion (which is a religious metaphor), in Fleck the mood of the group has to change (which is a conceptual transfer from art history, and the concept of mood was one of the key concepts for temple architects). Both examples are given in the context of scientific discovery, and in both cases the passage is about a new emerging thought style (for Fleck, a shared mood [*Stimmung*] is a precondition of shared thought style) and about a new emerging paradigm. Both paradigm and thought style determine perception by the group. The source domain from which both paradigm and thought style are conceptualised is seeing *gestalts*. In both cases, the *gestalt* metaphor is also used to underline that it is impossible to understand previous thought style/paradigm in terms of the subsequent one (and vice versa). In both cases, the metaphor is used to show that the change is not induced by reasoning and logic, and that it happens independently of the intentions of the group’s members. In the present project, this line of investigation will be further pursued, in much more detail and on a large corpus of Fleck’s and Kuhn’s writings.

Fleck 1935 (original)	Fleck 1979 (translation)	Kuhn 1962 (original)
eine Massensuggestion, die die gesamte Mannschaft eines Schiffes, auf der Suche nach einem verunglückten Boote befindlich, dieses Boot mit den Insassen wahrnehmen ließ, sogar Signalzeichen und Rufe. Erst in der letzten Minute der Annäherung platzte auf einmal die kollektive Halluzination: das Boot entpuppte sich als ein Baum mit Asten und Blättern, von den Fluten getrieben. Dieser Fall könnte geradezu als Paradigma vieler Entdeckungen gelten: das stimmungsmäßige Gestaltsehen und der plötzliche Umschlag: andersartiges Gestaltsehen.	a case of mass suggestion which induced the entire crew of a ship, while searching for a boat in distress, to see this craft and its crew and even to hear shouts and see signals. This collective hallucination was suddenly dispelled but only during the last minute of approach. The "boat" turned out to be a tree with branches and leaves drifting in the water. This case could be considered the very paradigm of many discoveries. The mood-conforming gestalt-seeing and its sudden reversal: the different gestalt-seeing. Suddenly one can no longer	Practicing in different worlds, the two groups of scientists see different things when they look from the same point in the same direction. Again, that is not to say that they can see anything they please. Both are looking at the world, and what they look at has not changed. But in some areas they see different things, and they see them in different relations one to the other. That is why a law that cannot even be demonstrated to one group of scientists may occasionally seem intuitively obvious to another. Equally, it is why, before they can hope

<p>Plötzlich versteht man überhaupt nicht, wie die frühere Gestalt möglich war und wie das ihr Widersprechende unbemerkt bleiben konnte. Genau so verhält es sich mit der wissenschaftlichen Entdeckung, nur aus der Aufregung und dem Fieber in Gleichmaß und Dauer übersetzt. Die disziplinierte, gleichmäßige und viele Generationen dauernde Stimmung eines Kollektives erzeugt das "wirkliche Bild" genau so, wie die fieberhafte eine Halluzination. In beiden Fällen verlaufen parallel Stimmungswechsel (Denkstilwechsel) und Bildwechsel. (Fleck 1935, p. 117)</p>	<p>even understand how the previous form was possible and how features contradicting it could have gone unnoticed. The same situation obtains in scientific discovery, only translated from excitement and feverish activity into equanimity and permanence. The disciplined and even-tempered mood, persisting through many generations of a collective, produces the "real image" in exactly the same way as the feverish mood produces a hallucination. In both cases switch of mood (switch of thought style) and switch of image proceed in parallel. (Fleck 1979, p. 111)</p>	<p>to communicate fully, one group or the other must experience the conversion that we have been calling a paradigm shift. Just because it is a transition between incommensurables, the transition between competing paradigms cannot be made a step at a time, forced by logic and neutral experience. Like the gestalt switch, it must occur all at once (though not necessarily in an instant) or not at all. (Kuhn 1970, p. 150)</p>
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Risk assessment

The by far largest project risk is new pandemic, making travel to archives not only difficult but impossible. For this case, funds earmarked for travel are re-allocated to pay the archives for drawing copies of documents to be mailed to us.

4. Research methodology

The project will employ a set of methods common to the humanities:

1. Philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which involve surveying and analysing primary and secondary sources, retracing key concepts, arguments and references used and considering their context.

2. Archival research methods (item IV in the work plan).

3. Linguistic text analysis (items I, II, III, V, VI in the work plan), assisted with the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980, and developed by others, for instance, Jäkel 2002).

4. Philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which will be conceptual in nature: They involve, first, probing for the meanings – as sense and reference – of key terms in Fleck, Kuhn and other relevant authors, the presumed logical relations between these terms and their place in a larger argumentative framework. Second, this work will be argumentative itself, in terms of developing hypotheses on the grounds of the results of the philological, conceptual and archival work.

The team will be composed of scholars with expertise in philosophy of science and linguistics. As triangulating between three languages is a necessity for this inquiry, the team members possess excellent, native or near-native knowledge of English (Principal Investigator, Co-Investigator), German (Co-Investigator) and Polish (Principal Investigator).

5. Project literature

- Babich, B. E. (2003a). From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.
- Babich, B. E. (2003b). Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).
- Baldamus, W. (1976) *The structure of sociological inference*. Barnes & Noble Books.
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, & H. Korte (Eds.), *Human Figurations. Essays for/Aufsätze für Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156, *Amsterdams Sociologisch Tijdschrift*). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Baldamus, W. (1980). Letter to R. Merton, February 6, 1980. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5.
- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Chesham: Acumen. Reprint (2014) London: Routledge.
- Braunstein, J.-F. (2003). Thomas Kuhn lecteur de Ludwik Fleck. *Archives de Philosophie*, 66, 403–422.
- Brorson, S., & Andersen, H. (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109–129.
- Caneva, K.L. (2005). 'Discovery' as a site for the collective construction of scientific knowledge. *Historical Studies in the Physical and Biological Sciences*, Vol. 35, No. 2 (March), 175-291.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420–423.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé & B. G. Figueiredo (Eds.), *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.
- Dahms, H.-J. (2016). Thomas Kuhn's Structure: An "Exemplary Document of the Cold War Era"? In E. Aronova & S. Turchetti (Eds.), *Science Studies during the Cold War and Beyond: Paradigms Defected* (pp. 103–125). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.
- Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Fleck, L. (1935). Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006). *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego: „Powstanie i rozwój faktu naukowego” oraz inne pisma z filozofii poznania*. Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej.
- Hagner, M. (2012). Perception, knowledge and freedom in the age of extremes: on the historical epistemology of Ludwik Fleck and Michael Polanyi. *Studies in Eastern European Thought*, 64, 107–120
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266–276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157–168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163–173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.

- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) *Stimmung/Nastrój* as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives. *Foundations of Science* (early online).
- Jarnicki, P.; Greif, H. (2022) The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure', *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie* (early online since 8.06.2022, enclosed to the proposal).
- Jäkel, O. (2002). Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse. *English and American Studies in German*, 2001, 4-6.
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd edition 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn & R. K. Merton (Eds.), *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?* London/New York: Bloomsbury.
- Marín, M. P. (2010). Ludwik Fleck: precursor del pensamiento de Thomas Kuhn. *Eidos: Revista de Filosofía de la Universidad del Norte*(13), 130–149.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oberheim, E. (2012). *Feyerabend's Philosophy*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Reisch, G. A. (2016). Aristotle in the Cold War: On the Origins of Thomas Kuhn's The Structure of Scientific Revolutions. In R. J. Richards & L. Daston (Eds.), *Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions at Fifty: Reflections on a science classic*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.
- Sigurdsson, S. (2016). The nature of scientific knowledge: an interview with Thomas S. Kuhn. In *Shifting paradigms: Thomas S. Kuhn and the history of science* (pp. 17–30): Edition Open Access.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Trenn, T. J. (1981). Paper prepared for the Hamburg Colloquium on Ludwik Fleck held September 13th-16th, 1981: Some Reflections on the Chicago Edition of Fleck's Monograph. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5 .
- Werner, S., & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.
- Zittel, C. (2011). Ludwik Fleck und der Stilbegriff in den Naturwissenschaften. Stil als wissenschaftshistorische, epistemologische und ästhetische Kategorie. In H. Bredekamp & J. Krois (Eds.), *Sehen und Handeln*. Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, pp. 171–206.
- Zittel, C. (2014). Ludwik Flecks Gestaltbegriff und sein Blick auf die Gestaltpsychologie seiner Zeit. *NTM Zeitschrift für Geschichte der Wissenschaften, Technik und Medizin*, 22(1), 9–29.

PLAN BADAŃ

Lp.	Nazwa zadania	Podmioty
1	Analiza tekstów opublikowanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do roku 1962 włącznie - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
2	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Ludwika Flecka do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć z jego teorii i pojęć z teorii zastanych	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories	
3	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów opublikowanych)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of published texts)	
4	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Thomasa Kuhna [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	
5	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Jamesa Conanta [Harvard University Archives Repository]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in James Conant Archive [Harvard University Archives Repository]	
6	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Paula Feyerabenda [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	

7	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Roberta Mertona [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	
8	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Michaela Polanyi'ego [University of Chicago Library]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Archive research in Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library]	
9	Badania w innych archiwach i wywiady z osobami, które mogą posiadać wiedzę mogącą rzucić światło na genealogiczny związek między teoriami Flecka i Kuhna, jak na przykład rodzina Wilhelma Baldamusa, która przechowuje jego korespondencję, poszukiwanie materiałów Thaddeusa Trenna i Harolda K. Schillinga z Pennsylvania State University, Marka Kaca i Edwarda Shillsa.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Research in other archives and interviews with individuals who might possess Społecznych knowledge that could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, search for materials of Thaddeus Trenn and Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University, Mark Kac and Edward Shills.	
10	Analiza niepublikowanych tekstów Thomasa Kuhna (do roku 1962 włącznie) - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
11	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów niepublikowanych)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to Społecznych conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of unpublished texts)	

12	<p>Porównanie metafor stosowanych przez Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	<p>Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn</p>	
13	<p>Porównanie słownictwa Flecka i Kuhna (w odniesieniu do tego ostatniego, w ujęciu diachronicznym)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	<p>Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, in diachronic terms)</p>	
14	<p>Rozważenie możliwych wyjaśnień podobieństwa teorii Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Wydział Nauk Społecznych
	<p>Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn</p>	

ANKIETY CZŁONKÓW ZESPOŁU

KIEROWNIK (PI)

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

PRZEBIEG KARIERY NAUKOWEJ

Information on education, academic degrees/titles and employment

- From 08.2018 to 02.2022 - **assistant professor** (half-time) at Warsaw University of Technology; Faculty of Administration and Social Sciences.
- From 05.2015 - a member of the Academy of Young Scholars and Artists (Wrocław).
- From 05.2013 to 04.2016 - **associated researcher** of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (ETHZ) and University of Zurich. From 04.2013 to 09.2016 - principal investigator of the project (see projects).
- From 2012 - a **member of the Board** of Project Science Foundation, from 12.2016 to 12.2019 Chairman of the Board.
- 15 May 2012 - **Ph.D. in humanities**. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty.
- 2009-2011 - **investigator** within the doctoral project (University of Wrocław) funded by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (State Committee for Scientific Research in Poland [Komitet Badań Naukowych] N N101 060336).
- 15 July 2005 - **Master of Arts**. The University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty, Institute of Polish Philology.

It should be noted that although PI's academic career has lasted for over a dozen years (he began his doctoral studies in 2005), the period of his full-time employment lasted for 5 years and two and a half months (from April 2013 to September 2016 - full time, from October 2018 to February 2022 - half time). During his doctoral studies, PI did not receive any scholarship that would allow him not to take up other works. He is a father of three children (born in 2011, 2015, and 2019).

Research stays at home and abroad

- From May 2013 to April 2016 - associated researcher of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich), [regular short stays within the realization of grant number 2012/06/M/HS2/00313].
- 07-09.2009 query in British Library (London), [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].
- 11-12.2009 query in Ludwik Fleck Archive in Zurich and Library of the University of Zurich [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336]

Lectures and presentations (from 2014)

- 17-19.09.2014, Toruń, international conference: "Situating Solidarities" (European Association for the Study of Science and Technology and Nicolaus Copernicus University), paper: "'Gestalts' of Ludwik Fleck";
- 27-29.11.2014, Berlin, international conference: "Self-Translation as Transfer of Knowledge" (Zentrum für Literatur- und Kulturforschung), paper: "Ludwik Fleck's Legacy – an Example of Self-Translation?";
- 3-8.08.2015, Helsinki, international conference: 15th Congress on Logic, Methodology, and Philosophy of Science 2015 (University of Helsinki), paper: "The reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives in English";
- 28-30.10.2015, Marburg, international conference: "Entangled science? Relocating GermanPolish scientific relations" (the Leibniz Association and the Polish Academy of Sciences), poster: "Ludwik Fleck's "Polish-German" theory of thought styles and thought collectives, and problems arising from its translation";
- 11-14.04.2019, Lviv, international conference: "Ludwik Fleck and His Thought Collectives" (Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Center for Urban History of East Central Europe, Ukrainian Catholic University), paper: "What is 'mood'? About translating of 'Stimmung/nastrój' into English".
- 23-26.06.2020, Singapore, international conference HOPOS 2020 (The Thirteenth Biennial Congress of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science), paper: "The role of (conceptual) metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings" selected for presentation but the event was canceled.
- 7-9.07.2021, Kent (online), international conference: The British Society for the Philosophy of Science 2021 Annual Conference, paper [with Hajo Greif]: "The Aristotle Experience and the Genesis of the Kuhnian Revolution".

Prizes and awards

Other significant achievements

Organization:

- 03.2016-international conference in Wrocław: "Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives – translations and receptions".
- 03.2014-international conference in Wrocław: "Ludwik Fleck – traditions, inspirations, interpretations".
- 01.2014-international workshop in Zurich: "Translation of Science – Science of Translation".
- 10.2009-First Polish Constructivist Symposium in Wrocław.
- 2008-2012 foundation of "Science of Science" circle in Wrocław - 34 meetings took place.

Other key information impacting the evaluation of the academic and research career

PUBLIKACJE NAUKOWE

1. Paweł Jarnicki, Hajo Greif, *The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure'* (2022), artykuł, *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*, early online (8.06.2022)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0
Otwarty dostęp: nie, DOI DOI 10.1515/agph-2020-0160
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
2. Paweł Jarnicki, *Stimmung/Nastrój as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives* (2021), artykuł, *Foundations of Science*, 27, pages 1207–1228, (2022, online: 05 April 2021)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 2
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI DOI 10.1007/s10699-021-09792-33
Status publikacji: opublikowane
3. Paweł Jarnicki, *On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translation* (2016), artykuł, *Translator*, 22:3, 271-286
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 14
Otwarty dostęp: nie, DOI DOI 10.1080/13556509.2015.1126881
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
4. Mauro L. Condé, Paweł Jarnicki, *Ludwik Fleck: Thought Style and Thought Collective in the Historiography of Science* (2024), rozdział, *Handbook for the Historiography of Science*, SPRINGER, editors: Mauro L. Condé, Marlon Salomon
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: przyjęta do publikacji, *Potwierdzenie przyjęcia do druku do pobrania z systemu, Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
5. Maria Ciesielska, Paweł Jarnicki, *Ludwik Fleck - mikrobiolog i filozof [Ludwik Fleck - microbiologist and philosopher]* (2021), książka, Oficyna Wydawnicza Politechniki Warszawskiej; ISBN 978-83-8156-251-5 (druk) ISBN 978-83-8156-252-2 (online)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane
6. Paweł Jarnicki, *The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989)* (2016), artykuł, *Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science*, 1 (2016 - special issue on Ludwik Fleck), p. 21-30
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI DOI 10.24117/2526-2270.2016.i1.05
Status publikacji: opublikowane
7. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metaforyczne konceptualizacje pojęcia 'tekstu' a przemiany stylów myślowych w literaturoznawstwie [Metaphorical conceptualizations of the concept of 'text' and changes of thought styles in history and theory of literature]* (2014), książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo 'Projekt Nauka'

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 4

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane

8. Paweł Jarnicki, Bożena Płonka-Syroka, Bogdan Balicki, *Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje [Ludwik Fleck - traditions - inspirations - interpretations] (in the volume: Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie [Two bibliographies of the reception of Ludwik Fleck and materials available on the Internet], p. 235–37; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim [Bibliography of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory in Polish], p. 239–55; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim [Bibliography of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory in English], p. 257–94; Posłowie [Afterword], p. 295–96) (2015)*, książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 6

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane

9. Paweł Jarnicki, *Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of "legitimation" [Polish extended version appeared as: O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka. In: Stan Rzeczy 10, p. 355-373] (2015)*, artykuł, Divinatio: Studia Culturologica Series, vol. 41, autumn-winter, p. 167-184

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane

10. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metafory dyskursu intertekstualności, metaforyka tekstylna [Metaphors of intertextuality. Textile metaphors] (2015)*, artykuł, Kształcenie Językowe, 13 (23): p. 49–72

Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0

Otwarty dostęp: nie

Status publikacji: opublikowane

DOKONANIA ARTYSTYCZNE

b.d.

BADANIA NAUKOWE FINANSOWANE PRZEZ NCN

DANE POBRANE AUTOMATYCZNIE

Tytuł w języku polskim: **Filologiczna analiza filozoficznych dzieł Ludwika Flecka oraz ich tłumaczeń w językach: polskim, niemieckim i angielskim**

Nr rejestracyjny:

2012/06/M/HS2/00313

Źródło(a) finansowania: NCN, Nazwa konkursu: b.d.

Kwota: **405 512 PLN**

Podmiot realizujący:

Projekt Nauka. Fundacja na rzecz promocji nauki polskiej

Data rozpoczęcia realizacji: **2013-03-25**, Data zakończenia realizacji: **2016-08-24**

Wynik oceny:

Uznanie umowy za wykonaną

Lista najważniejszych publikacji będących rezultatem projektu:

Publikacje w czasopiśmie:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Sandra Lang ("Introduction"); Paweł Jarnicki ("The beginnings..."), Introduction; The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989), *Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of*

- Science, 1, 3-5; 21-30, Graduate Program in History (Science and Culture in History) of Federal University of Minas Gerais (Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais), Brasil, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, On the Shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the Bilingual Philosophical Legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English Translations, *The Translator*, 22 (3), 271–286, Routledge, 2016, IF: 0.483, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka, *Stan Rzeczy*, 10, 355-373, Instytut Socjologii UW, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of “legitimation”, *Divinatio*, 41 (Aut.-Win.), 167-184, University of Sofia, Department of Cultural Studies, 2015, IF: 0, - Opublikowane

Publikacje książkowe/ rozdziały w publikacjach książkowych:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim; Poślowie, Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje, (nie dotyczy), 235-296, Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich we Wrocławiu, 2015, Wrocław, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2705.3208>, - Opublikowane

b.d.

INNE PROJEKTY BADAWCZE

b.d.

NAJWAŻNIEJSZE OSIĄGNIĘCIE NAUKOWE

The most important achievement is the clarification of the status of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives. Its specific situation generates specific problems for translators, who unfortunately had not recognized this specific status of Fleck's theory, so all the existing translations have to be deeply revised. Fleck's philosophical/sociological theory was expressed in two languages (Polish and German) more or less simultaneously by a bilingual author, who did not self-translate his texts into the second language but published original texts in both of these languages. It means that both Polish and German texts are of equal value, and if we want to speak of the level of equivalence, I argue we can find it at the level of concepts - it means that expressions that differ in lexical meaning may denote the very same concept. The problem is described - with an example of "circulation of thoughts" [Denkverkehr/krążenie myśli] expression - in the paper "On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations" published in *The Translator*.

OPUS 25 (submitted 06.2023) – rejected at the first stage – 76,38%

A1. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (30%) – **4,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

A2. POTENTIAL IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%) – **1,50** (on a scale of 0 to 2).

A3. FEASIBILITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%) – **1,75** (on a scale of 0 to 2).

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (40%) – **3,50** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

GENERAL JUSTIFICATION

The Panel of Experts agreed that the topic of the proposal is very important. There was also agreement that the PI is uniquely qualified to carry out the proposed research. However, the Panel of Experts also expressed serious concerns about the proposed research. These concerns were twofold. First, the research plan was not very clear about the publication plans and dissemination, which are supposed to be the key components of the proposed research. Second, while the PI is undoubtedly an authority on Fleck, their background in Kuhn scholarship and general international visibility were less obvious.

INDIVIDUAL REVIEWS

A1. SCIENTIFIC QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (30%)

Expert 1:

This is a potentially very significant project on the influence of Fleck's philosophy on Kuhn's philosophical system. It would have been good to have more information about the details of the archival research involved

Expert 2:

The proposal showcases a project of notable scientific significance, centering on the intricate relationships between the conceptual frameworks of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn and exploring the potential influence of Fleck on Kuhn. This overarching aim not only raises the compelling question of whether Kuhn was influenced by Fleck, but it also introduces a fresh layer of investigation - a reexamination of key concepts in their works. This endeavour holds promise for unveiling novel interpretations that could transcend traditional boundaries in the history of philosophy of science. The project's research plan is a standout feature, meticulously breaking down tasks and revealing how they contribute to the overarching goal. This methodical approach, complemented by a detailed timeline, ensures a systematic and comprehensive investigation.

However, while the main objective is well defined, there is a notable absence of a detailed publication plan. A stronger commitment to disseminating findings through well-chosen publication avenues could enhance the project's impact and accessibility. Additionally, the conference engagement strategy appears to be concentrated in the final year, potentially limiting the project's visibility and engagement with the scholarly community. Thus, the project's strength in scientific quality is established through its ambitious central aim, rigorous research plan, and the promise of

groundbreaking reinterpretations. Addressing the publication and conference strategy could further enhance its scientific impact and outreach.

A2. POTENTIAL IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%)

Expert 1:

The impact of the proposed research is not insignificant, but it may be more relevant for the Fleck community than for the history of philosophy of science.

Expert 2:

The potential impact of this research project is palpable. By revealing the intricacies of the interplay between Fleck and Kuhn's ideas, the project opens doors to fresh perspectives in the history of philosophy of science. The anticipated reinterpretations could recalibrate prevailing narratives and inspire scholarly dialogues. However, the project's full impact might be hinged upon its ability to connect with a wider audience, necessitating a comprehensive publication plan and a broader conference strategy. Engaging experts with diverse perspectives as external collaborators could further enhance the project's resonance and its contribution to the evolving discourse.

A3. FEASIBILITY OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT (15%)

Expert 1:

A very strong case was made in the application for the feasibility of the project (also underlined by the principal investigator's obviously significant expertise

Expert 2:

The feasibility of the project appears strong, as evidenced by the comprehensive research plan, systematic timeline, and well-considered risk mitigation strategies. The well-defined main research objective and the precise interconnections between tasks underscore the project's rigor. The risk mitigation plan acknowledges potential challenges, particularly external factors like pandemics, and offers alternative pathways to ensure progress. The PI's extensive expertise in the legacy of Ludwik Fleck serves as an additional pillar of feasibility. However, the PI's relatively short period of full-time academic employment may imply a certain level of early career status that needs to be aligned with the project's scope. Additionally, the absence of international collaborations could be addressed to further bolster the feasibility of the project.

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (40%)

Expert 1:

The principal investigator is without a doubt among the top historians of philosophy working on Fleck's work, but their publications are mostly published in not so top journals.

Expert 2:

The Principal Investigator (PI) of the research project possesses a nuanced blend of qualifications and accomplishments that lend an insightful perspective to the proposed endeavour. Although having received his PhD in 2012, his full-time academic employment spanning only five years situates him within the realm of an early career researcher.

The PI's publication record, as outlined in the proposal, reflects a diverse array of contributions. Notably, his authorship of three books in Polish, each dedicated to Ludwik Fleck – a central figure to

the project – underscores his dedication to the philosophical lineage underpinning the proposed research. While citation scores may appear moderate, it is important to recognise that these publications delve into a specialised realm, which can sometimes impede widespread recognition due to their focused nature.

Of particular significance is the PI's expertise in the heritage of Ludwig Fleck, a cornerstone theme linking directly to the project's aims. This positioning as a leading authority in the life and works of Fleck augments the project's credibility, suggesting a seamless integration of his knowledge into the proposed exploration of Fleck's influence on Thomas Kuhn.

The PI's growing conference presence highlights a willingness to engage with peers and to share insights on a broader platform. However, the absence of invited lectures in the PI's conference engagements might suggest that while his expertise is valued within academic circles, a broader international recognition may not yet be fully established.

STRENGTHS OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

The proposed research promises to explore the influence of the philosophical works of Fleck on Kuhn's philosophical system. This is a novel and original angle and could lead to research with significant impact for the relevant research communities in the history of philosophy and the history of the philosophy of science

Expert 2

- clear and engaging research objective: the proposal articulates a compelling research objective, delving into the interconnectedness of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn's conceptual frameworks and investigating potential influences, which promises to reshape historical interpretations.

- detailed research plan: the project's well-structured research plan breaks down tasks meticulously, showcasing a thoughtful approach that contributes to the overarching goal while maintaining a systematic focus.

- comprehensive risk mitigation: the proposal acknowledges potential challenges and offers comprehensive risk mitigation strategies, showcasing careful consideration of obstacles and providing alternative routes to ensure project advancement.

- expertise of the PI: the PI's extensive knowledge of Ludwik Fleck's legacy stands out, positioning the PI as a key figure in the area and adding credibility to the project's exploration.

- potential for novel interpretations: by reevaluating concepts in the works of Fleck and Kuhn, the project has the potential to generate fresh insights that challenge established narratives in the history of philosophy of science.

WEAKNESSES OF THE PROPOSAL:

Expert 1

the application could be more specific about the details of the archival research to be undertaken as part of the proposed research. While the principal investigator is clearly a top Fleck researcher, their background and preparedness on the philosophy of Thomas Kuhn is less obvious or at least less demonstrable

Expert 2

- publication plan absence: despite the project's rigour, a lack of a detailed publication plan is notable. A more explicit commitment to sharing findings through reputable publication avenues could amplify the project's reach and scholarly impact.

- concentrated conference engagement: the strategy of reserving conference engagement predominantly for the final year might hinder the project's visibility and dialogue within the academic community, warranting consideration for broader engagement throughout the project's lifespan.

- limited international collaborations: the project doesn't involve international collaborations, which could potentially limit diverse perspectives and inputs. Inclusion of experts with differing stances could enrich the research and its conclusions.

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

OPUS 27

Wniosek o finansowanie projektu badawczego

Na ramionach niewidocznego olbrzyma? Odkrywanie wpływu Ludwika Flecka na Thomasa Kuhna

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich

OPIS SKRÓCONY

[w języku angielskim]

1) Scientific goal of the project

Despite the numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and collectives and Thomas Kuhn's theory of scientific development, neither the nature nor the extent of Fleck's influence on Kuhn has been adequately documented or analyzed to date. This project in the history of philosophy of science aims to explore in depth the possible genealogical relationship between these two theories.

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). Given that Kuhn read *Entstehung* more than a decade before writing *Structure*, these similarities may not be coincidental. Given the number and degree of similarity between key concepts, it is likely that Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thinking was considerable. However, Kuhn only acknowledged Fleck's importance in a few places, and only in passing and with qualifications. Yet the nature, depth and extent of Fleck's influence on Kuhn have not been well documented or analyzed. The aim of this study is to provide a detailed account of the possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to common philosophy of science comparisons of two "ready-made" theories, the present study will build on the few more historically minded investigations of the Fleck-Kuhn relationship and provide a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence of Fleck's writings on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. It will do so by critically examining primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analyzing previously unrecognized evidence. It will use the information from these sources to explore a range of possible hypotheses about Fleck's influence on Kuhn and assess their merits.

The guiding hypothesis of this project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he and many philosophers of science after him have generally acknowledged. The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at one end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of their existence but only superficially appreciated their emergence or did not fully understand them, so that any talk of influence is exaggerated (Wray 2016, 4). At most, Fleck anticipated some of Kuhn's views in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without giving him proper credit (Baldamus 1977, 135, 151). Between these extremes are views that Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it either had only an indirect and unconscious or even subconscious influence on him, or that Kuhn's reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his earlier ideas.

2) Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which Kuhn is widely considered an original philosopher of science, and at the same time it is clear to many specialists that the influence of Fleck is at least insufficiently documented. To remedy this situation, it is necessary both to compare the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and to trace the possible routes of conceptual transfer. Although both tasks are relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to show how and to what extent Fleck's concepts influenced Kuhn. While there have been previous attempts to demonstrate such influence, the novelty of this project lies in combining a historiographical analysis of shared influences with a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn, and the use of generative intelligence tools to analyze the similarities between the two theories.

In particular, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (e.g. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011, 2021a) – write little or nothing about Fleck or consider Fleck's influence on Kuhn superficial (Wray 2021b). On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, notably Baldamus (1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Mößner (2011), Peine (2011). However, most of these studies do not complement each other and remain limited to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently *thought style* versus *paradigm* and *thought collective* versus *scientific community*. With a few exceptions, these studies pay little attention to how Fleck's concepts may have actually influenced Kuhn's. Baldamus compares the vocabularies of Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books and implicitly charges Kuhn with plagiarism. Caneva (2005) goes so far as to suggest that Kuhn downplayed the importance of Fleck's influence in order to secure his intellectual property. According to these observations, research on the relationship between Kuhn's and Fleck's work needs to be deepened by asking what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved. It also needs to be broadened by analyzing the metaphors and development of vocabulary in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials, in light of his reading of Fleck and other, partly common, sources. Kuhn's theory is thus examined *in statu nascendi*.

In his three published statements from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6-7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed to have read *Entstehung* in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date from 1950/51, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures. However, from 1976 Kuhn started to claim that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was constrained by a limited grasp of Fleck's German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 merely confirmed ideas he had already conceived. At about the same time (in his 1976 *Foreword* to the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn began to trace the origins of his thinking to what he called the "Aristotle experience", which he traced back to 1947, when, as a graduate student in physics, he was asked by his supervisor, James B. Conant, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. As Kuhn struggled to understand Aristotle's *Physics*, he suddenly

realized that Aristotle's science was not false and meaningless, but simply different from the contemporary physics he himself had been taught. From 1976 onwards, Kuhn would describe this experience as a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were also born. This change of narrative coincides with the publication of Fleck's English translation. The significance of this change for the originality of Kuhn's thought will be explored through in-depth archival research (not only in the Kuhn archives, but also in the archives of J. Conant, P. Feyerabend, R. Merton, M. Polanyi, T. Trenn, H. Schilling, M. Kac, E. Shils, W. Baldamus) and linguistic analysis of Kuhn's theory *in statu nascendi* in comparison with Fleck's theory. (First steps in this direction were made in Jarnicki, Greif 2022). From Reisch (2019, 176, 221) we know that Fleck's "book appears in Kuhn's preliminary sketches for his [Kuhn's] Lowell Lectures" and that the initial title of the cycle (*The Creation of Scientific Objects*) "echoes" Fleck's *Entstehung*.

Numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account, mostly on the basis of secondary literature and cooperation with the group of external experts. Influences include the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017), and James B. Conant (Kuhn's teacher and superior at Harvard), but also Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015) and Stephen Toulmin. Common influences on Fleck and Kuhn will also be considered, especially those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and gestalt psychology (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is a matter for investigation. All the parallels and shared influences raise the question of the precise position of Fleck's influence on Kuhn. Whatever the outcome, we will gain new insights into Fleck's possible influence on Kuhn and a more historically grounded understanding of the history of contemporary philosophy of science and the social studies of science. The use of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) methods and tools to analyze the similarities (concepts, motifs, theses, argumentation, narration, style and examples) between two theories may yield additional, less obvious insights that will be critically evaluated by the research team members and the group of external experts.

3) Concept and work plan

Preliminary research

In addition to working on the peculiarities of translating Fleck (Jarnicki 2016), the PI has published two extensive articles in the last four years (Jarnicki 2021; Jarnicki, Greif 2022). The first article shows that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój* belongs to the realm of musical metaphor (the term cannot be properly translated into English and is usually rendered as "mood") and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). According to Oliveira (2017), one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been completely independent. In the second article, the authors analyze Kuhn's few statements on Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his "Aristotle experience" in 1947 and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience precisely when he heard about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn played a direct role in the translation of Fleck's book into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who persuaded Merton to have the University of Chicago Press publish Fleck's book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, and Kuhn reluctantly agreed – and began to recount the Aristotle experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle Experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* may have effectively diverted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the basis of further linguistic and archival research.

Work Plan

This research rests on three pillars: 1. **textual analysis** (both using the corpus analysis toolkit and with the aid of GenAI tools) of Kuhn's (both published and unpublished) and Fleck's writings, 2. **analysis of secondary sources**, and 3. **archival research**. While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analyzed on a literary and linguistic level, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into the similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources documenting any influence Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilized to interpret the nature of these similarities and differences. In addition to direct influences, it will be necessary to identify common points of reference for Fleck and Kuhn in existing literature, for example in Gestalt psychology and art history. Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and scattered in various archives. It is here that the most novel insights are to be expected. In analyzing the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it is important to bear in mind that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and had to "translate" Fleck into contemporary English as he read.

More specifically, the three-fold structure of the project is as follows:

1. Textual analysis aims to answer the following questions:

1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the texts (published and unpublished) written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?

1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?

1.1.2. In pre-1962 texts, did Kuhn use phrases closer to Fleck's to describe similar phenomena?

1.2. Does the choice of metaphors used by both Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?

1.3. What are the similarities between the two theories (concepts, motifs, theses, argumentation, style and examples) and what are the major differences between the two theories?

2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:

2.1. What influences and points of reference did Fleck and Kuhn share?

2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts is attributed to Fleck's writings?

3. Archival research aims to provide:

3.1. Unpublished sources documenting the nature and extent of the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn, as well as shared influences as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.

3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for textual analysis as indicated in 1.1., 1.2. and 1.3 above.

The project is divided into **four nine-month periods** during which we will **A**) first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III, IV below), **B**) then conduct archival research (V below) and analysis of unpublished texts (VI, VII below) in order to be able to **C**) compare relevant data on Kuhn's and Fleck's theories and answer the question of what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VIII, IX, X below), and **D**) reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that attempt to explain the similarity (XI below).

I. Textual analysis of the published writings of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 – see point 1.1. for the published writings of Thomas Kuhn.

II. Textual analysis of published texts by Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 with regard to metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. with regard to published texts by Thomas Kuhn.

III. Textual analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings in terms of metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. regarding texts by Ludwik Fleck.

IV. Comparative analysis of corpora of Fleck's and Kuhn's (published) texts using generative artificial intelligence tools.

V. Archival research in

i. The Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] – collect unpublished texts to be analyzed in terms of vocabulary development and metaphors used – especially materials and unpublished notes documenting his reading (e.g. *Notes and Ideas* notebook 1949), as well as working versions of Kuhn's books and papers written before 1962: *The Copernican Revolution* (1957), *Structure* (earlier versions, but also reviews and correspondence about it), Guggenheim proposal, Lowell lectures, *The Essential Tension* (1959), *The Function of Measurement in Modern Physical Science* (1961), *The Function of Dogma in Scientific Research* (1963); check whether Kuhn made any notes on ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949; check when Kuhn first read about *Gestalt* psychology; search for early references to the "Aristotle experience"; check whether Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible; search the correspondence between Kuhn and Merton about the English translation of Fleck.

ii. James Conant Archive [part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] – check for mentions of Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn and others,

iii. **Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive** [British Library of Political and Economic Science, Library of the London School of Economics] – check for any mentions of Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently, and that they both stayed together and discussed a lot in Berkeley before publishing their texts on incommensurability),

iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] – study materials for the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,

v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] – check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*) and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi, check whether Fleck is mentioned in correspondence between Polanyi and Mark Kac who had known Fleck personally.

vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know more about the genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as the family of Wilhelm Baldamus who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).

VI. Textual analysis of unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 – see point 1.1. for unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn.

VII. Textual analysis of Thomas Kuhn's unpublished texts up to and including 1962 with regard to metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. for unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn.

VIII. Comparison of the metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.

IX. Comparison of Fleck's and Kuhn's vocabulary (with regard to the latter, taking into account the development of his vocabulary over time).

X. Comparative analysis of corpora of Fleck's and Kuhn's texts (unpublished) and comparative analysis of the *Structure* with its earlier versions using generative artificial intelligence tools.

XI. Consideration of possible explanations for the similarity of the two theories – from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of the existing literature.

In order to ensure a prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive under (V) will be preceded by a detailed enquiry with the keepers of the archive as to the nature and extent of the material to be expected.

Risk assessment

By far the greatest project risks concern archival research: Firstly, we must expect to find less and less conclusive evidence than our preliminary research suggests. In this case we will have to focus more on analyzing the published and unpublished material that is already known and available. Secondly, we may have to contend with externally induced travel disruptions that could impede field research visits. In anticipation of this eventuality, funds earmarked for travel will in this case be reallocated to pay the archives for drawing copies of documents to be sent to us by post or digitally.

4) Research methodology

The project will employ a range of methods:

1. Philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which include the collection and analysis of primary and secondary sources, the tracing of key concepts, arguments and references used, and the consideration of their context;
2. Archival research methods (item V of the work plan);
3. Linguistic text analysis (items I-III, VI-IX in the work plan), supported by the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation, etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980 and developed by others, e.g. Jäkel 2002);
4. Philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which include semantic analysis of key terms and the development of hypotheses based on the results of philological, conceptual and archival work;
5. Generative AI methods and tools – customized **solutions will be designed and created (by Jarosław Chudziak) based on foundational Language Models [using APIs to OpenAI (GPT4o) or Google (Gemini) or open-source solutions based on PHI-3 or Mistral]. Multi-agent platform paradigm will be used when appropriate (items IV, X).**

Publication plan

The project will result in at least 5 articles to be submitted to international journals (140 or 200 points according to the Polish list of journals) about:

1. The development of Kuhn's vocabulary and a comparison of Kuhn's vocabulary with Fleck's vocabulary.
2. A comparison of metaphors and the purposes of their use by Fleck and Kuhn.
3. The results of archival research.
4. The results of GenAI analysis of the similarities between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories (concepts, motifs, theses, argumentation, narration, style and examples).
5. Discussion the results of the research presented in Articles 1-4 in the context of the secondary literature and Kuhn's inspirations other than Fleck; to answer the question of what makes Fleck's and Kuhn's theories similar and to consider any hypotheses that might explain this similarity.

5) Research team

The team will be composed of **Paweł Jarnicki (PI, Ossoliński National Institute)**, **Hans-Joachim Greif** (Co-Investigator 1, Department of Philosophy and Ethics in Administration, Warsaw University of Technology) and **Jarosław Chudziak** (Co-Investigator 2, Institute of Computer Science, Warsaw University of Technology), i.e. scholars with expertise in Philosophy of Science (PI, CI1), Linguistics (PI) and Generative Artificial Intelligence (CI2). As this investigation requires triangulation between three languages, the team members have native or near-native skills in English (PI, CI1 and 2), German (CI1) and Polish (PI). The materials found and prepared in the course of the linguistic, philosophical and GenAI analysis will be consulted and critiqued by a **group of external experts**, including Fleck and Kuhn experts from Poland (Michał Kokowski, Artur Koterski, Wojciech Sady) and abroad (Nicholas Binney, Kenneth Caneva, Mauro Condé, Leandro Giri, Juan Mayoral, Nicola Mößner, Hans-Jörg Rheinberger). **These include experts who have studied Kuhn's archive** (Giri, Mayoral), supporters (Sady) or opponents (Mayoral, Caneva) of the most radical plagiarism hypothesis. All of the above researchers were informed of the nature of the project and agreed to participate in the work of the group of external experts. Each of the external experts will be invited for a six-day stay in Wrocław (in the second half of the project).

6) Project literature

Babich, B. E. (2003a). From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.

Babich, B. E. (2003b). Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).

Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, H. Korte, eds., *Human Figurations. Essays for Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156). Amsterdam.

Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In M. Erickson, C. Turner (2016). *The Sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.

- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Acumen (2014 Routledge).
- Bird, A. (2022). Thomas Kuhn, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2022 Edition), E. N. Zalta., ed.
- Brorson, S., H. Andersen (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109-129.
- Caneva, K.L. (2005). 'Discovery' as a site for the collective construction of scientific knowledge. *Historical Studies in the Physical and Biological Sciences*, 35, 2 (March), 175-291.
- Cedarbaum, D. G. (1983). Paradigms. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 14, 3, p. 173- 213.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420-423.
- Conant, J.B. (1953). *Modern Science and Modern Man*. Garden City, NY: A Doubleday Anchor Book.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé, B. G. Figueiredo, eds., *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.**
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.**
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1989, *Die Wissenschaftsphilosophie Thomas S. Kuhns: Rekonstruktion und Grundlagenprobleme*. Eng. Trans. (1993). *Reconstructing Scientific Revolutions: Thomas S. Kuhn's Philosophy of Science*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (1990). Kuhn's conception of incommensurability. *Stud. in Hist. and Phil. of Sci. Part A*, 21, 481-92.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266-276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157-168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163-173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). *Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, English and American Studies in German*, 4-6.**
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) Stimmung/Nastroj as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives. *Foundations of Science* 27, 1207-1228.**
- Jarnicki, P; Greif, H. (2022) The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure', *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*, early online (8.06.2022).
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd ed. 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn, R. K. Merton. eds., *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?*: Bloomsbury.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.**
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Peine, A. (2011). Challenging incommensurability: What we can learn from Ludwik Fleck for the analysis of configurational innovation. *Minerva*, 49(4), 489-508.
- Reisch, G.A. (2019). *The Politics of Paradigms*. Albany: SUNY Press.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Werner, S. & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*, Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.
- Wray, K. B., ed. (2021a). *Interpreting Kuhn*, Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2021b). *Kuhn's Intellectual Path*, Cambridge University Press.

OPIS SZCZEGÓŁOWY

[w języku angielskim]

1) Scientific goal of the project

Despite the numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and collectives and Thomas Kuhn's theory of scientific development, neither the nature nor the extent of Fleck's influence on Kuhn has been adequately documented or analyzed to date. This project in the history of philosophy of science aims to explore in depth the possible genealogical relationship between these two theories.

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). In his theory of thought styles and thought collectives, Fleck, like Kuhn later, resisted speculation about how science should work, while stressing the importance of how it does work. Both Fleck and Kuhn explicitly claimed that scientific knowledge is not simply additive, that it changes as a whole, and questioned the classical definition of truth and the possibility of pure observation. Fleck, like Kuhn later, observed the influence of social factors and non-verbalizable elements on the content of scientific knowledge and examined the role of the history of science in the reflection on science. For Fleck, scientists linked by a "thought style" form a "thought collective", which is not very different from Kuhn's "scientific community". Kuhn's use of the term "paradigm" often does not follow his own specific technical meaning, but the broad meaning of a "conceptual framework". This broad meaning is fairly close to Fleck's "thought style". Fleck, like Kuhn later, saw stages in the development of a thought style. At moments of breakthrough (Fleck writes of "intellectual unrest"), scientists seem to see alternately the old "Gestalt" and the new one, and after the breakthrough the world in which scientists live will have changed. Fleck also referred to the incommensurability and untranslatability of thought styles, and the dependence of the meaning of words on thought styles – all concepts that would resurface in Kuhn.

Given that Kuhn read *Entstehung* more than a decade before writing *Structure*, these similarities may not be coincidental. Given the number and degree of similarity between key concepts, it is likely that Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thinking was considerable. However, Kuhn only acknowledged Fleck's importance in a few places, and only in passing and with qualifications. Yet the nature, depth and extent of Fleck's influence on Kuhn have not been well documented or analyzed. The aim of this study is to provide a detailed account of the possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to common philosophy of science comparisons of two "ready-made" theories, the present study will build on the few more historically minded investigations of the Fleck-Kuhn relationship and provide a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence of Fleck's writings on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. It will do so by critically examining primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analyzing previously unrecognized evidence. It will use the information from these sources to explore a range of possible hypotheses about Fleck's influence on Kuhn and assess their merits.

The guiding hypothesis of this project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he and many philosophers of science after him have generally acknowledged. The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at one end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of their existence but only superficially appreciated their emergence or did not fully understand them, so that any talk of influence is exaggerated: "Fleck (1935/1979), for example, is often cited as having anticipated Kuhn, although more careful studies suggest that the similarities between their views are superficial." (Wray 2016, p. 4) At most, Fleck anticipated some of Kuhn's views in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without giving him proper credit: "The reader who is familiar with Kuhn's work will easily recognize that the majority of [Fleck's] terms is virtually identical with the basic terminology of *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*." (Baldamus 1977, p. 151) "Invented by Ludwik Fleck [the concept of 'scientific community' ...] remained ignored until Thomas Kuhn appropriated it in 1962." (Baldamus 1977, p. 135) Between these extremes are the views that Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, but that it had either an indirect and unconscious or even subconscious influence on him, which might be supported by the observation that Fleck "even illustrated the idea with some of the same examples Kuhn later adopted" (Oberheim 2012, p. 128); or that Kuhn's reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his earlier ideas, which might be supported by Baldamus's (1979) observation that key concepts present in Fleck can be found in Kuhn's writings with increasing frequency over the years.

2) Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which Kuhn is widely considered an original philosopher of science ("Thomas Samuel Kuhn (1922–1996) is one of the most influential philosophers of science of the twentieth century, perhaps the most influential. His 1962 book *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* is one of the most cited academic books of all time." Bird 2022). At the same time, it is clear to many specialists that the influence of Fleck is at least insufficiently documented.

On the one hand, statistics from the Scopus database (search according to: Article title, Abstract, Keywords, Authors) show that there are many more works about Kuhn as about Fleck published between 1979 and 2023.

Between 1979 and 2023, Scopus lists 2930 articles about or related to Kuhn, but only 195 about or related to Fleck.

On the other hand, a pilot survey among Polish academics conducted by the PI in May 2020 documents a perceived need to acknowledge Fleck's contribution (P. Jarnicki, *A Survey on the Opinion of Polish Researchers on the Relationship between the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn*). The survey was conducted on a sample of 23 Polish philosophers who consider their knowledge of Kuhn's and Fleck's theories to be at least good. According to the majority of respondents, there was an influence of Fleck on Kuhn, which Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge.¹

To remedy this situation, it is necessary both to compare the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and to trace the possible routes of conceptual transfer. Although both tasks are relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to show how and to what extent Fleck's concepts influenced Kuhn. While there have been previous attempts to demonstrate such influence, the novelty of this project lies in combining a historiographical analysis of shared influences with a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn, and the use of generative intelligence tools to analyse the similarities between the two theories.

In particular, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (e.g. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011, 2021a) – write little or nothing about Fleck or consider Fleck's influence on Kuhn superficial (Wray 2021b). For example, Alexander Bird (2000) discusses Fleck entirely separately from Kuhn as just one of many elements of the background that "encouraged the rejection of the picture of science as the accumulation of knowledge driven by a rational scientific method". In a subsection on Fleck, Kuhn's name is not even mentioned. Similarly, Marcum (2015) briefly discusses Fleck as one intellectual influence among others, such as Wittgenstein. Part of the task of the present proposal is to justify the assumption that Fleck's influence on Kuhn was more prominent and pronounced than Kuhn scholarship generally acknowledges.

On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, notably Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Braunstein (2003), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Cedarbaum (1983),

¹ To the question about the connection between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, 1 answered "don't know" and only 1 pointed that there is "no influence", 5 chose "anticipated" (which we interpret as no genealogical connection), 5 chose "forerunner" (which we interpret as weak genealogical connection), 7 chose "source of inspiration" (which we interpret as genealogical connection), 2 chose "strong influence" (which we interpret as significant genealogical connection), 2 chose "plagiarism". So, 16/23 Polish philosophers see the weaker or stronger genealogical connection. To the question if "Thomas Kuhn has acknowledged the merits of Ludwik Fleck sufficiently", 3 answered "don't know", only 5 answered "yes" and as many as 15 (i.e. 65%) answered "no".

Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Dahms (2016), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Marin (2010), Mößner (2011), Peine (2011). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to a comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently *thought style* versus *paradigm* and *thought collective* versus *scientific community*. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus's, which compares the vocabularies of Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books, little attention has been paid to how Fleck's concepts might actually have influenced Kuhn's. Therefore, research on the relationship between Kuhn's and Fleck's work needs to be deepened by asking what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved. It also needs to be broadened by analyzing the metaphors and the development of vocabulary in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials, in light of his reading of Fleck and other, partly common, sources. Tracing the underlying genealogical relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, whatever its concrete nature, will help to shed light on the conceptual similarities and differences involved.

Even when authors sympathetic to Fleck, such as Peine (2011) or Collins (2012), write about the relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, they usually do not recognize this relationship as a genealogical one. Peine's intention, for example, is to show that some of Fleck's concepts are complementary to Kuhn's theory, as if they were synchronous. By starting from a discussion of the differences between two "ready-made" theories, Peine easily convinces himself that Kuhn rejected more than he adopted from Fleck: "while Kuhn has indeed resembled some of Fleck's central ideas, he was reluctant to accept Fleck's more radical claim that science is an essentially social process". In contrast, the present study will begin by identifying the most undeniable similarities, and Fleck's theory will be compared to Kuhn's not as a "ready-made" theory, but first and foremost as a theory in *statu nascendi*.

In the late 1970s, Wilhelm Baldamus (1977, 1979), in comparing the development of Kuhn's vocabulary over time with that of Fleck, implicitly suggested that Thomas Kuhn may have plagiarized Fleck, in the sense of "appropriating" Fleck's key ideas and concepts to a greater extent than he would acknowledge. These accusations – presumably because of the popularity of Kuhn's book and his authority at the time – were never thoroughly investigated. Baldamus was more outspoken in his private correspondence with Robert Merton (Baldamus 1980). In particular, suspicions of plagiarism or other forms of illicit appropriation of Fleck's ideas by Kuhn are often raised informally, but rarely discussed in writing. The only explicit reference to a possible charge of plagiarism against Kuhn in the literature is to be found in what is actually a rather awkward denial of the charge. Babette Babich (2003b) claims that even if Kuhn had intended to refer to Fleck to a greater extent than he did, or even if he had been inclined to commit plagiarism, he would have been prevented from doing so by the partly inquisitorial nature of Cold War anti-communism in the US at the time. Any reference to such "ideologically problematic terms like 'thought collective' and 'thought style'" would have jeopardized Kuhn's reputation and academic career.

Conversely, Collins (2012) writes that Kuhn was not "as original as we all once thought", **because "Fleck did it first and, in a lot of ways did it best", while adding that Kuhn ultimately was the one "responsible for telling the history of science in a thought-collective kind of way", because he was the one who "created the social change by coming along at the right time and writing in English."** Some might conclude that even if the most extreme explanation of the similarities between Kuhn and Fleck is true, namely that Kuhn plagiarized Fleck, the fact remains that Kuhn had a huge impact on the history of philosophy of science, not Fleck, so that Fleck's philosophy is just a historical footnote. Of course, one could think this way – the one who has been successful, the one who has had a successful career, standing on the shoulders of other people's intellectual achievements, is the one who carries the day. But that is thinking in categories that would be considered outside the realm of science – cynical thinking. If there is any reasonable evidence to support the suspicion that Thomas Kuhn illicitly appropriated his most important philosophical ideas from Ludwik Fleck, then this possibility must be explicitly considered (Jarnicki, Greif 2022).

There is another article that, while not examining the Fleck-Kuhn relationship in detail, provides arguments that show the importance of the project. Caneva (2005) notes the similarities between the theories, even describing the two as "essentially indistinguishable". He notes that the quality of the introduction to Fleck's book, written by Kuhn, is curious because it contrasts with Caneva's observation (Kuhn was his supervisor) that Kuhn was "an unsurpassed master when it came to understanding texts and teasing out their meanings and implications". Caneva then analyses Kuhn's statements and finds the reasons he gives for his dislike of Fleck "hardly cogent". Caneva concludes his article with the message that once we realize **the similarity between the two theories, "It is hard to resist the speculation that [...] Kuhn distanced himself from his Polish predecessor the better to secure what he wished to be regarded as his intellectual property."** Although Caneva's article does not settle the matter conclusively, and he himself is very skeptical about the charge of plagiarism [private correspondence 2023], the paper does indeed confirm the need to study the relationship between the two theories.

Even if Fleck's and Kuhn's theories appear different to an observer today – he or she might be aware, for example, of the differences between Fleck's and Kuhn's concepts of "incommensurability" – it is important to remember that such differences were probably not nearly as obvious as they are today. In the wake of the publication of the *Structure*, a wide variety of approaches to the social and cultural studies of science developed, and we are now aware of many more nuances that were probably imperceptible to people who read the *Structure* immediately after its publication, when it not only caused a great stir but also had yet to give rise to the very social and cultural studies of science that now form the observer's vantage point. This is an argument against the claim that the similarity between Kuhn and Fleck is superficial on closer inspection. It is only now that we are able to point out all the differences. It should also be emphasized that in the case of an obvious relationship between two authors, it would be inappropriate in terms of strategy and method of investigation to discuss the differences without first considering the similarities. In order to adequately discuss the differences between Kuhn's and Fleck's theories, we must first thoroughly examine and explain the similarities between them and identify, as far as possible, which of these similarities are of a genealogical nature.

On the other hand, many influences that shaped both Fleck's and Kuhn's views are not at all obvious to the contemporary observer but were nevertheless important to them in all the nuances and details that escape us today. Accordingly, numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account, mostly on the basis of secondary literature and cooperation with the group of external experts. Influences include the French epistemologists, especially **Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem** (see Simons 2017), and James B. Conant (Kuhn's teacher and superior at Harvard, Kuhn "never discusses how Conant influenced him" (Wray 2021b, 25)), but also Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015) and Stephen Toulmin. An analysis of the relationship between Kuhn and the French epistemologists shows that there are indeed similarities (Simons 2017), but these appear to be far fewer than between Fleck and Kuhn, while the former but not the latter are documented in Kuhn's footnotes. Wray's (2016) downplaying of Fleck's influence in his demonstration of Conant's influence on Kuhn is weakened by the fact that Conant read Fleck's book in 1950 (see Trenn 1981), so there may still be a mediated influence. Wray (2021b), in analyzing Conant's influence on Kuhn, gives equal weight to Conant's 1947 and 1953 texts, whereas Kuhn and Conant read Fleck in late 1949/early 1950. None of the common themes identified by Wray (2021b) in Conant and Kuhn are absent from Fleck's book. From what Wray writes, it seems that Conant's influence on Kuhn can be detected primarily in the *Copernican Revolution*.

According to Moleski (2006), Kuhn and Polanyi met in 1958, and after the publication of Kuhn's *Structure*, Polanyi had a (not publicly stated) belief that Kuhn had been dishonest to him. Jacobs (2002), who argues for Kuhn's unacknowledged debt to Polanyi, claims that Kuhn's notion of scientific community is taken from Polanyi rather than Fleck, because Fleck's thought collective "denotes a considerably wider class of social groups". Debt to Fleck certainly does not exclude debt to Polanyi, but Kuhn read Fleck earlier than he read Polanyi. We must also consider the possibility that Kuhn, with Polanyi's help, limited Fleck's general theory of thought collectives, applicable to science, fashion, religion and other fields, to scientific communities. However, Fleck's book was in fact a study of a scientific thought collective, while many of Kuhn's concepts, such as "paradigm shift", were later readily applied to domains other than science.

Common influences on Fleck and Kuhn will also be considered, especially those from art history (Alois Riegl and **Heinrich Wölfflin**) and **gestalt psychology (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka)**. The question of whether Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is a matter for investigation. Oliveira's (2017) paper on the first – unpublished – chapter of the structure shows that, at the beginning, one of Kuhn's key ideas was to make the image of science appear closer to the image of art (as the latter develops in a non-cumulative way). In doing so, he transferred some elements of art history insights to the way we understand science. Since Fleck was informed by the concepts of style and mood (*nastrój*) in art history, it seems justified to ask whether these influences – on Kuhn and Fleck – were entirely independent (Jarnicki 2021). This question may become even more pertinent in light of the observation that Fleck remained critical of art historical notions of style that presented it as an objective characteristic of a given collective that would allow for equally objective comparison, rather than the nucleus of a proto-concept of incommensurability as it would later be articulated by Kuhn (Zittel 2011).

The influence of *Gestalt* psychologists on both authors is obvious and straightforward by comparison. It seems that both Kuhn and Fleck have similarly transferred (this is a kind of metaphor) the knowledge of psychologists to epistemology (for Fleck's reference to *Gestalt* psychology, see Zittel 2014 and Hagner 2012; the latter comparatively evaluates the importance of *Gestalt* psychology on Fleck and Michael Polanyi, who has also been

cited as an under-appreciated influence on Kuhn, see above). In 1979, Cedarbaum (1983) interviewed Kuhn and wrote: **“Also, Kuhn allows that Fleck’s discussion of, and emphasis on, *Gestalt* psychology may have awakened his own interest in the field; that contribution alone would make G.D.S.F. [Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact] enormously significant in the formation of *Structure*.”**

All the parallels and shared influences raise the question of the precise position of Fleck’s influence on Kuhn. In his three published statements from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6-7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed to have read *Entstehung* in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* **date from 1950/51, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures (“The development of Kuhn’s new image of the nature of science began with the 1951 Lowell lectures”, Marcum 2015)**, i.e., after reading Fleck. However, from 1976 Kuhn started to claim that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was constrained by a limited grasp of Fleck’s German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 merely confirmed ideas he had already conceived. This change of narrative over the years is the main evidence for Kuhn’s changing perception of Fleck’s importance for his own thought, and ultimately for Fleck’s insufficiently acknowledged influence (Jarnicki, Greif 2022).

In any case, the focus of Kuhn scholarship has long been distracted from the possible influences of Fleck (and Polanyi?) because of a peculiar Kuhnian narrative. Beginning in 1976 (in his *Foreword to Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*, the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn began to trace the origins of his argument to what he called the “Aristotle experience”. According to his own account, this foundational experience occurred in 1947, when, as a graduate student in physics, he was asked by his supervisor, James B. Conant, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. As Kuhn struggled to understand Aristotle’s *Physics*, he suddenly realized that Aristotle’s science was not false and meaningless, but simply different from the contemporary physics he himself had been taught. According to the autobiographical narrative that Kuhn would develop from 1976 onwards, this was a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were also born. Many Kuhn scholars followed this narrative for many years (Jarnicki, Greif 2022). One aim of this project is to test the credibility of Kuhn’s narrative in light of evidence for traces of his ideas about revolutions and paradigms that he may have formulated between his Aristotle experience in 1947 and his encounter with *Entstehung* in 1949, and any reading of *Gestalt* psychologists or art historians before that time.

The significance of this change for the originality of Kuhn’s thought will be explored through in-depth archival research (not only in the Kuhn archives, but also in the archives of J. Conant, P. Feyerabend, R. Merton, M. Polanyi, T. Trenn, H. Schilling, M. Kac, E. Shils, W. Baldamus) and linguistic analysis of Kuhn’s theory *in statu nascendi* in comparison with Fleck’s theory. (First steps in this direction were made in Jarnicki, Greif 2022). From Reisch (2019, 176, 221) we know that Fleck’s “book appears in Kuhn’s preliminary sketches for his [Kuhn’s] Lowell Lectures” and that the initial title of the cycle (*The Creation of Scientific Objects*) “echoes” Fleck’s *Entstehung*.

However, if it is true that Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge Fleck’s influence in one way or another, an important complementary task will be to reflect on what Kuhn may have missed in his adoption of Fleck’s thought in particular – and, consequently, what the tradition in the history and philosophy of science that he spawned may have missed as well. There are some relevant insights for contemporary philosophy of science to be gleaned here, for example from Fleck’s concept of *Stimmung/nastroj*, which is not properly translatable into English – it is usually translated as ‘mood’ and apparently not grasped by Kuhn – but which is crucial to Fleck’s approach. The project’s PI can build on previous work on this topic (Jarnicki 2016, Jarnicki 2021). Another idea of Fleck’s that Kuhn did not adopt is the active and passive elements of knowledge – an idea that allowed Fleck to take a reasonable position in the relativism debate (Binney 2023).

Only once we have answered the question of what the two theories have in common, and once we can say with certainty what Kuhn did not take from Fleck, will it be possible to appreciate Kuhn’s innovations – which appear to be primarily his concept of paradigms in the narrow sense, and the notion of a revolutionary rather than an evolutionary development of science. Only when we know what ideas Kuhn adopted from Fleck, and how, can we properly assess the nature and influence of the most famous book on the philosophy of science of the twentieth century. The results of this research may therefore be relevant beyond the disciplinary debates in the history of philosophy of science. Whatever the outcome, we will gain new insights into Fleck’s possible influence on Kuhn and a more historically grounded understanding of the history of contemporary philosophy of science and the social studies of science. The use of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) methods and tools to analyze the similarities (concepts, motifs, theses, argumentation, narration, style and examples) between two theories may yield

additional, less obvious insights that will be critically evaluated by the core team members and the group of external experts.

3) Concept and work plan

Preliminary research – previous work

In 2016, the PI published an article in *The Translator*: “On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations”. Using the example of the concept of *communication/circulation* of thoughts [*Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli*], it was shown that since both Fleck’s Polish and his German texts are original texts (i.e. one theory has been formulated in two languages), a translator of Fleck’s work or should take into account that the level of equivalence between these original texts is the level of concepts (rather than the level of lexical meaning). Similarly, when examining the relationship between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories, we will assume similarity not so much at the level of linguistic expressions, but at the level of concepts and their relations.

In addition to his work on the specifics of translating Fleck (Jarnicki 2016), the PI has published two substantial articles in the last four years (Jarnicki 2021; Jarnicki, Greif 2022). The first article shows that Fleck’s concept of *Stimmung/nastroj* belongs to the realm of musical metaphor (the term cannot be properly translated into English and is usually rendered as “mood”) **and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl)**. According to Oliveira (2017), one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn’s philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been completely independent.

In the second article, the authors analyses Kuhn’s few statements on Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his “Aristotle experience” in 1947 and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience precisely when he heard about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn played a direct role in the translation of Fleck’s book into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who persuaded Merton to have the University of Chicago Press publish Fleck’s book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, and Kuhn reluctantly agreed – and began to recount the Aristotle experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle Experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* may have effectively diverted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the basis of further linguistic and archival research.

Preliminary research – vocabulary development

A prime example of how tracing the development of Kuhn’s vocabulary can prove fruitful is the evolution of his use of the word ‘thought’. In Kuhn’s first book (1957) we find the following passages:

Such texts are a relatively frequent and extremely significant phenomenon in the *development of scientific thought*. They may be described as texts that *shift* the direction in which *scientific thought develops* [...] **As a whole the *De Revolutionibus*** stands almost entirely within an ancient astronomical and cosmological tradition; yet within its generally classical framework are to be found a few novelties which *shifted* the direction of *scientific thought* in ways unforeseen by its author and which gave rise to a rapid and complete break with the ancient tradition. (Kuhn 1957, p. 135) [emphasis – PJ]

[...] **the *De Revolutionibus*** marks a *shift* in the direction in which astronomical *thought developed*. (Kuhn 1957, p. 182) [emphasis – PJ].

Thus in 1957 Kuhn writes about the “development of thought”, whereas in his second book (1962) “thought” in this sense appears only once, apparently by chance: “conflict between competing schools of scientific thought” (Kuhn 1970, p. 96), because in 1962 he prefers to write about the development of science rather than of thought.

As we know, Ludwik Fleck wrote about the “development of thought”, “thought styles” and “thought collectives”. This is the first of the tracks to be followed: is it possible that Kuhn initially wrote about the development of thought under Fleck’s influence, only to free himself from Fleck’s vocabulary after 13 years? This makes it more likely that Kuhn, over time, narrowed Fleck’s general theory to science.

Preliminary research – metaphors with shared aims

The table below compares quotations from Fleck (1935 original and 1979 translation) and Kuhn (1962) which use similar metaphors. Both texts are about a group of people who see one thing, but over time come to see something else. In Kuhn the group has to experience a conversion (which is a religious metaphor), in Fleck the mood of the group has to change (which is a conceptual transfer from art history, and the concept of mood was one of the key concepts for temple architects). Both examples are given in the context of scientific discovery, and in both cases the passage is about a newly emerging thought style (for Fleck, a shared mood is a precondition for a shared thought style) and a newly emerging paradigm. Both paradigm and thought style determine the group's perception. The source domain from which both paradigm and thought style are conceptualized is seeing gestalten. In both cases, the gestalt metaphor is also used to emphasize that it is impossible to understand the previous thought style/paradigm in terms of the subsequent one (and vice versa). In both cases, the metaphor is used to show that the change is not induced by reasoning and logic, and that it happens independently of the intentions of the group members. In the present project, this line of enquiry is pursued in much more detail and on a large corpus of Fleck's and Kuhn's writings.

Fleck 1935 (original)	Fleck 1979 (translation)	Kuhn 1962 (original)
<p>eine Massensuggestion, die die gesamte Mannschaft eines Schiffes, auf der Suche nach einem verunglückten Boote befindlich, dieses Boot mit den Insassen wahrnehmen ließ, sogar Signalzeichen und Rufe. Erst in der letzten Minute der Annäherung platzte auf einmal die kollektive Halluzination: das Boot entpuppte sich als ein Baum mit Ästen und Blättern, von den Fluten getrieben. Dieser Fall könnte geradezu als Paradigma vieler Entdeckungen gelten: das stimmungsmäßige Gestaltsehen und der plötzliche Umschlag: andersartiges Gestaltsehen. Plötzlich versteht man überhaupt nicht, wie die frühere Gestalt möglich war und wie das ihr Widersprechende unbemerkt bleiben konnte. Genau so verhält es sich mit der wissenschaftlichen Entdeckung, nur aus der Aufregung und dem Fieber in Gleichmaß und Dauer übersetzt. Die disziplinierte, gleichmäßige und viele Generationen dauernde Stimmung eines Kollektives erzeugt das "wirkliche Bild" genau so, wie die fieberhafte eine Halluzination. In beiden Fällen verlaufen parallel Stimmungswechsel (Denkstilwechsel) und Bildwechsel. (Fleck 1935, p. 117)</p>	<p>a case of mass suggestion which induced the entire crew of a ship, while searching for a boat in distress, to see this craft and its crew and even to hear shouts and see signals. This collective hallucination was suddenly dispelled but only during the last minute of approach. The "boat" turned out to be a tree with branches and leaves drifting in the water. This case could be considered the very paradigm of many discoveries. The moodconforming gestalt-seeing and its sudden reversal: the different gestalt-seeing. Suddenly one can no longer even understand how the previous form was possible and how features contradicting it could have gone unnoticed. The same situation obtains in scientific discovery, only translated from excitement and feverish activity into equanimity and permanence. The disciplined and even-tempered mood, persisting through many generations of a collective, produces the "real image" in exactly the same way as the feverish mood produces a hallucination. In both cases switch of mood (switch of thought style) and switch of image proceed in parallel. (Fleck 1979, p. 111)</p>	<p>Practicing in different worlds, the two groups of scientists see different things when they look from the same point in the same direction. Again, that is not to say that they can see anything they please. Both are looking at the world, and what they look at has not changed. But in some areas they see different things, and they see them in different relations one to the other. That is why a law that cannot even be demonstrated to one group of scientists may occasionally seem intuitively obvious to another. Equally, it is why, before they can hope to communicate fully, one group or the other must experience the conversion that we have been calling a paradigm shift. Just because it is a transition between incommensurables, the transition between competing paradigms cannot be made a step at a time, forced by logic and neutral experience. Like the gestalt switch, it must occur all at once (though not necessarily in an instant) or not at all. (Kuhn 1970, p. 150)</p>

Work Plan

This research rests on three pillars:

1. **Textual analysis** (both using the corpus analysis toolkit and with the aid of GenAI tools) of Kuhn's (both published and unpublished) and Fleck's writings,
2. **Analysis of secondary sources**, and
3. **Archival research**.

While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analyzed on a literary and linguistic level, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into the similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources documenting any influence Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilized to interpret the nature of these similarities and differences.

In addition to direct influences, it will be necessary to identify common points of reference for Fleck and Kuhn in existing literature, for example in *Gestalt* psychology and art history. Although they lived in different places at different times and worked under different conditions, both authors seem to have been embedded in a similar intellectual milieu that deserves to be reconstructed.

Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and scattered in various archives. It is here that the most novel insights are to be expected. Therefore, archival research in various locations in Europe and the USA will be one of the pillars of the project. In analyzing the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it is important to bear in mind that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and had to 'translate' Fleck into contemporary English as he read.

More specifically, the three-fold structure of the project is as follows:

1. Textual analysis aims to answer the following questions:

- 1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the texts (published and unpublished) written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?
 - 1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?
 - 1.1.2. In pre-1962 texts, did Kuhn use phrases closer to Fleck's to describe similar phenomena?
- 1.2. Does the choice of metaphors used by both Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?
- 1.3. What are the similarities between the two theories (concepts, motifs, theses, argumentation, narration, style and examples) and what are the major differences between the two theories?

2. Analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:

- 2.1. What influences and points of reference did Fleck and Kuhn share?
- 2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts is attributed to Fleck's writings?

3. Archival research aims to provide

- 3.1. Unpublished sources documenting the nature and extent of the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn, as well as shared influences as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.
- 3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for textual analysis as indicated in 1.1., 1.2. and 1.3 above.

The project is divided into **four nine-month periods** during which we will

- A)** first carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III, and IV below),
- B)** then conduct archival research (V) and analysis of unpublished texts (VI-VII below) in order to be able to
- C)** compare relevant data on Kuhn's and Fleck's theories and answer the question of what constitutes the similarity between the two theories (VIII, IX, X below), and
- D)** reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that attempt to explain the similarity (XI below).

- I. Textual analysis of the published writings of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 – see point 1.1. for the published writings of Thomas Kuhn.
- II. Textual analysis of published texts by Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 with regard to metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. with regard to published texts by Thomas Kuhn.
- III. Textual analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings in terms of metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. regarding texts by Ludwik Fleck.
- IV. Comparative analysis of corpora of Fleck's and Kuhn's (published) texts using generative artificial intelligence tools.
- V. Archival research in
 - i. The Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] – collect unpublished texts to be analyzed in terms of vocabulary development and metaphors used – especially materials and unpublished notes documenting his reading (e.g. *Notes and Ideas* notebook 1949), as well as working versions of Kuhn's books and papers written before 1962: *The Copernican Revolution* (1957), *Structure* (earlier versions, but also reviews and correspondence about it), Guggenheim proposal, Lowell lectures, *The Essential Tension* (1959), *The Function of Measurement in Modern Physical Science* (1961), *The Function of Dogma in Scientific Research* (1963); check whether Kuhn made any notes on ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949; check when Kuhn first read about Gestalt psychology; search for early references to the "Aristotle experience"; check whether Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible; search the correspondence between Kuhn and Merton about the English translation of Fleck.
 - ii. James Conant Archive [part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] – check for mentions of Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn and others,
 - iii. **Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive** [British Library of Political and Economic Science, Library of the London School of Economics] – check for any mentions of Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently, and that they both stayed together and discussed a lot in Berkeley before publishing their texts on incommensurability),
 - iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] – study materials for the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,
 - v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] – check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*) and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi, check whether Fleck is mentioned in correspondence between Polanyi and Mark Kac who had known Fleck personally.
 - vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know more about the genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as the family of Wilhelm Baldamus who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).
- VI. Textual analysis of unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 – see point 1.1. for unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn.
- VII. Textual analysis of Thomas Kuhn's unpublished texts up to and including 1962 with regard to metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. for unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn.
- VIII. Comparison of the metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.
- IX. Comparison of Fleck's and Kuhn's vocabulary (with regard to the latter, taking into account the development of his vocabulary over time).
- X. Comparative analysis of corpora of Fleck's and Kuhn's texts (unpublished) and comparative analysis of the *Structure* with its earlier versions using generative artificial intelligence tools.
- XI. Consideration of possible explanations for the similarity of the two theories – from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of the existing literature.

In order to ensure a prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive under (V) will be preceded by a detailed enquiry with the keepers of the archive as to the nature and extent of the material to be expected.

Risk assessment

By far the greatest project risks concern archival research: Firstly, we must expect to find less and less conclusive evidence than our preliminary research suggests. In this case we will have to focus more on analyzing the published and unpublished material that is already known and available. Secondly, we may have to contend with externally induced travel disruptions that could impede field research visits. In anticipation of this eventuality, funds earmarked for travel will in this case be reallocated to pay the archives for drawing copies of documents to be sent to us by post or digitally.

4) Research methodology

The project will employ a range of methods:

1. Philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which include the collection and analysis of primary and secondary sources, the tracing of key concepts, arguments and references used, and the consideration of their context.
2. Archival research methods (item V of the work plan).
3. Linguistic text analysis (items I-III, VI-IX in the work plan), supported by the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation, etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980 and **developed by others, e.g. Jäkel 2002**). **A list of abstract concepts will be defined (target domains of metaphorical projection)**, with the aim of defining them as abstractly as possible. A corpus of texts for analysis will be constructed. A preliminary analysis of the corpus will be carried out – searching for the concept itself and for the abstract definition. The result will be a list of ways of talking about abstract concepts and a list of metaphors (source domains of metaphorical projection). In the next step, a proper analysis of the corpus will be carried out, looking for other expressions derived from the source domains identified in the previous step. Of particular importance here are suspected synonyms and etymologies of certain expressions. Special attention will be paid to expressions in quotation marks or accompanied by the phrases “as”, “as if”, “so to speak”, etc. The result is a list of target domains with abstract definitions and source domains and their corresponding expressions. An analysis of the purpose of the use of a given metaphor and of what the metaphor enables the author to say – both in what it “highlights” and in what it “hides” in Lakoff and Johnson’s terms – will allow a comparison of its use by the two authors.
4. philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which will be conceptual in nature: First, philosophical analysis will explore the meanings – as sense and reference – of key terms in Fleck, Kuhn, and other relevant authors, the presumed logical relationships between these terms, and their place in a larger argumentative framework. Secondly, this work will itself be argumentative, in the sense of developing hypotheses based on the results of philological, conceptual and archival work.
5. generative AI methods and tools – customized **solutions will be designed and created (by Jarosław Chudziak)** based on foundational Language Models [using APIs to OpenAI (GPT4o) or Google (Gemini) or open-source solutions based on PHI-3 or Mistral]. Multi-agent platform paradigm will be used when appropriate (items IV, X).

Publication plan

The project will result in at least 5 articles to be submitted to international journals (140 or 200 points according to the Polish list of journals) about:

1. The development of Kuhn’s vocabulary and a comparison of Kuhn’s vocabulary with Fleck’s vocabulary.
2. A comparison of metaphors and the purposes of their use by Fleck and Kuhn.
3. The results of archival research carried out to evaluate the explanatory hypotheses concerning similarities between Kuhn and Fleck.
4. The results of GenAI analysis of the similarities between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories (concepts, motifs, theses, argumentation, narration, style and examples).
5. Discussion the results of the research presented in Articles 1-4 in the context of the secondary literature and Kuhn’s inspirations other than Fleck; to answer the question of what makes Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories similar and to consider any hypotheses that might explain this similarity.

5) Research team

The team will be composed of **Paweł Jarnicki** (PI, Ossoliński National Institute), **Hans-Joachim Greif** (Co-Investigator 1, Department of Philosophy and Ethics in Administration, Warsaw University of Technology) and **Jarosław Chudziak** (Co-Investigator 2, Institute of Computer Science, Warsaw University of Technology), i.e. scholars with expertise in Philosophy of Science (PI, C11), Linguistics (PI) and Generative Artificial Intelligence (C12). As this investigation requires triangulation between three languages, the team members have native or near-native skills in English (PI, C11 and 2), German (C11) and Polish (PI).

Hans-Joachim Greif is a philosopher working in the field of history, philosophy, and social studies of science and technology. He is well versed in Fleck's work and has the linguistic and philosophical background necessary to analyse Fleck's German-language writings and compare them with their English translations. He has one pertinent publication with the PI (Jarnicki, Greif 20022) and also commands some basic knowledge of AI and computational methods.

Jarosław Chudziak holds a PhD in technical sciences and teaches at Warsaw University of Technology and Kozminski University. He specializes in artificial intelligence, data analytics and intelligent information systems. In his career, he has implemented technology transformation projects at international consulting firms (PwC, KPMG, and Accenture). His research and lectures focus on AI, decision models, ML techniques, and the use of advanced algorithms in business.

The materials found and prepared in the course of the linguistic, philosophical and GenAI analysis will be consulted and critiqued by a **group of external experts**, including Fleck and Kuhn experts from Poland (Michał Kokowski, Artur Koterski, Wojciech Sady) and abroad (Nicholas Binney, Kenneth Caneva, **Mauro Condé**, **Leandro Giri**, **Juan Mayoral**, **Nicola Mößner**, **Hans-Jörg Rheinberger**). **These include experts who have studied Kuhn's archive** (Giri, Mayoral), supporters (Sady) or opponents (Mayoral, Caneva) of the most radical plagiarism hypothesis. All of the above researchers were informed of the nature of the project and agreed to participate in the work of the group of external experts.

Each of the external experts will be invited for a **six-day stay in Wrocław** (in the second half of the project), during which the team members will present the results of their previous inquiries to the experts (items I-VII and X in the work plan). The external experts will assist in the realization of items VIII-IX and XI.

- **Nicholas Binney (from September 2025 at Institut für Geschichte, Theorie und Ethik der Medizin, Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf, Germany, as Marie Curie-Skłodowska Fellow)** – young researcher interested in application of Fleck's theory (considers it more useful than Kuhn's)
- **Kenneth Caneva** (emeritus, University of North Carolina at Greensboro, USA) – expert in Kuhn and Fleck, compared their theories, knew Kuhn personally (Kuhn was his supervisor)
- **Mauro Condé (Departamento de História da Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Brasil)** – expert in Kuhn, Fleck and Wittgenstein
- **Leandro Giri (Departamento de Ciencias Sociales, Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero, Argentina)** – expert in Kuhn, cooperated with Pablo Melogno who unexpectedly died. Giri continues Melogno's project based on research in **Kuhn's archives ("The unpublished writings of Thomas Kuhn: 1980–1994")**
- **Michał Kokowski (Instytut Historii Nauki Polskiej Akademii Nauk, Poland)** – expert in Kuhn, author of the book *Thomas S. Kuhn and the issue of the Copernican revolution* published in Polish
- **Artur Koterski (Wydział Filozofii i Socjologii, Uniwersytet Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej, Poland)** – expert in Kuhn and Fleck
- **Juan Mayoral (Unidad Predepartamental de Filosofía, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain)** – expert in Kuhn, conducted research in Kuhn archives
- **Nicola Mößner (Institut für Philosophie, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover, Germany)** – expert in Fleck and Kuhn, compared Fleck's and Kuhn's theory
- **Hans-Jörg Rheinberger (Max-Planck-Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte, Germany)** – expert in Fleck and Kuhn and leading figure in history of science
- **Wojciech Sady (Instytut Filozofii, Uniwersytet Śląski, Poland)** – expert in Kuhn and Fleck, proponent of plagiarism hypothesis

6) Project literature

- Babich, B. E. (2003a). From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.
- Babich, B. E. (2003b). Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).
- Baldamus, W. (1976) *The structure of sociological inference*. Barnes & Noble Books.
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, H. Korte, eds., *Human Figurations. Essays for Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In M. Erickson, C. Turner (2016). *The Sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Baldamus, W. (1980). Letter to R. Merton, February 6, 1980. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5.
- Binney, N. (2023). Ludwik Fleck's reasonable relativism about science. *Synthese* 201, 40.
- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Acumen (2014 Routledge).
- Bird, A. (2022). Thomas Kuhn, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2022 Edition), E. N. Zalta., ed.
- Braunstein, J.-F. (2003). Thomas Kuhn lecteur de Ludwik Fleck. *Archives de Philosophie*, 66, 403–422.
- Brorson, S., H. Andersen (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109-129.
- Caneva, K.L. (2005). 'Discovery' as a site for the collective construction of scientific knowledge. *Historical Studies in the Physical and Biological Sciences*, 35, 2 (March), 175-291.
- Cedarbaum, D. G. (1983). Paradigms. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 14, 3, p. 173- 213.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420-423.
- Conant, J. B. (1947). *On Understanding Science: An Historical Approach*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Conant, J.B. (1953). *Modern Science and Modern Man*. Garden City, NY: A Doubleday Anchor Book.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). **Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência**. In M. L. L. Condé, B. G. Figueiredo, eds., *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). **Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência**. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.
- Dahms, H.-J. (2016). Thomas Kuhn's **Structure: An "Exemplary Document of the Cold War Era"**? In E. Aronova & S. Turchetti (Eds.), *Science Studies during the Cold War and Beyond: Paradigms Defected* (pp. 103–125). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.
- Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006), Z. Cackowski, S. Symotiuik, eds. *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego*. Lublin: Wydawnictwo UMCS.
- Galison, P. (2016). Practice All the Way Down, in R. J. Richards, L. Daston, eds., *Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions at Fifty: Reflections on a Scientific Classic*, pp. 42–69. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Giri L., P. Melogno, H. Miguel, ed. (2023). *Perspectives on Kuhn. Contemporary Approaches to the Philosophy of Thomas Kuhn*, Springer.

- Hagner, M. (2012). Perception, knowledge and freedom in the age of extremes: on the historical epistemology of Ludwik Fleck and Michael Polanyi. *Studies in Eastern European Thought*, 64, 107–120.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1989, *Die Wissenschaftsphilosophie Thomas S. Kuhns: Rekonstruktion und Grundlagenprobleme*. Eng. Trans. (1993). *Reconstructing Scientific Revolutions: Thomas S. Kuhn's Philosophy of Science*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (1990). Kuhn's conception of incommensurability. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 21, 481-92.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (1995). Two Letters of Paul Feyerabend to Thomas S. Kuhn on a Draft of The Structure of Scientific Revolutions, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science* 26 (September), 353-387.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (2006), More letters by Paul Feyerabend to Thomas S. Kuhn on Proto-Structure, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A* 37, Issue 4, 610-632.
- Hufbauer, K. (2012). From Student of Physics to Historian of Science: T. S. Kuhn's Education and Early Career, 1940–1958. *Physics in Perspective* 14, 421–470.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266-276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157-168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163-173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jäkel, O. (2002).** *Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, English and American Studies in German*, 4-6.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) Stimmung/Nastrój as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives.** *Foundations of Science* 27, 1207-1228.
- Jarnicki, P; Greif, H. (2022) The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure', *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*, early online (8.06.2022).
- Kokowski, M. (2001), *Thomas S. Kuhn (1922–1996) a zagadnienie rewolucji kopernikowskiej*, Warszawa.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd ed. 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The Essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn, R. K. Merton. eds., *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii–xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (2021), George Reisch, ed. *The Quest for Physical Theory*. MIT.
- Lakoff, G., Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?* London/New York: Bloomsbury.

- Marin, M. P. (2010). Ludwik Fleck: precursor del pensamiento de Thomas Kuhn. *Eidos: Revista de Filosofía de la Universidad del Norte* (13), 130–149.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Melogno, P., A. Courtoisie (2019). Stepping into the 60s: Thomas Kuhn's Intellectual Turn towards the Philosophy of Science. *Daimon* 76, 23–33.
- Melogno P. (2022). From Externalism to Internalism: The Historiographical Development of Thomas Kuhn, *Foundations of Science*, 27, 371–385.
- Melogno, P., L. Giri (2023). Towards a Genealogy of Thomas Kuhn's Semantics, *Perspectives on Science*, 31 (4): 385–404.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oberheim, E. (2012). *Feyerabend's Philosophy*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Peine, A. (2011). Challenging incommensurability: What we can learn from Ludwik Fleck for the analysis of configurational innovation. *Minerva*, 49(4), 489-508.
- Reisch, G. A. (2016). Aristotle in the Cold War: On the Origins of Thomas Kuhn's The Structure of Scientific Revolutions. In R. J. Richards & L. Daston (Eds.), *Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions at Fifty: Reflections on a science classic*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.
- Reisch, G.A. (2019). *The Politics of Paradigms*. Albany: SUNY Press.
- Sigurdsson, S. (2016). The nature of scientific knowledge: an interview with Thomas S. Kuhn. In *Shifting paradigms: Thomas S. Kuhn and the history of science* (pp. 17–30): Edition Open Access.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Trenn, T. J. (1981). Paper prepared for the Hamburg Colloquium on Ludwik Fleck held September 13th-16th, 1981: Some Reflections on the Chicago Edition of Fleck's Monograph. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5.
- Werner, S. & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.
- Wray, K. B., ed. (2021a). *Interpreting Kuhn*, Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2021b). *Kuhn's Intellectual Path*, Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B., ed. (2024). *Kuhn's The Structure of Scientific Revolutions at 60*. Cambridge University Press.
- Zittel, C. (2011). Ludwik Fleck und der Stilbegriff in den Naturwissenschaften. Stil als wissenschaftshistorische, **epistemologische und ästhetische Kategorie**. In H. Bredekamp & J. Krois (Eds.), *Sehen und Handeln*. Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, pp. 171–206.
- Zittel, C. (2014). Ludwik Flecks Gestaltbegriff und sein Blick auf die Gestaltpsychologie seiner Zeit. *NTM Zeitschrift für Geschichte der Wissenschaften, Technik und Medizin*, 22(1), 9–29.

PLAN BADAŃ [w języku polskim i angielskim]

Lp.	Nazwa zadania	Podmioty
1	Analiza tekstów opublikowanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do roku 1962 włącznie - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
2	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Ludwika Flecka do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć z jego teorii i pojęć z teorii zastanych	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories	
3	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów opublikowanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do 1962 roku)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962)	
4	Analiza porównawcza korpusów tekstów Flecka i Kuhna (opublikowanych) metodami, narzędziami i platformami GenAI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Comparative analysis of Fleck's and Kuhn's (published) text corpora with methods, tools and platforms of GenAI	
5	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Thomasa Kuhna [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	

6	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Jamesa Conanta [Harvard University Archives Repository]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in James Conant Archive [Harvard University Archives Repository]	
7	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Paula Feyerabenda [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	
8	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Roberta Mertona [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	
9	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Michaela Polanyi'ego [University of Chicago Library]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library]	
10	Badania w innych archiwach i wywiady z osobami, które mogą posiadać wiedzę mogącą rzucić światło na genealogiczny związek między teoriami Flecka i Kuhna, jak na przykład rodzina Wilhelma Baldamusa, która przechowuje jego korespondencję, poszukiwanie materiałów Thaddeusa Trenna i Harolda K. Schillinga z Pennsylvania State University, Marka Kaca i Edwarda Shilsa.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Research in other archives and interviews with individuals whose knowledge could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, search for materials of Thaddeus Trenn and Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University, Mark Kac and Edward Shils.	

11	Analiza tekstów Thomasa Kuhna, które napisał w 1962 roku i wcześniej, a które nie zostały opublikowane przed 1963 rokiem - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Analysis of Thomas Kuhn's texts that he wrote in 1962 and earlier, which were not published before 1963 - development of vocabulary	
12	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów Kuhna, które napisał w 1962 roku i wcześniej, a które nie zostały opublikowane przed 1963 rokiem)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of texts that Kuhn wrote in 1962 and earlier, which were not published before 1963)	
13	Porównanie metafor stosowanych przez Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	
14	Porównanie słownictwa Flecka i Kuhna (w odniesieniu do tego ostatniego, w ujęciu diachronicznym)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Comparison of vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, in diachronic terms)	
15	Analiza porównawcza korpusów tekstów Flecka i Kuhna (nieopublikowanych) metodami, narzędziami i platformami GenAI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Comparative analysis of Fleck and Kuhn (unpublished) text corpora with methods, tools and platforms of GenAI	
16	Rozważenie możliwych wyjaśnień podobieństwa teorii Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	

WSPÓŁPRACA MIĘDZYNARODOWA

Czy projekt realizowany we współpracy międzynarodowej?		TAK
Rodzaj współpracy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Współpraca międzynarodowa z partnerami z zagranicznych instytucji naukowych, którzy nie ubiegają się o środki finansowe na ten cel w ramach ogłaszanych przez instytucje partnerskie programów, organizowanych we współpracy z NCN w oparciu o procedurę agencji wiodącej 	
Kraje	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Argentyna • Brazylia • Hiszpania • Niemcy • Stany Zjednoczone Ameryki 	

Podmioty - Argentyna

Lp.	Podmiot
1	Departamento de Ciencias Sociales, Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero (National University of Tres de Febrero)

Podmioty - Brazylia

Lp.	Podmiot
1	Departamento de História da Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (University of Minas Gerais)

Podmioty - Hiszpania

Lp.	Podmiot
1	Unidad Predepartamental de Filosofía, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Zaragoza (University of Zaragoza)

Podmioty - Niemcy

Lp.	Podmiot
1	Max-Planck-Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte (Max Planck Institute for the History of Science)
2	Institut für Philosophie, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover (Leibniz University Hannover)
3	Institut für Geschichte, Theorie und Ethik der Medizin, Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf (Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf)

Podmioty - Stany Zjednoczone Ameryki

Lp.	Podmiot
1	University of North Carolina at Greensboro

Opis korzyści wynikających ze współpracy międzynarodowej [w języku angielskim]

A group of international experts will be established in order to match the multilingual Polish-German-English and multi-sited nature of the research. It will also help to gather the broadest possible expertise on the relationship between Fleck and Kuhn.

In particular, the international expert group's tasks will be:

A. to critically evaluate the results of research tasks 1-12 (see Research plan), i.e., a) the results of linguistic inquiries into vocabulary and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn and b) archival research;

B. to discuss the conclusions of Tasks 13-16, i.e., comparison of vocabulary and metaphors between Fleck and Kuhn, results of GenAI analysis, and especially the arguments for and against various hypotheses explaining the similarity between Fleck's and Kuhn's conceptions.

Among the members of the group will be experts both from Poland (Michał Kokowski, Artur Koterski, Wojciech Sady) and from abroad (Nicholas Binney, Kenneth Caneva, Mauro Condé, Leandro Giri, Juan Mayoral, Nicola Mößner, Hans-Jörg Rheinberger). Two of the researchers (Giri, Mayoral) have already conducted research in Kuhn's archives. Consulting with them will help improve searches in the archive there.

A group of external experts is particularly important when it comes to formulating arguments for and against the most radical and controversial hypothesis of plagiarism. Inviting both a proponent (Sady) and opponents (Caneva, Mayoral) of this hypothesis along with defenders of "softer" hypotheses to the group of experts will ensure consideration of all explanatory perspectives and make the results of the project more balanced. We plan to cooperate remotely from the beginning of the project and have one six-day meeting with each expert in Wrocław in the second half of the project.

All of the above-mentioned researchers are informed of the content of the project and expressed their willingness to participate in the work of the group of external experts.

ANKIETY CZŁONKÓW ZESPOŁU [w języku angielskim]

KIEROWNIK (PI)

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

PRZEBIEG KARIERY NAUKOWEJ**Information on education, academic degrees/titles and employment**

- From 08.2018 to 02.2022 - **assistant professor** (half-time) at Warsaw University of Technology; Faculty of Administration and Social Sciences.
- From 05.2015 - a member of the Academy of Young Scholars and Artists (Wrocław).
- From 05.2013 to 04.2016 - **associated researcher** of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (ETHZ) and University of Zurich. From 04.2013 to 09.2016 - principal investigator of the project (see projects).
- From 2012 - a **member of the Board** of Project Science Foundation, from 12.2016 to 12.2019 Chairman of the Board.
- 15 May 2012 - **Ph.D. in humanities**. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty.
- 2009-2011 - **investigator** within the doctoral project (University of Wrocław) funded by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (State Committee for Scientific Research in Poland [Komitet Badań Naukowych] N N101 060336).
- 15 July 2005 - **Master of Arts**. The University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty, Institute of Polish Philology.

It should be noted that although PI's academic career has lasted for over a dozen years (he began his doctoral studies in 2005), the period of his **full-time employment lasted for 5 years and two and a half months** (from April 2013 to September 2016 - full time, from October 2018 to February 2022 - half time). During his doctoral studies, PI did not receive any scholarship that would allow him not to take up other works. He is a father of three children (born in 2011, 2015, and 2019).

Research stays at home and abroad

- From May 2013 to April 2016 - **associated researcher** of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich), [regular short stays within the realization of grant number 2012/06/M/HS2/00313].
- 07-09.2009 query in British Library (London), [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].
- 11-12.2009 query in Ludwik Fleck Archive in Zurich and Library of the University of Zurich [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].

Lectures and presentations (from 2014)

- 18.09.2023, Gdańsk, Council of the Baltic Sea States Summer University 2023 - Strategic Narratives of Baltiness - Foundations and Identity, **invited talk**: "Do we know what we see or do we see what we know? Seminar on epistemic conditioning of sensual perception";
- 7-9.07.2021, Kent (online), **international conference**: The British Society for the Philosophy of Science 2021 Annual Conference, paper [with Hajo Greif]: "The Aristotle Experience and the Genesis of the Kuhnian Revolution".
- 23-26.06.2020, Singapore, **international conference** HOPOS 2020 (The Thirteenth Biennial Congress of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science), paper: "The role of (conceptual) metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings" selected for presentation but the event was canceled.
- 11-14.04.2019, Lviv, **international conference**: "Ludwik Fleck and His Thought Collectives" (Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Center for Urban History of East Central Europe, Ukrainian Catholic University), paper: "What is 'mood'? About translating of 'Stimmung/nastrój' into English".
- 28-30.10.2015, Marburg, **international conference**: "Entangled science? Relocating GermanPolish scientific relations" (the Leibniz Association and the Polish Academy of Sciences), poster: "Ludwik Fleck's "Polish-German" theory of thought styles and thought collectives, and problems arising from its translation";
- 3-8.08.2015, Helsinki, **international conference**: 15th Congress on Logic, Methodology, and Philosophy of Science 2015 (University of Helsinki), paper: "The reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives in English";
- 27-29.11.2014, Berlin, **international conference**: "Self-Translation as Transfer of Knowledge" (Zentrum für Literatur- und Kulturforschung), paper: "Ludwik Fleck's Legacy – an Example of Self-Translation?";
- 17-19.09.2014, Toruń, **international conference**: "Situating Solidarities" (European Association for the Study of Science and Technology and Nicolaus Copernicus University), paper: "'Gestalts' of Ludwik Fleck".

Prizes and awards

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Other significant achievements

Organization:

- 03.2016 - **international conference** in Wrocław (together with Martina Schluender, Rainer Egloff, Ohad Parnes, Sandra Lang): "Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives – translations and receptions".
- 03.2014 - **international conference** in Wrocław: "Ludwik Fleck – traditions, inspirations, interpretations".
- 01.2014 - **international workshop** in Zurich (together with Martina Schluender, Rainer Egloff and Johannes Fehr): "Translation of Science – Science of Translation".
- 10.2009 - First Polish Constructivist Symposium in Wrocław (together with Bogdan Balicki).
- 2008-2012 foundation of "Science of Science" circle in Wrocław - 34 meetings took place.

Other key information impacting the evaluation of the academic and research career

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PUBLIKACJE NAUKOWE

1. Mauro L. Conde, Paweł Jarnicki, *Ludwik Fleck: Thought Style and Thought Collective in the Historiography of Science* (2023), rozdział, In: Condé, M.L., Salomon, M. (eds) Handbook for the Historiography of Science. Historiographies of Science. Springer, Cham.
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0
Otwarty dostęp: nie, DOI 10.1007/978-3-030-99498-3_5-2
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
2. Paweł Jarnicki, Hajo Greif, *The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure'* (2022), artykuł, Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie, vol. 106, no. 2, 2024, pp. 313-349 (early online 8.06.2022)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 2
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI 10.1515/agph-2020-0160
Status publikacji: opublikowane
3. Paweł Jarnicki, *Stimmung/Nastrój as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives* (2021), artykuł, Foundations of Science, 27, pages 1207–1228, (2022, online: 05 April 2021)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 4
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI 10.1007/s10699-021-09792-33
Status publikacji: opublikowane
4. Paweł Jarnicki, *On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translation* (2016), artykuł, Translator, 22:3, 271-286
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 17
Otwarty dostęp: nie, DOI 10.1080/13556509.2015.1126881
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
5. Maria Ciesielska, Paweł Jarnicki, *Ludwik Fleck - mikrobiolog i filozof [Ludwik Fleck - microbiologist and philosopher]* (2021), książka, Oficyna Wydawnicza Politechniki Warszawskiej; ISBN 978-83-8156-251-5 (druk) ISBN 978-83-8156-252-2 (online)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
6. Paweł Jarnicki, *Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of "legitimation" [Polish extended version appeared as: O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka In: Stan Rzeczy 10, p. 355-373]* (2015), artykuł, Divinatio: Studia Culturologica Series, vol. 41, autumn-winter, p. 167-184
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane

7. Paweł Jarnicki, *The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989)* (2016), artykuł, *Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science*, 1 (2016 - special issue on Ludwik Fleck), p.21-30
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI 10.24117/2526-2270.2016.i1.05
Status publikacji: opublikowane
8. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metaforyczne konceptualizacje pojęcia 'tekstu' a przemiany stylów myślowych w literaturoznawstwie [Metaphorical conceptualizations of the concept of 'text' and changes of thought styles in history and theory of literature]* (2014), książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo 'Projekt Nauka'
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 5
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane
9. Paweł Jarnicki, Bożena Płonka-Syroka, Bogdan Balicki, *Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje [Ludwik Fleck - traditions - inspirations - interpretations] (in the volume: Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie [Two bibliographies of the reception of Ludwik Fleck and materials available on the Internet], p. 235–37; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim [Bibliography of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory in Polish], p. 239–55; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim [Bibliography of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory in English], p. 257–94; Posłowie [Afterword], p. 295–96)* (2015), książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 7
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane
10. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metafory dyskursu intertekstualności, metaforyka tekstylna [Metaphors of intertextuality. Textile metaphors]* (2015), artykuł, *Kształcenie Językowe*, 13 (23): p. 49–72
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane

DOKONANIA ARTYSTYCZNE

b.d.

BADANIA NAUKOWE FINANSOWANE PRZEZ NCN

DANE POBRANE AUTOMATYCZNIE

Tytuł: **Filologiczna analiza filozoficznych dzieł Ludwika Flecka oraz ich tłumaczeń w językach: polskim, niemieckim i angielskim**

Nr rejestracyjny:
2012/06/M/HS2/00313

Źródło(a) finansowania: NCN, Nazwa konkursu: HARMONIA-3

Kwota: **405 512 PLN**

Podmiot realizujący:
Projekt Nauka. Fundacja na rzecz promocji nauki polskiej

Data rozpoczęcia realizacji: **2013-03-25**, Data zakończenia realizacji: **2016-08-24**

Wynik oceny:
Uznanie umowy za wykonaną

Lista najważniejszych publikacji będących rezultatem projektu:
Publikacje w czasopiśmie:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Sandra Lang ("Introduction"); Paweł Jarnicki ("The beginnings..."), Introduction; The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989), *Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science*, 1, 3-5; 21-30, Graduate Program in History (Science and Culture in History) of Federal University of Minas Gerais (Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais), Brasil, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, On the Shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the Bilingual Philosophical Legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English Translations, *The Translator*, 22 (3), 271–286, Routledge, 2016, IF: 0.483, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka, *Stan Rzeczy*, 10, 355-373, Instytut Socjologii UW, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of “legitimation”, *Divinatio*, 41 (Aut.-Win.), 167-184, University of Sofia, Department of Cultural Studies, 2015, IF: 0, - Opublikowane

Publikacje książkowe/ rozdziały w publikacjach książkowych:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim; Poślowie, Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje, (nie dotyczy), 235-296, Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich we Wrocławiu, 2015, Wrocław, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2705.3208>, - Opublikowane

b.d.

INNE PROJEKTY BADAWCZE

b.d.

NAJWAŻNIEJSZE OSIĄGNIĘCIE NAUKOWE

The most important achievement is the clarification of the status of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives. Its specific situation generates specific problems for translators, who unfortunately had not recognized this specific status of Fleck's theory, so all the existing translations have to be deeply revised. Fleck's philosophical/sociological theory was expressed in two languages (Polish and German) more or less simultaneously by a bilingual author, who did not self-translate his texts into the second language but published original texts in both of these languages. It means that both Polish and German texts are of equal value, and if we want to speak of the level of equivalence, I argue we can find it at the level of concepts - it means that expressions that differ in lexical meaning may denote the very same concept. The problem is described - with an example of "circulation of thoughts" [Denkverkehr/krążenie myśli] expression - in the paper "On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations" published in *The Translator*.

OPUS 27 (submitted 06.2024) – rejected at the first stage – 76,50%

A. PROJECT ASSESSMENT (65%) – **4,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5)

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (35%) – **3,50** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

GENERAL JUSTIFICATION

Panel of experts agreed that the project addresses an important issue within Kuhn scholarship. Nevertheless, the panel of experts raised specific aspects related to how the author have chosen concepts and relationships to achieve the study goals; the contribution of LLMs, the proposed methodology and potential risks were not sufficiently described. Another weakness was not sufficiently clear description of the wider impact of the project. Another concern of the panel of experts was that although PI's scientific track record and research achievements are good, they are of limited international recognition in terms of quality and contribution to science. The PI has good experience researching issues similar to the ones proposed in the project but, the most important of these studies are not published internationally.

INDIVIDUAL REVIEWS

A. PROJECT ASSESSMENT (65%)

Expert 1

The basic idea of the project is excellent. The project aims to systematically investigate the intellectual relationship between Thomas Kuhn and Ludwig Fleck, a lesser known figure who predates Kuhn and had very similar idea with which Kuhn may have been familiar. This seems to fill a very evident gap in contemporary research in the history of philosophy, and given the extent of Kuhn's influence on the philosophy of science it could have broad reaching impact. The proposed combination of archival research, linguistic analysis, and the innovative use of generative AI tools is interesting, but there is a surprising lack of concern about the risks of the latter. A particular concern is that it may be difficult or even impossible to discern the rationale for the outputs of any such model, and this lack of transparency could hinder the project's ability to provide clear and convincing evidence for its claims. The project is overall well-organised and otherwise feasible.

Expert 2

In terms of scientific quality the project proposes ambitious aim of definitely resolving the issue of Kuhn's reliance on Fleck's publications. However, it seems that out of three proposed approaches (textual analysis, secondary sources and archival research) only the latter may bring out new evidence. The archival research is well and comprehensively planned. It is not sufficiently clear how LLM-based approach will contribute to the aim of the project.

The project in general seems feasible, given the team competencies. However, there is a concern with the planned computational analysis of the yet non-existent corpora.

Given the vast amount of publications on Kuhn and Fleck it seems that if successful the project may lead to new results of interest to historians involved in them, but it is rather unlikely that it will have a major impact beyond them.

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (35%)

Expert 1

The PI has a range of relevant expertise and a good-track record relative to career stage and opportunity (they have not been in full-time academic employment for much of the time since their PhD) with some experience of international publication and plenty of experience in international dissemination

Expert 2

PI has extensive expertise on the topic which is documented in his international (and national) publications and presentations. He also developed a network of national and international collaborators interested in the topic which will be relied upon in the project.

NARODOWE CENTRUM NAUKI

OPUS-29

Wniosek o finansowanie projektu badawczego

Na ramionach niewidocznego olbrzyma? Odkrywanie wpływu Ludwika Flecka na Thomasa Kuhna

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich

OPIS SKRÓCONY

[w języku angielskim]

On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant?

Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

Scientific goal of the project

Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn developed similar theories about how scientific ideas evolve. Since Kuhn read Fleck's work years before writing his own, the similarities between their theories may not be a coincidence. This project aims to examine how much Fleck actually influenced Kuhn by looking at original sources and evidence, going beyond the usual comparisons. A variety of ideas about Fleck's impact will be explored, ranging from the suggestion that Kuhn was barely familiar with Fleck's work to the claim that he borrowed heavily without giving proper credit.

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935; hereafter referred to as *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962; hereafter referred to as *Structure*). Since Kuhn read *Entstehung* more than a decade before writing *Structure*, it is clear that these similarities are not purely coincidental. The number and degree of similarity between key concepts suggests that Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thinking was significant. However, Kuhn only acknowledged Fleck's importance in a few places, briefly and with qualifications. Nevertheless, the nature, depth and scope of Fleck's influence on Kuhn remain poorly documented and analysed to date.

This study of the history of the philosophy of science aims to provide an in-depth account of the genealogical relationship between the works of Fleck and Kuhn, based on the best available evidence. Unlike the commonplace comparison of two 'ready-made' theories in philosophy of science, this study builds on a few more historically minded inquiries into the Fleck–Kuhn relation to provide a more comprehensive, coherent and systematic account of the influence of Fleck's writings on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory. This will be achieved by critically considering primary and secondary sources, and by gathering and analysing hitherto unacknowledged evidence. The information gathered from these sources will be used to explore a **range of hypotheses concerning Fleck's influence on Kuhn, and their merits will be assessed.** The project's guiding hypothesis is that Fleck's work was more significant to Kuhn than Kuhn and subsequent philosophers of science generally acknowledged.

The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes the statement, at its sceptical end, that the two theories were largely formulated independently. This is based on the idea that Kuhn was only superficially familiar with the *Entstehung*, or did not fully understand it. Therefore, any talk of influence is exaggerated (Wray 2016, 4). At most, Fleck anticipated some of Kuhn's views in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum are suggestions of plagiarism, whereby Kuhn allegedly took central ideas from Fleck without properly acknowledging him (Baldamus 1977, pp. 135, 151). Between these extremes are views that Kuhn read and understood Fleck's book, either influencing him unconsciously or helping him to develop and substantiate his previous ideas.

Significance of the project

Thomas Kuhn is often viewed as an original thinker in the philosophy of science, but some experts believe that Ludwik Fleck's influence on him is not fully recognized. This project will compare the words, metaphors, and ideas used by Fleck and Kuhn, using historical and linguistic analysis to figure out how Fleck's concepts might have shaped Kuhn's work. By looking at their shared influences and how Kuhn's ideas developed over time, the project aims to provide a clearer picture of Fleck's impact on Kuhn and the history of science. This interdisciplinary project will appeal not only to historians of the philosophy of science, but also to anyone interested in research ethics.

Today, Kuhn is widely regarded as an original philosopher of science. At the same time, many specialists agree that the influence of Fleck is insufficiently documented. In order to address this, it is necessary to compare the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck, and to trace the possible routes of conceptual transfer. While both tasks are relevant and will be considered in this project, the project's main contribution will be to demonstrate the extent to which Fleck's concepts influenced Kuhn. While previous attempts have sought to demonstrate such an influence, this project is novel in combining a historiographical analysis of

shared influences with a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in the work of both authors, in order to analyse the similarities between their theories.

Notably, many prominent Kuhn scholars, including Hoyningen-Huene (1989; 1990), Bird (2000), Marcum (2015), and Wray (2011; 2021a), have written little or nothing about Fleck, or have dismissed his influence on Kuhn as superficial (Wray, 2021b). Conversely, numerous studies compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, including those by Baldamus (1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Brorson and Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a) and Mößner (2011), Peine (2011) and Winneke (1993). However, most of these studies do not complement each other, remaining limited to an ahistorical comparative analysis of concepts, most notably *thought style* versus *paradigm*, and *thought collective* versus *scientific community*. With a few exceptions, these studies pay little attention to how Fleck's concepts may have influenced Kuhn's thinking. Baldamus compares the vocabulary used in Fleck's 1935 book and Kuhn's 1962 book, and implicitly accuses Kuhn of plagiarism. Caneva (2005) even suggests that Kuhn played down the importance of Fleck's influence in order to protect his intellectual property. Based on these observations, research into the relationship between the work of Kuhn and Fleck needs to be expanded by examining the similarities between their theories, concepts, motifs and examples. The analysis should also be broadened to include the metaphors and vocabulary development in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials, in light of his reading of Fleck and other sources, some of which are common to both authors. Kuhn's theory is thus examined *in statu nascendi* (in the state of being born).

In his three published statements from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6–7; Kuhn 1979, ix–x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed to have read *Entstehung* in 1949. We also know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date from 1950/51, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures. However, from 1976, Kuhn began to suggest that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 had been limited by his grasp of the German language, and that what he found in *Entstehung* merely confirmed ideas he had already conceived. Around the same time, in his 1976 Foreword to the English translation of *Entstehung*, Kuhn began to attribute his thinking to what he termed the Aristotle Experience, dating it back to 1947. At that time, he was a physics graduate student and was asked by his supervisor, James B. Conant, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. As he struggled to understand Aristotle's *Physics*, Kuhn suddenly realised that Aristotle's science was not false or meaningless, but simply different to the contemporary physics he had been taught. From 1976 onwards, Kuhn described this experience as a moment of revelation, marking the birth of the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms. This change in narrative coincided with the publication of Fleck's English translation. The significance of this change for the originality of Kuhn's thought will be explored through in-depth archival research (not only in the Kuhn archives, but also in the archives of J. Conant, P. Feyerabend, R. Merton, M. Polanyi, T. Trenn, H. Schilling, M. Kac and E. Shils) and a linguistic analysis of Kuhn's developing theory compared with Fleck's. (The first steps in this direction were taken in Jarnicki & Greif, 2022). Reisch (2019, pp. 176–221) informs us that Fleck's book appears in Kuhn's preliminary sketches for his Lowell Lectures and that the initial title of the lecture series, *The Creation of Scientific Objects*, echoes Fleck's *Entstehung*.

Apart from Fleck, numerous influences on Kuhn will be taken into account, mostly on the basis of secondary literature and collaboration with a group of external experts. These influences include French epistemologists such as Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons, 2017), as well as James B. Conant (Kuhn's teacher and superior at Harvard). Other influences include Michael Polanyi (Moleski, 2006; Jacobs, 2006b; Jacobs, 2009), Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum, 1983; Marcum, 2015) and Stephen Toulmin. Common influences on Fleck and Kuhn will also be considered, particularly those from the fields of art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestalt* psychology (Wolfgang Köhler and Kurt Koffka). Whether Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is a matter for investigation. The parallels and shared influences raise the question of the precise extent of Fleck's influence on Kuhn. Regardless of the outcome, new insights into Fleck's potential influence on Kuhn will be gained, as well as a more historically grounded understanding of the history of the philosophy of contemporary science and the social studies of science.

Concept and work plan

Preliminary research indicates a notable, yet understated, influence of Ludwik Fleck on Thomas Kuhn, particularly concerning shared inspirations from art history and the evolving narrative of Kuhn's Aristotle Experience. The project will systematically investigate this relationship through three main pillars: extensive textual analysis of both authors' published and unpublished works,

critical review of secondary sources, and in-depth archival research in various key collections. This comprehensive approach aims to uncover the precise nature and extent of Fleck's influence on Kuhn's theories, comparing their vocabulary and metaphors, and evaluating various hypotheses from parallel discovery to potential plagiarism.

Preliminary research

In addition to addressing the challenges of translating Fleck's work (Jarnicki, 2016), the Principal Investigator (PI) has published two substantial articles on this topic in the last four years (Jarnicki, 2021; Jarnicki & Greif, 2022). The first article demonstrates that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój* belongs to the realm of musical metaphor — the term cannot be accurately translated into English, but is often rendered as 'mood' — and that he adopted it from art historians such as Wölfflin and Riegl. According to Oliveira (2017), one of the most important sources of inspiration for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison between the development of art and science. An analysis of printed sources suggests that this shared inspiration from art history may not have been entirely independent. In the second article, the authors analyse Kuhn's sparse comments on Fleck alongside the evolution of his recollections of his Aristotle Experience in 1947. They conclude that Kuhn began to attribute revelatory significance to this experience when he learned of the work on an English translation of Fleck's book. It is doubtful that Kuhn played a direct role in translating Fleck's book into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who persuaded Merton to publish the translation with the University of Chicago Press. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, which he reluctantly agreed to do, recounting the Aristotle Experience differently in the process. Referring to the Aristotle Experience narrative as the inspiration for the *Structure* may have distracted scholars from considering other potential influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue through further linguistic and archival research.

Work Plan

This research is based on three pillars: 1) **textual analysis** of Kuhn's (published and unpublished) writings and Fleck's writings using the Corpus Analysis Toolkit; 2) **analysis of secondary sources**; and 3) **archival research**.

A careful literary and linguistic analysis of the published and unpublished works of Kuhn and Fleck will provide novel insights into the similarities and differences in their thought processes. Secondary sources documenting Fleck's potential influence on Kuhn will then be used to interpret these findings. In addition to identifying direct influences, it will be necessary to establish the common points of reference that Fleck and Kuhn had in existing literature, for example in *Gestalt* psychology and art history. Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and scattered across various archives. It is here that the most novel insights are to be expected. When analysing the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it is important to bear in mind that Kuhn read about Fleck's theory in German and had to translate it into contemporary English as he read. The project is structured as follows:

1. **The aim of textual analysis** is to answer the following questions:
 - 1.1. **Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary** in his published and unpublished texts written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?
 - 1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those in *Structure* (e.g. incommensurability, revolution, scientific community)?
 - 1.1.2. In texts written before 1962, did Kuhn use phrases closer to those used by Fleck to describe similar phenomena?
 - 1.2. Do the metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck to develop their theories and those of existing theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between them?
 - 1.3. What similarities and differences exist between the two theories in terms of concepts, motifs, theses, argumentation, style and examples?
2. **The analysis of secondary sources aims** to answer the following questions:
 - 2.1. What influences and points of reference did Fleck and Kuhn share?
 - 2.2. **What influence did Fleck's writings have on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts?**
3. **Archival research aims** to provide:

3.1. **Unpublished sources documenting the nature and extent of the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn, as well as shared influences, as indicated in sections 2.1 and 2.2.**

3.2 Additional (unpublished) materials for textual analysis, as indicated in 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 above.

The project is divided into four nine-month periods. During the first period, we will carry out an analysis of the published texts (I, II, III and IV below). During the second period, we will conduct archival research (V below) and analyse unpublished texts (VI and VII below). During the third period, we will compare **relevant data on Kuhn's and Fleck's theories (VIII, IX and X below)** and answer the question of what constitutes the similarity between the two theories. During the fourth period, we will reflect on various hypotheses in the existing secondary literature on both authors that attempt to explain the similarity (XI below).

I. Textual analysis of the published writings of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 – see point 1.1. for the published writings of Thomas Kuhn.

II. Textual analysis of published texts by Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 with regard to metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. with regard to published texts by Thomas Kuhn.

III. **Textual analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings in terms of metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. regarding texts by Ludwik Fleck.**

IV. **Comparative analysis of corpora of Fleck's and Kuhn's (published) texts using Corpus Analysis Toolkit.**

V. Archival research in

i. The Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] – collect unpublished texts to be analysed in terms of vocabulary development and metaphors used – especially materials and unpublished notes documenting his reading (e.g. Notes and Ideas notebook 1949), **as well as working versions of Kuhn's books and papers written before 1962: *The Copernican Revolution* (1957), *Structure* (earlier versions, but also reviews and correspondence about it), Guggenheim proposal, *Lowell Lectures*, *The Essential Tension* (1959), *The Function of Measurement in Modern Physical Science* (1961), *The Function of Dogma in Scientific Research* (1963);** check whether Kuhn made any notes on ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949; check when Kuhn first read about *Gestalt psychology*; **search for early references to the Aristotle Experience; check whether Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible;** search the correspondence between Kuhn and Merton about the English translation of Fleck.

ii. James Conant Archive [part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] – check for mentions of Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn and others,

iii. **Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, Library of the London School of Economics]** – check for any mentions of Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently, and that they both stayed together and discussed a lot in Berkeley before publishing their texts on incommensurability),

iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] – study materials for the **American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,**

v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] – **check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*)** and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi, check whether Fleck is mentioned in correspondence between Polanyi and Mark Kac who had known Fleck personally.

vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know more about the genealogical **relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as the family of Wilhelm Baldamus who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).**

VI. Textual analysis of unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 – see point 1.1. for unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn.

VII. Textual analysis of Thomas Kuhn's unpublished texts up to and including 1962 with regard to metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. for unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn.

VIII. Comparison of the metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.

IX. Comparison of Fleck's and Kuhn's vocabulary (with regard to the latter, taking into account the development of his vocabulary over time).

X. Comparative analysis of corpora of Fleck's and Kuhn's texts (unpublished) and comparative analysis of the *Structure* with its earlier versions using Corpus Analysis Toolkit.

XI. Consideration of possible explanations for the similarity of the two theories – from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of the existing literature.

In order to ensure a prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive under (V) will be preceded by a detailed enquiry with the keepers of the archive as to the nature and extent of the material to be expected.

Risk assessment

By far the greatest project risks concern archival research. Firstly, we should expect to find less conclusive evidence than our preliminary research suggests. In this case, we will need to focus more on analysing the published and unpublished material that is already available. Secondly, we may have to contend with travel disruptions caused by external factors that could impede field research visits. In anticipation of this, funds earmarked for travel will be reallocated to pay the archives to draw up copies of documents to be sent to us by post or digitally.

Research methodology

The project will use a variety of methods.

1. **Philological methods**, which will be used throughout the work plan. These methods include collecting and analysing primary and secondary sources, tracing key concepts, arguments and references, and considering their context.
2. **Archival research methods** (item V of the work plan);
3. **Linguistic text analysis** (items I–III and VI–IX of the work plan), supported by the AntConc Corpus Analysis Toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation, etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980 and developed by others, e.g. Jäkel, 2002).
4. **Philosophical methods** (in all sections of the work plan), including semantic analysis of key terms and developing hypotheses based on the results of philological, conceptual, and archival work.

Publication plan

The project will result in at least 4 articles to be submitted to international journals (140 or 200 points according to the Polish list of journals) about:

1. **The development of Kuhn's vocabulary and a comparison of Kuhn's vocabulary with Fleck's vocabulary.**
2. A comparison of metaphors and the purposes of their use by Fleck and Kuhn.
3. The results of archival research.
4. Discussion the results of the research presented in Articles 1-3 in the context of the secondary literature **and Kuhn's inspirations other than Fleck; to answer the question of what makes Fleck's and Kuhn's theories similar and to consider any hypotheses that might explain this similarity.**

Research team

The team will be composed of **Paweł Jarnicki** (PI, National Ossolinski Institute) and **Hans-Joachim Greif** (Co-Investigator 1, Department of Philosophy and Ethics in Administration, Warsaw University of Technology), i.e. scholars with expertise in Philosophy of Science (PI, CI1), Linguistics (PI). As this investigation requires triangulation between three languages, the team members have native or near-native skills in English (PI, CI1), German (CI1) and Polish (PI). The materials found and prepared in the course of the linguistic and philosophical analysis will be consulted and critiqued by a **group of external experts**, including Fleck and Kuhn experts from Poland (**Michał Kokowski, Artur Koterski, Wojciech Sady**) and abroad (**Nicholas Binney, Kenneth Caneva, Mauro Condé, Leandro Giri, Juan Mayoral, Nicola Mößner, Hans-Jörg Rheinberger**). These include experts who have studied Kuhn's archive (Giri, Mayoral), supporters (Sady) or opponents (Mayoral, Caneva) of the most radical plagiarism hypothesis. All of the above researchers were informed of the nature of the project and agreed to participate in the work of the group of external experts. Each of the external experts will be invited for a six-day stay in Wrocław (in the second half of the project).

Project literature

- Babich, B. E. (2003a). From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.
- Babich, B. E. (2003b). Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, H. Korte, eds., *Human Figurations. Essays for Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In M. Erickson, C. Turner (2016). *The Sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Acumen (2014 Routledge).
- Bird, A. (2022). Thomas Kuhn, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2022 Edition), E. N. Zalta., ed.
- Brorson, S., H. Andersen (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109-129.
- Caneva, K.L. (2005). 'Discovery' as a site for the collective construction of scientific knowledge. *Historical Studies in the Physical and Biological Sciences*, 35, 2 (March), 175-291.
- Cedarbaum, D. G. (1983). Paradigms. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 14, 3, p. 173- 213.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420-423.
- Conant, J.B. (1953). *Modern Science and Modern Man*. Garden City, NY: A Doubleday Anchor Book.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé, B. G. Figueiredo, eds., *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argumentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1989, *Die Wissenschaftsphilosophie Thomas S. Kuhns: Rekonstruktion und Grundlagenprobleme*. Eng. Trans. (1993). *Reconstructing Scientific Revolutions: Thomas S. Kuhn's Philosophy of Science*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (1990). Kuhn's conception of incommensurability. *Stud. in Hist. and Phil. of Sci. Part A*, 21, 481-92.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266-276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157-168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163-173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). *Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, English and American Studies in German*, 4-6.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) *Stimmung/Nastrój* as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives. *Foundations of Science* 27, 1207-1228.
- Jarnicki, P; Greif, H. (2022) The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure', *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*, early online (8.06.2022).
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd ed. 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn, R. K. Merton. eds., *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii– xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (2022). *The last writings of Thomas S. Kuhn: Incommensurability in science*. Ed. B. Mladenović, University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago.

- Marcum, J. A. (2015). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?*: Bloomsbury.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery*, 33(2), 8-24.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.**
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Peine, A. (2011). Challenging incommensurability: What we can learn from Ludwik Fleck for the analysis of configurational innovation. *Minerva*, 49(4), 489-508.
- Reisch, G.A. (2019). *The Politics of Paradigms*. Albany: SUNY Press.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Werner, S. & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Winneke, S. (1993). Ludwik Fleck—Zur Wirkung eines Wirkungslosen, In Helmuth Albrecht (ed.) *Naturwissenschaft und Technik in der Geschichte. 25 Jahre Lehrstuhl für Geschichte der Naturwissenschaft und Technik am Historischen Institut der Universität Stuttgart*, Stuttgart, Verlag für Geschichte der Naturwissenschaften und der Technik, 357–367.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*, Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.**
- Wray, K. B., ed. (2021a). *Interpreting Kuhn*, Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2021b). *Kuhn's Intellectual Path*, Cambridge University Press.

OPIS SZCZEGÓŁOWY

[w języku angielskim]

On the Shoulders of an Invisible Giant? Uncovering Ludwik Fleck's Influence on Thomas Kuhn

1) Scientific goal of the project

Despite the numerous similarities between **Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and collectives** and **Thomas Kuhn's theory of scientific development**, neither the nature nor the extent of Fleck's influence on Kuhn has been adequately documented or analysed to date. This **project in the history of philosophy of science** aims to explore in depth **the possible genealogical relationship between these two theories**.

There are numerous similarities between Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and collectives in *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache* (1935, henceforth *Entstehung*) and Thomas Kuhn's theory in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962, henceforth *Structure*). In his theory of thought styles and thought collectives, Fleck, like Kuhn later, resisted speculation about how science should work, while stressing the importance of how it does work. Both Fleck and Kuhn explicitly claimed that scientific knowledge is not simply additive, that it changes as a whole, and questioned the classical definition of truth and the possibility of pure observation. Fleck, like Kuhn later, observed the influence of social factors and non-verbalizable elements on the content of scientific knowledge and examined the role of the history of science in the reflection on science. For Fleck, scientists linked by a „thought style” form a „thought collective”, which is not very different from Kuhn's „scientific community”. Kuhn's use of the term „paradigm” often does not follow his own specific technical meaning, but the broad meaning of a „conceptual framework”. This broad meaning is fairly close to Fleck's „thought style”. Fleck, like Kuhn later, saw stages in the development of a thought style. At moments of breakthrough (Fleck writes of „intellectual unrest”), scientists seem to see alternately the old *Gestalt* and the new one, and after the breakthrough the world in which scientists live will have changed. Fleck also referred to the incommensurability and untranslatability of thought styles, and the dependence of the meaning of words on thought styles – all concepts that would resurface in Kuhn.

Given that Kuhn read *Entstehung* more than a decade before writing *Structure*, these similarities may not be coincidental. Given the number and degrees of similarity between key concepts, it is likely that **Fleck's influence on Kuhn's thinking was considerable**. However, Kuhn only acknowledged Fleck's importance in a few places, and only in passing and with qualifications. Yet the nature, depth and extent of Fleck's influence on Kuhn have not been well documented or analysed. The aim of this study is to provide a detailed account of the **possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's work** in light of the best available evidence. In contrast to common philosophy of science comparisons of two „ready-made” theories, the present study will build on the few more historically minded investigations of the Fleck-Kuhn relationship and provide a more comprehensive, coherent and **systematic account of the influence of Fleck's writings on the genesis and development of Kuhn's theory**. It will do so by critically examining primary and secondary sources and by gathering and analysing previously unrecognized evidence. It will use the information from these sources to **explore a range of possible hypotheses about Fleck's influence on Kuhn** and assess their merits.

The guiding hypothesis of this project is that Fleck's work was more important to Kuhn than he and many philosophers of science after him have generally acknowledged. The spectrum of explanatory hypotheses concerning the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn's thought includes, at one end, the statement that both theories were formulated largely independently, as Kuhn knew of their existence but only superficially appreciated their emergence or did not fully understand them, so that any talk of influence is exaggerated: „Fleck (1935/1979), for example, is often cited as having anticipated Kuhn,

although more careful studies suggest that the similarities between their views are superficial.” (Wray 2016, p. 4) At most, Fleck anticipated some of Kuhn’s views in a process of parallel discovery. At the other end of the spectrum are suggestions of plagiarism, according to which Kuhn took central ideas from Fleck without giving him proper credit: „The reader who is familiar with Kuhn’s work will easily recognize that the majority of [Fleck’s] terms is virtually identical with the basic terminology of *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*.” (Baldamus 1977, p. 151) „Invented by Ludwik Fleck [the concept of ‘scientific community’ ...] remained ignored until Thomas Kuhn appropriated it in 1962.” (Baldamus 1977, p. 135) Between these extremes are the views that Kuhn read and understood Fleck’s book, but that it had either an indirect and unconscious or even subconscious influence on him, which might be supported by the observation that Fleck „even illustrated the idea with some of the same examples Kuhn later adopted” (Oberheim 2012, p. 128); or that Kuhn’s reading of Fleck helped him to develop and substantiate his earlier ideas, which might be supported by Baldamus’s (1979) observation that key concepts present in Fleck can be found in Kuhn’s writings with increasing frequency over the years.

2) Significance of the project

Today we have a situation in which Kuhn is widely considered an original philosopher of science („Thomas Samuel Kuhn (1922–1996) is one of the most influential philosophers of science of the twentieth century, perhaps the most influential. His 1962 book *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* is one of the most cited academic books of all time.” Bird 2022). At the same time, it is clear to many specialists that the influence of Fleck is at least insufficiently documented.

On the one hand, statistics from the Scopus database (search according to: Article title, Abstract, Keywords, Authors) show that there are many more works about Kuhn as about Fleck published between 1979 and 2023.

Between 1979 and 2023, Scopus lists 2930 articles about or related to Kuhn, but only 195 about or related to Fleck.

On the other hand, a pilot survey among Polish academics conducted by the PI in May 2020 documents a perceived need to acknowledge Fleck’s contribution (P. Jarnicki, *A Survey on the Opinion of Polish Researchers on the Relationship between the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn*). The survey was conducted on a sample of 23 Polish philosophers who consider their knowledge of Kuhn’s and Fleck’s theories to be at least good. According to the majority of respondents, there was an influence of Fleck on Kuhn, which Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge.¹

¹ To the question about the connection between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories, 1 answered „don’t know” and only 1 pointed that there is „no influence”, 5 chose „anticipated” (which we interpret as no genealogical connection), 5 chose „forerunner” (which we interpret as weak genealogical

To remedy this situation, it is necessary both to compare the vocabulary and metaphors used by Kuhn and Fleck and to trace the possible routes of conceptual transfer. Although both tasks are relevant and will be considered in this project, its main contribution will be to show how and to what extent **Fleck's concepts influenced Kuhn. While there** have been previous attempts to demonstrate such influence, the novelty of this project lies in combining a historiographical analysis of shared influences with a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in the work of both authors, in order to analyse the similarities between their theories.

In particular, many eminent Kuhn scholars – especially Hoyningen-Huene (e.g. 1989, 1990), but also Bird (2000), Marcum (2015) and Wray (2011, 2021a) – write little or nothing about Fleck or consider Fleck's influence on Kuhn superficial (Wray 2021b). For example, Alexander Bird (2000) discusses Fleck entirely separately from Kuhn as just one of many elements of the background that „encouraged the rejection of the picture of science as the accumulation of knowledge driven by a rational scientific method”. In a subsection on Fleck, Kuhn's name is not even mentioned. Similarly, Marcum (2015) briefly discusses Fleck as one intellectual influence among others, such as Wittgenstein. Part of the task of the present proposal is to justify the assumption that Fleck's influence on Kuhn was more prominent and pronounced than Kuhn scholarship generally acknowledges.

On the other hand, there are numerous studies that compare the theories of Fleck and Kuhn, notably Baldamus (1976, 1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Braunstein (2003), Brorson & Andersen (2001), Cedarbaum (1983), Collins (2012), Condé (2005, 2018), Dahms (2016), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Marín (2010), Mößner (2011), Peine (2011) and Winneke (1993). However, most of these studies are not complementary to each other and remain confined to an ahistorical comparative analysis of concepts – most prominently *thought style* versus *paradigm* and *thought collective* versus *scientific community*. Among these studies, with the exception of Baldamus's, which compares the vocabularies of Fleck's 1935 and Kuhn's 1962 books, little attention has been paid to how Fleck's concepts might actually have influenced Kuhn's. Therefore, research on the relationship between Kuhn's and Fleck's work needs to be deepened by asking what constitutes the similarity between the theories, concepts, motifs and examples involved. It also needs to be broadened by analysing the metaphors and the **development of vocabulary in Kuhn's writings, including his unpublished materials, in light of his** reading of Fleck and other, partly common, sources. Tracing the underlying genealogical relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, whatever its concrete nature, will help to shed light on the conceptual similarities and differences involved.

Even when authors sympathetic with Fleck, such as Peine (2011) or Collins (2012), write about the relationship between Fleck and Kuhn, they usually do not recognize this relationship as a genealogical one. Peine's intention, for example, is to show that some of Fleck's concepts are complementary to Kuhn's theory, as if they were synchronous. By starting from a discussion of the differences between two “ready-made” theories, Peine easily convinces himself that Kuhn rejected more than he adopted from Fleck: „while Kuhn has indeed resembled some of Fleck's central ideas, he was reluctant to accept Fleck's more radical claim that science is an essentially social process”. In contrast, the present study will begin by identifying the most undeniable similarities, and Fleck's theory will be compared to Kuhn's not as a „ready-made” theory, but first and foremost as a theory in *statu nascendi* (in the state of being born).

In the late 1970s, Wilhelm Baldamus (1977, 1979), in comparing the development of Kuhn's vocabulary over time with that of Fleck, implicitly suggested that Thomas Kuhn may have plagiarized Fleck, in the sense of „appropriating” Fleck's key ideas and concepts to a greater extent than he would

connection), 7 chose „source of inspiration” (which we interpret as genealogical connection), 2 chose „strong influence” (which we interpret as significant genealogical connection), 2 chose „plagiarism”. So, 16/23 Polish philosophers see the weaker or stronger genealogical connection. To the question if „Thomas Kuhn has acknowledged the merits of Ludwik Fleck sufficiently”, 3 answered „don't know”, only 5 answered „yes” and as many as 15 (i.e. 65%) answered „no”.

acknowledge. These accusations – presumably because of the popularity of Kuhn’s book and his authority at the time – were never thoroughly investigated. Baldamus was more outspoken in his private correspondence with Robert Merton (Baldamus 1980). In particular, suspicions of plagiarism or other forms of illicit appropriation of Fleck’s ideas by Kuhn are often raised informally, but rarely discussed in writing. The only explicit reference to a possible charge of plagiarism against Kuhn in the literature is to be found in what is actually a rather awkward denial of the charge. Babette Babich (2003b) claims that even if Kuhn had intended to refer to Fleck to a greater extent than he did, or even if he had been inclined to commit plagiarism, he would have been prevented from doing so by the partly inquisitorial nature of Cold War anti-communism in the US at the time. Any reference to such „ideologically problematic terms like ‘thought collective’ and ‘thought style’” would have jeopardized Kuhn’s reputation and academic career.

Conversely, Collins (2012) writes that Kuhn was not „as original as we all once thought”, because **“Fleck did it first and, in a lot of ways did it best”**, while adding that Kuhn ultimately was the one **“responsible for telling the history of science in a thought-collective kind of way”**, because he was the one who **“created the social change by coming along at the right time and writing in English.”** Some might conclude that even if the most extreme explanation of the similarities between Kuhn and Fleck is true, namely that Kuhn plagiarized Fleck, the fact remains that Kuhn had a huge impact on the history of philosophy of science, not Fleck, so that Fleck’s philosophy is just a historical footnote. Of course, one could think this way – the one who has been successful, the one who has had a successful career, standing on the shoulders of other people’s intellectual achievements, is the one who carries the day. But that is thinking in categories that would be considered outside the realm of science – cynical thinking. **If there is any reasonable evidence to support the suspicion that Thomas Kuhn illicitly appropriated his most important philosophical ideas from Ludwik Fleck, then this possibility must be explicitly considered** (Jarnicki & Greif 2022).

There is another article that, while not examining the Fleck-Kuhn relationship in detail, provides arguments that show the importance of the project. Caneva (2005) notes the similarities between the theories, **even describing the two as „essentially indistinguishable”**. He notes that the quality of the introduction to Fleck’s book, written by Kuhn, is curious because it contrasts with Caneva’s observation (Kuhn was his supervisor) that Kuhn was **„an unsurpassed master when it came to understanding texts and teasing out their meanings and implications”**. Caneva then analyses Kuhn’s statements and finds the reasons he gives for his dislike of Fleck **„hardly cogent”**. Caneva concludes his article with the message that once we realize the similarity between the two theories, **“It is hard to resist the speculation that [...] Kuhn distanced himself from his Polish predecessor the better to secure what he wished to be regarded as his intellectual property.”** Although Caneva’s article does not settle the matter conclusively, and he himself is very skeptical about the charge of plagiarism (private correspondence 2023), the paper does indeed confirm the need to study the relationship between the two theories.

Even if Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories appear different to an observer today – he or she might be aware, for example, of the differences between Fleck’s and Kuhn’s concepts of „incommensurability” – it is important to remember that such differences were probably not nearly as obvious as they are today. In the wake of the publication of the *Structure*, a wide variety of approaches to the social and cultural studies of science developed, and we are now aware of many more nuances that were probably imperceptible to people who read the *Structure* immediately after its publication, when it not only caused a great stir but also had yet to give rise to the very social and cultural studies of science that now form the observer’s vantage point. This is an argument against the claim that the similarity between Kuhn and Fleck is superficial on closer inspection. It is only now that we are able to point out all the differences. It should also be emphasized that in the case of an obvious relationship between two authors, it would be inappropriate in terms of strategy and method of investigation to discuss the differences without first considering the similarities. In order to adequately discuss the differences

between Kuhn's and Fleck's theories, we must first thoroughly examine and explain the similarities between them and identify, as far as possible, which of these similarities are of a genealogical nature.

On the other hand, many influences that shaped both Fleck's and Kuhn's views are not at all obvious to the contemporary observer but were nevertheless important to them in all the nuances and details that escape us today. Accordingly, **numerous influences on Kuhn apart from Fleck will be taken into account**, mostly on the basis of secondary literature and cooperation with the group of external experts. Influences include the French epistemologists, especially Gaston Bachelard, Alexandre Koyré, Hélène Metzger, Émile Meyerson and Georges Canguilhem (see Simons 2017), and James B. Conant (Kuhn's teacher and superior at Harvard, Kuhn „never discusses how Conant influenced him” (Wray 2021b, 25)), but also Michael Polanyi (Moleski 2006, Jacobs 2006b, Jacobs 2009) and Ludwig Wittgenstein (Cedarbaum 1983, Marcum 2015) and Stephen Toulmin. An analysis of the relationship between Kuhn and the French epistemologists shows that there are indeed similarities (Simons 2017), but these appear to be far fewer than between Fleck and Kuhn, while the former but not the latter are documented in Kuhn's footnotes. Wray's (2016) downplaying of Fleck's influence in his demonstration of Conant's influence on Kuhn is weakened by the fact that Conant read Fleck's book in 1950 (see Trenn 1981), so there may still be a mediated influence. Wray (2021b), in analysing Conant's influence on Kuhn, gives equal weight to Conant's 1947 and 1953 texts, whereas Kuhn and Conant read Fleck in late 1949/early 1950. None of the common themes identified by Wray (2021b) in Conant and Kuhn are absent from Fleck's book. From what Wray writes, it seems that Conant's influence on Kuhn can be detected primarily in the *Copernican Revolution*.

According to Moleski (2006), Kuhn and Polanyi met in 1958, and after the publication of Kuhn's *Structure*, Polanyi had a (not publicly stated) belief that Kuhn had been dishonest to him. Jacobs (2002), who argues for Kuhn's unacknowledged debt to Polanyi, claims that Kuhn's notion of scientific community is taken from Polanyi rather than Fleck, because Fleck's thought collective „denotes a considerably wider class of social groups”. Debt to Fleck certainly does not exclude debt to Polanyi, but Kuhn read Fleck earlier than he read Polanyi. We must also consider the possibility that Kuhn, with Polanyi's help, limited Fleck's general theory of thought collectives, applicable to science, fashion, religion and other fields, to scientific communities. However, Fleck's book was in fact a study of a scientific thought collective, while many of Kuhn's concepts, such as “paradigm shift”, were later readily applied to domains other than science.

Common influences on Fleck and Kuhn will also be considered, especially those from art history (Alois Riegl and Heinrich Wölfflin) and *Gestalt* psychology (Wolfgang Köhler, Kurt Koffka). The question of whether Fleck and Kuhn adopted these sources independently of each other is a matter for investigation. Oliveira's (2017) paper on the first – unpublished – chapter of the *Structure* shows that, at the beginning, one of Kuhn's key ideas was to make the image of science appear closer to the image of art (as the latter develops in a non-cumulative way). In doing so, he transferred some elements of art history insights to the way we understand science. Since Fleck was informed by the concepts of style and mood (*nastrój*) in art history, it seems justified to ask whether these influences – on Kuhn and Fleck – were entirely independent (Jarnicki 2021). This question may become even more pertinent in light of the observation that Fleck remained critical of art historical notions of style that presented it as an objective characteristic of a given collective that would allow for equally objective comparison, rather than the nucleus of a proto-concept of incommensurability as it would later be articulated by Kuhn (Zittel 2011).

The influence of *Gestalt* psychologists on both authors is obvious and straightforward by comparison. It seems that both Kuhn and Fleck have similarly transferred (this is a kind of metaphor) the knowledge of psychologists to epistemology (for Fleck's reference to *Gestalt* psychology, see Zittel 2014 and Hagner 2012; the latter comparatively evaluates the importance of *Gestalt* psychology on Fleck and Michael Polanyi, who has also been cited as an under-appreciated influence on Kuhn, see above). In 1979, Cedarbaum (1983) interviewed Kuhn and wrote: “Also, Kuhn allows that Fleck's discussion of, and emphasis on, *Gestalt* psychology may have awakened his own interest in the field; that

contribution alone would make G.D.S.F. [Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact] enormously significant in the formation of *Structure*.”

All the parallels and shared influences raise the question of the precise position of Fleck’s influence on Kuhn. In his three published statements from 1962 to 1995 (Kuhn 1970, pp. 6-7; Kuhn 1979, ix-x; Kuhn et al. 2000, p. 283), Kuhn explicitly claimed to have read *Entstehung* in 1949, and we know that his earliest attempts to write the *Structure* date from 1950/51, when he was preparing his Lowell Lectures (“The development of Kuhn’s new image of the nature of science began with the 1951 Lowell lectures”, Marcum 2015), i.e., after reading Fleck. However, from 1976 Kuhn started to claim that his understanding of Fleck in 1949 was constrained by a limited grasp of Fleck’s German writing, and that what he found in Fleck in 1949 merely confirmed ideas he had already conceived. This change of narrative over the years is the main evidence for Kuhn’s changing perception of Fleck’s importance for his own thought, and ultimately for Fleck’s insufficiently acknowledged influence (Jarnicki & Greif 2022).

In any case, the focus of Kuhn scholarship has long been distracted from the possible influences of Fleck (and Polanyi?) because of a peculiar Kuhnian narrative. Beginning in 1976 (in his *Foreword to Genesis and Development of a Scientific Fact*, the English translation of *Entstehung*), Kuhn began to trace the origins of his argument to what he called the Aristotle Experience. According to his own account, this foundational experience occurred in 1947, when, as a graduate student in physics, he was asked by his supervisor, James B. Conant, to prepare lectures on the history of mechanics for non-scientists. As Kuhn struggled to understand Aristotle’s *Physics*, he suddenly realized that Aristotle’s science was not false and meaningless, but simply different from the contemporary physics he himself had been taught. According to the autobiographical narrative that Kuhn would develop from 1976 onwards, this was a moment of revelation in which the notions of scientific revolutions and paradigms were also born. Many Kuhn scholars followed this narrative for many years (Jarnicki & Greif 2022). One aim of this project is to test the credibility of Kuhn’s narrative in light of evidence for traces of his ideas about revolutions and paradigms that he may have formulated between his Aristotle Experience in 1947 and his encounter with *Entstehung* in 1949, and any reading of *Gestalt* psychologists or art historians before that time.

The significance of this change for the originality of Kuhn’s thought will be explored through in-depth archival research (not only in the Kuhn archives, but also in the archives of J. Conant, P. Feyerabend, R. Merton, M. Polanyi, T. Trenn, H. Schilling, M. Kac, E. Shils, W. Baldamus) and linguistic analysis of Kuhn’s theory *in statu nascendi* in comparison with Fleck’s theory. (First steps in this direction were made in Jarnicki & Greif 2022). From Reisch (2019, 176, 221) we know that Fleck’s “book appears in Kuhn’s preliminary sketches for his [Kuhn’s] Lowell Lectures” and that the initial title of the cycle (*The Creation of Scientific Objects*) “echoes” Fleck’s *Entstehung*.

However, if it is true that Kuhn did not sufficiently acknowledge Fleck’s influence in one way or another, an important complementary task will be to reflect on what Kuhn may have missed in his adoption of Fleck’s thought in particular – and, consequently, what the tradition in the history and philosophy of science that he spawned may have missed as well. There are some relevant insights for contemporary philosophy of science to be gleaned here, for example from Fleck’s concept of *Stimmung/nastrój*, which is not properly translatable into English – it is usually translated as ‘mood’ and apparently not grasped by Kuhn – but which is crucial to Fleck’s approach. The project’s PI can build on previous work on this topic (Jarnicki 2016, Jarnicki 2021). Another idea of Fleck’s that Kuhn did not adopt is the active and passive elements of knowledge – an idea that allowed Fleck to take a reasonable position in the relativism debate (Binney 2023).

Only once we have answered the question of what the two theories have in common, and once we can say with certainty what Kuhn did not take from Fleck, will it be possible to appreciate Kuhn’s innovations – which appear to be primarily his concept of paradigms in the narrow sense, and the notion of a revolutionary rather than an evolutionary development of science. Only when we know

what ideas Kuhn adopted from Fleck, and how, can we properly assess the nature and influence of the most famous book on the philosophy of science of the twentieth century. The results of this research may therefore be relevant beyond the disciplinary debates in the history of philosophy of science. Whatever the outcome, we will gain **new insights into Fleck's possible influence on Kuhn** and a more **historically grounded understanding of the history of contemporary philosophy of science and the social studies of science**.

3) Concept and work plan

Preliminary research – previous work

In 2016, the PI published an article in *The Translator*: “On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations”. Using the example of the concept of *communication/circulation* of thoughts [*Denkverkehr/krążenie myśli*], it was shown that since both Fleck's Polish and his German texts are original texts (i.e. one theory has been formulated in two languages), a translator of Fleck's work should take into account that the level of equivalence between these original texts is the level of concepts (rather than the level of lexical meaning).. Similarly, when examining the relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, we will assume similarity not so much at the level of linguistic expressions, but at the level of concepts and their relations.

In addition to his work on the specifics of translating Fleck (Jarnicki 2016), the PI has published two substantial articles in the last four years (Jarnicki 2021; Jarnicki & Greif 2022). The first article shows that Fleck's concept of *Stimmung/nastrój* belongs to the realm of musical metaphor (the term cannot be properly translated into English and is usually rendered as “mood”) and that he adopted it from art historians (Wölfflin and Riegl). According to Oliveira (2017), one of the most important inspirations for Thomas Kuhn's philosophy of science was the comparison of the development of art and science. The analysis of printed sources shows that this common inspiration from art history may not have been completely independent.

In the second article, the authors analyse Kuhn's few statements on Fleck in comparison with the development of his recollections of his Aristotle Experience in 1947 and conclude that Kuhn began to ascribe the weight of a revelation to this experience precisely when he heard about the work on an English translation of Fleck. It is doubtful that Kuhn played a direct role in the translation of Fleck's book into English. According to our limited knowledge of the R. Merton archive, the initiative came from T. Trenn, who persuaded Merton to have the University of Chicago Press publish Fleck's book in translation. In 1975, Merton asked Kuhn to write a foreword, and Kuhn reluctantly agreed – and began to recount the Aristotle Experience in a different light. Citing the Aristotle Experience narrative as his inspiration for the *Structure* may have effectively diverted scholarly attention from other influences. The present project seeks to shed additional light on this issue on the basis of further linguistic and archival research.

Preliminary research – vocabulary development

A prime example of how tracing the development of Kuhn's vocabulary can prove fruitful is the evolution of his use of the word ‘thought’. In Kuhn's first book (1957) we find the following passages:

Such texts are a relatively frequent and extremely significant phenomenon in the *development of scientific thought*. They may be described as texts that *shift* the direction in which *scientific thought develops* [...] As a whole the *De Revolutionibus* stands almost entirely within an ancient astronomical and cosmological tradition; yet within its generally classical framework are to be found a few novelties which *shifted* the direction of *scientific thought* in ways unforeseen by its author and which gave rise to a rapid and complete break with the ancient tradition. (Kuhn 1957, p. 135) [emphasis – PJ]

[...] the *De Revolutionibus* marks a *shift* in the direction in which astronomical *thought developed*. (Kuhn 1957, p. 182) [emphasis – PJ].

Thus in 1957 Kuhn writes about the „development of thought”, whereas in his second book (1962) „thought” in this sense appears only once, apparently by chance: „conflict between competing schools of scientific thought” (Kuhn 1970, p. 96), because in 1962 he prefers to write about the development of science rather than of thought.

As we know, Ludwik Fleck wrote about the „development of thought”, „thought styles” and „thought collectives”. This is the first of the tracks to be followed: is it possible that Kuhn initially wrote about the development of thought under Fleck’s influence, only to free himself from Fleck’s vocabulary after 13 years? This makes it more likely that Kuhn, over time, narrowed Fleck’s general theory to science. An analysis of the working versions of the *Structure* could shed some light on this.

Preliminary research – metaphors with shared aims

The table below compares quotations from Fleck (1935 original and 1979 translation) and Kuhn (1962) which use similar metaphors. Both texts are about a group of people who see one thing, but over time come to see something else. In Kuhn the group has to experience a conversion (which is a religious metaphor), in Fleck the mood of the group has to change (which is a conceptual transfer from art history, and the concept of mood was one of the key concepts for temple architects). Both examples are given in the context of scientific discovery, and in both cases the passage is about a newly emerging thought style (for Fleck, a shared mood is a precondition for a shared thought style) and a newly emerging paradigm. Both paradigm and thought style determine the group’s perception. The source domain from which both paradigm and thought style are conceptualized is seeing *Gestalts*. In both cases, the *Gestalt* metaphor is also used to emphasize that it is impossible to understand the previous thought style/paradigm in terms of the subsequent one (and *vice versa*). In both cases, the metaphor is used to show that the change is not induced by reasoning and logic, and that it happens independently of the intentions of the group members. In the present project, this line of enquiry is pursued in much more detail and on a large corpus of Fleck’s and Kuhn’s writings.

Fleck 1935 (original)	Fleck 1979 (translation)	Kuhn 1962 (original)
eine Massensuggestion, die die gesamte Mannschaft eines Schiffes, auf der Suche nach einem verunglückten Boote befindlich, dieses Boot mit den Insassen wahrnehmen ließ , sogar Signalzeichen und Rufe. Erst in der letzten Minute der Annäherung platzte auf einmal die kollektive Halluzination: das Boot entpuppte sich als ein Baum mit Asten und Blättern , von den Fluten getrieben. Dieser Fall könnte geradezu als Paradigma vieler Entdeckungen gelten: das stimmungsmäßige Gestaltsehen und der plötzliche Umschlag: andersartiges Gestaltsehen. Plötzlich versteht man überhaupt nicht, wie die	a case of mass suggestion which induced the entire crew of a ship, while searching for a boat in distress, to see this craft and its crew and even to hear shouts and see signals. This collective hallucination was suddenly dispelled but only during the last minute of approach. The „boat” turned out to be a tree with branches and leaves drifting in the water. This case could be considered the very paradigm of many discoveries. The moodconforming gestalt-seeing and its sudden reversal: the different gestalt-seeing. Suddenly one can no longer even understand how the previous form was possible and how features	Practicing in different worlds, the two groups of scientists see different things when they look from the same point in the same direction. Again, that is not to say that they can see anything they please. Both are looking at the world, and what they look at has not changed. But in some areas they see different things, and they see them in different relations one to the other. That is why a law that cannot even be demonstrated to one group of scientists may occasionally seem intuitively obvious to another. Equally, it is why, before they can hope to communicate fully, one group or the other must experience the conversion that we have

<p>frühere Gestalt möglich war und wie das ihr Widersprechende unbemerkt bleiben konnte. Genau so verhält es sich mit der wissenschaftlichen Entdeckung, nur aus der Aufregung und dem Fieber in Gleichmaß und Dauer übersetzt. Die disziplinierte, gleichmäßige und viele Generationen dauernde Stimmung eines Kollektives erzeugt das „wirkliche Bild“ genau so, wie die fieberhafte eine Halluzination. In beiden Fällen verlaufen parallel Stimmungswechsel (Denkstilwechsel) und Bildwechsel. (Fleck 1935, p. 117)</p>	<p>contradicting it could have gone unnoticed. The same situation obtains in scientific discovery, only translated from excitement and feverish activity into equanimity and permanence. The disciplined and even-tempered mood, persisting through many generations of a collective, produces the „real image“ in exactly the same way as the feverish mood produces a hallucination. In both cases switch of mood (switch of thought style) and switch of image proceed in parallel. (Fleck 1979, p. 111)</p>	<p>been calling a paradigm shift. Just because it is a transition between incommensurables, the transition between competing paradigms cannot be made a step at a time, forced by logic and neutral experience. Like the gestalt switch, it must occur all at once (though not necessarily in an instant) or not at all. (Kuhn 1970, p. 150)</p>
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Work Plan

This research rests on three pillars:

1. **Textual analysis** of Kuhn's (both published and unpublished) and Fleck's writings,
2. **Analysis of secondary sources**, and
3. **Archival research**.

While the published works of Kuhn and Fleck, if carefully analysed on a literary and linguistic level, will already provide some relevant and novel insights into the similarities and differences between their ways of thinking, secondary sources documenting any influence Fleck may have had on Kuhn will be mobilized to interpret the nature of these similarities and differences.

In addition to direct influences, it will be necessary to identify common points of reference for Fleck and Kuhn in existing literature, for example in *Gestalt* psychology and art history. Although they lived in different places at different times and worked under different conditions, both authors seem to have been embedded in a similar intellectual milieu that deserves to be reconstructed.

Some of the relevant primary and secondary sources may still be unpublished and scattered in various archives. It is here that the most novel insights are to be expected. Therefore, archival research in various locations in Europe and the USA will be one of the pillars of the project. In analysing the possible genealogical relationship between the two theories, it is important to bear in mind that Kuhn learned about Fleck's theory in German and had to 'translate' Fleck into contemporary English as he read.

More specifically, the three-fold structure of the project is as follows:

1. Textual analysis aims to answer the following questions:

- 1.1. Does the development of Kuhn's vocabulary in the texts (published and unpublished) written before the publication of *Structure* indicate a possible genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories?
 - 1.1.1. What vocabulary did Kuhn use to describe phenomena similar to those described in *Structure* (incommensurability, revolution, scientific community, etc.)?
 - 1.1.2. In pre-1962 texts, did Kuhn use phrases closer to Fleck's to describe similar phenomena?
- 1.2. Does the choice of metaphors used by both Kuhn and Fleck to create concepts of their theories and concepts of received theories indicate a possible genealogical relationship between these two theories?
- 1.3. What are the similarities between the two theories (concepts, motifs, theses, argumentation, narration, style and examples) and what are the major differences between the two theories?
2. The analysis of secondary sources aims to answer the following questions:
 - 2.1. What influences and points of reference did Fleck and Kuhn share?
 - 2.2. What kind and degree of influence on the development of Kuhn's vocabulary and theoretical concepts is attributed to Fleck's writings?
3. Archival research aims to provide
 - 3.1. Unpublished sources documenting the nature and extent of the influence of Fleck's writings on Kuhn, as well as shared influences as indicated in 2.1 and 2.2.
 - 3.2. Additional (unpublished) materials for textual analysis as indicated in 1.1., 1.2. and 1.3 above.

The project is divided into **four nine-month periods** during which we will

- A) first carry out an **analysis of the published texts** (I, II, III, and IV below),
- B) then conduct **archival research** (V) and **analyse unpublished texts** (VI-VII below) in order to be able to
- C) **compare relevant data on Kuhn's and Fleck's theories** and answer the question of **what constitutes the similarity between the two theories** (VIII, IX, X below), and
- D) reflect on **various hypotheses** in the existing secondary literature on both authors **that attempt to explain the similarity** (XI below).

- I. Textual analysis of the published writings of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 – see point 1.1. for the published writings of Thomas Kuhn.
- II. Textual analysis of published texts by Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 with regard to metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. with regard to published texts by Thomas Kuhn.
- III. Textual analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings in terms of metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (thought style, thought collective, collective mood, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. regarding texts by Ludwik Fleck.
- IV. Comparative analysis of corpora of Fleck's and Kuhn's (published) texts using Corpus Analysis Toolkit.
- V. Archival research in
 - i. The Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections] – collect unpublished texts to be analysed in terms of vocabulary development and metaphors used – especially materials and unpublished notes documenting his reading (e.g. *Notes and Ideas* notebook 1949), as well as working versions of Kuhn's books and papers written before 1962: *The Copernican Revolution* (1957), *Structure* (earlier versions, but also reviews and correspondence about it), Guggenheim proposal, Lowell lectures, *The Essential Tension* (1959), *The Function of Measurement in Modern Physical Science* (1961), *The Function of Dogma in Scientific Research* (1963); check whether Kuhn made any notes on ideas similar to those presented in *Structure* before 1949; check when Kuhn first read about *Gestalt* psychology; search for early references to the

Aristotle Experience; check whether Kuhn's copy of Fleck's book is accessible; search the correspondence between Kuhn and Merton about the English translation of Fleck.

ii. James Conant Archive [part of the Harvard University Archives Repository] – check for mentions of Fleck in correspondence with Thomas Kuhn and others,

iii. Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophisches Archiv, Universität Konstanz] and Lakatos' Archive [British Library of Political and Economic Science, Library of the London School of Economics] – check for any mentions of Fleck in correspondence between Kuhn and Feyerabend and between Feyerabend and Lakatos (it is claimed that Feyerabend and Kuhn came up with the idea of incommensurability independently, and that they both stayed together and discussed a lot in Berkeley before publishing their texts on incommensurability),

iv. Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University] – study materials for the American edition of Fleck's book, correspondence with Thomas Kuhn, correspondence with others about Fleck,

v. Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library] – check whether Polanyi read Fleck's book, we know that Fleck sent him a copy in 1959 (after reading Polanyi's *Personal Knowledge*) and whether there is any correspondence between Fleck and Polanyi, check whether Fleck is mentioned in correspondence between Polanyi and Mark Kac who had known Fleck personally.

vi. Research in other archives and interviews with those who might know more about the genealogical relationship between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as the family of Wilhelm Baldamus who keep his correspondence, Thaddeus Trenn, Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University (who exchanged some letters with Fleck in 1959, see Werner 2011).

VI. Textual analysis of unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 – see point 1.1. for unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn.

VII. Textual analysis of Thomas Kuhn's unpublished texts up to and including 1962 with regard to metaphors used to create concepts of his theory (paradigm, scientific community, scientific revolution, etc.) and concepts of received theories (truth, observation, fact, etc.) – see item 1.2. for unpublished texts by Thomas Kuhn.

VIII. Comparison of the metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.

IX. Comparison of Fleck's and Kuhn's vocabulary (with regard to the latter, taking into account the development of his vocabulary over time).

X. Comparative analysis of corpora of Fleck's and Kuhn's texts (unpublished) and comparative analysis of the *Structure* with its earlier versions.

XI. Consideration of possible explanations for the similarity of the two theories – from parallel discoveries to plagiarism – based on the research carried out in the project and analysis of the existing literature.

In order to ensure a prudent allocation of resources, any visit to an archive under (V) will be preceded by a detailed enquiry with the keepers of the archive as to the nature and extent of the material to be expected.

Risk assessment

By far the greatest project risks concern archival research: Firstly, we must expect to find less, and less conclusive, evidence than our preliminary research suggests. In this case we will have to focus more on analysing the published and unpublished material that is already known and available. Secondly, we may have to contend with externally induced travel disruptions that could impede field research visits. In anticipation of this eventuality, funds earmarked for travel will in this case be reallocated to pay the archives for drawing copies of documents to be sent to us by post or digitally.

4) Research methodology

The project will employ a range of methods:

- 1) Philological methods (in all parts of the work plan), which include the collection and analysis of primary and secondary sources, the tracing of key concepts, arguments and references used, and the consideration of their context.
- 2) Archival research methods (item V of the work plan).
- 3) Linguistic text analysis (items I-III, VI-X in the work plan), supported by the AntConc corpus analysis toolkit (concordance, word list, collocation, etc.) and conceptual metaphor theory (formulated by Lakoff and Johnson in 1980 and developed by others, e.g. Jäkel 2002). A list of abstract concepts will be defined (target domains of metaphorical projection), with the aim of defining them as abstractly as possible. A corpus of texts for analysis will be constructed. A preliminary analysis of the corpus will be carried out – searching for the concept itself and for the abstract definition. The result will be a list of ways of talking about abstract concepts and a list of metaphors (source domains of metaphorical projection). In the next step, a proper analysis of the corpus will be carried out, looking for other expressions derived from the source domains identified in the previous step. Of particular importance here are suspected synonyms and etymologies of certain expressions. Special attention will be paid to expressions in quotation marks or accompanied by the phrases „as”, „as if”, „so to speak”, etc. The result is a list of target domains with abstract definitions and source domains and their corresponding expressions. An analysis of the purpose of the use of a given metaphor and of what the metaphor enables the author to say – both in what it „highlights” and in what it „hides” in Lakoff and Johnson’s terms – will allow a comparison of its use by the two authors.
- 4) philosophical methods (in all parts of the work plan), which will be conceptual in nature: First, philosophical analysis will explore the meanings – as sense and reference – of key terms in Fleck, Kuhn, and other relevant authors, the presumed logical relationships between these terms, and their place in a larger argumentative framework. Secondly, this work will itself be argumentative, in the sense of developing hypotheses based on the results of philological, conceptual and archival work.

Publication plan

The project will result in at least 4 articles to be submitted to international journals (140 or 200 points according to the Polish list of journals) about:

1. The development of Kuhn’s vocabulary and a comparison of Kuhn’s vocabulary with Fleck’s vocabulary.
2. A comparison of metaphors and the purposes of their use by Fleck and Kuhn.
3. The results of archival research carried out to evaluate the explanatory hypotheses concerning similarities between Kuhn and Fleck.
4. Discussion the results of the research presented in Articles 1-3 in the context of the secondary literature and Kuhn’s inspirations other than Fleck; to answer the question of what makes Fleck’s and Kuhn’s theories similar and to consider any hypotheses that might explain this similarity.

5) Research team

The team will be composed of **Paweł Jarnicki (PI, Ossoliński National Institute)** and **Hans-Joachim Greif** (Co-Investigator 1, Department of Philosophy and Ethics in Administration, Warsaw University of Technology) i.e. scholars with expertise in Philosophy of Science (PI, CI1) and Linguistics (PI). As this investigation requires triangulation between three languages, the team members have native or near-native skills in English (PI, CI1), German (CI1) and Polish (PI).

Hans-Joachim Greif is a philosopher working in the field of history, philosophy, and social studies of science and technology. He is well versed in Fleck’s work and has the linguistic and philosophical background necessary to analyses Fleck’s German-language writings and compare them with their English translations. He has one pertinent publication with the PI (Jarnicki & Greif 20022) and also commands some basic knowledge of AI and computational methods.

The materials found and prepared in the course of the linguistic and philosophical analysis will be consulted and critiqued by a **group of external experts**, including Fleck and Kuhn experts from Poland (**Michał Kokowski, Artur Koterski, Wojciech Sady**) and abroad (**Nicholas Binney, Kenneth Caneva, Mauro Condé, Leandro Giri, Juan Mayoral, Nicola Mößner, Hans-Jörg Rheinberger**). These include experts who have studied Kuhn's archive (Giri, Mayoral), supporters (Sady) or opponents (Mayoral, Caneva) of the most radical plagiarism hypothesis. **All of the above researchers were informed of the nature of the project and agreed to participate in the work of the group of external experts.**

Each of the external experts will be invited for a six-day stay in Wrocław (in the second half of the project), during which the team members will present the results of their previous inquiries to the experts (items I-VII and X in the work plan). The external experts will assist in the realization of items VIII-IX and XI.

- **Nicholas Binney** (from September 2025 at Institut für Geschichte, Theorie und Ethik der Medizin, Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf, Germany, as Marie Curie-Skłodowska Fellow) – young researcher interested in application of Fleck's theory (considers it more useful than Kuhn's)
- **Kenneth Caneva** (emeritus, University of North Carolina at Greensboro, USA) – expert in Kuhn and Fleck, compared their theories, knew Kuhn personally (Kuhn was his supervisor)
- **Mauro Condé** (Departamento de História da Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Brasil) – expert in Kuhn, Fleck and Wittgenstein
- **Leandro Giri** (Departamento de Ciencias Sociales, Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero, Argentina) – expert in Kuhn, cooperated with Pablo Melogno who unexpectedly died. Giri continues Melogno's project based on research in Kuhn's archives ("The unpublished writings of Thomas Kuhn: 1980–1994")
- **Michał Kokowski** (Instytut Historii Nauki Polskiej Akademii Nauk, Poland) – expert in Kuhn, author of the book *Thomas S. Kuhn and the issue of the Copernican revolution* published in Polish
- **Artur Koterski** (Wydział Filozofii i Socjologii, Uniwersytet Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej, Poland) – expert in Kuhn and Fleck
- **Juan Mayoral** (Unidad Predepartamental de Filosofía, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain) – expert in Kuhn, conducted research in Kuhn archives
- **Nicola Mößner** (Institut für Philosophie, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover, Germany) – expert in Fleck and Kuhn, compared Fleck's and Kuhn's theory
- **Hans-Jörg Rheinberger** (Max-Planck-Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte, Germany) – expert in Fleck and Kuhn and leading figure in history of science
- **Wojciech Sady** (Instytut Filozofii, Uniwersytet Śląski, Poland) – expert in Kuhn and Fleck, proponent of plagiarism hypothesis

6) Project literature

- Babich, B. E. (2003a). From Fleck's Denkstil to Kuhn's paradigm: conceptual schemes and incommensurability. *International Studies in the Philosophy of Science*, 17(1), 75-92.
- Babich, B. E. (2003b). Kuhn's paradigm as a parable for the Cold War: incommensurability and its discontents from Fuller's Tale of Harvard to Fleck's *Unsung Lvov*. *Social Epistemology*, 17(2-3).
- Baldamus, W. (1976) *The structure of sociological inference*. Barnes & Noble Books.
- Baldamus, W. (1977). Ludwig Fleck and the Development of the Sociology of Science. In P. R. Gleichman, J. Goudsblum, H. Korte, eds., *Human Figurations. Essays for Norbert Elias* (pp. 135–156). Amsterdam.
- Baldamus, W. (1979). Das exoterische Paradox der Wissenschaftsforschung. *Zeitschrift für allgemeine Wissenschaftstheorie*, 10(2), 213–233. Engl. transl. In M. Erickson, C. Turner (2016). *The Sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Baldamus, W. (1980). Letter to R. Merton, February 6, 1980. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5.
- Binney, N. (2023). Ludwik Fleck's reasonable relativism about science. *Synthese* 201, 40.
- Bird, A. (2000). *Thomas Kuhn*. Acumen (2014 Routledge).
- Bird, A. (2022). Thomas Kuhn, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2022 Edition), E. N. Zalta., ed.
- Braunstein, J.-F. (2003). Thomas Kuhn lecteur de Ludwik Fleck. *Archives de Philosophie*, 66, 403–422.
- Brorson, S., H. Andersen (2001). Stabilizing and Changing Phenomenal Worlds: Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn on Scientific Literature. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science*, 32, 109-129.
- Caneva, K.L. (2005). 'Discovery' as a site for the collective construction of scientific knowledge. *Historical Studies in the Physical and Biological Sciences*, 35, 2 (March), 175-291.
- Cedarbaum, D. G. (1983). Paradigms. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 14, 3, p. 173- 213.
- Collins, H. (2012). Comment on Kuhn. *Social Studies of Science*, 42, 420-423.
- Conant, J. B. (1947). *On Understanding Science: An Historical Approach*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Conant, J.B. (1953). *Modern Science and Modern Man*. Garden City, NY: A Doubleday Anchor Book.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2005). Paradigma versus Estilo de Pensamento na História da Ciência. In M. L. L. Condé, B. G. Figueiredo, eds., *Ciência, História e Teoria* (pp. 123–146). Belo Horizonte: Argvmentvm.
- Condé, M. L. L. (2018). Mutações no Estilo de Pensamento: Ludwik Fleck e o Modelo Biológico na Historiografia da Ciência. *Revista de Filosofia Moderna e Contemporânea*.
- Dahms, H.-J. (2016). Thomas Kuhn's Structure: An "Exemplary Document of the Cold War Era"? In E. Aronova & S. Turchetti (Eds.), *Science Studies during the Cold War and Beyond: Paradigms Defected* (pp. 103–125). New York: Palgrave Macmillan US.
- Erickson, M., & Turner, C. (2016). *The sociology of Wilhelm Baldamus: Paradox and inference*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Fleck, L. (1935). *Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache*. Basel: Benno Schwabe & Co. Eng. transl. (1979). *Genesis and development of a scientific fact*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Fleck, L. (2006), Z. Cackowski, S. Symotiuk, eds. *Psychosocjologia poznania naukowego*. Lublin: Wydawnictwo UMCS.
- Galison, P. (2016). Practice All the Way Down, in R. J. Richards, L. Daston, eds., *Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions at Fifty: Reflections on a Scientific Classic*, pp. 42–69. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Giri L., P. Melogno, H. Miguel, ed. (2023). *Perspectives on Kuhn. Contemporary Approaches to the Philosophy of Thomas Kuhn*, Springer.

- Hagner, M. (2012). Perception, knowledge and freedom in the age of extremes: on the historical epistemology of Ludwik Fleck and Michael Polanyi. *Studies in Eastern European Thought*, 64, 107–120.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P., 1989, *Die Wissenschaftsphilosophie Thomas S. Kuhns: Rekonstruktion und Grundlagenprobleme*. Eng. Trans. (1993). *Reconstructing Scientific Revolutions: Thomas S. Kuhn's Philosophy of Science*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (1990). Kuhn's conception of incommensurability. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 21, 481-92.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (1995). Two Letters of Paul Feyerabend to Thomas S. Kuhn on a Draft of The Structure of Scientific Revolutions, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science* 26 (September), 353-387.
- Hoyningen-Huene, P. (2006), More letters by Paul Feyerabend to Thomas S. Kuhn on Proto-Structure, *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A* 37, Issue 4, 610-632.
- Hufbauer, K. (2012). From Student of Physics to Historian of Science: T. S. Kuhn's Education and Early Career, 1940–1958. *Physics in Perspective* 14, 421–470.
- Jacobs, S. (1987). Scientific Community: Formulations and Critique of a Sociological Motif. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 38, 266-276.
- Jacobs, S. (2002). The genesis of 'scientific community'. *Social Epistemology*, 16, 157-168.
- Jacobs, S. (2006a). Models of scientific community: Charles Sanders Peirce to Thomas Kuhn. *Interdiscip. Sci. Rev.*, 31, 163-173.
- Jacobs, S. (2006b). Michael Polanyi and Thomas Kuhn: priority and credit. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 25-36.
- Jacobs, S. (2009). Thomas Kuhn's memory. *Intellectual History Review*, 19(1), 83-101.
- Jäkel, O. (2002). *Metaphors in Abstract Domains of Discourse, English and American Studies in German*, 4-6.
- Jarnicki, P. (2016) On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations, *The Translator*, 22:3, 271-286.
- Jarnicki, P. (2021) *Stimmung/Nastrój* as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives. *Foundations of Science* 27, 1207-1228.
- Jarnicki, P; Greif, H. (2022) The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure', *Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie*, early online (8.06.2022).
- Kokowski, M. (2001), *Thomas S. Kuhn (1922–1996) a zagadnienie rewolucji kopernikowskiej*, Warszawa.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1957). *The Copernican revolution: Planetary astronomy in the development of western thought*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2nd ed. 1970.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1977). *The Essential Tension: Selected studies in scientific tradition and change*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1979). Foreword. In T. J. Trenn, R. K. Merton. eds., *Genesis and development of a scientific fact* (pp. vii– xi). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. & others (2000). *The road since structure: philosophical essays, 1970-1993*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kuhn, T. S. (2021), George Reisch, ed. *The Quest for Physical Theory*. MIT.
- Kuhn, T. S. (2022). *The last writings of Thomas S. Kuhn: Incommensurability in science*. Ed. B. Mladenović, University of Chicago Press.
- Lakoff, G., Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Marcum, J. A. (2015). *Thomas Kuhn's revolutions: A historical and an evolutionary philosophy of science?* London/New York: Bloomsbury.

- Marín, M. P. (2010). Ludwik Fleck: precursor del pensamiento de Thomas Kuhn. *Eidos: Revista de Filosofía de la Universidad del Norte* (13), 130–149.
- Moleski, M. X. (2006). Polanyi vs. Kuhn: worldviews apart. *Tradition and Discovery: The Polanyi Society Periodical*, 33(2), 8–24.
- Melogno, P., A. Courtoisie (2019). Stepping into the 60s: Thomas Kuhn's Intellectual Turn towards the Philosophy of Science. *Daimon* 76, 23–33.
- Melogno P. (2022). From Externalism to Internalism: The Historiographical Development of Thomas Kuhn, *Foundations of Science*, 27, 371–385.
- Melogno, P., L. Giri (2023). Towards a Genealogy of Thomas Kuhn's Semantics, *Perspectives on Science*, 31 (4): 385–404.
- Mößner, N. (2011). Thought styles and paradigms—a comparative study of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas S. Kuhn. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 42, 362–371.
- Oberheim, E. (2012). *Feyerabend's Philosophy*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Oliveira, J. C. P. de (2017). Thomas Kuhn, the Image of Science and the Image of Art: The First Manuscript of Structure. *Perspectives on Science*, 25(6), 746–765.
- Peine, A. (2011). Challenging incommensurability: What we can learn from Ludwik Fleck for the analysis of configurational innovation. *Minerva*, 49(4), 489–508.
- Reisch, G. A. (2016). Aristotle in the Cold War: On the Origins of Thomas Kuhn's The Structure of Scientific Revolutions. In R. J. Richards & L. Daston (Eds.), *Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions at Fifty: Reflections on a science classic*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press.
- Reisch, G.A. (2019). *The Politics of Paradigms*. Albany: SUNY Press.
- Sigurdsson, S. (2016). The nature of scientific knowledge: an interview with Thomas S. Kuhn. In *Shifting paradigms: Thomas S. Kuhn and the history of science* (pp. 17–30): Edition Open Access.
- Simons, M. (2017). The many encounters of Thomas Kuhn and French epistemology. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 61, 41–50.
- Trenn, T. J. (1981). Paper prepared for the Hamburg Colloquium on Ludwik Fleck held September 13th–16th, 1981: Some Reflections on the Chicago Edition of Fleck's Monograph. *Robert K. Merton Papers*, MS #1439, Box 331, folder 9, series VII.5.
- Werner, S. & Zittel, C. (Eds.) (2011). *Denkstile und Tatsachen: gesammelte Schriften und Zeugnisse*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Winneke, S. (1993). Ludwik Fleck—Zur Wirkung eines Wirkungslosen, In Helmuth Albrecht (ed.) *Naturwissenschaft und Technik in der Geschichte. 25 Jahre Lehrstuhl für Geschichte der Naturwissenschaft und Technik am Historischen Institut der Universität Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Verlag für Geschichte der Naturwissenschaften und der Technik*, 357–367.
- Wray, K. B. (2011). *Kuhn's Evolutionary Social Epistemology*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2016). The Influence of James B. Conant on Kuhn's Structure of Scientific Revolutions. *HOPOS: The Journal of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science*, 6, 1–23.
- Wray, K. B., ed. (2021a). *Interpreting Kuhn*, Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B. (2021b). *Kuhn's Intellectual Path*, Cambridge University Press.
- Wray, K. B., ed. (2024). *Kuhn's The Structure of Scientific Revolutions at 60*. Cambridge University Press.
- Zittel, C. (2011). Ludwik Fleck und der Stilbegriff in den Naturwissenschaften. Stil als wissenschaftshistorische, epistemologische und ästhetische Kategorie. In H. Bredekamp & J. Krois (Eds.), *Sehen und Handeln*. Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, pp. 171–206.
- Zittel, C. (2014). Ludwik Flecks Gestaltbegriff und sein Blick auf die Gestaltpsychologie seiner Zeit. *NTM Zeitschrift für Geschichte der Wissenschaften, Technik und Medizin*, 22(1), 9–29.

PLAN BADAŃ [w języku polskim i angielskim]

Lp.	Nazwa zadania	Podmioty
1	Analiza tekstów opublikowanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do roku 1962 włącznie - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Text analysis of the published texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
2	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Ludwika Flecka do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć z jego teorii i pojęć z teorii zastanych	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories	
3	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów opublikowanych)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of published texts)	
4	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Thomasa Kuhna [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in Thomas Kuhn Archive [Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Libraries. Department of Distinctive Collections]	
5	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Jamesa Conanta [Harvard University Archives Repository]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in James Conant Archive [Harvard University Archives Repository]	
6	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Paula Feyerabenda [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in Paul Feyerabend Archive [Philosophische Archiv, Universität Konstanz]	

7	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Roberta Mertona [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in Robert Merton Archive [Rare Book & Manuscript Library, Columbia University]	
8	Badania archiwalne w Archiwum Michaela Polanyi'ego [University of Chicago Library]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Archive research in Michael Polanyi Archive [University of Chicago Library]	
9	Badania w innych archiwach i wywiady z osobami, które mogą posiadać wiedzę mogącą rzucić światło na genealogiczny związek między teoriami Flecka i Kuhna, jak na przykład rodzina Wilhelma Baldamusa, która przechowuje jego korespondencję, poszukiwanie materiałów Thaddeusa Trenna i Harolda K. Schillinga z Pennsylvania State University, Marka Kaca i Edwarda Shillsa.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Research in other archives and interviews with individuals who might possess Spółecznych knowledge that could shed light on the genealogical relation between Fleck's and Kuhn's theories, such as for instance Wilhelm Baldamus' family, who keep his correspondence, search for materials of Thaddeus Trenn and Harold K. Schilling from Pennsylvania State University, Mark Kac and Edward Shills.	
10	Analiza niepublikowanych tekstów Thomasa Kuhna (do roku 1962 włącznie) - rozwój słownictwa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Text analysis of the unpublished texts of Thomas Kuhn up to and including 1962 - vocabulary development	
11	Rekonstrukcja najważniejszych metafor używanych przez Thomasa Kuhna do konceptualizacji abstrakcyjnych pojęć jego teorii i pojęć teorii zastanych (analiza tekstów niepublikowanych)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Reconstruction of the most important metaphors used by Thomas Kuhn to Spółecznych conceptualize abstract concepts of his theory and concepts of the received theories (analysis of unpublished texts)	

12	Porównanie metafor stosowanych przez Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Comparison of metaphors used by Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	
13	Porównanie słownictwa Flecka i Kuhna (w odniesieniu do tego ostatniego, w ujęciu diachronicznym)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Comparison vocabulary of Fleck and of Kuhn (in respect to the latter, in diachronic terms)	
14	Rozważenie możliwych wyjaśnień podobieństwa teorii Ludwika Flecka i Thomasa Kuhna	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich
	Consideration of possible explanations of the similarity of the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn	

WSPÓŁPRACA MIĘDZYNARODOWA

Czy projekt realizowany we współpracy międzynarodowej?		TAK
Rodzaj współpracy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Współpraca międzynarodowa z partnerami z zagranicznych instytucji naukowych, którzy nie ubiegają się o środki finansowe na ten cel w ramach ogłaszanych przez instytucje partnerskie programów, organizowanych we współpracy z NCN w oparciu o procedurę agencji wiodącej 	
Kraje	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Argentyna Brazylia Hiszpania Niemcy Stany Zjednoczone Ameryki 	

Podmioty - Argentyna

Lp.	Podmiot
1	Departamento de Ciencias Sociales, Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero (National University of Tres de Febrero)

Podmioty - Brazylia

Lp.	Podmiot
1	Departamento de História da Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (University of Minas Gerais)

Podmioty - Hiszpania

Lp.	Podmiot
1	Unidad Predepartamental de Filosofía, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Zaragoza (University of Zaragoza)

Podmioty - Niemcy

Lp.	Podmiot
1	Max-Planck-Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte (Max Planck Institute for the History of Science)
2	Institut für Philosophie, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover (Leibniz University Hannover)
3	Institut für Geschichte, Theorie und Ethik der Medizin, Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf (Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf)

Podmioty - Stany Zjednoczone Ameryki

Lp.	Podmiot
1	University of North Carolina at Greensboro

Opis korzyści wynikających ze współpracy międzynarodowej [w języku angielskim]

A group of international experts will be established in order to match the multilingual Polish-German-English and multisited nature of the research. It will also help to gather the broadest possible expertise on the relationship between Fleck and Kuhn.

In particular, the international expert group's tasks will be:

1. to critically evaluate the results of research tasks 1-11 (see Research plan), i.e.,
 - the results of linguistic inquiries into vocabulary and metaphors in Fleck and Kuhn and
 - archival research;
2. to discuss the conclusions of Tasks 12-14, i.e., comparison of vocabulary and metaphors between Fleck and Kuhn, results of corpus analysis, and especially the arguments for and against various hypotheses explaining the similarity between Fleck's and Kuhn's conceptions.

Among the members of the group will be experts both from Poland (Michał Kokowski, Artur Koterski, Wojciech Sady) and from abroad (Nicholas Binney, Kenneth Caneva, Mauro Condé, Leandro Giri, Juan Mayoral, Nicola Mößner, Hans-Jörg Rheinberger). Two of the researchers (Giri, Mayoral) have already conducted research in Kuhn's archives.

Consulting with them will help improve searches in the archive there.

A group of external experts is particularly important when it comes to formulating arguments for and against the most radical and controversial hypothesis of plagiarism. Inviting both a proponent (Sady) and opponents (Caneva, Mayoral) of this hypothesis along with defenders of "softer" hypotheses to the group of experts will ensure consideration of all explanatory perspectives and make the results of the project more balanced. We plan to cooperate remotely from the beginning of the project and have one six-day meeting with each expert in Wrocław in the second half of the project.

All of the above-mentioned researchers are informed of the content of the project and expressed their willingness to participate in the work of the group of external experts.

ANKIETY CZŁONKÓW ZESPOŁU [w języku angielskim]

KIEROWNIK (PI)

dr Paweł Maciej Jarnicki

PRZEBIEG KARIERY NAUKOWEJ

Information on education, academic degrees/titles and employment

- From 08.2018 to 02.2022 - **assistant professor** (half-time) at Warsaw University of Technology; Faculty of Administration and Social Sciences.
- From 05.2015 - a member of the Academy of Young Scholars and Artists (Wrocław).
- From 05.2013 to 04.2016 - **associated researcher** of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (ETHZ) and University of Zurich. From 04.2013 to 09.2016 - principal investigator of the project (see projects).
- From 2012 - a **member of the Board** of Project Science Foundation, from 12.2016 to 12.2019 Chairman of the Board.
- 15 May 2012 - **Ph.D. in humanities**. University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty.
- 2009-2011 - **investigator** within the doctoral project (University of Wrocław) funded by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland (State Committee for Scientific Research in Poland [Komitet Badań Naukowych] N N101 060336).
- 15 July 2005 - **Master of Arts**. The University of Wrocław, Philological Faculty, Institute of Polish Philology.

It should be noted that although PI's academic career has lasted for over a dozen years (he began his doctoral studies in 2005), the period of his **full-time employment lasted for 5 years and two and a half months** (from April 2013 to September 2016 - full time, from October 2018 to February 2022 - half time). During his doctoral studies, PI did not receive any scholarship that would allow him not to take up other works. He is a father of three children (born in 2011, 2015, and 2019).

Research stays at home and abroad

- From May 2013 to April 2016 - associated researcher of Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at Collegium Helveticum at Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich - ETHZ) and University of Zurich (Universität Zürich), [regular short stays within the realization of grant number 2012/06/M/HS2/00313].
- 07-09.2009 query in British Library (London), [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].
- 11-12.2009 query in Ludwik Fleck Archive in Zurich and Library of the University of Zurich [within a doctoral grant - number N N101 060336].

Lectures and presentations

- 18.09.2023, Gdańsk, Council of the Baltic Sea States Summer University 2023 - Strategic Narratives of Balticness - Foundations and Identity, **invited talk**: "Do we know what we see or do we see what we know? Seminar on epistemic conditioning of sensual perception";
- 7-9.07.2021, Kent (online), **international conference**: The British Society for the Philosophy of Science 2021 Annual Conference, paper [with Hajo Greif]: "The Aristotle Experience and the Genesis of the Kuhnian Revolution".
- 23-26.06.2020, Singapore, **international conference** HOPOS 2020 (The Thirteenth Biennial Congress of the International Society for the History of Philosophy of Science), paper: "The role of (conceptual) metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's philosophical writings" selected for presentation but the event was canceled.
- 11-14.04.2019, Lviv, **international conference**: "Ludwik Fleck and His Thought Collectives" (Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Center for Urban History of East Central Europe, Ukrainian Catholic University), paper:

"What is 'mood'? About translating of 'Stimmung/nastrój' into English".

- 28-30.10.2015, Marburg, **international conference**: "Entangled science? Relocating GermanPolish scientific relations" (the Leibniz Association and the Polish Academy of Sciences), poster: "Ludwik Fleck's "Polish-German" theory of thought styles and thought collectives, and problems arising from its translation";
- 3-8.08.2015, Helsinki, **international conference**: 15th Congress on Logic, Methodology, and Philosophy of Science 2015 (University of Helsinki), paper: "The reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives in English";
- 27-29.11.2014, Berlin, **international conference**: "Self-Translation as Transfer of Knowledge" (Zentrum für Literatur- und Kulturforschung), paper: "Ludwik Fleck's Legacy – an Example of Self-Translation?";
- 17-19.09.2014, Toruń, **international conference**: "Situating Solidarities" (European Association for the Study of Science and Technology and Nicolaus Copernicus University), paper: "'Gestalts' of Ludwik Fleck".

Prizes and awards

Other significant achievements

Organization:

- 03.2016 - **international conference** in Wrocław (together with Martina Schluender, Rainer Egloff, Ohad Parnes, Sandra Lang): "Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives – translations and receptions".
- 03.2014 - **international conference** in Wrocław: "Ludwik Fleck – traditions, inspirations, interpretations".
- 01.2014 - **international workshop** in Zurich (together with Martina Schluender, Rainer Egloff and Johannes Fehr): "Translation of Science – Science of Translation".
- 10.2009 - First Polish Constructivist Symposium in Wrocław (together with Bogdan Balicki).
- 2008-2012 foundation of "Science of Science" circle in Wrocław - 34 meetings took place.

Other key information impacting the evaluation of the academic and research career

PUBLIKACJE NAUKOWE

1. Mauro L. Conde, Paweł Jarnicki, *Ludwik Fleck: Thought Style and Thought Collective in the Historiography of Science* (2023), rozdział, Condé, M.L., Salomon, M. (eds) Handbook for the Historiography of Science. Historiographies of Science. Springer, Cham.
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytoowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: nie, DOI DOI 10.1007/978-3-030-99498-3_5-2
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
2. Paweł Jarnicki, Hajo Greif, *The 'Aristotle Experience' Revisited: Thomas Kuhn Meets Ludwik Fleck on the Road to 'Structure'* (2022), artykuł, Archiv für Geschichte der Philosophie, vol. 106, no. 2, 2024, pp. 313-349 (early online 8.06.2022)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytoowań): 5
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI DOI 10.1515/agph-2020-0160
Status publikacji: opublikowane
3. Paweł Jarnicki, *Stimmung/Nastrój as Content of Modern Science: On Musical Metaphors in Ludwik Fleck's Theory of Thought Styles and Thought Collectives* (2021), artykuł, Foundations of Science, 7, pages 1207–1228, (2022, online:

- 05 April 2021)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 5
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI DOI 10.1007/s10699-021-09792-33
Status publikacji: opublikowane
4. Paweł Jarnicki, *On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translation* (2016), artykuł, *Translator*, 22:3, 271-286
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 17
Otwarty dostęp: nie, DOI DOI 10.1080/13556509.2015.1126881
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
5. Maria Ciesielska, Paweł Jarnicki, *Ludwik Fleck - mikrobiolog i filozof [Ludwik Fleck - microbiologist and philosopher]* (2021), książka, Oficyna Wydawnicza Politechniki Warszawskiej; ISBN 978-83-8156-251-5 (druk) ISBN 978-83-8156-252-2 (online)
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane, *Publikacja do pobrania z systemu*
6. Paweł Jarnicki, *Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of "legitimation" [Polish extended version appeared as: O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka In: Stan Rzeczy 10, p. 355-373]* (2015), artykuł, *Divinatio: Studia Culturologica Series*, vol. 41, autumn-winter, p. 167-184
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane
7. Paweł Jarnicki, *The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989)* (2016), artykuł, *Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science*, 1 (2016 - special issue on Ludwik Fleck), p.21-30
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 1
Otwarty dostęp: tak, DOI DOI 10.24117/2526-2270.2016.i1.05
Status publikacji: opublikowane
8. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metaforyczne konceptualizacje pojęcia 'tekstu' a przemiany stylów myślowych w literaturoznawstwie [Metaphorical conceptualizations of the concept of 'text' and changes of thought styles in history and theory of literature]* (2014), książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo 'Projekt Nauka'
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 5
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane
9. Paweł Jarnicki, Bożena Płonka-Syroka, Bogdan Balicki, *Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje [Ludwik Fleck - traditions - inspirations - interpretations] (in the volume: Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie [Two bibliographies of the reception of Ludwik Fleck and materials available on the Internet], p. 235–37; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim [Bibliography of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory in Polish], p. 239–55; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim [Bibliography of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's theory in English], p. 257–94; Postłowie [Afterword], p. 295–96)* (2015), książka, Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 7
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane
10. Paweł Jarnicki, *Metafory dyskursu intertekstualności, metaforyka tekstylna [Metaphors of intertextuality. Textile metaphors]* (2015), artykuł, *Kształcenie Językowe*, 13 (23): p. 49–72
Liczba cytowań (bez autocytowań): 0
Otwarty dostęp: nie
Status publikacji: opublikowane

DOKONANIA ARTYSTYCZNE

b.d.

BADANIA NAUKOWE FINANSOWANE PRZEZ NCN

DANE POBRANE AUTOMATYCZNIE

Tytuł: Filologiczna analiza filozoficznych dzieł Ludwika Flecka oraz ich tłumaczeń w językach: polskim, niemieckim i angielskim

Nr rejestracyjny:

2012/06/M/HS2/00313

Źródło(a) finansowania: NCN, Nazwa konkursu: HARMONIA-3

Kwota: **405 512 PLN**

Podmiot realizujący:

Projekt Nauka. Fundacja na rzecz promocji nauki polskiejData rozpoczęcia realizacji: **2013-03-25**, Data zakończenia realizacji: **2016-08-24**

Wynik oceny:

Uznanie umowy za wykonaną

Lista najważniejszych publikacji będących rezultatem projektu:

Publikacje w czasopiśmie:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Sandra Lang ("Introduction"); Paweł Jarnicki ("The beginnings..."), Introduction; The beginnings of the reception of Ludwik Fleck's ideas in Polish (1936-1989), *Transversal: International Journal for the Historiography of Science*, 1, 3-5; 21-30, Graduate Program in History (Science and Culture in History) of Federal University of Minas Gerais (Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais), Brasil, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, On the Shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the Bilingual Philosophical Legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English Translations, *The Translator*, 22 (3), 271–286, Routledge, 2016, IF: 0.483, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, O problemach z tłumaczeniami dwujęzycznej spuścizny na przykładzie pojęcia „legitymacji” Ludwika Flecka, *Stan Rzeczy*, 10, 355-373, Instytut Socjologii UW, 2016, IF: 0, - Opublikowane
- Paweł Jarnicki, Problems with translations of Ludwik Fleck: the example of the concept of “legitimation”, *Divinatio*, 41 (Aut.-Win.), 167-184, University of Sofia, Department of Cultural Studies, 2015, IF: 0, - Opublikowane

Publikacje książkowe/ rozdziały w publikacjach książkowych:

- Paweł Jarnicki, Dwie bibliografie recepcji Ludwika Flecka i materiały dostępne w Internecie; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku angielskim; Bibliografia recepcji teorii Ludwika Flecka w języku polskim; Poślowie, Ludwik Fleck – tradycje – inspiracje – interpretacje, (nie dotyczy), 235-296, Wydawnictwo Fundacji Projekt Nauka & Uniwersytet Medyczny im. Piastów Śląskich we Wrocławiu, 2015, Wrocław, <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2705.3208>, - Opublikowane

b.d.

INNE PROJEKTY BADAWCZE

b.d.

NAJWAŻNIEJSZE OSIĄGNIĘCIE NAUKOWE

The most important achievement is the clarification of the status of Ludwik Fleck's theory of thought styles and thought collectives. Its specific situation generates specific problems for translators, who unfortunately had not recognized this specific status of Fleck's theory, so all the existing translations have to be deeply revised. Fleck's philosophical/sociological theory was expressed in two languages (Polish and German) more or less simultaneously by a bilingual author, who did not self-translate his texts into the second language but published original texts in both of these languages. It means that both Polish and German texts are of equal value, and if we want to speak of the level of equivalence, I argue we can find it at the level of concepts - it means that expressions that differ in lexical meaning may denote the very same concept. The problem is described - with an example of "circulation of thoughts" [Denkverkehr/krażenie myśli] expression - in the paper "On the shoulders of Ludwik Fleck? On the bilingual philosophical

legacy of Ludwik Fleck and its Polish, German and English translations" published in The Translator.

OPUS 29 (submitted 06.2025) – rejected at the first stage – 73,00%

A. PROJECT ASSESSMENT (65%) – **4,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5)

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (35%) – **3,00** (on a scale of 0 to 5).

GENERAL JUSTIFICATION

The panel recognized the scientific quality of the project, particularly highlighting the importance of research into Fleck's influence on Kuhn. However, concerns were raised regarding the scope of the project, since it does not consider the contemporary research in philosophy of science on the topics treated by Fleck and Kuhn. Following the panel discussion, it was determined that the feasibility of the project is clearly given, but that its potential impact is rather limited given its limited scope. Based on a comparison with other PIs, the qualifications of the Principal Investigator were assessed as solid as regards the research output on Fleck, but the field of publications was assessed to be narrow given its nearly exclusive concentration on Fleck. The panel judged the output in terms of publications in well recognized, international journals in history and philosophy of science to be in need of improvement.

INDIVIDUAL REVIEWS

A. PROJECT ASSESSMENT (65%)

Expert 1

A) SCIENTIFIC QUALITY

1. Scientific Relevance

Given that there are important similarities between the philosophical proposals of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn, the aim is to discover to what extent Kuhn owes his reading of Fleck's works, although this debt has not been acknowledged or has only been partially acknowledged. If this hypothesis is true, the project would be of great scientific relevance as it would reveal one of the sources and influences received by Th. Kuhn, one of the classic authors of Kuhn's 20th-century philosophy of science.

2. Importance

The main objective of the project is to trace the genealogy of the most relevant ideas of Th. Kuhn (1922-1996), which have greatly influenced the philosophy of contemporary science, while clearly establishing which are his original contributions and which are those he borrowed from L. Fleck (1896-1961), a Polish thinker, scientist, and sociologist who in the 1930s introduced the concept of the "thought collective" (Denkkollektiv), which has greatly influenced the philosophy of science and social constructivism.

3. Originality

Th. Kuhn's book, "The Structure of Scientific Revolutions" (1962), is one of the most influential works of 20th-century thought, while Fleck, a Polish scientist and philosopher, remains known primarily to specialists. We know that Kuhn owned Fleck's book, "Entstehung und Entwicklung einer wissenschaftlichen Tatsache" (1935) and that he read it in 1949, before writing his own, but historians tend to dismiss any substantial connection. At best, they accept a parallel discovery of the main theories of both authors or a vague inspiration, given Kuhn's limited knowledge of German. Some insinuations of plagiarism have never been contrasted with evidence. The originality of this project lies in establishing the actual influence Kuhn received from Fleck.

4. Novelty of the research or tasks to be performed

The main novelty lies in the project's aim to explore the different possibilities that may explain the similarity between Fleck's and Kuhn's thinking. This objective is achieved by exploring all possible hypotheses to explain the similarities between Fleck's and Kuhn's philosophical proposals and concepts: 1) Parallel discovery: Both thinkers independently reached similar conclusions. 2) Subconscious inspiration: Kuhn read Fleck but absorbed his concepts without realizing their origin. 3) Discreet influence: Fleck's work guided Kuhn's thinking more than he himself admitted. 4) Unacknowledged borrowing: Kuhn borrowed key concepts without giving them due credit.

5. Relevance of the methodology and work plan to the scientific objectives of the project, including (if applicable) the appropriate integration of the sex and/or gender dimension into the project content.

The chosen methodology is in line with the research theme and hypothesis: it will compare the words, metaphors, and ideas used by Fleck and Kuhn, using historical and linguistic analysis to determine how Fleck's concepts may have shaped Kuhn's work. Thus, the novel aspect of the project consists of combining a historiographical analysis of shared influences with a comparative linguistic analysis of key concepts and metaphors in the work of both authors.

The integration of the sex and/or gender dimension into the project content is not stated.

6. Scientific quality of the project in an international context.

Scientific quality in an international context is reflected in the analysis of the literature shared by the international scientific community that, in one way or another, addressed this issue (Baldamus (1977, 1979), Babich (2003a, 2003b), Brorson and Andersen (2001), Collins (2012), Conde (2005, 2018), Cedarbaum (1983), Jacobs (1987, 2002, 2006a), Mößner (2011), Peine (2011), and Winneke (1993).)

It is important to determine the influences on Kuhn, as he was one of the most important philosophers of science of the 20th century. The quality of his contributions would not be diminished if the project revealed Fleck's influences, and, in turn, Fleck's thought would receive greater and more just international recognition.

B) FEASIBILITY

1. Work plan and methodology related to achieving the proposed objectives within the established timeframe.

The work plan and research methodology are based on three pillars: 1) exhaustive textual analysis of the published and unpublished works of both authors; 2) critical review of secondary sources; and 3) exhaustive archival research in various key collections. Through this work plan and methodological approach, we seek to uncover the extent of Fleck's influence on Kuhn's theories, comparing his

vocabulary and metaphors, and evaluating various hypotheses, from parallel discovery to possible plagiarism.

2. Risk management plan.

- The risks relate to archival research. Specifically, the requester expresses fear of finding less conclusive evidence than the preliminary investigation suggests.
- Another risk is having to deal with travel disruptions caused by external factors, so a budget has been allocated for copies of documents that will be sent to us by mail or digitally from various archives.

C) POTENTIAL IMPACT

- If the central hypothesis of the research is confirmed, the project would have a certain international impact because it would offer a renewed and updated perspective on the philosophers of science L. Fleck and Th. Kuhn.
- The choice of presenting the results through the publication of four internationally relevant scientific articles also guarantees a certain international impact.
- Having a team of international collaborators also contributes to this being a project that transcends Poland's national borders and is of international interest. The materials found and prepared during the linguistic and philosophical analysis will be consulted and critiqued by a group of external experts, including Fleck and Kuhn experts from Poland (Michał Kokowski, Artur Koterski, Wojciech Sady) and abroad (Nicholas Binney, Kenneth Caneva, Mauro Conde, Leandro Giri, Juan Mayoral, Nicola Mößner, Hans-Jörg Rheinberger). These include experts who have studied Kuhn's archive (Giri, Mayoral), as well as proponents (Sady) and opponents (Mayoral, Caneva) of the most radical plagiarism hypothesis.
- Finally, since the authors are classic authors of 20th-century philosophy of science, any new developments that may arise would have an impact on the international philosophical community.

STRENGTHS

- Ambition in addressing the influences received by a classic author in the philosophy of science such as Th. Kuhn and L. Fleck.
- The methodology combines philological methods, linguistic analysis of texts, and philosophical methods (in all sections of the work plan), including the semantic analysis of key terms and the development of hypotheses based on the results of philological, conceptual, and archival work.
- The fact that no hypothesis was initially ruled out speaks to the equanimity and objectivity with which the principal investigator and his team approached the project.

WEAKNESSES

- Excessive emphasis on the project hypothesis (undeclared influences on Kuhn's work from the Polish philosopher and scientist L. Fleck), without taking into account that this is a minor aspect that does not affect the quality, philosophical trajectory, or public recognition of both authors.
- The possibility of not finding conclusive evidence, accepted by the applicant, diminishes the value and reliability of the investigation.

- The research team (excluding voluntary external collaborators) is very small, as only two researchers will be responsible for the main tasks of the project.

Expert 2

The project is continuous with the researcher's focus on Ludwik Fleck during the last ten years at least. The purpose is to conduct a thorough investigation of Fleck's influence on Thomas Kuhn. Dr. Jarnicki is fully familiar with the research on Kuhn and Fleck, having contributed himself to the research on Fleck. The project is clearly structured and feasible. It is a solid project, but it could be broadened in scope, taking into account the systematic discussion in contemporary philosophy of science of the issues raised by Fleck and Kuhn.

B. QUALIFICATIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR (35%)

Expert 1

1. Qualifications of the principal investigator.

- Paweł Jarnicki (Principal Investigator, National Ossolinski Institute).

- Qualifications of the principal investigator. He earned a Master of Arts (Philology) in 2005. His PhD in Humanities (Philology) was awarded in 2012 by the University of Wrocław.

- Career. From 2013 to 2016, he was a Research Associate at the Ludwik Fleck Zentrum at the Collegium Helveticum (University of Zurich). From 2018 to 2022, he was an assistant professor (part-time) at the Warsaw University of Technology. From 2012, he was a member of the Board of the Scientific Project Foundation and from 2016 to 2019, its Chairman.

2. Assignment of Research Tasks.

The assignment of tasks is structured in great detail, establishing 14 distinct research tasks ranging from textual analysis of Thomas Kuhn's published texts up to 1962 and the vocabulary used; through the reconstruction of the metaphors of both authors; research in various archives; and, finally, explanations of the similarity between the theories of Ludwik Fleck and Thomas Kuhn.

3. Research Facilities and Equipment.

Those available at the National Ossoliński Institute and other institutions whose archives will be reviewed during research trips and short stays. Small equipment and materials such as a notebook and camera will be purchased under the project's expense.

4. International Cooperation (if any); other factors affecting the project's viability.

The project benefits from international cooperation with partners from foreign research institutions that do not apply for funding under programs launched by partner institutions in cooperation with the NCN in accordance with the lead agency's procedure. The countries are: Argentina, Brazil, Germany, Spain, and the United States.

The group of international experts was created to complement the multilingual (Polish-German-English) and multi-site research, which will contribute to gathering the greatest possible amount of knowledge on the relationship between Fleck and Kuhn.

STRENGTHS

- 10 Research Papers have been selected and published in reputable books and journals.

- 4 Research Papers and 1 Chapter/Book have been published within the framework of NCN-FUNDED RESEARCH, entitled "Philological analysis of Ludwik Fleck's philosophical works and its translations in Polish, English, and German."

WEAKNESSES

- The principal investigator has declared career breaks: "It should be noted that although PI's academic career has lasted for over a dozen years (he began his doctoral studies in 2005), the period of his full-time employment lasted for 5 years and two and a half months (from April 2013 to September 2016 - full time, from October 2018 to February 2022 - half time). During his doctoral studies, PI did not receive any scholarship that would allow him not to take up other works. He is a father of three children (born in 2011, 2015, and 2019)".

- His full-time employment period lasted five years and two and a half months (from April 2013 to September 2016, full-time, and from October 2018 to February 2022, part-time).

- University Education in Philology, fundamentally.

- The principal investigator's participation in international conferences has been limited, resulting in the limited international exposure of the research developed to date.

Expert 2

Dr. Jarnicki obtained his PhD in humanities at the University of Wrocław in 2012. From 2018 to 2022, he was assistant professor at the Warsaw Institute of Technology. Before that, he was employed from 2013 to 2016 at the Ludwik Fleck Centre at Collegium Helveticum in Zurich. There are 9 presentations at national and international conferences listed between 2014 and 2023. The publications are mainly on Ludwik Fleck, in Polish and in English. Dr. Jarnicki is a recognised researcher on Fleck. But the field of publications with its focus nearly exclusively on Fleck is rather narrow. There are only few publications in peer-reviewed, recognised international journals.